

THE VAT SITHOR INSCRIPTION: TRANSLATION, COMMENTARY, AND
REFLECTIONS ON BUDDHIST TRADITIONS IN TENTH-CENTURY CAMBODIA

By

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To Tara and Eva

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In the *Rāmāyaṇa* there is a Sanskrit saying that goes, *matsyā iva narā nityaṃ bhakṣayanti parasparam* ('people, like fish, always are looking to devour one another'). Fortunately during my academic studies and research I have not found this to be the case. From the beginning, I have been overwhelmed by the constant support and encouragement of my mentors, peers, family, friends, and the wider academic community of scholars working in the field of Buddhist and Khmer studies. I owe a tremendous amount of debt and gratitude to many people and institutions for their support, guidance, and kindness.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

[]	restoration brackets
<i>Bb</i>	<i>Bodhisattvabhūmi</i>
<i>BEFEO</i>	Bulletin de l'École française d'Extrême-Orient
BHS	Buddhist Hybrid Sanskrit Dictionary, see Edgerton 1953
c.	<i>circa</i>
CE	Common Era
corr.	an obvious correction
DOK	Dictionary of Old Khmer, see Jenner 2009a and 2009b
<i>EDMD</i>	<i>Ekādaśamukhadhāraṇī</i>
EFEQ	École française d'Extrême-Orient
fig(s).	figure(s)
fl.	flourished
fn.	footnote
fr.	from
<i>IC</i>	<i>Inscriptions du Cambodge</i> , see Cœdès 1937 – 1966
<i>ISSC</i>	Inscriptions sanscrites de Campā et du Cambodge, see Bergaigne and Barth 1893
<i>JA</i>	<i>Journal Asiatique</i>
<i>KVS</i>	<i>Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra</i>
<i>Laṅ</i>	<i>Laṅkāvatārasūtra</i>
lit.	literally
M.	Majjhima Nikāya
<i>MAV</i>	<i>Madhyāntavibhāga</i>
<i>MBh</i>	<i>Mahābhārata</i>

MSA	<i>Mahāyānasūtrālamkāra</i>
Msaṃ	<i>Mahāyānasamgraha</i>
MVT	<i>Mahāvairocana Tantra/Sūtra</i>
M.W.	Monier-Williams Sanskrit-English Dictionary, see Monier-Williams 1899
n.	note
NIC	<i>Nouvelles inscriptions du Cambodge II & III</i> , see Pou 2002
P.	Pali
PED	The Pali–English Dictionary, see Davids 1905
pl.	plate
SHK	<i>Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānikan</i>
SHKM	<i>Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānan Mantranaya</i>
Skt.	Sanskrit
SN.	Saṃyutta Nikāya
st.	stanza
STTS	<i>Sarvatathāgatatattvasamgraha</i>
Tib.	Tibetan

Abstract of Dissertation Presented to the Graduate School
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My dissertation provides a new translation of the tenth-century Vat Sithor inscription from Cambodia, along with commentary and additional reflections on Buddhist traditions during this era in Cambodia's history. This English translation represents a first since the only full translation of the inscription is the French version published by George Coédès sixty years ago in his *Inscriptions du Cambodge*. An examination of the Vat Sithor inscription, with recourse to other contemporary tenth-century epigraphical and art historical sources from Cambodia, demonstrates that Buddhist traditions during this period exhibited the following five characteristics: (1) the doctrinal and epistemological foundations of tenth-century Buddhists were grounded in Yogācāra traditions and emphasized the path of the bodhisattva, (2) evidence of newly arising tantric Buddhist elements first appeared in Cambodia during this period and were beginning to be adapted to these Yogācāra foundations, (3) triadic configurations of Buddhist figures are dominant, with triads including the Buddha and Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) being the most prevalent, (4) on the ground Buddhist practices that revolved around the acquisition of merit (such as image construction and gift giving)

constituted the most visible and dominant form of Buddhist expression and practice, and finally (5) Buddhist monastic ideas and positions are sometimes expressed through a rhetoric of Buddhist and Brahmanical rivalry.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

In the mid-tenth century of the Common Era a sandstone stele was erected in the present-day vicinity of the Buddhist Wat of Sithor, a monastery located in the Khsach Kandal district of Kandal province in southeastern Cambodia.¹ The inscription—now known as the Vat Sithor inscription because of the location of its discovery—was officially commissioned to decree a royal order from Jayavarman V (r. c. 968–c. 1000/1001) concerning the proper observances and duties to be followed by the local Buddhist community, especially with regard to monastery-related matters.² The inscription also includes a lengthy eighteen-line invocation praising the path of the

¹ The Cambodian word ‘Wat’ or ‘Vat’ (វត្ត) may refer, in general, to a temple complex or, more specifically, a Buddhist monastery. The etymology of the word comes from the Pali word *vatta* (‘that which is done’ or ‘is customary,’ as in ‘duty,’ ‘service,’ etc.; PED, s.v. *vatta*). The word, therefore, refers (ideally) to a demarcated location at which proper services, customs, duties, and so forth are observed and carried out.

I should point out now that there continues to be no universal standard for representing Khmer words in the Roman/Latin script. Throughout this dissertation I have decided to employ the simplified Romanized spellings used by the Carte Interactive des Sites Archéologiques Khmers (CISARK, <http://www.site-archeologique-khmer.org/>). For example, ‘Vat Kdei Char’ instead of ‘Văt Kdëi Ćâr’ (e.g., Cœdès’ usage) would be an example of the spelling employed by CISARK. The only time I will depart from this method is when directly citing other sources that have used other spelling methods. Although other systems sometimes represent greater phonetic accuracy, the simplified spellings are less convoluted for reading. The International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) continues to be the most accurate phonological method for representing Khmer sounds in writing; this method, however, is unfamiliar to many and very seldom used outside linguistic-related works.

Lastly, Sanskrit and Pali words will be represented using the International Alphabet of Sanskrit Transliteration (I.A.S.T.) method.

² The Vat Sithor inscription is classified as K. 101 according to the classification system devised by George Cœdès. The inventory schema begun by Cœdès is used throughout this dissertation to reference the corpus of inscriptions from Cambodia and Campā (an area today associated with central and southern Vietnam). Inscriptions assigned a number prefixed with ‘C.’ refer to Campā inscriptions and inscriptions prefixed with ‘K.’ refer to Khmer, or Cambodian inscriptions. The first version of this classification system was published in “Inventaire des inscriptions du Champa et du Cambodge,” *BEFEO* 8 (1908): 37–92. A later supplement appeared in “Supplement à l’Inventaire des inscriptions,” *BEFEO* 15 (1915): 173–80. The current standard is George Cœdès and Henri Parmentier, *Listes générales des inscriptions et des monuments du Champa et du Cambodge* (Hanoi: Imprimerie d’Extrême-Orient, 1923). This was followed with two supplements which appeared in volumes I and II of Cœdès’ *Inscriptions du Cambodge [IC]* (1937–1966). At the time of writing this dissertation, an EFEO project known as the *Corpus of Inscriptions of Campā* was in the process of updating the inventory of Campā inscriptions (<http://isaw.nyu.edu/publications/inscriptions/campa/about.html>). The list of Khmer inscriptions is being updated as well.

bodhisattva and a eulogy praising the qualities and exploits of an important Buddhist *ācārya* named Kīrtipaṇḍita. Line-for-line, no other tenth-century inscription coming from Cambodia contains as much information pertaining to Buddhist epistemology, affairs, and activities as the Vat Sithor inscription.³ Although it would be somewhat inaccurate and misleading to label this epigraphical source a *Buddhist* inscription (much like one might call the *Lotus Sūtra* a Buddhist text) since it was composed in order to present a royal order of the king to the local Buddhist community. Nevertheless, the Vat Sithor inscription, taken by itself, provides scholars with more information on forms of Buddhism than any other single inscription coming from tenth-century Cambodia. This alone makes the Vat Sithor inscription worthy of attention and additional dedicated research. When coupled with the fact that no written records other than inscriptions survive from this era of Cambodia's history, the Vat Sithor inscription becomes even more notable for the rare insights it can provide on Buddhist traditions during this period. My dissertation, therefore, provides an entirely new translation of the entire Vat Sithor inscription, along with chapters devoted to related topics, together with commentary and additional reflections on Buddhist traditions in tenth-century Cambodia. This English translation will also represent a first since the only full translation of the inscription is the French version published by George Cœdès sixty years ago in his *Inscriptions du Cambodge* (6: 195–211).⁴

³ Only the three tenth-century inscriptions coming from Bat Cum (K. 266–268) come close. Regarding the Bat Cum inscriptions, see Cœdès (1908b). For a recent re-translation and examination of the Bat Cum inscriptions in German, see Mertens (2005). I will return to these inscriptions several times throughout this dissertation.

⁴ The sixth volume of *IC* which contains the Vat Sithor inscription was published in 1954.

While the Vat Sithor inscription contains quantitatively more information on Buddhist traditions than any other single Cambodian inscription from this era, this is not equivalent to saying that the inscription itself is voluminous, or that the information it contains pertaining to Buddhist traditions is overly abundant. While this 200-line inscription is important, examining it in isolation would not be as profitable as examining it in conjunction with other contemporary epigraphical sources. The diversity of information contained in other tenth-century inscriptions, although not as quantitatively impressive as the Vat Sithor inscription, contribute additional information that aid in reconstructing a richer and more well-rounded picture of what these traditions may have been like in a tenth-century Cambodian setting. These epigraphical sources are unfortunately limited, and often fragmentary, and so in order to ‘flesh out’ the picture there will be need to occasionally draw upon Cambodia’s impressive art-historical record and other material sources when applicable. An examination of the Vat Sithor inscription, with recourse to these other contemporary tenth-century epigraphical and art historical sources, will demonstrate that Buddhist traditions during this period exhibited the following five characteristics: (1) the doctrinal and epistemological foundations of tenth-century Buddhists were grounded in Yogācāra traditions and emphasized the path of the bodhisattva, (2) evidence of newly arising tantric Buddhist elements first appeared in Cambodia during this period and were beginning to be adapted to these Yogācāra foundations, (3) triadic configurations of Buddhists figures are dominant, with triads including the Buddha and Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) being the most prevalent, (4) on the ground Buddhist practices that revolved around the acquisition of merit (such as image construction and gift giving) constituted the most visible and

dominant form of Buddhist expression and practice, and finally (5) Buddhist monastic ideas and positions are sometimes expressed through a rhetoric of Buddhist and Brahmanical rivalry. As these points are addressed, the Vat Sithor inscription will sometimes serve as a starting point for the discussions and for comparing other pieces of information from tenth-century Cambodia pertaining to Buddhist traditions.

An Overview of the Vat Sithor Inscription

As stated previously, the Vat Sithor inscription was discovered in the modern Buddhist Wat of Sithor. This monastery is located in the Khsach Kandal district of present-day Kandal province and situated just over a mile (2 km) west of the Tonle Toch River, a site located in the heart of a riverine network that likely facilitated communications and trade during the tenth-century, as well as earlier and later periods. The inscription was first reported in 1882 by Abel Bergaigne (1882: 147–48) who provided a brief description of its content and noted that the inscription had been transcribed by Émile Senart.

The following year in 1883, Senart published an article entitled, “Une Inscription Buddhique du Cambodge” in *Revue Archéologique* that not only provided additional information on the inscription, but also examined the Buddhist content of the inscription in an effort to better understand tenth-century forms of Buddhism in Cambodia. Senart’s work is unfortunately plagued by an overly critical perspective that tended to marginalize forms of Buddhism in early Cambodia as corrupt and superstitious, particularly the ritual aspects.⁵ He also tended to promote a kind of religious syncretism

⁵ Senart’s article is now particularly noteworthy for the scholar interested in the history of Buddhist studies in that the work is a good example of how early researchers viewed Mahāyāna and later tantric forms of Buddhism as degraded derivatives of some pure original form of Buddhism often associated with so-called ‘Southern’ branches of Buddhism represented by Theravāda forms located in Sri Lanka. According

between Buddhism and, for him, earlier Brahmanical practices. This theory of religious syncretism was widely shared during Senart's time, and continues to exert influence on how religious traditions are viewed during the pre-Angkorian and Angkorian eras of Cambodia's past.⁶ Ironically, clues provided by the Vat Sithor inscription suggest that the forms of Buddhism being practiced (including the ideology, the epistemology, and the monastic lifestyles associated with such practices) were rather normative in that they were typically in line with what one would expect in other regions of South and Southeast Asia where Buddhists were active, especially the overwhelming concern for activities thought to accrue religious merit. Furthermore, stanzas from the inscription that have led Senart and others to assume some kind of religious syncretism between Buddhist and their Brahmanical rivals does not hold up to scrutiny when the same stanzas are interpreted in the context of other textual sources.

Eventually in 1954 with the publication of volume six of his *Inscriptions du Cambodge*, George Cœdès edited the inscription and provided a full French translation (6: 195–211). Cœdès' work remains the only complete translation of the inscription in print today. Since the time of Cœdès only excerpts of the inscription have been

to early scholars like Senart, the most superstitious and misguided of all were the Khmer forms of Buddhism (as represented by the inscription) which were compared to the apparently more correct forms of so-called 'Northern' Buddhism (primarily associated with Nepal and Tibet). For example Senart writes, "Elle nous apparaît ici fourvoyée déjà dans les pratiques superstitieuses qui déshonorent le buddhisme moderne du Nord, attachant, par exemple, un prix infini aux mudrâs, sorte de gestes cabalistiques, qui sont ici représentés comme le cœur même des buddhas," (1883: 188).

⁶ By using the term pre-Angkorian I am broadly referencing the period prior to the time of Jayavarman II (r. 790–c. 835), whose reign is commonly regarded as marking the transition between the pre-Angkorian period and the Angkorian period (the latter so-called Angkorian era lasting, roughly, to the fifteenth century).

(re)translated by a few scholars wishing emphasize select portions related to their individual research projects.⁷

The inscription itself was engraved on a stele made of grey sandstone. The stele has four sides, each containing fifty lines of Sanskrit for a total of 200 lines of composition. For convenience the sides are referred as side A, B, C, and D. With the exception of the final two stanzas on side D, the entire inscription is composed in *śloka* meter.⁸ Stanzas ninety-nine and one hundred are composed in *upajāti* meter.⁹ The inscription consists of seven distinct sections which are clearly demarcated by the presence of an engraved ornamental circle with the appearance of a stylized flower not uncommon in the Cambodian epigraphical record. These punctuated breaks occur at the end of lines eighteen and thirty-six on side A, line fifty on side B, lines ten and thirty on side C, and finally at the end of lines fourteen and fifty on side D.

⁷ For example, see Snellgrove (2001) and Sharrock (2006). Both these works contain excerpts of the inscription translated into English. Note, however, that Snellgrove's translation excerpts are primarily just an English translation of Coëdés' earlier French translation. The English translation excerpts in the work of Sharrock were provided for him by Tadeusz Skorupski.

⁸ Also known as the *anuṣṭubh* meter, the *śloka* meter basically consists of a stanza containing four quarters known as *pādas*. The word *pāda* literally means 'foot.' Each *pāda* consists of two groups of four syllables each; therefore, each *pāda* consists of eight syllables. The last group in each half-verse (i.e., the second and forth *pādas*) consists of a double iambus: √--√, where √ refers to a light syllable and – refers to a heavy syllable. The preceding four syllables may either be light or heavy. The last two syllables of both the first and third *pādas* are reversed (i.e., √--√). An entire stanza (where √ refers to either a light or heavy syllable) would look like this:

√√√√ √---√ / √√√√ √--√ /
 √√√√ √---√ / √√√√ √--√ //

There exists additional guidelines that determine how a *pāda* is to begin, restrictions regarding final syllables, permitted variants, and so forth; however, the above summary is enough to illustrate the basic construction of a *śloka* meter.

⁹ The *upajāti* meter is a mixed meter consisting (usually) of *indravajrā* meter (---√√√√√) or *upendravajrā* meter (√√√√√√√). Both meters consist of eleven syllables. The primary difference between these two meters being whether the first syllable is light (i.e., *upendravajrā*) or heavy (i.e., *indravajrā*).

Section I: Stanzas I–IX (Side A Lines 1–18)

The inscription opens with a traditional Sanskrit panegyric that extols the three embodiments of the Buddha’s ineffable realization of thusness, or enlightenment. This concept of three embodiments is commonly, but misleadingly, referred to as the three ‘bodies’ of the Buddha (*trikāya*): the *dharmakāya* (‘embodiment of Dharma’), *sambhogakāya* (‘embodiment for enjoyment’), and *nirmāṇakāya/nairmāṇika* (embodiment(s) of manifestation’).¹⁰ In addition to the three-*kāya*, the opening section also praises the excellent Dharma of the Buddha, bodhisattvas, as well as those practitioners who grasp and follow the teachings which lead to liberation.

Surprisingly, with the exception of Senart whose assertions are woefully out of date, this opening section of the inscription has received little attention from scholars beyond mere translation. Even recently when scholars such as Snellgrove (2001) and Sharrock (2006) revisited this inscription in order to make claims regarding Buddhism during the tenth century (and later), they merely glossed this section and focused on retranslating other select sections in order to draw their conclusions. This is regrettable since the opening section of this inscription provides a fair amount of information about the Buddhist doctrinal foundations that would have likely influenced the composer(s) of the inscription. If scholars hope to better understand the form, or forms, of Buddhism being referenced throughout the inscription, the entire inscription must be taken into account, not merely part of it.

¹⁰ The inscription reads *sāmbhoga*° instead of *sambhoga*°. Additionally, *nirmāṇa* and *nairmāṇika* both have geminized nasals (e.g., *nirmmāṇa nairmmāṇika*) and are not compounded with the term °*kāya*. Distinctions between ‘body’ and ‘embodiment’ for the Sanskrit term *kāya* will be discussed in detail in chapter three.

The opening eighteen lines of this inscription have generally, and somewhat generically, been categorized as depicting a form of Mahāyāna Buddhism. Evidence for this is found in stanzas praising the three-*kāya* doctrine mentioned above (st. I–III), reference to Buddha fields (st. V), stanzas praising bodhisattvas and the bodhisattva path (st. VII–VIII), and the compassionate emphasis placed on undertaking such a path in order to alleviate the suffering of the world (st. IX). These so-called Mahāyāna characteristics have long been noted by scholars examining this, and other, inscriptions. What is needed here, however, is an examination of the Buddhist elements in the inscription that endeavor to go beyond treating this so-called Mahāyāna Buddhism as a monolithic entity representing a singular and coherent form of Buddhism.

In other words, what is often uncritically referred to “the Mahāyāna” or “Mahāyāna Buddhism” is not, in reality, a homogenous tradition, sect, school, or movement supposedly representing some kind of break from earlier forms of Buddhism (Nattier 2003: esp. 193–97). Describing, therefore, the type of Buddhism alluded to in inscriptions like the Vat Sithor inscription as “Mahāyāna” in terms of a sect, school, or movement is not really helpful at all since such a designation relays little more than the vague generalities of the scholar corresponding to an imagined entity.¹¹ What needs to be understood is that in addition to honoring the embodiments of the Buddha and bodhisattvas this opening section of the inscription emphasizes the core defining feature of the Buddhist traditions of the time. This defining feature is the path of the

¹¹ Perhaps it is also significant to note that the actual term *mahāyāna* is never used in the Cambodian epigraphical record prior to the eleventh century, and then in the eleventh century only once. The point being that the word Mahāyāna is never used to describe Buddhist doctrine, practice or even Buddhist themselves during the tenth century, or preceding centuries for that matter. The inscription in which the term occurs is K. 410 which contains the dates 944, 947, and another damaged Śaka date. See Coédès (1929: 21, n. XIX).

bodhisattva; in other words, the dedicated Buddhist practicing the path to supreme and perfect enlightenment. Stanza VIII praises those individuals who undertake this path, and stanza IX praises those who in recognizing the afflictions of the world nevertheless undertake this path of awakening. Mahāyāna, then, conforms to Nattier’s observations on the meaning of Mahāyāna as understood in the Sanskrit text *Ugraparipṛcchā*. She writes:

For the authors of this sūtra, the Mahāyāna is nothing more, and nothing less, than a synonym of the “bodhisattva path.” For the *Ugra*, in other words, the Mahāyāna is not a school, a sect, or a movement, but a particular spiritual *vocation*, to be pursued within the existing Buddhist community. To be “Mahāyānist”—that is, to be a bodhisattva—thus does not mean to adhere to some new kind of “Buddhism,” but simply to practice Buddhism in its most rigorous and demanding form (2003: 195, italics in original).

I should be clear in that I am not suggesting any correlations between the *Ugraparipṛcchā* and the inscriptions of Cambodia. Instead, I am claiming that Nattier’s observations on Mahāyāna appear to hold true in the context of certain tenth-century inscriptions from Cambodia as well. If correct, the so-called Mahāyāna Buddhists discussed in the Vat Sithor inscription refer to, in the most general and basic sense, a community of Buddhist individuals following a common soteriological vocation—the path of the bodhisattva. If Nattier is correct, these Buddhists did not likely see themselves as part of some new movement or different kind of Buddhism called Mahāyāna; but rather simply as Buddhists (in a long line of Buddhists that could be traced back to the Buddha) who had opted to undertake the path of the bodhisattva, a path which meant (to them) simply “practicing Buddhism in its most rigorous and demanding form” in hopes of attaining the same stage of advancement as the Buddha himself, complete and perfect enlightenment.

This opening section also both explicitly and implicitly encapsulates the doctrinal foundations informing this vocational pursuit. On this point the inscription is clear. The path of the bodhisattva is specifically grounded in Yogācāra ('practitioners of *yoga*') doctrinal foundations. Often incorrectly glossed over as a type of Buddhist idealism, the term Yogācāra shares many of the problems that the term Mahāyāna does in that it is not a homogenous term, nor does it refer to a single identity or a monolithic doctrinal system. As is clearly stated in the Lusthaus' work on the subject, the term Yogācāra refers to "many texts and doctrinal positions, disseminated throughout a number of cultures in a variety of languages" (2003: 6).

Referring to Yogācāra as a particular school should be avoided, and this kind of language has created some misconceptions. Highlighting Yogācāra influence and doctrinal foundations in the Vat Sithor inscription is not an invitation to claim for the presence of so-called Yogācāra schools of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia. This is as misleading as speaking of Mahāyāna schools. The presence of epistemological Yogācāra terms like *cittamātra* (st. VIII) reveal that the vocational pursuit of the path of the bodhisattva was informed by, or framed within, the epistemology of Yogācāra and its doctrinal foundations, nothing more.

The prime example of a Yogācāra doctrinal foundation is the presence of the three-*kāya* doctrine mentioned above.¹² While various embodiments of Buddha systems were in place prior to the development of Yogācāra forms of thought and practice, it was in Yogācāra circles that the three-*kāya* model developed beyond earlier

¹² Alex Wayman once noted that, "It is significant that the theory of three *buddha* bodies arose in the Yogācāra school" (1965: 69, italics in original). While this particular work of Wayman's is a bit dated, his observation is valid concerning the origin of the *trikāya* system. For an updated study, see Makransky (1997). The topic of the *trikāya* receives ample attention in chapter three.

formulations.¹³ Another example of Yogācāra influence is found in the explicit reference to the central epistemological position of Yogācāra thought mentioned above, *cittamātra* (st. VIII). Often literally translated as ‘mind-only,’ *cittamātra* refers to the epistemological position that everything we know, conceive, are aware of and so forth are known through cognition. In other words, everything we know is ‘nothing but mind constructions’ (*cittamātra*) or ‘nothing but conscious constructions’ (*vijñaptimātra*), and we often confuse these mental constructions or interpretations of the world for the world itself.¹⁴

Other indicators of Yogācāra influence in the inscription are also present outside of the opening eighteen lines. For example, stanza twenty-eight states how the *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita rekindled the teachings of texts like the *Madhyāntavibhāga* (*The Discriminations of Middle from Extremes*), an important text in many Yogācāra circles.

Section II: Stanzas X–XVIII (Side A Lines 19–36)¹⁵

The second section of the Vat Sithor inscription contains a panegyric for Jayavarman V (r. c. 968–1000/1001). Besides the typical poetic embellishments lavished on the king that focus on aesthetic exaggeration so characteristic of inscriptions in South and Southeast Asia, the opening stanza of this section contains an important piece of historical information in the form of a date. Stanza X indicates that in 890 Śaka (968 CE) Jayavarman V began his reign.

¹³ Williams (2010: 172–82) provides a general overview on the bodies of the Buddha.

¹⁴ See Lusthaus (2003: 538–39) for a succinct summary of what Yogācāra practitioners perceived to be the problem with how the world is viewed.

¹⁵ Cœdès’ summary of the inscription contains a minor typo since he wrote that section II of the inscription began at stanza IX and ended at XVIII (*IC* 6: 196). This is incorrect. The second section begins at stanza X. This is obviously a minor typo in that Cœdès correctly indicated on the previous page that section I ended at stanza IX.

Although perhaps nothing more than poetic exaggeration meant to enhance the qualities of the king, stanza XIII indicates that disorder and improper moral conduct were endemic prior to his ascension, something which he supposedly addressed and corrected during his reign. This allusion to the lapse in moral discipline may be more than stock poetic praise since: (1) the primary purpose of the inscription was to proclaim Jayavarman's official order regarding the maintenance and regulation of Buddhist hermitages and monasteries, and (2) the section devoted to the *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita (section III, stanzas XIX–L) states how he reinvigorated Buddhist practices that had lapsed.

Section III: Stanzas XIX–L (Side A Lines 37–50 and Side B Lines 1–50)

Writing with regard to the reign of Jayavarman V (r. c. 968–1000/01), the historian L. P. Briggs once noted that, “There is probably no reign in the history of the ancient Khmers in which more distinguished ministers, scholars, and dignitaries are mentioned in the inscriptions” (1951: 135). One such dignitary was the Buddhist *ācārya* (‘master’) Kīrtipaṇḍita.¹⁶ Section three, which comprises the largest section of the entire inscription, is devoted to eulogizing the activities of this eminent Buddhist. The amount of space devoted to Kīrtipaṇḍita, more than three times the amount of space devoted to the king, suggests that he was an especially important person during this time period; which, in turn, suggests that advocates of Buddhist traditions had continued to become more influential during this period.

All that is known about Kīrtipaṇḍita comes from this inscription. Like the Buddhist Kavindrārimathana before him who was active during much of Rājendravarman's reign

¹⁶ Readers are also directed to an article by Peter Sharrock (2012) focusing on Kīrtipaṇḍita that appeared during the writing of this dissertation.

(944–c. 968), Kīrtipaṇḍita was responsible for part of the building regime during the reign of both king Rājendravarman as well as his son Jayavarman V.¹⁷ Whether Kīrtipaṇḍita held a specific titled position with official privileges and responsibilities associated with such construction is unknown; however, the conclusion that he played an important role in this field is supported by the inscription which indicates that he erected and consecrated new Buddhist images, as well as repaired previously installed Buddhist images that had been damaged or neglected. The founding of these images often coincided with the construction of shrines (*prāsāda*), gates (*dvāra*), hermitages (*āśrama*), and reservoirs (*jalāśaya*). Kīrtipaṇḍita was also responsible for performing special rites within the palace that ensured such goals as the pacification and prosperity of the kingdom. References to the rites of pacification (*śānti*) and prosperity (*puṣṭi*) also suggests that tantric elements (also present in non-Buddhist traditions) emphasizing a repertoire of elaborate, yet purportedly efficacious, forms of praxis were beginning to exert some level of influence in tenth-century Cambodia. Other indications suggesting that certain aspects of tantric forms of Buddhism were being adopted is found elsewhere in the inscription as well. For example, the third section of the inscription also notes how Kīrtipaṇḍita traveled about for tantric texts (st. XXIX).

Section IV: Stanzas LI–LV (Side C Lines 1–10)

This section begins by reiterating that Jayavarman’s decree outlining what permissible activities should be followed, and that his orders adhere to the Buddha’s Dharma. The main purpose of this section is to proclaim that all the monthly festivals described in the teachings (Skt. *śāstrāḥ*) are to be regularly maintained for the benefit of

¹⁷ Stanza XLIX clearly establishes that Kīrtipaṇḍita was active during Rājendravarman’s reign.

all living beings, and that the eleventh *nakṣatra* ('constellation' / 'asterism') of *pūrvaphalguṇī* ('First Reddish One' = Leonis) were considered most auspicious.

Section V: Stanzas LVI–LXV (Side C Lines 11–30)

The inscription then continues with some of the permissible observances and practices of the Buddhist community, such as the number of times to sound the community gong which demarcates the time slots of religious activities (st. LVI–LVII). Among some of the more interesting pieces of information is a brief discussion on what constitutes a properly consecrated monastery, as opposed to a building merely serving as a storage facility (st. LX–LXII). A key technical term used in stanza LXI, *brahmapuṇya* ('merit of Brahma,' a special and immense form of merit), is particularly important in that the usage of the term in the Vat Sithor inscription corresponds exactly to its usage in the *Samṅhabhedavastu* of the Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya, and this observation suggests that the Buddhist monks at Vat Sithor may have followed this particular Vinaya tradition. The possibility that early Cambodian Buddhists followed the Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya has been previously suggested by Snellgrove (2001: 819), but no evidence was provided to support this claim. Connecting the use of the term *brahmapuṇya* in stanza LXI with its use in the Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya, however, appears to support Snellgrove's initial observation. If true, it will be more accurate to refer to these tenth-century Buddhists as Mūlasarvāstivādin monks and refrain from calling them "Mahāyāna" monks as if the latter referred to some kind of school or branch of Buddhism. The term *brahmapuṇya* is discussed in more detail in chapter two's translation notes.

The last reference to Kīrtipaṇḍita also occurs in this section. The reference occurs in the last stanza of the section (st. LXV), and although the reference is only implicit it

appears quite clear that individual alluded to is, indeed, Kīrtipaṇḍita. After recording the proper establishment of the monastery, the last stanza in the section concludes by indicating that Kīrtipaṇḍita took up permanent residence at the monastery. This appears to indicate that Kīrtipaṇḍita may have been a Buddhist monk.

Section VI: Stanzas LXVI–LXXXII (Side C Lines 31–50 and Side D Lines 1–14)

The next section records certain rites and regulations of the community. The inscription proclaims that at allotted times all members of the community, especially the officiant in charge of ritual offerings, (Skt. *yājaka*), are to perform the rites prescribed by the Buddha (st. LXVII). Keeping in line with many Buddhist textual sources, another stanza indicates that members of the Buddhist community are not to partake in Brahmanical sacrificial rites (st. LXVIII). Although not explicit, chapter seven demonstrates that this stanza was likely referring to sacrificial rites involving animals. The presence of tantric elements can be observed in a stanza which records that the *purohita* ('sacerdotal minister') worthy of donations/fees is the one "who is learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, *vidyā*, *mantra*, *mudrā* and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṇṭā*)" (st. LXIX). This appears to be a redefinition of traditional Brahmanical role for purposes of extolling the importance of being knowledgeable in Buddhist ritual rites as well. These are but a few examples of the rites and regulations outlined in this section. Too often some of the lines in this section have been misread and then used to suggest that the demarcations between Buddhists and Brahmanical officials were somehow uniquely strained in early Cambodia, that these two groups were even more antagonistic toward one another than in other areas of the world; however, a closer look at other Buddhist textual sources, including monastic guidelines found in the Vinaya traditions, demonstrates that

inscriptions like Vat Sithor contain stanzas that are merely reiterating particular normative monastic positions. The number of references in Buddhist textual sources, for example, that decry the efficacy of Brahmanical sacrifices is overwhelming. Postulating, therefore, a metanarrative that suggests a particularly antagonistic clash between Buddhists and Brahmins entirely misses the point that the Vat Sithor inscription is a document primarily concerned with proper behavior and activities in a Buddhist monastic setting. Lines that indicate Buddhists were not to participate in certain activities were not proclamations highlighting for outside parties some kind of historical bad-blood between two groups; instead, they were simply reminders to Buddhist monks that certain activities performed by other sectarian groups co-existing in the same proximity violated certain monastic regulations. This, of course, is not to suggest that there may not have been any friction whatsoever between tenth-century Buddhists in Cambodia and other regional Brahmanical groups, but rather it is to argue that such friction was neither extreme nor unique to a tenth-century Cambodian setting. It was simply part of a Buddhist and Brahmin rhetoric inherent in both circles since the formation of Buddhism in early India.

Unfortunately, this section is also incomplete since the latter part, beginning on side D of the stele, is badly damaged. Stanzas LXXVI–LXXVII are ruined and unreadable; stanzas LXXVIII–LXXX contain obvious lacunae.

Section VII: Stanza LXXXIII–C (Side D Lines 15–50)

The final section represents a typical closing eulogy highlighting the virtues and benefits of properly adhering to the Dharma and respecting esteemed gurus. The section also gives warning to those who would demean the Dharma. Such warnings are sometimes followed with specific repercussions.

An Overview of Other Tenth-Century Buddhist-Related Inscriptions

As previously mentioned, on occasion it will be worthwhile to refer to other tenth-century epigraphical sources when discussing Buddhist traditions during this time; therefore, it is necessary to provide a basic overview of those sources. In general, inscriptions with Buddhist content refers to those inscriptions that contain varying degrees of Buddhist elements, sometimes disparate, that may, or may not be, the primary focus of the inscription. Such content may document Buddhist activities like performing donations for the sake of accruing merit, praise Buddhist beings such as the bodhisattvas, or merely make a passing reference to a Buddhist doctrinal concept. Although there are exceptions, one would be hard-pressed to label the majority of these inscriptions as purely Buddhist inscriptions since such a strict sectarian label is misleading in that the focus of these inscriptions is often on other matters such as land grants and revenue, with the inclusion of Buddhist elements sometimes playing a secondary, tertiary, or even inconsequential role. Nevertheless, an overview of the Buddhist elements contained in these inscriptions will provide the starting point for a deeper examination and analysis into the types of Buddhism being practiced in Cambodia during the tenth century.

The tenth-century epigraphical record is quite large; however, the number of inscriptions during this period that contain Buddhist information is rather small. There are twenty-nine tenth-century inscriptions that either document Buddhist activities, praise Buddhist beings, record an individual connected with Buddhism, or simply make a passing reference to a Buddhist concept, and most of these inscription are from the mid- to late tenth century (table1-1). The majority of them belong to the reign of Rājendravarman and his succeeding son Jayavarman V. Sixteen were likely composed

during the reign of Rājendravarman; eleven were probably composed during Jayavarman's reign. Inscription K. 432 is an exception in that it was likely composed during the end of Yaśovarman's reign (889 – ca. 910) which concluded at the beginning of the tenth century. K. 1154 does not contain enough information to assign it with certainty to either Rājendravarman's or Jayavarman's reign, although it is clearly a tenth-century inscription (Pou, *NIC* 129). Although this is a relatively small number of inscriptions, one should note that these inscriptions nevertheless represent a significant increase in Buddhist references since between the entire ninth to the first half of the tenth century there are only around three or five Buddhist-related inscriptions in the known Cambodian epigraphical record.¹⁸

These twenty-nine inscriptions only represent, at best, around 8 to 10 percent of the total inscriptions currently known to have been composed during the tenth-century in Cambodia.¹⁹ Ascertaining a more specific percentage is exceedingly difficult due to the

¹⁸ Indravarman's reign (r. 877–889) has two inscriptions with Buddhist elements (K. 655 and K. 495), while Yaśovarman's reign (r. 889–c. 910) contains either three (K. 290, K. 772, and K. 432) or just two (K. 290 and K. 432) depending on where one chronologically places the undated K. 772. I believe K. 772, like K. 202, probably belongs to the later reign of Rājendravarman. See chapter four for an additional discussion on both K. 202 and K. 772.

¹⁹ This rough estimate is based on the classificatory information found in the Cœdès (*IC*, 8) and Jacques (1971). Cœdès' work includes the following statistics:

Number of dated and contextually dated inscriptions between 822 Śaka (900 CE) and the beginning of Rājendravarman's reign in 944 CE = 48 (34 and 14 respectively).

Number of dated and contextually dated inscriptions during Rājendravarman's reign (944–c. 967/968) = 53 (36 and 17 respectively).

Number of dated and contextually dated inscriptions during Jayavarman V's reign (c. 968–c. 1000/1001) = 72 (53 and 19 respectively).

The total number of dated and contextually dated tenth-century inscriptions according to Cœdès' estimates is then 173. It should be noted that I am following Cœdès in counting inscriptions like K. 231 as four tenth-century inscriptions (e.g., 231¹, 231², 231³, & 231^{S1}).

To this number of 173, we could add Cœdès' provisional list of 55 additional undated tenth-century inscriptions for a total of 228 possible tenth-century inscriptions. Jacques' supplement would not likely

current lack of a master list that has eliminated duplicate inscriptions, added unpublished ones, and revised and consolidated other older circulating lists (Lustig 2009: 104–09). The fact that many inscriptions are undated also presents a number of difficulties. While some of these inscriptions can be attributed to the tenth century based on contextual material such as the recording of specific information pertaining to certain reigns, or by linguistic and paleographic methodologies relating to such things as vocabulary, script, and style, other inscriptions remain problematic and can only be included within a general range that may precede or extend beyond the temporal parameters of the tenth century. Nevertheless, an estimate of 8 to 10 percent is sufficient enough to demonstrate that despite the clear indication of increased references to Buddhist elements in the epigraphical record of the mid- to late tenth century Buddhist traditions must have remained subordinate to other sectarian traditions such as forms of Śaivism in terms of prestige, power, and popularity among the majority of society's upper echelons during this period.

The significant increase in Buddhist-related inscriptions also coincides with an overall increase in the number of inscriptions that were composed at this time. More inscriptions come from the tenth and eleventh centuries than any other period in Cambodia's history, and the primary reasons for this are directly connected to changes taking place in the political and administrative infrastructure. In looking at this pattern, Michael Vickery (1985: 226) addressed two questions: (1) the rise to power of Sūryavarman I (r. 1002–49), and (2) the dynamics of state and political development in

affect this figure much, if at all, since the few inscriptions listed as occurring in Śaka tenth-century (c. 978–c. 1077 CE) appear to be late Śaka tenth-century, and therefore, they probably belong to the eleventh century CE.

Angkorian Cambodia. With regard to the dynamics of state and political development, Vickery first revisited Philippe Stern's work concerning the cyclical pattern of development at Angkor in which Stern observed a pattern of priorities in the construction activities of four Angkorian kings: Indravarman (r. 877–889), Yaśovarman (r. 889–c. 910), Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 968), and Jayavarman VII (r. 1182–c. 1210).²⁰ Vickery (1985: 228) wrote:

Each of these reigns began with some kind of public works, usually large reservoirs (Indravarman, Yaśovarman, Jayavarman), or the rehabilitation of the capital, including its waterworks (Rājendravarman). Then they built ancestral temples in honour of their immediate ancestors, and finally a temple mountain for the worship of the central state cult. The pattern is clearest for the first two and last of those reigns, and appears somewhat attenuated in the case of Rājendravarman.

But according to Stern there is a “zone of imprecision” from Rājendravarman until Jayavarman VII because such an ordered pattern of construction cannot be identified. Vickery noted, however, that this very same “zone of imprecision” includes the reigns of Jayavarman V (r. c. 968–1000/01) and Sūryavarman I (r. c. 1002–1050) from which the greatest number of inscriptions are produced, and at which time, together with the following reign of Udayādityavarman II (r. 1050–1066), a large number of works of construction were undertaken. Thus Vickery (1985: 229) noted, “The apparent change of rhythm, then, is not due to any relative lack of evidence, but must have been real, resulting from important changes in administrative procedures, social organization, or economic requirements.” Vickery's follow-up observations are worth quoting at length.

²⁰ I have updated the dates to reflect the majority of current scholarship. Also, there is still much debate concerning such king lists and the dates associated with certain rulers, but I have set these problems aside in order to focus on the patterns found in the epigraphical record that will help place tenth-century forms of Buddhism in a proper context. For more on such debates, see Golzio (2000 and 2001) and Vickery (2001). Both authors also consider the observations and conclusions of previous scholarship.

There is also, as noted above, general scholarly agreement that the period of Jayavarman V and Sūryavarman saw a rapid development in the administrative apparatus, the bureaucracy, a conclusion which has been reached on the basis of the much greater number of inscriptions dealing with administrative questions: land acquisition and transfer, foundation of temples directly by officials rather than by kings, and inscriptions extolling the achievements of official families. The increase in official inscriptions is both absolute and relative to the number of royal inscriptions, that is, those apparently emanating directly from the king or deal mainly with his activities and initiatives. Whereas in the reigns of Indravarman and Yaśovarman the great majority of all inscriptions, and in particular the most important, dealing with the construction of important temples and other edifices, are royal, the number of such impressive royal inscriptions declines under Rājendravarman, and in the reign of Jayavarman V not only are there more official inscriptions, but some of the most impressive new works of construction are attributed to named officials and the king's initiative is ignored.

There is thus another rhythm corresponding to that found by Stern. The latter is accompanied by a distinctive royal imprint on the epigraphic record while in his "zone of imprecision" the records are mainly authored by officials. That is, Stern's rhythm is gradually attenuated as the epigraphic record indicates increasing importance of aristocrat-officials vis-a-vis the central royalty (1985: 229).

Thus a fundamental change began to take place within the administrative infrastructure at the end of Yaśovarman's reign and the beginning of Rājendravarman's reign. The administrative infrastructure expanded and became more complex, which, in turn, increased the roles and influences of administrative officials. So, in short, beginning with the reign of Rājendravarman, and peaking during the reigns of Jayavarman V and Sūryavarman I, there was a distinct decrease in the number of royal inscriptions and a concurrent increase in the number of inscriptions concerned with the deeds and prerogatives of administrative officials whose roles had become increasingly more significant within the Angkorian administrative infrastructure. This pattern is present even in the small sample of Buddhist-related inscriptions listed previously.

Many of Vickery's observations remain valid today. Eileen Lustig (2009), however, provides the most recent and thorough work to date on this topic. With regard to the distinction between royal and non-royal inscriptions she writes:

We see two quite different expressions of royal power in the many roles of the ruler mentioned in the non-royal inscriptions in the 10th and 11th centuries and the content of the royal inscriptions predominating in the 9th, and 12th–13th centuries. The royal inscriptions, many issued as edicts, express power, stress the generosity, bravery and wisdom of the kings, and compare their qualities with those of the gods. Those of the officials emphasize material wealth and status, often referring to their ancestry, the purchase of lands, their endowment of religious foundations and the privileges granted to them (2009: 132).

Again, even the small sample of inscriptions from this period focusing only on Buddhist-related material support many of Vickery and Lustig's observations. For the first time in the mid-tenth century we have important Buddhist officials such as Kavīndrārimathana and Kīrtipaṇḍita recorded in the inscriptions (e.g., K. 266, 267, 268, and 111). Praise is lavished on these officials for their deeds and various building projects that included: installing Buddhist images, building temples and shrines, performing rites for the ruler, constructing reservoirs, repairing older temples and images, and so forth. Kavīndrārimathana was responsible for the construction of Rājendravarman's Mebon temple, as well as a large reservoir and smaller canal. In addition to a number of building projects, Kīrtipaṇḍita performed pacification and prosperity rites for the king and his territory. Both officials erected many Buddhist images at various sites. The emphasis on such things as material wealth, the purchase of lands, and endowment of religious foundations is also clearly expressed in the Vat Kdei inscription (K. 157) which documents how the official Vīrendravikhyāta and his family constructed a sanctuary for Avalokiteśvara and Prajñāpāramitā. Other notable accomplishments are listed such as how Vīrendravikhyāta also had a large reservoir

constructed for bathing the images and watering the land, and how he had property set aside for a monastery. One of the Peung Preah Put Loe inscriptions (K. 173) records how a Buddhist *ācārya* named Kīrttivara performed a number of donative activities at the sacred site of Mount Mahendra (i.e., Mount Kulen). The Prasat Pram inscription (K. 180) records some of the endowments of Śivasoma, the *guru* of Rudrācārya, an *ācārya* of Rājendravarman, including how the revenue from one of his donations was allocated among several Śaivite sites and one Buddhist location.²¹ The non-royal Don Tri inscription (K. 198) records how Upendra, an individual who had family employed by Rājendravarman, donated property to Ārya Maitri (i.e., the Buddha Maitreya). These are just a few examples indicating the increased importance of officials during a period when the administrative infrastructure in early Cambodia was undergoing significant change that included expansion and increased complexity.

Donors, Land, Merit, and the Cult of Images

A majority of the inscriptions in table 1.1 are intimately connected with the landscape in some form, predominantly in the form of revenue, administration, and stewardship. Often the inscriptions record the installation of a Buddhist image for the primary purpose of recording which tracts of land were to be presided over by the divinity, along with noting the specific revenue and resources to be allocated to the

²¹ A number of servants, grass, and flowers were allocated to Śrīghaṇa (i.e., the Buddha) of Amarendrapura (st. XLII–XLIII). This inscription has been often misinterpreted as an example of religious syncretism because for some it seemed odd that a Śaivite was also allocating a portion of his donation to the Buddha. This position has been heavily critiqued by Estève (2009: 335) who wrote, “À la lecture de ce fait, Bhattacharya comprenait que « le Buddha (Śrīghaṇa) était adoré par les śivaïtes »; or, le texte parle seulement d’un partage de revenus. Il est évident qu’il peut sembler étonnant qu’un dévot de Śiva fasse des donations dans un même mouvement à Śiva et au Buddha. Mais le sens d’un tel comportement est loin d’être évident ; il ne saurait, en tout cas, correspondre à une définition du syncrétisme. Nous pouvons relever néanmoins l’existence d’un temple bouddhique à Amarendrapura sous le règne de Rājendravarman.”

divinity (or divinities).²² This is particular true of the Khmer language inscriptions (Buddhist and non-Buddhist related) that are much more concerned with practical socioeconomic matters than their Sanskrit counterparts.

The installation of Buddhist images is frequently recorded as a meritorious act that will benefit not only the donor on an individual scale, but also the wider community connected with the land over which the divinity is expected to preside over. The rhetoric behind Buddhist ideas on the economy of merit (the symbiotic exchange of material donations for religious merit) likely allowed for easier incorporation into established social and economic processes. The connection between merit acquisition, land, and Buddhist images is exemplified in the Vat Kdei inscription (K. 157). The stele records how after forest land had been cleared and a village had been constructed an image of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara was consecrated and installed for the welfare of both the land and its people. The inscription also notes how the water of a constructed reservoir was used to ritually bathe the two images of Avalokiteśvara and an image of Prajñāpāramitā; this water, in turn, was responsible for nourishing the surrounding land. Similarly, the Sanskrit portion of the Kôk Samrong inscription (K. 239) records how a

²² Here I should justify the use of terms such as *divine*, *divinity*, *divine being* to describe a Buddha or bodhisattva since they are words I will often employ for convenience throughout the dissertation. The Cambodian epigraphical is clear that the Buddha and bodhisattvas were considered *devas*, just like gods from other traditions such as Śiva, Viṣṇu, and Brahmā. This categorical equivalence is attested in K. 180 when the Devī at Maruktapura, the *liṅga* of Śivapurālaya, and the Śrīghaṇa (i.e., Buddha) of Amarendrapura are all explicitly referred to as the three *devas*. Skt. *maruktalasure devyāṃ liṅge śivapurālaye / amarendrapure pi śrīghaṇe sadbhaktivatsale // daśadvayam iman dāsavibhāgaṃ samakalpayat / triṣu deveṣu puṣpādikuśadānāya bhaktitah //*, Coedès (1913: 25). K. 214 also refers to a family's images of Avalokiteśvara and Prajñāpāramitā as *devas*. Skt. *tena pūrvvapraṭiṣṭhāpya gotrasya jagadīśvaram / munīndrajananī bhūyaḥ sthāpitāgniviyadvilaiḥ // pūrvvat tatra deveṣu kṛtvā gotrasya kalpanāṃ / dāsīdāsahiraṇyādī dravyaṃ so dād viśeṣataḥ //*, Coedès (IC 2: 204). These are just two among many examples. The word *deva* is often translated into English simply as 'god,' or sometimes as 'celestial being.' It comes from the root √div which means 'to shine' or 'be bright,' so more literally *devas* mean the 'shining ones' (often above). English words like *divinity* and *divine* are cognates of √div/*deva*, and thus I will use such terms because they are actually linguistically closer to the words used to describe these beings in the Sanskrit. The reader must abandon, however, many of the attached cultural meanings these words have gathered in the west, especially in connection with Christian traditions.

donor installed what appears to be a Lokeśvara *liṅga* and an accompanying sanctuary on the land in 961 CE with hopes of acquiring merit for his parents, the ruler, his *guru*, kinsmen, and friends.²³ The donor also expressed hope that his actions would alleviate the sufferings of others and lead to rebirth as the son of the Buddha (i.e., a bodhisattva). As is customary, it is the Khmer section of the inscription that is devoted to land transactions and the donations of various gifts such as cattle, servants, tracts of land, and so forth offered up to presiding tutelary deity Jagannāthakeśvara (presumably the divinity is equivalent to the *liṅga* mentioned in the Sanskrit section).

The donation and installation of images, and the ritual practices connected with these images, are the most common meritorious acts documented in the inscriptions. As mentioned above, not only was ritually installing an image in a sanctuary thought to bring about personal advantageous benefits, but such an action was believed to bring about widespread prosperity for the community and land. Some of common rituals associated with the images included: consecrations ceremonies such as the eye-opening rite that invited the divinity into the sanctuary and image (Skt. *unmīla*), ritual bathing of the images that resulted in merit (Skt. *snāna*), and the recitation of chants and hymns in the presence of the image.²⁴

²³ On the appropriation of terminology like *liṅga* by Buddhists in early Cambodia, Sanderson (2004: 424–25) writes, “The Mahāyāna was already well placed to do this [i.e., empower and protect the state], especially since it had provided itself through the Way of Mantras (*mantranayaḥ*, *mantrayānam*) with an elaborate and impressive system of rituals designed along Śaiva lines to offer its royal patrons exactly the protective and apotropaic benefits promised by their rivals. However, the Mahāyānist versatility of method (*upāyakauśalam*) that enabled this development went a step further among the Khmers. For they adopted the Śaiva practice of installing deities under names that incorporate that of the founder. Moreover, in the case of Lokeśvara, these names end in *-īśvara*, as do those of Śiva-images. Indeed in one case such a Lokeśvara is even referred to as a Liṅga [i.e., K. 239], a surprising inroad from Śaiva terminology.”

²⁴ cf. K. 111 and K. 157 for explicit references to these rites.

Often the Buddhist figures are invoked and installed as part of a triad, with some combination of the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, Prajñāpāramitā, and Vajrapāṇi being most common. The importance of the triadic configurations appears to be just as much a result of a pressure to compete with ubiquitous non-Buddhist triads in Cambodia (e.g., the triad Śiva, Viṣṇu, and Brahmā, to name one) as the number three's own significance within Buddhist traditions. With regard to the first, the epigraphical record sometimes describes Buddhist figures such as Avalokiteśvara and Vajrapāṇi by employing allusions to non-Buddhist deities. These descriptions often conjure up disparaging images of their competitors in order to elevate the status of the Buddhist figures. One of the Prasat Beng Vien inscriptions (K. 872), for example, praises the four-armed Avalokiteśvara as if he displayed, and inherently possessed, both the qualities of Śiva and Viṣṇu (i.e., Harihara).²⁵ The Bat Cum inscriptions (K. 266–286) place the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi in obvious juxtaposition with the god Indra in order to both appropriate the latter's abilities and to supersede them. The northern shrine inscription, for example, insists that Vajrapāṇi's thunderbolt, unlike Indra's, is not blunt, and it is capable of destroying pride (Skt. *mada*).²⁶

The number three itself, however, also has a various significant meanings within Buddhist traditions, and these meanings are occasionally referenced implicitly and explicitly in the inscriptions. The two most important triadic configurations in Buddhist traditions used in the inscriptions are the Three Jewels of Buddhism (the Buddha, the

²⁵ Skt. *caturbhujadharam vande lokesvaram ivesvaram / darśayantaṃ svaviṣṇutvañ caturyyugadhare kalau //*, Cœdès (IC 5: 99).

²⁶ The stanza uses to a pun to allude to Indra's inability to defeat the monster Mada. Skt. *śrīvajrapāṇir avatāṃ mahatāṃ vibhūtiṃ / yo dvinmadāpakṛtikalyam akunṭhitāgram // vajraṃ vahan prahasatīva sahasranetraṃ / saṃgrāmaṃvairimadakuṅṭhitavandhyavajram //*, Cœdès (1908b: 233).

Dharma, and the Saṅgha) and the Three Embodiments of the Buddha (the *dharmakāya*, the *sambhogakāya*, and the *nirmāṇakāya*). The Vat Sithor inscription references both of these important concepts, often embedding one triadic reference within another triadic reference.²⁷ K. 214 also references the Three Embodiments of the Buddha, while K. 432, K. 806, K. 239, K. 339, and K. 214 all praise the Three Jewels of Buddhism.

Rājendravarman and Expressions of Culture

The Mebon inscription of Rājendravarman opens with an invocation to the gods Śiva and his tripartite manifestation (i.e., the Trimūrti), Gaurī, Nārāyaṇa, Brahmā, and Gaṅgā (K. 528, st. I–VII).²⁸ This invocation is then followed by a long eulogy dedicated to Rājendravarman before recording his foundations which included: a Siddheśvara *liṅga* at Siddhaśivapura, a *liṅga* of Śarva and two images of Śarvāṇī also at Siddhaśivapura, two unnamed images during the inauguration of Bhadreśvara, an image of Śauri and Gaurī and *liṅga* of Śaṃbhu to the south of Yaśodharataṭṭāka, a *liṅga* of Smarāri, two images of Śiva and Pārvatī in the likeness of his father and mother, and an image of Viṣṇu and Brahmā (st. CCI–CCVIII).²⁹

The Śaivite character of this inscription is obvious, and is not surprising since localized forms of Śaivism were the dominant sectarian traditions patronized by most of

²⁷ See chapter two for detailed examination the triads referenced in the Vat Sithor inscription.

²⁸ See Finot (1925b: 309–52) for the Mebon inscription. See Sharan (1981: 39–94) for an English translation (of Finot’s French translation). Regarding the so-called Trimūti manifestation, the opening stanza of this inscription is clear that Śiva divides himself into three (Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Śiva) to give himself the pleasure of creation, preservation, and destruction. Therefore, in the tenth-century Cambodian context of this particular inscription, the roles of these three gods are not equal (or even separate), but are ultimately just manifestations of a supreme Śiva.

²⁹ Śarva, Śauri, Smarāri and Śaṃbhu are different manifestations of Śiva. Śarvāṇī and Gaurī are different manifestations of Umā/Pārvatī.

the ruling elite during the Pre-Angkorian and Angkorian eras. Despite this overt Śaivite characteristic, amid this important inscription is another stanza that has attracted the attention of scholars desiring to highlight the emerging influence and presence of Buddhist traditions during the reign of Rājendravarman. In the section eulogizing Rājendravarman, stanza 172 proclaims that:

Nothing could compare with the full measure of his (Rājendravarman's) virtues: having become aware of the Buddhist doctrine, he honored it unerringly alongside other sectarian traditions.³⁰

Another similar isolated reference to Buddhist doctrine is couched within another royal inscription of Rājendravarman: the Pre Rup inscription (K. 806), which begins with another invocation to Śiva (Śambhu). Immediately following references to the *Mahābhārata* and the Vedas (st. CCLXXIV), stanza 275 mentions the Yogācāra

³⁰ K. 528, st. CLXXII. Skt. *yasyopamānaṃ sañjātan na kiñcid guṇavistaraiḥ / vuddhvā vauddhaṃ mataṃ mene nyatīrthair api nānyathā //*, Finot (1925b). Finot (1925b: 348) admittedly had some difficulty with the second verse. He translated the entire stanza as follows: Rien n'était comparable à l'ampleur de ses vertus : ayant compris la doctrine bouddhique, il n'avait pas d'idées fausses, même sous l'influence d'autres maîtres (?). More recently, Julia Estève (2009: 363) has translated the stanza as: Rien ne souffrait la comparaison avec la multitude de ses qualités ; s'étant éveillé, il croyait la doctrine bouddhique et non autrement même en compagnie d'autres maîtres.

I believe that both *anyatīrthaiḥ* and *nānyathā* should be rendered adverbially in relation to *mene*. Unlike both Finot and Estève, however, I do not think *anyatīrtha* has to be rendered as narrowly as 'd'autres maîtres' ('other masters'), although this does preserve the basic sense of the word. Instead, the term appears to be more broadly encompassing other (non-Buddhist) sectarian traditions, and by extension the doctrines espoused by these other groups. This meaning is well attested in the related word *anyatīrthika* (BHS, s.v. *anyatīrthika*).

Lastly, rendering *nānyathā* in an overly exclusive manner to mean 'no other' or 'not otherwise' does not make much contextual sense in this inscription (or others) which clearly depicts Rājendravarman honoring other traditions (in the sense of giving due respect). The Sanskrit *anyathā* can also be translated adverbially as 'falsely,' 'erroneously,' etc. Here I take the negative particle *na* as a double negative, thus rendering *nānyathā* as 'unerringly.' On the other hand, an alternative that is closer to 'no other' or 'not otherwise' could be 'one-pointedly' (i.e., 'he honored it one-pointedly . . .'). I thank Travis Smith and Jason Neelis for taking the time to discuss this stanza with me.

epistemological and soteriological concept of *vijñapti(-mātra)*, often glossed as ‘nothing but cognition or consciousness.’³¹

Because of him (i.e., Rājendravarman)—who arose by the elevation of his own Dharma—the righteous entreaty of king Yaśovarman, which was free (*śūnyā*) of motive (*artha*) just as the object (*artha*) of cognition (*vijñapti*) spoken about by the Yogācāra³² (is also ultimately empty = *śūnyā*), attained a significance similar to the Triad (i.e., Buddha, Dharma and Saṅgha).³³

With regard to such passing references that highlight a purported knowledge of Buddhist doctrines by the king, one should be cautious in placing too much weight on Rājendravarman’s level of personal interest in, or affiliation to, Buddhist traditions during his time. While there appears no need to doubt the inscription’s claim that Rājendravarman was familiar—to some extent—with influential Buddhist doctrines being espoused within his domains, no strong evidence exists to suggest that these panegyric claims had any other purpose beyond boasting about the diverse knowledge, respectful piousness, and magnanimousness of the king. Embedded within the panegyric section of the previously mentioned Mebon inscription, for example, the reference to knowledge of Buddhist doctrine is just one of many praiseworthy stanzas highlighting the king’s multitude of virtues relating to, for lack of better phrase, the prestige of oral and literary knowledge. The proceeding stanza in the Mebon inscription

³¹ This concept is often misrepresented and misunderstood in writings by claiming that Buddhists maintain(ed) that ‘nothing but consciousness exists.’ As discussed in Lusthaus (2003), however, *vijñapti-mātra* more accurately is a concept of cognitive closure which instead means “all our efforts to get beyond ourselves are nothing but projections of our consciousness.” And thus, the term *vijñapti-mātra* is treated as “an epistemic caution, not an ontological pronouncement” (2003: 5–6).

³² In other words, spoken about by those individuals who adhere to the Yogācāra epistemological position that everything about reality is known through cognition (our minds), and this mental interpretation of the world should not be confused with reality itself since such subject/object distinctions that comprise these interpretations are ultimately ‘empty’ of any independent and intrinsic nature.

³³ Skt. *yācñā yaśovarmmanṛpasya yogācāroktavijñaptir ivārthaśūnyā / dharmmyā svadharmmoddaraṇodhatena yenārthavattāṃ gamitā trayīva //*

highlights the king's inclination toward grammar (CLXXI), a following stanza indicates how he followed Manu (CLXXIV), and another stanza explains how his knowledge of the four Vedas assisted in warding off misfortunes (LXXXI).³⁴

So too in the latter example from the Pre Rup inscription, the solitary reference to knowledge of the Buddhist Yogācāra concept of *vijñapti-mātra* is couched among other Sanskrit lines praising the king's diverse knowledge and accomplishments. Stanza 274 of the Pre Rup inscription—a stanza that comes just before the Buddhist reference—praises Rājendravarman's restoration of the great city of Yaśodharapura (i.e., Angkor) by likening the success of this accomplishment to how Vyāsa, son of Satyavān, filled the *Mahābhārata* with the Vedas. Stanza XIV highlights Rājendravarman's study of the Vedas, stanza XVIII cites that the king studied six means of knowledge and employs an array of Vedāntic terminology, and several other stanzas simply boast of the king's high-level of knowledge (e.g., st. XLIX and st. CCLIX).

As Julia Estève (2009) has demonstrated in her critique of claims purporting religious syncretism in Angkorian Cambodia, prestige associated with “savoir pan-religieux,” and the need to boast of it in epigraphical documents, is a common practice that spans the entire Angkorian period.³⁵ For Estève this is merely a formal “l'expression d'une culture,” and this is not indicative of any actual religious affiliation. Regarding the specific stanza from the Mebon stele inscription cited above, she writes

³⁴ The Sanskrit word for 'grammar' in stanza CLXXI is *śabdaśāstra* ('science or treatise on words'). This could refer to Sanskrit grammar in general (much like the related term *śabdaśāsana*), or it could refer to a particular grammar text called the Śabdaśāstra.

³⁵ Estève (2009: 359–65). Also note her comments on inscriptions K. 806 and K. 834 for similar isolated references to Buddhist concepts, and how such inscriptions can be understood as an expression of culture.

that the stanza is a kind of homage to Buddhism without representing any real kind of affiliation (363).

Of course such references, even if isolated, do point to a Buddhist presence in tenth-century Cambodia. The reason for taking the time here to demonstrate that there is a difference between panegyric expressions glorifying a ruler's broad spectrum of religious oral and literary knowledge and actual religious affiliation is that this misconception is only one part of a broader misconception relating to the relationship between the rulers' Rājendravarman and Jayavarman V and their role in either promoting or hindering forms of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia. The current paradigm (either assumed or explicitly stated) is that both Rājendravarman and his son Jayavaraman V, despite upholding the localized Śaivite customs associated with rulers since the time of Jayavarman II, were sympathetic to forms of Buddhism, and therefore, both rulers, to a certain extent, tolerated forms of Buddhism operating alongside other competing sectarian traditions within their domain. This royal toleration, it is assumed, was the primary reason that enabled Buddhist traditions to co-exist with other more dominant sectarian traditions of the time. The assumption that these rulers were sympathetic to, and tolerant of, forms of Buddhism is partly the result of previous scholarship's interpretation of those isolated references discussed above about the rulers honoring and being knowledgeable of Buddhist traditions in the inscriptions. If one questions the extent to which these rulers had any real sympathy for, or affiliation with, Buddhism, then one should also question this notion of tolerance and passive patronage which is linked to assumptions of sympathy and affiliation.

In writing about religion during the reign Rājendravarman, L. P. Briggs cited part of stanza 172 of the Mebon inscription discussed above and concluded:

The inscriptions of Rājendravarman II show a great variety of religious practices and an *extreme toleration* [. . .] Although he was a Śivaite, as his posthumous name indicates, Rājendravarman II was *very tolerant of Buddhism*. In his early life he seems to have made a deep study of Buddhism and to have decided to remain a Śivaite (Briggs, 1951: 131, italics my own).

Based on these remarks, there are fundamental misconceptions relating to both the primary purpose of the particular stanza within the Mebon inscription and how much of a role Rājendravarman and other kings in tenth-century Cambodia played in determining the success or failure of a particular religious tradition. Again, what should be understood as simply a praiseworthy expression of diverse religious knowledge meant to elevate the stature of Rājendravarman has been interpreted by Briggs as an indication of a royal policy sanctioning religious toleration.³⁶

Briggs was not alone in his thinking. For example, in his discussion on the religious environment of ancient Cambodia, M. K. Sharan (1981: 229) wrote that “The two kings (i.e., Rājendravarman and his son Jayavarman V) helped to establish Buddhism on a second footing in Cambodia.” Once again, implicit in these observations is the assumption that it was the ruler’s active initiative, as well as the ruler’s toleration and sanction, that were primarily responsible for the establishment and successful co-existence of Buddhist traditions during the mid- to late tenth century.

We need to examine the assumption that Buddhist traditions operating and competing within the same socio-political environment as other sectarian groups

³⁶ It could also be argued that contemporary scholarship’s tendency to understand sectarian co-existence in terms of needed toleration or syncretism is an anachronism.

required the toleration of those ruling in early Cambodia for their success and presence. While some level of royal support and dependence was surely necessary, overemphasizing this explanation as the primary reason for the expansion of Buddhist traditions during this period is overly reductive in that it myopically stresses functional sociopolitical influences at the cost of marginalizing factors connected with tradition itself that also account, in part, for its own success and failure. Buddhist religious practices, ideologies, soteriologies, and practitioners surely also played a role in the increased influence of the tradition. In short, you cannot make claims about a religion without examining the religion itself. The point here may be subtle, but important. By questioning the uncritical and overemphasized correlation between the alleged needed support of Rājendravarman and Jayavarman and the success of Buddhist traditions, some of the focus of this particular discourse can be shifted to the Buddhists themselves who likely played a more proactive and influential role in establishing and expanding their own traditions in Cambodia during this time. Again, stressing the agency of Buddhists themselves, however, does not mean that a certain level of royal support and dependence would not have been required, only that such support and dependence does not satisfactorily explain by itself the expansion of the Buddhist traditions during this period.³⁷ Nor does royal sanction alone actually explain why Rājendravarman and Jayavarman would have offered such tolerance and support to less influential and less dominant Buddhist groups and individuals in the first place.

³⁷ Lustig (2009: 131) observes a certain level of necessary dependence in her analysis of royal involvement described in the epigraphical record compared with non-royal inscriptions. She suggests that the authors of non-royal inscriptions were “explicitly stating their dependence on the ruler in various ways for their position, status, and wealth and for sanctioning their actions.”

Yogācāra and Tantric Ideas in Tenth-Century Cambodia

A possible explanation for the increasing success of Buddhist traditions may be related to the emerging tantric Buddhist presence that is first attested during this period.³⁸ Elements of tantric Buddhism first appear in the epigraphical record during mid-tenth century, and it is very likely that these emerging forms of Buddhism provided access to the same rites and expressions of power and piety employed by other non-Buddhist traditions, such as the more dominant forms of Śaivism. For some officiants, these new forms of Buddhism may have also provided access, a connective link if you will, to a previously monopolized administrative network of opportunity and power that was just beginning to expand and complexify. Tantric modes of expression aesthetically and functionally similar to those employed by Śaivite and Brahmanical groups may have allowed less influential administrative officials the same ability to map their relationships—familial, socio-political, socio-economic, and otherwise—into a shared cultural landscape via religious foundations, donations, and apotropaic rituals using an alternative and competing Buddhist model of expression understood to be equally valid, if not superior to other sectarian traditions.³⁹ The Vat Sithor inscription, for

³⁸ The most overt tantric-related examples found in the inscriptions are as follows: (1) indication that various sacred utterances and hand gestures including *vidyās*, *mantras*, *mudrās*, and heart syllables were employed, (2) indication that there was a division between exoteric and esoteric teachings, (3) the employment of tantric ritual objects such as the *vajra* and the bell, (4) reference to tantric manifestations of Buddhist figures such as Ekādaśamukha, an eleven-faced manifestation of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara, (5) the sudden presence of the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi, (6) the use of apotropaic rites by learned Buddhist ritual experts, and (7) explicit reference to a tantric texts such as *Sarvatathāgatātattvasaṃgraha*. Support for nearly all these observations can be found in K. 111. The reference to Ekādaśamukha, discussed in chapter six, is found in K. 168. Vajrapāṇi is found in K. 772, 266, 267, 268, and 225, for example. Additional support for a tantric presence comes from items such as bronze images of Ekādaśamukha which are also discussed in chapter six, and an alphabet diagram (Skt. *prastāra*) discovered at Bat Cum, an item that Woodward (2011) argues is connected with two tantric texts.

³⁹ For more on the tantric Buddhism's appropriation of concepts and practices from non-Buddhist sources, see Sanderson (1995).

example, notes that the Buddhist Kīrtipaṇḍita employed ritual rites of pacification and prosperity for the king, and these rites were adapted to Buddhist traditions from similar rituals in non-Buddhist sources that can be traced back to the Vedas. The Vat Sithor inscription even redefines the role of the *purohita* (a Brahmanical sacerdotal minister) as one who is familiar with both traditional practices and tantric Buddhist practices involving, among other things, the use of the *vajra* and the bell, iconic ritual implements in Buddhist tantric traditions. As previously mentioned, we also witness this process of appropriation in inscriptions like those at Bat Cum that illustrate how obvious effort was taken to elevate Buddhist figures like Avalokiteśvara and Vajrapāṇi over their non-Buddhist counterparts. All of this seems to be part of a greater revival of Buddhist traditions taking place during this time, something also indicated in the epigraphical record. For example, the Vat Sithor inscription claims that a resurgence of Buddhist traditions was occurring in the mid-tenth century after a period of being marginalized and overshadowed. The record indicates, for instance, that the *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita reinvigorated local Buddhists by restoring old and bringing new Buddhist teachings from distant lands, and these new teachings are specifically called *tantras* (st. XXIX).

That elements of tantric Buddhism could be successful was also in part due to the Yogācāra foundations of Buddhist traditions in early Cambodia. In the earlier summary of the Vat Sithor inscription, I have already briefly discussed how Yogācāra forms of thought provided the primary (not necessarily only) epistemological and doctrinal foundations for Buddhist traditions in the tenth century, a topic that will be given even greater attention in chapter three. In short, the most conspicuous signs to indicate this foundation include: (1) an emphasis in the epigraphical record on the developed

doctrine concerning the three embodiments of the Buddha (Skt. *trikāya*), a concept that finds its fullest expression in Yogācāra sources, (2) explicit epigraphical reference to central Yogācāra concepts such as *cittamātra* and *vijñapti-mātra*, and (3) explicit and implicit epigraphical reference to important Yogācāra texts, such as the *Madhyāntavibhāga* cited in the Vat Sithor inscription.

The connection between Yogācāra epistemology and tantric Buddhism has long been established. In the early twentieth century, N. J. Krom noted similar connections between Yogācāra thought deriving from Asaṅga and Dignāga and the so-called tantric school in his analysis of Borobudur and early Javanese Buddhism.⁴⁰ Similarly, Bruno Petzold, et. al. (1995: 363) writes, “It may be that the early Yogācāra teaching of Asaṅga and Vasubandhu was still considerably influenced by Nāgārjuna’s nihilism, and that the late Yogācāra teaching, especially in Tibet, was inclined to Tantrism.” Yogācāra concepts such as the idea of an individual undergoing a fundamental transformation (Skt. *āśrayaparivṛtti*) were also particularly influential in tantric forms of Buddhism (Davidson 2002: 164).

So it appears that the foundational aspects of Buddhist traditions in Cambodia were ideal for accommodating an incoming stimulus of tantric concepts and practices. This repertoire of concepts and practices were probably aesthetically and functionally similar to established Brahmanical ideas and rituals, thereby allowing Buddhist traditions to compete at a level previously impossible.

⁴⁰ Krom (1927, 2: 315) wrote, “What is generally called the Tantra-school, as we shall see, in all respects agrees with the practice of the Yogācārya’s; it is not always possible to separate them clearly, but even with the inadequate proofs we possess, it is at once apparent that we have to do with a continuous development or evolution from Asaṅga to the present day Lamaism.” Krom’s language is antiquated, but his point remains valid.

Summary of Chapters

Chapter two contains an English translation of the entire Vat Sithor inscription, along with substantial notes that provide commentary on many aspects of the inscription. I endeavored to remain as literal to the Sanskrit as possible and only strayed from this priority when providing a literal translation would have produced awkward phraseology or unintelligible results. When a more loose translation is provided for a stanza it is accompanied with a footnote explaining the justification for my decision. Despite my best attempts, some lines remained problematic and difficult to understand. Such instances are also noted.

As the whereabouts of the original stele were unknown during the writing of this dissertation, the primary sources for my translation were scanned copies of the estampages on file with the École française d'Extrême-Orient (EFEO) and Cœdès' transcription contained in volume six of *Inscriptions du Cambodge*.⁴¹

A few minor corrections have been made to Cœdès' transcription of the inscription. As such changes are few and not very significant, this information has been relegated to an appendix containing a complete Romanized transliteration of the Sanskrit. The primary advantage of reproducing the Sanskrit is that it alleviates the need to have access to Cœdès' work for cross reference.

Chapter three contains an in-depth analysis of the first eighteen lines of the Vat Sithor inscription in order to better understand the Buddhist triadic elements and

⁴¹ The EFEO estampe is n0745. The scans of estampe are numbered as follows: EFEOB-est.n0745_A, EFEOB-est.n0745_A_bas, EFEOB-est.n0745_A_haut, EFEOB-est.n0745_B, EFEOB-est.n0745_B_bas, EFEOB-est.n0745_B_haut, EFEOB-est.n0745_C, EFEOB-est.n0745_C_bas, EFEOB-est.n0745_C_haut, EFEOB-est.n0745_D, EFEOB-est.n0745_D_bas, EFEOB-est.n0745_D_haut.

I thank Dominique Soutif with the EFEO in Siem Reap for his assistance and for kindly providing the requested scans of the estampages for my research. For Cœdès' transcription, see (*IC*, 6: 197–202).

underlying epistemology informing the opening section. An examination will show that the opening eighteen lines of the inscription reveal an overwhelming concern with the path of the bodhisattva and the Yogācāra epistemological foundations comprising that path. The opening panegyric of a Sanskrit inscription is called a *maṅgala*. Since this compositional component of Sanskrit can be rather formulaic, and tends to lack hard historical data, it sometimes receives less attention from those scholars primarily interested in dates, genealogies, battles, consecrations, and other pertinent pieces of information deemed important for historical reconstructions. This chapter demonstrates, however, that a more in-depth examination of this opening section provides valuable insight into the epistemological foundations of the Buddhist traditions active during this period, and (in some cases) what practices and pursuits would have been emphasized. Such information constitutes a valuable form of historical data just as important as any date or genealogy. Thus, the poetic Sanskrit *maṅgala* is not merely aesthetic, but informative. As such, it is imperative to look beyond the embellishment to the meanings being embellished.

Chapter four focuses on an officiant and architect named Kavīndrārimathana, a fervent Buddhist advocate active during the reign of Rājendravarman. The chapter has two primary goals. First, an investigation into Kavīndrārimathana's activities demonstrates that proponents of Buddhist traditions had attained a level of royal recognition during the tenth-century that was greater than that of any previous era. This trend would continue with the activities of the Buddhist Kīrtipaṇḍita during the reign of Rājendravarman's son, Jayavarman. Second, I argue that Kavīndrārimathana's presence in epigraphical records is actually more extensive than previously imagined by

proposing that he is also recorded under the name of Kavīndrācārya in two other tenth-century Cambodian inscriptions: the Prasat Beng inscription (K. 772), and the Phnom Banan inscription (K. 202). If correct, this observation would further bolster the position that Buddhists had become increasingly active and established during the mid- to late tenth century, and likely more influential.

Chapter five takes a closer look at the Buddhist *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita and how he is depicted in the Vat Sithor inscription. Although tentative and based upon circumstantial evidence, the chapter argues that Kīrtipaṇḍita's travels abroad for Buddhist material were likely conducted among the neighboring polities of Campā (present-day regions of central and southern Vietnam).

Chapter six devotes special attention to understanding the bodhisattva Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) in a tenth-century Cambodian context. Since Lokeśvara's presence in the Cambodian epigraphical and art historical records is only rivaled by the Buddha, any discussion on tenth-century Buddhist traditions must give attention to this important figure. By examining the epigraphical and art historical records of early Cambodia, as well the epigraphical record from Campā, chapter six argues that the bodhisattva Lokeśvara goes from a relatively minor figure in Cambodia during the pre-Angkorian period to an increasingly important figure within an emerging tantric context beginning around the tenth century. Since it will be argued that Lokeśvara's increased importance in tenth-century Cambodia arose amid newly emerging strains of tantric Buddhism in the region, it is within this tantric context that the chapter begins to reassess the various ways in which this bodhisattva may have been understood.

Chapter seven demonstrates that the argument surrounding certain stanzas in the Vat Sithor and Bat Cum inscriptions that have been interpreted as proof of strained relations between tenth-century Buddhists and co-existing Brahmanical groups is overstated, and such a position can only be maintained by ignoring the Buddhist monastic context of the inscriptions. These stanzas that have been interpreted as marginalizing and subordinating Buddhists instead indicated that certain activities performed by other non-Buddhist groups co-existing in the same area were not to be participated in since they represented monastic violations established in Buddhist Vinaya traditions. In other words, the stanzas were not included by anti-Buddhist individuals with intentions to demean, marginalized, or subordinate; rather, they were included as reminders for Buddhist monks that certain activities would incur demerit, and thus hinder the monk in his progress along the Buddhist path. The goal, therefore, was not to deprive and subordinate, but rather to educate, remind, and promote proper behavior pertaining to Buddhist monastic ways of life in a tenth-century Cambodian setting.

Chapter eight focuses entirely on the three tenth-century sanctuaries of Phnom Trap, a site located in the Bantheay district of Kampong Cham province about sixty-three kilometers (roughly forty miles) northeast of the capital Phnom Penh. Specifically, chapter eight reexamines the iconography found at Phnom Trap and argues that the figures depicted on the inner brick reliefs of the three structures are Buddhist, not Vaiṣṇava or Śaiva as as described in early surveys and never challenged. By highlighting the Buddhist orientation of this site, my dissertation once again

demonstrates that tenth-century forms of Buddhism in Cambodia were much more widespread and influential than previously acknowledged.

Table 1-1. Tenth-Century Cambodia Inscriptions with Buddhist-Related Content

Inscription (Reference)	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
Reign of Yaśovarman			
K. 432 (IC 2: 119–120)	Late Ninth or Early Tenth Century	Kâmpong Chhnang	Invocation to the <i>tathāgata</i> ('thus gone one' = the Buddha), allusion to the defeat of Māra, and praise to the Three Jewels of Buddhism (the Buddha, Dharma, and Saṅgha)
Reign of Rājendravarman			
K. 290* (IC 3: 231–33)	c. Tenth Century	Siem Reap	Mentions donative activities of Kavīndrārimathana, a known advocate of Buddhist traditions
K. 772 (IC 7: 104–05)	c. Tenth Century	Siem Reap	Kavīndrācārya = Kavīndrārimathana (?); comparisons to Prajñāpāramitā, Vajrapāṇi, and the worlds of Buddhas
K. 202 (IC 7: 40–41)	c. Tenth Century	Battambang	Kavīndrācārya = Kavīndrārimathana (?) and possible reference to Lokeśvara
K. 872 (IC 5: 97–104)	944 CE	Siem Reap	Opening invocation praises the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā; the doctrine of <i>saṃsāra</i> ('cycle of rebirth') referenced; music and hymns performed on behalf of the Jina (i.e., the Buddha) tower of the Muni (i.e., the Buddha) constructed; expressed desire to be reborn in the Buddhist realm of Sukhāvātī
K. 173 (JA 1914 (1): 637–44)	947 CE	Siem Reap	Praise directed to the Buddha, as well as non-Buddhist deities worship by other co-existing sectarian groups
K. 174 (JA 1914 (1): 637–44)	947 CE	Siem Reap	Praise directed to an image of the <i>tathāgata</i>
K. 180 (BEFEO 13 (6): 17–26)	947 CE	Preah Vihear	Mentions donations and revenues to the Buddha (Śrīghaṇa) of Amarendrapura, as well as other non-Buddhist deities in various locations
K. 238 (IC 6: 119–122)	949 CE	Siem Reap	Records the installation of, and donations to, an image of Trailokyānātha (i.e., Lokeśvara) by Bajrendrācārya

Table 1-1. Continued

Inscription (Reference)	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
Reign of Rājendravarman Continued			
K. 528 (BEFEO 25: 309–53)	952 CE	Siem Reap	Praise of the ruler Rājendravarman indicates that he knew the Buddha’s Dharma and honored it alongside other sacred things
K. 266, 267, and 268 (JA 1908 (2): 213–52; Mertens 2005)	953 CE	Siem Reap	Invocations to Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, Prajñāpāramitā, and Lokeśvara; records various activities of Kavīndrārimathana such as the installation and consecration of Buddhist images including the Buddha, Vajrāpaṇi, Prajñāpāramita, and Lokanātha
K. 157 (IC 6: 123–27)	953 CE	Kâmpong Thom	Praise and installation of Avalokiteśa/Lokeśa and Devī (= Prajñāpāramitā) images; ritual bathing of images recorded
K. 806 (IC 1: 73–142)	961 CE	Siem Reap	Stanza praising Rājendravarman is made by means of a poetic comparison to the doctrines of <i>viññapti-mātra</i> and <i>sūnyatā</i> of Buddhist Yogācāra traditions and the Three Jewels of Buddhism
K. 198 (IC 6: 147–49)	966 CE	Battambang	Records the donation of property and servants to Parameśvara (Śiva) and <i>ārya</i> Maitri (the Buddha Maitreya)
K. 239 (IC 3: 79–84)	966 CE	Siem Reap	Invocation to the Three Jewels of Buddhism; fragmented reference to the installation of a ‘-keśvaraliṅga’ (Lokeśvara ?; called Jagannāthakeśvara, ‘Lord Protector of the World,’ in the Khmer section); includes a declaration for the transference of merit so that others have a positive rebirth and avoid suffering; expressed desire by donor to be reborn as the son of a Buddha (<i>buddhātmaja</i> ; i.e., a bodhisattva); reference to nirvāṇa; some officials, such as <i>loñ</i> Sugata, have Buddhist names.

Table 1-1. Continued

Inscription (Reference)	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
Reign of Jayavarman V			
K. 1154 (NIC: 129)	Tenth Century (Reign Unknown)	Unknown	Inscription on back of a stele depicting an eight-armed representation of Lokeśvara; includes a reference to Lokeśvara's ' <i>oṃ maṇipadme hūṃ'</i> mantra.
K. 240 (IC 3: 76–77)	Between 968 and 977 CE for the first part of the inscription on south doorjamb; 979 CE for the next part of the inscription	Siem Reap	Records the donation of accessories and servants to a Buddhist figure called Trailokyavijya; the second part of the southern doorjamb records offerings of servants to Lokeśvara later in 979 CE.
K. 339 (IC 5: 164–69)	Tenth Century	Siem Reap	Invocation to the Three Jewels of Buddhism; reference to Buddhist doctrine of impermanence (Skt. <i>anitya</i>); some of Jayavarman's administrators are recorded as being eminent Buddhists and masters the Dharma and yoga; administrators are noted for installing Buddhist images and constructing reliquary shrines Invocation to the Three Embodiments of the Buddha; praises Dharma, Three Jewels, and path of the bodhisattva; references to Buddhist texts; records activities such as the installation of Buddhist images by the Buddhist <i>ācārya</i> Kīrtipaṇḍita; details regulations and practices followed at a Buddhist monastery
K. 111 (IC 6: 195–211)	c. 968 CE	Kandal	Documents the history of various Śaivite and Buddhist foundations over time at the site of Damrañ; records the installation of an image of Munīndra ('Prince of Sages,' i.e., the Buddha)
K. 1141 (Cha-em Kaeokhla 1986)	970 CE	Korat region Northeast of Bangkok	

Table 1-1. Continued

Inscription (Reference)	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
Reign of Jayavarman V Continued			
K. 417 (IC 2: 48–50)	970 CE	Siem Reap	Ornaments donated to a Lokeśa (i.e., Lokeśvara) image; Praise to Lokeśvara for saving suffering beings from the torments of hell (a possible reference to events in the <i>Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra</i>)
K. 168 (IC 6: 168–69)	972 CE	Siem Reap	Records offerings to Ekādaśamukha, Lokeśvara, and Bhagavatī (i.e., Prajñāpāramitā)
K. 214 (IC 2: 202–06)	982 CE	Banteay Mean Chey	Praises the Absolute Truth (<i>paramārtha</i>) which takes the form of the Three Embodiments of the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā; servants are assigned to the upkeep of both Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā
K. 887 (IC V: 153–55)	983 CE	Siem Reap	Records the installation of an image of the Jina; one individual has a Buddhist name, Nirvāṇanātha.
K. 452 (IC 5: 156–57)	988 CE	Siem Reap	Records the donation of a Lokeśa image, along with various goods to a monastery
K. 225 (IC 3: 66–69)	989 CE	Banteay Mean Chey	Recorded on a stone <i>caitya</i> depicting Buddhist figures, the inscription mentions how one Padmavairocana installed images of Prajñāpāramitā, Indra, Maitreya, the Buddha, Lokeśvara and Vajrin (i.e., Vajrapāṇi); the six Buddhist perfections (Skt. <i>pāramitā</i>) are also recorded

Table 1-1. Continued

Inscription (Reference)	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
Reign of Jayavarman V Continued			
K. 257 (IC 4: 140–50; Estève 2009: 452–60)	Actually consists of two inscriptions dating to 979 CE and 994 CE	Siem Reap	Includes reference to the site of Chpār Ransī, a site with attested Buddhist affiliations; the phrase <i>vrah chpār</i> means the ‘god of Chpār (Ransī),’ a likely epithet for the Buddha

Table 1.1 Note.—Support for identifying Trailokyānātha as Lokeśvara in K. 238 comes from the Prasat Beng inscription (K. 230, IC 6: 241–46), an early eleventh-century inscription from the reign of Sūryavarman. Although damaged, the Buddhist character of this inscription is beyond doubt since it opens with an invocation to the embodiments of the Buddha, Trailokyanātha, and Vajrapāṇi. The Khmer section of the inscription specifically says that the casted image of Lokeśvara is named Trailokyanātha.

* K.290 is a very important Buddhist inscription relating the founding of Saugatāśrama by Yaśovarman which dates to the end of the ninth century. My statistical inclusion of K. 290 among tenth-century inscriptions, however, is referring specifically to the appended and damaged Khmer lines on side D that record donative activities on the part of Rājendrarvarman’s Buddhist minister, Kavindrārimathana. See chapter four for more on this inscription.

CHAPTER 2
ENGLISH TRANSLATION OF VAT SITHOR INSCRIPTION (K.111)

Side A

I. I honor the Embodiment of Dharma¹ which is like the moon, shining in the reservoir of the pure mind, (and) even though pervading all that is perceptible to senses it is freed from the (five) aggregates² just as (the moon is freed) from Rāhu.³

¹ The Buddhist character of the inscription is immediately made clear by this opening stanza which invokes the *dharmakāya* ('Embodiment of Dharma'). The *dharmakāya* is one of three embodiments of the Buddha in what is known as the *trikāya* ('three embodiments') doctrine. The other two embodiments are the *sambhogakāya* ('Embodiment for [Communal] Enjoyment [of the Dharma]') and the *nirmāṇakāya/nairmāṇika* ('Embodiment in Manifestations'), both of which are also invoked in stanzas II and III. The *trikāya* invoked in this inscription represents a later formulation directly connected with Yogācāra circles of thought which reformulated earlier two-*kāya* descriptions found in texts from the Pali canon and other textual sources such as the *Prajñāpāramitā* literature (Makransky, 1997). According to influential Yogācāra texts such as the *Mahāyānasūtrālaṃkāra* (*MSA*), the *Mahāyānasamgraha*, and the *Madhyantavibhāga* (a text which is cited in stanza XXVIII of this inscription), the *dharmakāya* is equivalent to the realization of thusness (Skt. *tathatā*); that is, the ultimate nature of things which is hidden from the view of unenlightened beings by their own mental obstructions. The ultimate nature of things is the non-duality of all phenomena; in other words, an unenlightened being is unenlightened due to a false subject-object cognition. A full discussion of this *trikāya* and this stanza is presented in chapter three of this dissertation.

The first nine stanzas of this inscription are devoted to praising the embodiments of the Buddha (I–III), the Dharma of the Buddha (IV–VI), and bodhisattvas along with the bodhisattva path (VII–IX).

² The Buddhist technical term for 'aggregates' (Skt. *skandha*) refers to five psychophysical aggregates that makeup a sentient being: physical form (*rūpa*), feelings (*vedanā*), recognition (*saṃjñā*), volitional formations (*saṃskāra*), and self-consciousness (*vijñāna*). These *skandhas* represent a schema for classifying a particular type of phenomena, in this case, they explain, for Buddhists, what is a person. The *skandhas* aid in deconstructing what a person actually is by illustrating the impermanent, selfless, and suffering nature of what is nominally referred to as a 'person.' In the Yogācāra epistemological context of this stanza, the *skandhas* represent what is known as the basis or foundation (Skt. *āśraya*) that must be transformed or overturned (Skt. *parāvṛtti*) if the cognitive change necessary for awakening is to occur. In general, the basic understanding of the *dharmakāya* (*i.e.*, the realization of thusness, the non-duality of all phenomena) is that it is freed or liberated from the basis (in this context, the psychophysical *skandhas*) because the affective and cognitive obstructions within those psychophysical aggregates have been cognitively transformed or overturned (Skt. *parāvṛtti*). Cf. *MSA* 9.12 and 9.60 and their respective *bhāṣya*. See Davidson (1985: 189–91) and chapter two of this dissertation for more on the transformation of the basis (Skt. *āśraya-parāvṛtti*) and its connection with both the *skandhas* and *dharmakāya*.

³ Rāhu, literally 'the seizer,' is the name of the *asura* said to swallow the moon and sun, thereby causing eclipses. A Buddhist account of the story is told in the *Devaputtasamṃyutta* of the *Saṃyutta Nikāya* (I.2.ṣ9–10). In that etiological account the moon (P. Candimā) is seized by the *asura* Rāhu, but upon recollecting the Buddha and sending out a fervent prayer the Buddha demands that Rāhu release the moon. The Buddha explains that the moon has taken refuge in the Buddha and, hence, is protected. Fearful that his head may be split into seven parts if he disobeys the Buddha, Rāhu releases the moon. The same incident occurs with the sun (P. Suriya), and the story unfolds in the same manner. Rāhu also plays a part in the narrative of the churning of the ocean of milk as told in *MBh* I.016. Based on the

II. Bow to⁴ the *maṇḍala*⁵ of the Embodiment for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma),⁶ the light of the Embodiment of Dharma; (it is) filled with the power of various manifestations (*nirmāṇa*) to be mastered by great sages for the attainment of perfection (*siddha*).⁷

III. I bow to the Embodiment of Manifestation⁸ of the Virtuous Ones, which is pleasing (and) grants the wishes of (those in) the world just like a wish fulfilling tree.

IV. Bow to the Good Dharma which is tranquil, excellent, inconceivable, inexpressible, and the domain of the passionless ascetics of the Sage.⁹

V. I bow to the Dharma which is grasped through meditation and proclaimed by the Embodiment for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma) (*sāmbhogī*)¹⁰ conforming to the respective insight befitting their attained stage (*bhūmi*).¹¹

popularity of the churning narrative in both art historical and epigraphical sources from early Cambodia it is likely that Rāhu was a well-known figure.

⁴ *namadhvam* (imperative, 2nd person, plural of √nam) – ‘incline,’ ‘bow,’ ‘yield,’ ‘submit to.’

⁵ The term *maṇḍala* may refer to a circle, disk, or some kind of circular object. In this context it is specifically referring to the halo-like rays encircling the sun. The various manifestations of the Embodiment for (Communal) Enjoyment (*sāmbhogakāya*) are likened to a halo of light whose rays are emitting from the sun; the sun, in turn, is identified with the *dharmakāya*, or Embodiment of Dharma. The *sāmbhogīkāya* are said to proclaim and teach the Dharma to assemblies of bodhisattvas.

⁶ *sāmbhogatanu*—‘Embodiment(s) for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma)’—is equivalent to *sāmbhogakāya*. The words *tanu* and *kāya* both mean ‘body’ or ‘embodiment.’

⁷ The second portion of this stanza is alluding to ritual practices in which a practitioner meditates on the various manifestations of buddhas or bodhisattvas visually depicted on Buddhist *maṇḍalas*, often understood as visual depictions of the domain of a particular buddha.

⁸ The *nirmāṇīkāya* are diverse and limitless manifestations of enlightenment responsible for assuming a variety of forms in order to communicate knowledge of the Dharma to various beings.

⁹ All references to the Sage (Skt. *muni*) in capitals refer to the Buddha.

¹⁰ Here, the term *sāmbhogī* may simply be referring to the Buddha; however, I am specifically interpreting the reference as an abbreviated way to refer to the Buddha’s second embodiment, the *sāmbhogakāya*. Again, the *sāmbhogakāya* is responsible for proclaiming and teaching the Dharma to assemblies of bodhisattvas. This verse indicates that the *sāmbhogakāya* tailors its teaching of the Dharma to the respective level of understanding of the aspiring bodhisattva(s), which can be ascertained by the current stage (Skt. *bhūmi*) of development that has been attained by the bodhisattva(s) along the bodhisattva path. This theme of conforming the presentation of the Dharma to the disposition and cognitive abilities of the audience is continued in the next two stanzas (st. VI and VII).

¹¹ Here I disagree with Coedès’ suggestion that *bhūmi* does not refer to the *bodhisattvabhūmi*, but rather a Buddha field (*buddhakṣetra*). Coedès translated the stanza as follows: “Je salue la Loi, qui est conforme à la sagesse des (Buddha) entrés chacun dans sa Terre, qui a été annoncée par (les Buddha) revêtus de leur Corps communiel, et qui se laisse saisir par la méditation” (IC, 6: 202). His footnote concerning his

VI. The will of the Buddha, like a crystal which is transparent and devoid of its own color, adapts to conditions by utilizing the speech of gods, *daityas*, and so on; may it purify all.

VII. Glory to those bodhisattvas who assume the form of Brahmā and other (gods) in order to fulfill the wishes of various devotees, and who are well established in fields (*bhūmi*) such as Nirābhāsa.¹²

VIII. Having understood that, like a dream, the world is *cittamātra* ('nothing but constructions of the mind'),¹³ I praise those who are intent on its (the world's) welfare, (and who) have entered the seven stages¹⁴ (of the bodhisattva path), of which Muditā is the first (stage).¹⁵

translation of *bhūmi* as 'Terre' states, "Il s'agit sans doute ici des Terres de Buddha (*buddhakṣetra*), dans chacune desquelles réside ou enseigne un Buddha, et non des bodhisattvabhūmi dont il sera question aux st. VII et VIII (*Ibid.*, 202, n.2). Dayal (1932: 270–90) discusses at length the various ways to understand the term *bhūmi* in the context of the bodhisattva path. See Kawamura (1981 and 2004) and Buswell and Gimello (1992) for more recent discussions on the bodhisattva path.

¹² The term *nirābhāsa* can be variously translated as 'formlessness,' 'unmanifested,' and 'imagelessness.' I think there are two ways to understand *nirābhāsa* in the context of this stanza. First, *nirābhāsa* may simply be alluding to the bodhisattva's ability to assume various forms to assist devotees of varying dispositions and levels of knowledge; hence, they are 'without form' or reside in a field or state of 'formlessness.' However, I think one should also note that *nirābhāsa* may be "referring to the state of mind of the realized person, a condition in which one perceives things directly, without the mediation of conceptual recognition or interpretation of any kind" (Ray, 2005: 131). Ray's observations on *nirābhāsa* are based on its usage in the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra*. The obvious Yogācāra influence on this inscription supports understanding *nirābhāsa* as a highly developed state or stage of the bodhisattva in which things are perceived directly.

¹³ The use of the term *cittamātra* is revealing in that it supports the conclusion that the epistemological foundations for many Buddhists of the time would have been derived from Yogācāra forms of Buddhism. The term occurs once again in stanza XXVII of this inscription. Often literally translated as 'mind-only,' *cittamātra* refers to the epistemological position that everything we know, conceive, are aware of, and so forth are known through cognition. In other words, all we know are 'nothing but mind constructions' (*cittamātra*) or 'nothing but conscious constructions' (*vijñaptimātra*), and we often confuse these mental constructions or interpretations of the world for the world itself. Consult Lusthaus (2003) for a thorough account of the concept of *cittamātra* and Yogācāra Buddhism (as well as a detailed account of many misconceptions). A discussion on *cittamātra* can also be found in chapter three of this dissertation.

¹⁴ The reference to seven stages (*saptabhūmiḥ*) of the bodhisattva path may seem rather perplexing since the ten-stage classificatory system (*daśabhūmi*) was well-established by the tenth century. Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 203, n. 1) reconciled the reference to seven stages with the ten-stage schema by simply stating that the first seven stages constitute a distinct group onto themselves, and he references the *MSA* (IV, 2) for support. In other words, for Cœdès, the inscription is merely referencing the first seven, of ten, stages of the bodhisattva path. I have come to agree with Cœdès' suggestion, but it is in need of additional explanation in order to better understand the entire meaning of the verse, especially how that relates to the forms of Buddhist knowledge informing the authors of the inscription. The stanza in the *MSA* referenced by Cœdès is discussing how the arising of thought (Skt. *cittotpāda*) consists of four types: *ādhimokṣa*, *śuddhādhyāsayika*, *vaipākya* and *aṇavarjita*.

Skt. *cittotpādo 'dhimokṣo 'sau śuddhādhyāsayiko 'paraḥ / vaipākya bhūmiṣu matastathāvaraṇavarjitaḥ //* (*MSA*, IV, 2).

IX. I honor those who, like a mother, observing the pain of the world and being afflicted by that pain, direct the jewel-like mind toward awakening (*bodhau*) in order to alleviate it (i.e., *duḥkha*).¹⁶

X. There was a king (called) Śrī Jayavarman whose lotus-feet were kissed by the bees that were the crowns of propitious kings, (and) who came to possess the kingdom in 890.¹⁷

These four types arise or develop during the various stages of ten-stage bodhisattva path. For example, as explained in the *bhāṣya* for this stanza, the arising of *ādhimokṣa* ('fervent aspiration') occurs within the first six stages of the bodhisattva path. The arising of *śuddhādhyaśayika* ('superior pure intentions') is a quality of a bodhisattva in the first seven stages, and it is this grouping Cœdès must have been referring to. Additionally, the seventh stage in the ten-stage schema of the bodhisattva path is the *dūrāṅgamā-bhūmi*, the "proceeding from afar stage [in which a bodhisattva gets beyond one's self to help others]" (Kawamura, 2004: 59; see Dayal (1932: 270–90) for a more detailed account). Thus, a seventh-stage bodhisattva is one whose superior pure intentions (*śuddhādhyaśayika*) are being extended beyond one's self in order to strive for the welfare of other sentient beings. This does, indeed, appear to correspond to the theme being stressed in the inscription since praise is specifically being extended to those individuals engaged in the welfare of others, and who have entered the seven stages (or perhaps the translation should be "entered the seventh stage") of the bodhisattva path.

With that said, however, it is important to note that the number of *bhūmis* comprising the bodhisattva path varied among texts and traditions, and perhaps the Buddhists connected with this inscription adhered to a form of Buddhism in which the path only consisted of seven stages. Dayal (1932: 271), for example, has argued that the original number of bodhisattva stages likely consisted of seven. The configuration of the bodhisattva path in the *Bodhisattvabhūmi* (*Bb*) consists of thirteen *vihāras* and seven *bhūmis* (*Bb* II.4, III.3). Additionally, the *Laṅkāvatārasūtra* (*Laṅ*) also mentions seven stages, although it fails to specify those stages (*Laṅ* II, 54). Still, the suggestion that the bodhisattva path mentioned in this inscription may have only consisted of seven stages is weakened by the additional reference to *mudita* ('joy') being the name of the first stage of the bodhisattva path in st. VIII. The *mudita**bhūmi*, or *pramudita**bhūmi*, is the name of the first stage according ten-stage classificatory system found in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*. Conversely, the first *bhūmi* of the seven-stage system found in the *Bodhisattvabhūmi* is *gotrabhūmi*. There is a *pramuditavihāra* in the *Bodhisattvabhūmi*, but it is the third of thirteen *vihāras* and is specifically associated with the third *bhūmi* of that system known as *śuddhādhyaśayabhūmi*. For more on the various configurations of the path of bodhisattva, see the above references and Williams (2010: 200–08, esp. n. 27).

¹⁵ Again, *Mudita* is the first of ten stages in the bodhisattva path according to the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*. The complete list of stages is as follows: (1) *pramudita**bhūmi* (2) *vimala**bhūmi* (3) *prabhākarī**bhūmi* (4) *arcīṣmatī**bhūmi* (5) *sudurjayā**bhūmi* (6) *abhimukhī**bhūmi* (7) *dūrāṅgamā**bhūmi* (8) *acala**bhūmi* (9) *sadhumatī**bhūmi* (10) *dharmama**ghabhūmi*.

¹⁶ Cf. stanza I.36 from Śāntideva's *Bodhicaryāvatāra*: I bow down to the bodies of those in whom that excellent jewel, the Mind, has arisen, and towards whom even harm will lead to happiness. To those mines of happiness, I go for refuge. (trans. Crosby and Skilton, 1995: 8). Skt. *teṣāṃ śarīrāṇi namaskaromi yatroditaṃ tadvaracittaratnam / yatrāpakāro'pi sukhānubandhī sukhākarāṃstān śaraṇaṃ prayāmi //*.

¹⁷ The year 890 is literally denoted by the terms: *aṅga* ('limb' = 8), *dvāra* ('gate' = 9), *vyoma* ('sky' = 0). The date is according to the Śaka era and is equivalent to c. 968 CE. The Jayavarman of this inscription is specifically Jayavarman V, son of Rājendravarman, who reigned from c.968 to c.1000/1001. Stanzas X–XVIII of this inscription are devoted to praising this ruler.

XI. Wherever the beneficial sun rises, even though impartial, in that very moment the virtuous rise like lotuses (and) spontaneously the darkness of the wicked is destroyed.

XII. Leading his subjects like a father along the path of heaven and liberation, the reins of sacred tradition steer the horses that are our own sense faculties away from wrong paths.

XIII. He who appeared like the midday sun when time had obscured the path of good conduct honored by noble men from Manu onward which had been obscured by the darkness of time.

XIV. Wherein virtues, beginning with valor, were established, and were transferred to others by contact (*tādātmyena*), just as heat (is transferred to) metal when in a fire.

XV. Although through force of will he restrained himself from seizing the wives of (his) enemies; through (his) learning, he somehow seized Supreme Knowledge herself.

XVI. Though she was abandoned by (Yudhiṣṭhira,) the son of Dharma, in the great ocean of the stain of the Kali Age, he shall rescue the good lady of Truth with his two hands of Śruti and Smṛti.¹⁸

XVII. Although (knowledge of) statecraft is common to all kings, he was one to whom statecraft was an inherent (quality); just as purifying waters for living beings are inherent to a sacred site (*tīrthālayam*).

XVIII. Like a compassionate father, he wiped away the tears of his suffering citizens with informants (*cāra*)¹⁹ that acted as his outstretched hands.

¹⁸ Yudhiṣṭhira was the eldest of five Pāṇḍava brothers in the epic *Mahābhārata*. The stanza is comparing Yudhiṣṭhira and the ruler Jayavarman. While Yudhiṣṭhira is frequently described as upright and pious, he eventually participated in a dice game in which he staked himself, his brothers, his kingdom, and even his wife, Draupadī. Yudhiṣṭhira lost the dice game and was forced into exile with his brothers and Draupadī, but not before the innocent Draupadī was first dragged before an audience, insulted, humiliated and almost completely stripped of her clothing. The 'good lady Truth' may be an allusion to what Draupadī embodies, as well as her abandonment by Yudhiṣṭhira who failed to properly protect her by staking her in a dice game and making possible her subsequent humiliation at the hands of Duryodhana. The stanza indicates that Jayavarman will restore Truth during the current Kali Age (*i.e.*, the current degenerate age) with the tradition that is 'heard' (Śruti) and the tradition that is 'remembered' (Smṛti), with these two foundational traditions being likened to the king's hands.

¹⁹ The Sanskrit word *cāra* refers to an informant or type of spy. I have followed Olivelle's (2013: xv) translation of the term as 'informants' since this English word better reflects its usage in other Sanskrit sources such as Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra*. In the *Arthaśāstra*, for example, the term *cāra* is always used as a type of employed informant within society that provides useful reports and information to the ruler, his "eyes and ears," so to speak. Section 1.12.23 of the *Arthaśāstra* discusses how one should employ informants (*cāra*) among forest dwellers in order to obtain information concerning enemies. Section

XIX. His (Jayavarman V's) trusted emissary was the *ācārya*²⁰ Kīrtipaṇḍita, a learned man who had crossed over the ocean of knowledge, and whose fame spread like the light of the full moon.²¹

XX. Having crossed over the oceans of all teachings (*śāstra*) by means of the/his vessel of energy,²² having obtained the jewels of true value,²³ he shared with those desirous of the riches of the mind.

XXI. His virtues, beginning with benevolence, were said to be like the heat of the fire, whereas his faults were adventitious (*āgantukā*) like the fluidity of iron.²⁴

1.19.13 describes how during the fifth part of the day a ruler should consult with his counselors by dispatching letters and going over secret intelligence provided by his network of informants (*cāra*). For additional references, also refer to sections 2.7.29 and 2.35.10 in Olivelle (2013: 80, 92, 113 and 174).

In the above stanza, Jayavarman's informants act, or literally 'appear' (Skt. *ākāra*), as his hands in that they are responsible for reporting back to him important information regarding the well-being of his subjects. With this information he is able to take appropriate measures to ensure their happiness. In this way his hands and informants are analogous in that they are both able to skillfully seek out and discover those who are suffering in his realm. Compare Coëdès' translation (*IC*, 6 : 204) which fails to take *cāra* as 'informants' into account: "Comme un père chéri de ses enfants, il séchait les larmes de ses sujets affligés en se servant de ses mains étendues."

²⁰ The title *ācārya* literally means one who knows or teaches the rules (*ācāra*). The term is often used to simply denote a master or teacher.

²¹ This stanza is playing off the literal meaning of Kīrtipaṇḍita's name, the learned one (*paṇḍita*) of renown/fame (*kīrti*). My translation of *ākīrṇakīrtipūrṇenduḥ* is, like Coëdès' own French translation, a bit loose in order to convey what I feel is the intended meaning of the compound in English. More literally (and blandly) the qualifying compound could be translated as 'a full moon of overspreading fame.' It seems clear, however, that what is being conveyed is that Kīrtipaṇḍita's fame was full like the moon when it is full; in other words, his fame covered (or spread throughout) the land like the light of the full moon.

²² The translation 'vessel of energy' comes from the Sanskrit compound *vīrya-uḍupa*. The word *uḍupa* refers to a raft or small boat of some kind. It can also refer to the moon since a small boat is shaped like the crescent moon (M.W., s.v. *uḍupa*). The secondary meaning of moon connects the imagery in this stanza with the preceding stanza which describes Kīrtipaṇḍita's fame spreading like the light of the moon. The word *vīrya* has a host of meanings, but has additional technical meanings in Buddhist traditions since it is traditionally the fourth *pāramitā* ('perfection') in both six and ten system classifications. The term refers to one's zeal, energy, power, tireless effort, and so forth. The inscription is indicating that Kīrtipaṇḍita was able to grasp all knowledge—including the highest knowledge of the Dharma—because of his zeal or energy.

²³ 'The jewels of true value' are the Three Jewels of Buddhism (*triratna*): (1) the Buddha, (2) the Dharma, and (3) the Saṅgha. The Saṅgha refers to the Buddhist community consisting of monks (*bhikṣu*), nuns (*bhikṣuṇī*), laymen (*upāsaka*), laywomen (*upāsikā*).

²⁴ The simile employed here is somewhat difficult to convey properly in English. The stanza is poetically suggesting that Jayavarman's virtuous qualities were all naturally inherent, much like heat is naturally inherent in fire. On the other hand, any faults were simply unnatural for one of his stature, much like iron that has been heated to liquid form was held to be an unnatural state for iron because such a state can only come about by the presence of other external forces (such as heat in this case). In other words, good qualities and Jayavarman himself are not considered two separate things since it is implied that you

XXII. If somehow passions such as anger arose in his heart, they quickly subsided (*jṛmbhitāḥ*) because of his obedience to knowledge (*vidyā*), just like the serpents of a snake charmer become dormant (*jṛmbhitāḥ*) because of the charmer's skill (*vidyā*).

XXIII. He whose mind was fixed on *yoga* during the four divisions of the day,²⁵ who was endowed with the quality of the Four Donations,²⁶ who was

cannot have one without the other, just like there will always be heat with fire. Unfavorable qualities, however, are unnatural and external to him just like the fluidity of iron is unnatural because it requires an external force to attain such a state. It should also be noted that the Sanskrit word *loha* literally means 'red,' and may refer to other red or reddish colored metals such as copper.

²⁵ The *saṃdhyā* refer to junctions of the day during which specific rites are often performed. Hence the term *saṃdhyā* often refers more specifically to a rite performed during a junction of the day (BHS, s.v. *saṃdhyā*) The more familiar *trisaṃdhyā* (three divisions or junctions of the day) refer to dawn, midday and dusk. The additional fourth junction of the day refers to midnight. By indicating that Kīrtipaṇḍita practiced *yoga* ('he whose mind was fixed on *yoga*,' Skt. *yogātmā*) not just at dawn, midday, and dusk, but also at midnight, the author(s) of the inscription implied that his Buddhist meditative activities were practiced both diligently and rigorously.

²⁶ The *caturdānam*, or 'Four Gifts/Charities/Donations,' may refer to the fourfold division of *dāna* popular in tantric forms of Buddhism that include: *dharmadānam* ('gift of Dharma'), *āmiṣadānam* ('gift of worldly possessions'), *abhayaadānam* ('gift of security/fearlessness'), and *maitrīdānam* ('gift of benevolence'). A few more words concerning this division, however, are in order.

As Coedès (*IC*, 6: 204, n. 4) noted, the four donations (*caturdānam*) could refer to a number of things, and he suggested that they may refer to the four requisites of Buddhist monks known as the *pratyaya* (P. *paccaya*): robes, food, bedding/shelter, and medicine. The four *pratyaya*, however, are usually considered a specific type of material gift, and therefore would fall under the broader category of *āmiṣadānam* (e.g., see Heim (2004: 127) for a short discussion of the *pratyaya* in context of Theravādin twofold and threefold divisions of *dāna*.) Additionally, the full adjectival phrase (*caturdānānvitaḥ*) used in the inscription appears to imply not only physically contributing four *dāna*, but also being endowed with their qualities due to the use of the word *anvita*. The Sanskrit term *anvita* literally means 'gone' (*ita*) 'along' (*anu-*), which Coedès extended to mean that Kīrtipaṇḍita 'offered' daily the four donations. However, the term *anvita* has a dual sense in that it can also be used to describe how something possesses or is endowed with a certain character or quality; in other words, *caturdānānvitaḥ* could also be taken to mean that Kīrtipaṇḍita was one who possessed the essential qualities of four *dāna*, or the qualities (often mental) necessary to properly partake in the activity of the four *dāna*. This interpretation coincides somewhat symmetrically with the meaning of the other adjectival phrase in the stanza which describes Kīrtipaṇḍita as having the character of the four *mudrā* (*caturmudrātmakaḥ*). Here the word *ātmaka* similarly parallels the meaning of *anvita*. Maria Heim (2004: 112) has noted that the language of gift giving is not to be restricted to the actual transference of a material object and could be used to describe a social transaction or interrelation. Here we might expand the usage of the language of gift giving to include a literary method employed to highlight the virtuous qualities of an individual. If this interpretation is correct, then it makes little sense to understand the four *dāna* cited in this stanza as being a reference to the *pratyaya*.

Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284), however, in looking at this particular verse simply translated *caturdānānvitaḥ* as 'giver of the four gifts,' which of course is also perfectly valid.

Pali texts often subdivide *dāna* into two or three types consisting of *āmiṣadharmā* (P. *amisadhamma*), *dharmadāna* (P. *hammadāna*), and sometimes *abhayaadāna* (again, see Heim (2004: esp. 127–32) for a discussion of *dāna* in a Theravādin context). In the context of subdividing each of the six *pāramitā* ('perfections') into three specific subtypes, the *Dharmasaṃgraha*, a Buddhist lexicographical text often

endowed with the character of the Four Mudrā,²⁷ [taught] the Dharma to the four assemblies everyday.²⁸

attributed to Nāgārjuna, provides the following threefold division for the first *pāramitā* of *dāna*: *dharmadānam*, *āmiṣadānam* and the *maitrīdānam* (*Dharmasaṃgraha*, 27, st. 105). Threefold subdivisions of the *pāramitā* are found in many Buddhist texts, especially Yogācāra texts, although not all of these threefold identifications are identical. Thus, for example, both the *Samdhinirmocana Sūtra* (IX, 12) and the *Mahāyānasamgraha* (IV, § 9) indicate that the three types of *dāna* are: *dharmadānam*, *āmiṣadānam*, and *abhayadānam* (thus echoing many Theravādin sources). These two texts differ from the *Dharmasaṃgraha* in that *maitrīdānam* is replaced by *abhayadānam*, the latter *abhayadānam* being more common in threefold schema. For more references to other threefold subdivisions of *dāna* and the other *pāramitā* in Buddhist texts—as well as other numbered subdivisions of *pāramitā* (excluding fourfold divisions)—see Lamotte’s translation of the *Mahāyānasamgraha* (n. to chapter IV, § 9, 190–92).

With the proliferation of fourfold schema in tantric Buddhist traditions *maitrīdānam* and *abhayadānam* are listed together for a total of four *dāna*: *dharmadānam*, *āmiṣadānam*, *abhayadānam*, and *maitrīdānam*. This particular enumeration is quite popular in modern Tibetan forms of Buddhism, especially in the Nyingma tradition. Support for this fourfold schema (Tib. *sbyin pa nam bzhi*) is often provided by citing the influential 18th century Rijdzin Jingme Lingpa’s (1729–1798) *Yon tan rin po che’i mdzod las ’bras bu’i theg pa rgya cher ’grel nram mkhyen shing rta* (e.g., Dahl, 2007: 194), a commentary on the tantric section of his own *Yon tan rin po che’i mdzod*. Such references are rather late. Support, however, for this fourfold division of *dāna* can also be found in a much earlier tantric text, the *Sarvadurgatipariśodhana Tantra*, a text first translated, according to Bu-ston, from Sanskrit into Tibetan sometime near the end of the eighth century by Śāntigarbha (a.k.a. Śāntagrabha) and Jayarakṣita (Skorupski, 1983: xxiv). Davidson (2002: 152, 158) mentions that Buddhaguhya (fl. c. 8th) is attributed authorship of the *Śarvadurgatipariśodhana*. He also writes that this text was one of several other esoteric texts such as the *Sarvatathāgatattvasaṃgraha* and *Mahāvairocanābhisambodhi* that were in use in India during the eighth and early ninth centuries, and such texts were purported by influential monks as belonging to a kind of esoteric “canon.”

²⁷ This could be reference to a fourfold schema popular within tantric Buddhist traditions. The Four Mudrā (‘seals’) are: *mahāmudrā* (‘great mudrā’), *samayamudrā* (‘pledge mudrā’), *dharmamudrā* (‘doctrine mudrā’), and *karmamudrā* (‘action mudrā’). This fourfold schema is present in many of the influential tantric texts circulating during the eighth and early ninth centuries in India. One such root text was the *Sarvatathāgatattvasaṃgraha* (*STTS*), which is explicitly mentioned in stanza XXIX of this inscription, thus strengthening a possible identification with the Four Mudrā listed above. The *STTS* also contains four main *maṇḍalas*, along with the Four-Mudrā *maṇḍala* which is a more condensed version of the rite outlined in the section for each of the four main *maṇḍalas* (see Weinberger (2003: chapter 1) for a detailed discussion). Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284) writes that the Four Mudrā are a distinguishing mark of the Yogatantra form of the Buddhist Way of Mantras and references the *Rgyud sde spyi’l nam par gzag pa rgyas par brjod* for support. Other tantric Buddhist texts containing the Four Mudrā listed above include, for example, the *Śrīparamādya Tantra* and the *Sarvadurgatipariśodhana Tantra*, just to name two more.

Another influential tantric Buddhist text, the *Guhyasamāja Tantra*, which may be mentioned in the eleventh-century Sab Bāk inscription (K.1158) depending on how *śrīsamāja* is interpreted (for K. 1158, see Prapandvidya (1990) and Estève (2009: 442–49)), has also been connected with the Four Mudrā. A summary of the *Guhyasamāja*’s teaching provided by Amoghavajra include the same four *maṇḍalas* and four kinds of *mudrā* found in the *STTS* (Giebel, 1995: 193). Additionally, the eighth-century Indian tantric exegete, Vilāsavajra, explains the opening words of the *Guhyasamāja* (*evaṃ mayā śrūtam*) in terms of the Four Mudrā: “Now, having clearly explained the succinct meaning of this introductory statement of the *Guhyasamāja-tantra*, I will hereafter interpret it according to the oral instruction of the Ācāryas. So, the letter *E* means the sacramental seal [*samayamudrā*]. The letter *vaṃ* indicates the great seal [*mahāmudrā*]. As for *ma*, it is the Dharma seal, and *yā* is the action seal [*karmamudrā*]. *Śrūtaṃ* provides a sense of commitment” (trans. in Davidson, 2002: 236). Also see Weinberger (2003: 272). Other

XXIV. Although he, a wealth of wisdom, gave away (all the) incalculable wealth he had amassed, still it was said by learned men that he abounded in the wealth of the six *piṭaka*.²⁹

XXV. In actions of every kind he acts for others; but never has it been said by anyone that he acted for himself.³⁰

fourfold *mudrā* classifications exist, however, in other tantric Buddhist texts. Astely-Kristensen's work (1991: 146–47) has shown, for example, that the tantric *Prajñāpāramitā in 150 Verses* (Japanese: *Rishukyō*, Taisho: 243) of Amoghavajra (705–774) discusses: (1) the *mudrā* of the Body of all Tathāgatas, (2) the *mudrā* of the Speech of all Tathāgatas, (3) the *mudrā* of the Mind of all Tathāgatas, and (4) the Vajra *mudrā* of all Tathāgatas.

²⁸ Four assemblies: monks (*bhikṣu*), nuns (*bhikṣuṇī*), laymen (*upāsaka*), laywomen (*upāsikā*).

²⁹ An important stanza that is frustratingly vague. Knowing the exact configuration of the *piṭaka* being used by Buddhists of this time period may have provided insight into the exact affiliations of the Buddhists, as well as other important pieces of information. Based on the sparse evidence available it is currently impossible to determine for sure what the six *piṭaka* referenced in this inscription actually represented. Additionally, my research as thus far failed to locate a single reference to a six *piṭaka* configuration. Evidence exists for a *pañcapīṭaka* ('five *piṭaka*') and various other configurations, but not six. For example, some later literary sources indicate that both Dharmagupta and Bahuśrutīya (a sub-sect of the Mahāsāṅghikas) traditions had a *pañcapīṭaka* which included the well know *Sūtrapīṭaka*, *Vinayapīṭaka*, and the *Abhidharmapīṭaka*, in addition to the *Bodhisattvapīṭaka* and *Dhāraṇīpīṭaka* (see Pagel (1995) for an in-depth discussion on the *Bodhisattvapīṭaka* in connection with sects and other *piṭaka*). According to Skilling (1997: 606–07, and n. 6 for additional sources of the *Vidyādharaṇīpīṭaka*) chapter four of Bhavya's *Tarkajvāla* records, among other things, that the Siddhārthikas of the Mahāsāṅghika-nikāya had a *Vidyādharaṇīpīṭaka*, the Bhadrāyānīyas of the Mahāsāṅghika-nikāya had a *Vaipulyapīṭaka*, and the Haimavatas of the Mahāsāṅghika-nikāya had a *Jātakapīṭaka*. Sorenson's work on the *Triśaraṇasaptati* (1986: 51–53, st. 57–58) indicates that Candrakīrti (c. 600–650 CE) speaks of the seven *piṭaka* of the Pūrvaśailas and Aparāśailas. Lamotte (1988: 286) cites Xuanzang's account of his visit to an Aśokan stūpa (T. 2087, ch. 9, 923a 2–10) where, according Xuanzang, the Mahāsāṅghika canon had been compiled. According to this later account, monks that had not participated in Kāśyapa's council compiled a so-called Dharmapīṭaka which consisted of five *piṭakas*: 1) *Sūtra*-, 2) *Vinaya*-, 3) *Abhidharma*-, *Kṣudraka*-, and a *Dhāraṇī*- (also see Skilling (1992: 115, n.1) for comments on the interchanging of *mantrapīṭaka* and *dhāraṇīpīṭaka* in Xuanzang's account). Interestingly, one arrives at the number six if one were to include the collective Dharmapīṭaka. Skilling (1992: 115) argues that "by the 6th century (at the very latest) Śrāvaka schools of the Mahāsāṅghika fold—the Pūrvaśailas, Aparāśailas, and Siddhārthas—as well as the Dharmaguptakas transmitted a separate *piṭaka*, most probably devoted to *mantras* and spells, known as the *Vidyādhara-pīṭaka*."

The above are just a few references highlighting the variety of *piṭaka* configurations among various Buddhist groups. Again, while it is impossible to determine for sure what the six *piṭaka* referenced in the inscription were based on the current evidence, I would tentatively suggest (guess) that five of the six may have included the *Sūtra*-, *Vinaya*-, and *Abhidharma*-, *Bodhisattva*-, and *Vidyādharaṇīpīṭaka*. The first three are not unreasonable to suggest since they are rather ubiquitous (but not universal) in *piṭaka* configurations. Additionally, the emphasis on bodhisattvas and the bodhisattva path at the beginning of the inscription (cf. st. VII–IX) would make including the *Bodhisattvapīṭaka* a reasonable guess, and the inscription's emphasis on *mantras* (cf. st. LXIX, for example) along with Skilling's observations noted above suggests that the *Vidyādharaṇīpīṭaka* may have been included. As for the sixth *piṭaka*, I would hazard to guess that it included a separate *Dhāraṇīpīṭaka* differentiated from the *Vidyādharaṇīpīṭaka*, but again this is merely an unsupported guess. Additional research on Mahāsāṅghika circles in southern India and early Cambodia's own connections with this part of the world may shed light on this problem in the future.

Side B

XXVI. When the monsoon of worldliness came, darkness enveloped the world; then, the moon of the Buddha's Dharma shone with the coming of autumn's bright fortnight.³¹

XXVII. The sun of doctrines such as *cittamātra* and *nairātmya*,³² eclipsed by the night of false doctrines, once again shone in the day.

XXVIII. He rekindled the lamp for the footpath of the Good Dharma—treatises (*śāstra*) like the *Madhyāntavibhāga*³³—which had been extinguished by the wind of Time.

XXIX. Having obtained the *Lakṣaṅgrantham Abhiprajñam*³⁴ from another kingdom,³⁵ he—subdued in his senses—taught *tantra* including the commentary on the *Tattvasaṅgraha*.³⁶

³⁰ Coedès (*IC*, 6: 205) rightly identified the underlying allusions to Sanskrit grammar in this stanza. Therefore, Kīrtipaṇḍita is the “Agent/Subject (*kartr*) being employed in/causing (*prayojayan*) active voice constructions for others (*parasmaipada*) with respect to all moods/tenses of verbs (*bhāva*) and objects (*karman*), but he never, they say, employs/causes the middle voice constructions for one's self (*ātmanepada*.” Admittedly, rendering a more literal translation of Sanskrit grammatical terminology produces awkward results in English. The stanza can be understood on yet another level by breaking apart the compounds *parasmaipada* and *ātmanepada*. For example, Kīrtipaṇḍita is understood to be the agent (*kartr*) responsible for creating (*prayojayan*) a place (*padam*) for others (*parasmai*) with respect to all beings (*bhāveṣu*) and results (*karmmasu*), but not, they say, a place (*padam*) for himself (*ātmane*). This reading appears to be supported in the inscriptions later emphasis on the proper establishment of a Buddhist monastery. Regardless, in this stanza the author(s) demonstrates his wittiness and literary acumen via pedantic allusions to Sanskrit grammatical terminology.

³¹ In this stanza darkness brought about during the rainy season is likened to the darkness that is ignorance. The Sanskrit word *tamas* carries the sense of both darkness and ignorance. More specifically, *tamas* often refers to some kind of obscuration of light brought about by some external force such as the obscuration of light by the sun or moon during an eclipse, or the darkness resulting from the full monsoon rain clouds. So too, ignorance is a type of mental darkness brought about by delusion, lack of knowledge, etc. Lastly, the autumn moon also signifies the time of the year in which the monsoon season comes to an end.

³² The Sanskrit term *nairātmya* refers to a foundational Buddhist doctrine which posits that all phenomena are ‘without self;’ that is, they are without any independent intrinsic nature. Therefore, according to the Yogācāra epistemological position of this inscription, everything we know, conceive, are aware of, and so forth are known through cognition; again, all we know are ‘nothing but mind constructions’ (*cittamātra*). Also see stanza VIII of this inscription and chapter three of this dissertation for *cittamātra*.

³³ The inscription actually reads *Madhyavibhāgaśāstra*, but it is clear that the inscription is referring to the *Madhyāntavibhāgaśāstra* of Maitreya, an important text within Yogācāra circles. Refer to the list of primary sources in the reference section for the *Madhyāntavibhāgaśāstra* and Stiramati's commentary.

³⁴ The *Lakṣaṅgrantham Abhiprajñam* (‘100,000-verses on Higher Wisdom’) may refer to the 100,000-verse *Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra* (‘100,000-verse Discourse on the Perfection of Wisdom’) according to Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284). I have been unable to locate a primary source reference that identifies *Lakṣaṅgrantham Abhiprajñam* with the 100,000-verse *Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra*; therefore, the connection I am making here is based solely on the observation made by Sanderson.

XXX. After meeting with the son of the lion of the Śākya, those elephant-like logicians (*tārkika*) who were stationed at the side of kings were humbled and overshadowed.

XXXI. Even the name of his disciple, whispered into the ears of disputants, caused panic (in them) like a *mantra* in a circle of snakes.

XXXII. He was appointed *guru* by delighted kings³⁷ and their ladies of the inner chambers,³⁸ and he constantly taught the Buddha Dharma seated upon the Dharma-pedestal.³⁹

³⁵ See chapter four of this dissertation for an in-depth discussion on the use of *pararāṣṭra* which can be variously translated as 'other/another kingdom/land' 'foreign kingdom/land,' 'enemy kingdom/land,' and so forth. In short, I argue that the polity (or polities) of Campā is a likely candidate for the travels of Kīrtipaṇḍita.

³⁶ Or: "taught the *tantra* including the *Tattvasaṅgraha* and its commentary." Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 205, n.3) suggested that the *Tattvasaṅgrahaṭīkā* mentioned here was Kamalaśīla's commentary of Śāntarakṣita's *Tattvasaṅgraha*. However, Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284) has recently argued that it is more probable that the text referenced here is the *STTS*, the principle text of the Yogatantras. Peter Sharrock (2006: 16–27, 300) is also convinced of this position. In going against Cœdès' position, Sanderson writes, "It appears more probable that having mentioned sources of the two major branches of the Sūtra tradition of the Mahāyāna (*i.e.*, the *Madhyāntavibhāgaśāstra* and the *Lakṣaṅgrantham Abhiprajñam*) he now speaks of the complementary Way of its commentary." I think this could be an important observation, and the keyword in Sanderson's statement is complementary. The tantric views and practices being adopted during this period were not intended to completely supplant the epistemological Buddhist foundations (in this case Yogācāra) so much as provide complementary methods of practice that expedite certain goals, like the attainment of Buddhahood for example, or achieve a goal in a different manner by the employment of a new, or redeveloped, practice. As Sanderson observed, this is supported in another stanza of the inscription alluding to both exoteric and esoteric forms of the Dharma established by Kīrtipaṇḍita (st. XLII). Based on the overall inscription, the bodhisattva path is still of primary importance, as are understanding reality in terms of key concepts such as *cittamātra* and *nairātmya* and adhering to monastic regulations. With the new addition of the Mantrayāna ('Way of Mantras') what is changing is how an inspiring practitioner proceeds along the bodhisattva path, and the additional techniques and practices employed during that journey. For more on the *STTS*, see Chandra and Snellgrove (1981: 5–67) and Weinberger (2003 and 2010).

³⁷ According to Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 285) the plural *rājabhiḥ* ('by kings') may, instead, be the plural of respect (*ādare bahuvacanam*), in which case the translation should read "by the delighted king and his ladies. . ."

³⁸ I have decided to translate *sāntaḥpuraiḥ* a bit more literally since terms such as 'wives' and 'harem' are misleading and unsatisfying. The Sanskrit *antaḥpura* refers to an inner chamber reserved for women in a ruler's household. Depending on the context these women may, or may not, be actual 'wives.' The term *harem* carries a negative connotation due to an over romanticized and imaginative usage in the West, and so I have avoided using this term as well.

³⁹ Regarding the Dharma-pedestal or Dharma-throne (Skt. *dharmāsana*), Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 285) writes that according to an account in the *Suvarṇabhāṣāsottamasūtra*, when the king wishes to hear that text "he should sprinkle the palace with scented water, scatter it with flowers, set up a highly, richly adorned Dharma throne for the preacher (*dharmabhāṇakaḥ*), decorating the place with chowries, parasols, banners and pennants, and a lower throne for himself on which he is to sit and listen without any thoughts of his royal power."

XXXIII. For the King (or Kings) of Kambu, he always conducted speeches which were, through experience, based on his own knowledge of times and places in the past

XXXIV. . . . (The condemned) . . . , by means of invoking conciliatory words, were made favorable to the king by him, even those deserving death because of various perils to the king were set free.

XXXV. Having noticed while performing the business of the king that ascetics had gone astray, those individuals were made known to the king by him (and they were) freed from their troubles and established in proper conduct.

XXXVI. Having been treated with hospitality, the king charged him with (performing) rites such as *puṣṭi* and *śānti*⁴⁰ inside the palace for the sake of protecting the kingdom's territory (*maṇḍala*).⁴¹

⁴⁰ The rites employed by Kīrtipaṇḍita were the rites of *puṣṭi* and *śānti*. The former is a rite of acquisition or augmentation, and in the context of the inscription it refers to the acquisition of, or augmenting of, the kingdom's welfare and prosperity. The latter is a rite of pacification, and in the context of the inscription refers to the peace and pacification of territories under the control of a ruler (or, perhaps, the territories a ruler desires to control). The inscription states that other similar rites were employed, but unfortunately these rites are not listed. Both rites appear in a number of texts, and not all the texts are Buddhist. In fact, Buddhist practitioners likely appropriated such rites from earlier Vedic and Brahmanical sources; see P.V. Kane (1930–62, 5: 734–43) who discusses pacification rites (*śānti*) during the Vedic period in addition to writing about pacification rites in the *Dharmaśāstra*. In *Dharmaśāstra* literature, *śānti* rites are considered *prāyaścitta*; in other words, they were considered to be rites related to atonement, penance, and expiation. The rite of pacification (*śāntikakarman*) is one of the six commonly listed rites comprising the *ṣaṭkarmāṇi* ('six rites') of purāṇic and śāstric Hindu traditions, as well as Indian tantric traditions in general. The list of six rites varies tremendously, but the most common set includes: (1) pacification (*śānti*), (2) subjugation (*vaśya*, *vaśīkaraṇa*), (3) immobilization (*stambhana*), (4) causing dissension (*vidveṣaṇa*), (5) eradication (*uccāṭana*), and (6) liquidation/killing (*māraṇa*). Again, the list varies; the rite of augmentation (*puṣṭikarman*), for example, is alternatively listed as one of the *ṣaṭkarmāṇi* in other sources; see Cuevas (2010: 183 n. 15) for examples of a number of other rites alternatively listed for the *ṣaṭkarmāṇi*. Also see Goudriaan (1978: 251–412) for an extended discussion on the six rites. For a detailed description of the *ṣaṭkarmāṇi* in the context of *abhiḥāra* (a term frequently translated as 'sorcery'), see Turstig (1985: 101–08). Turstig additionally demonstrates that *abhiḥāra* denoted a particular rite that had been incorporated into Tantric traditions. For example, Turstig draws attention to the use of *śānti* in Dāmodara's seventeenth-century text on the employment of *yantras* (instruments or diagrams used to 'control') in the *Yantracintāmaṇi*, also known as the *Kalpacintāmaṇi*. As Turstig (1985: 110–11) notes, there are different versions of the *Kalpacintāmaṇi*. For the *Kalpacintāmaṇi*, also see Bühnemann (2003: 568). Also see Bühnemann (2000) for a discussion on the six rites enumerated in the *Mantramahodadhi* ('Great Ocean of Mantras'), a Sanskrit text composed by Mahīdhara at Varanasi in 1588. Both *puṣṭi* and *śānti* rites are also part of the standard set of 'four actions' (Skt. *catuḥ karmāṇi*; Tib. *las bzhi*) in Indian and Tibetan ritual: (1) pacification (Skt. *śānti*; Tib. *zhi*), (2) augmentation (Skt. *puṣṭi*; Tib. *rgyas*), (3) subjugation (Skt. *vaśya*; Tib. *dbang*), and (4) ferocity (Skt. *raudra*; Tib. *drag*); for a general description of these four rites in a tantric context, see Snellgrove (1987, 1: 238). With regard to a tantric context, the eighth chapter of the *Samvarodaya Tantra*, which details sacramental ceremonies, mentions both *śānti* and *puṣṭi* together: "having prepared the sacrificial offering (bali) which is decorated with banners and a parasol the master (of ceremonies) should pay honor to it thus propitiating the divinities. Then he should ask the donor what ritual he has in mind, whether one for pacifying (*śānti*) or one for prosperity (*puṣṭi*); for the purpose of fulfillment and in accordance with the rite decided, he should carry through the ritual;"

trans. Snellgrove (1987, 1: 164). The *Samvarodaya Tantra* dates to no earlier than the eighth century, and has surviving Sanskrit and Tibetan manuscripts. For an alternative translation and additional information on the *Samvarodaya Tantra*, see Tsuda (1974). Finally, both *śānti* and *puṣṭi* occur together in chapter nine of the *STTS*, a tantric text belonging to Yogatantra classification. “Therefore, having accurately performed extensive rites in the Karma Maṇḍala, he should produce knowledge of the rites of the Vajrakula (‘Adamantine Family’). Starting in that place, he should train in knowledge beginning with the rite(s) of pacification (*śānti*). Concentrated in thought he ignites the fire with sweet-swelling wood and self-composed in Vajra-Wrath he burns up evils by offering sesame oil. With the very same wood he ignites the one consumes the oblation (= the fire god) and by offering grain, prosperity (*puṣṭi*) for the house is assured. The sage ignites the fire with mellifluous wood and offering there the young shoots of millet with clarified butter, he causes an extension of life. With the very same wood he ignites the one who consumes the oblation and by offering there the young shoots of *kuśa* grass together with oil, protection is always assured;” the first two lines are my translation, and the remaining lines are Snellgrove’s translation (1987, 1: 239). Skt. *athātra karmamaṇḍale yathāvad vidhivistaram kṛtvā vajrakulakarmajñānyutpādayet / tatrādīta eva śāntikarmādijñānam śikṣayet / samidbhirmadhurairagniṃ prajvālya susamāhitaḥ / vajrakrodhasamāpattiyā tilāṃ hutvā aghāndaheṭ // 1 // taireva tu samidbhistu prajvālya tu hutāśanam / taṇḍulāṃstu juhvan nityaṃ gṛhapuṣṭirbhaved dhruvaṃ // 2 // samidbhirmadhuraiścāpi agniṃ prajvālya paṇḍitaḥ / dūrvāpravālāṃ saghṛtān juhvannāyuh pravardhate // 3 // taireva tu samidbhistu prajvālya tu hutāśanam / kuśapravālāṃstailena juhvan rakṣā tu śāśvatam // iti // 4 //*, Chandra and Snellgrove (1981). As previously mentioned, Sanderson (2004) and Sharrock (2006 and 2012) maintain that this text—and not Kamalaśīla’s commentary on Śāntarākṣita’s *Tattvasaṃgraha* as Coëdès (IC, 6: 205, n. 3) believed—is the text cited in stanza XXIX of the inscription. The fact that both the *STTS* and the Vat Sithor inscription both explicitly cite the *śānti* rite(s), in connection with prosperity (*puṣṭi*), may strengthen this observation. In the context of the *STTS*, *śānti* is connected with the Vajrakula (Vajra or Adamantine Family), to which the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi belongs. In Cambodia, Vajrapāṇi first appears during this period in both epigraphical and the art historical sources, and this figure was evidently important to both Kavīndrārimathana and Kīrtipaṇḍita. Stanza XLV of the inscription describes how Kīrtipaṇḍita had reestablished more than ten images of Vajrapāṇi and Lokeśvara.

⁴¹ The kingdom’s *maṇḍala* (literally ‘circle’) can be thought of as simply the kingdom’s territory or realm. The term *maṇḍala* conveys the more complex and fragile nature of the political structures during this period, in which political power was much more diffused instead of truly consolidated. In general, the kingdom’s *maṇḍala* refers to a collective political structure in which a network of neighboring territories, each with their own local rulers, were subordinate to the core, or ruling, territory, whose own authority diminished with distance. The structure, as a whole, was maintained by a web of alliances, treaties and physical force. Inherently, this type of political structure was highly unstable as subordinate territories were constantly jockeying for position and attempting to establish themselves as superior to their neighbors. This is a highly abbreviated description of what S. J. Tambiah (1976: 102–31) labels the ‘galactic polity.’ More recently, Victor Lieberman (2003: 33) has abandoned Tambiah’s galactic polity in favor of the term ‘solar polity.’ In terms of a general model, I favor the additional nuances of Lieberman who writes: “Each realm was a ‘solar polity’ – this term is more descriptively accurate than S. J. Tambiah’s ‘galactic polity’ – in which provincial ‘planets’ revolved around a sun whose ‘gravitational pull’ diminished with distance. Insofar as each planet had its own satellite moons, its gravitational system replicated in decreasing scale the structure of the solar system as a whole. The farthest planets were ruled by hereditary tributaries; less distant realms, by powerful local families or relatives of the High King. All such leaders were tied to the overlord by webs of family, marriage, and patronage whose instability ensure constant fluctuations in the center’s territorial influence.” Of course, to some extent, this is an imported and ideal model that would have been localized, and thus different in ways specific to the geographical, cultural and temporal context of early Cambodia. Such localized differences in the political structures, however, are beyond the scope of this dissertation. A point to remember, however, is that the inscription specifically describes the employment of specialized rites that were thought to ensure the stability and function of a delicate political system, not some unified or monolithic territory with absolute control.

XXXVII. For the sake of protecting Buddhists, he reestablished an ardently-fashioned image of the Sage whose pedestal had increasingly fallen into disrepair.

XXXVIII. Having desired to lead uncultivated people to the gate of liberation, he offered with joy a gate covered with silver and riches to the Sage.

XXXIX. Having procured the Supreme Non-Dual Vehicle (*advayānuttaram yānam*) for others in the same manner (he had procured it for) himself, he dedicated a pair of palanquins made of gold and silver to the Sage.

XL. Covering the great abode of the Sage with copper (tiles), he erected a temple (*prāsāda*) richly adorned with gold and jewels and a silver lion throne.

XLI. Having striven to obtain for the sake of others the fruit in the field of the most eminent Muni, he dedicated 4000 *khāri*⁴² of rice to the Sage.

XLII. Having established the Good Dharma in both its exoteric and esoteric forms, he built for the purpose of worship separate hermitages (*āśrama*) for the Buddhist community and their guests.⁴³

XLIII. He donated to the Sage many male and female elephants, horses, buffaloes, bulls, cows, hermitages (*āśrama*), goods (*bhoga*), and female and male servants.

XLIV. In that place the protector Prajñāpāramitā, the mother of protectors, was established by him for the sake of continuing the luminous lineage of the Omniscient One.⁴⁴

⁴² According to Pou (1992: s.v. *khāri* and *tloñ*) the *khāri* is equivalent to *tloñ* and *thlañ* which all refer to “a measure for grains or salt : a large basket,” also see M.W., s.v. *khāra*.

⁴³ This stanza appears very clear that the Buddhism being practiced at this time had a complementary esoteric (Skt. *guhya*) form. Based on other pieces of information in the inscription, this complementary esoteric form may have included the addition of new texts (such as the *STTS* cited in st. XXIX) and a strong emphasis on practices involving *mudrās* (‘seals,’ or ‘hand gestures’), *mantras* (the uttering of sacred syllables or words), *vidyās* (‘incantations’) and so forth (cf. st. XXIII, XXXVI and XLII). It should be noted that such practices are not new in Buddhism, but merely attain a certain level of emphasis in tantric forms of thought and practice. For a basic overview of tantric thought and practices, see Anthony Tribe’s chapter in Williams and Tribe (2000: 192–244), as well as Isaacson (1998). For a more in-depth account on Indian esoteric Buddhism, see Davidson (2002).

⁴⁴ Compare Cœdès’ translation (*IC*, 6 : 206–07): Il érigea en cet endroit, pour perpétuer la lumière de la famille des Omniscients, une Prajñāpāramitā, mère des (Buddha) protecteurs. Additionally, Sarvavid is an epithet meaning ‘all-knowing’ and ‘omniscient,’ and it is often used to refer to the Buddha, a buddha, or even a bodhisattva (cf. *STSS* chapter eleven in Chandra and Snellgrove (1981) where Sarvavid = Vajrapāṇi). Sarvavid, however, is also an epithet often specifically used for Mahā-Vairocana, a possibility that would not be out of context in this inscription. For example, see *Mahāvairocanābhisaṃbodhi Tantra*,

XLV. He reestablished more than ten images of Vajrin and Lokeśa⁴⁵ which had previously been erected on a mountain by Śrī Satyavarman, and whose pedestals had been broken.

XLVI. On a mountain top in his own town called Kumārambha,⁴⁶ as well as in towns such as Amarendra, he erected (images of) Lokeśa and others.

XLVII. After restoring in (various) regions many sacred images of the Buddha which were worn and broken, he established many hermitages and ponds.

XLVIII. That gracious teacher of men, along with a company of his disciples, founded (an image) of the Sage; many temples and properties were assigned (to it).

XLIX. In Śaka 869 (947 CE), in the village of [?]rmmapaṭṭana, he established . . . (?) for the sake of others and himself.⁴⁷

L. All . . . by this order of the king . . . he . . . the offering (*piṇḍa*) of the radiant fire.

II.4.14 (Giebel (2005) and Hodge (2003) provide English translations), and numerous instances in the *Sarvadurgatipariśodhana* (see Skorupski (1983) for an English translation). Also see my footnote on this stanza in the transliteration section (Appendix A).

⁴⁵ In the compound *vajrilokeśa*, ‘vajri-’ may refer to the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi, and ‘-lokeśa’ may refer to the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara. This was how Coëdès’ interpreted the compound. More recently, however, Griffiths (2013: 48, n. 12 and 14) has suggested that the compound refers to a single kind of image called Vajrilokeśa. In accordance with his argument that the information in the later Sab Bāk inscription (K. 1158) can be fully reconciled with that in K. 111, he states that these Vajrilokeśa images can be identified with a group of images the Sab Bāk inscription calls ‘Buddhalokeśvara.’

⁴⁶ Although the exact location of Kīrtipaṇḍita’s hometown remains unknown, a detailed discussion on Kumārambha is undertaken in chapter four of this dissertation to narrow down the general region where this town may have been. In short, Kumārambha may have been located somewhere in the region of Hariharālaya. Hariharālaya is associated with the so-called Rolous group which includes temples like Preah Ko, Bakong and Lolei. It represents an area located eighteen kilometers (eleven miles) southeast of the city of Siem Reap.

⁴⁷ Although this portion of the inscription is damaged, the still legible date indicates that Kīrtipaṇḍita would have also been active during the preceding reign of Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 967/968). Rājendravarman was responsible for transferring the capital of his kingdom back to Yaśodharapura (i.e., the Angkor region) after it had been relocated—for reasons still not all together clear—to Chok Gargyar (Koh Ker) during the reign of Jayavarman IV (r. c. 928–c. 941). Koh Ker is around sixty-two miles (100 kilometers) northeast of Angkor. For recent research on Koh Ker, see Bourdonneau (2011). The important point to be made is that Kīrtipaṇḍita was active during an important period in which Rājendravarman was reestablishing the capital and restructuring his administrative infrastructure, a project that involved numerous public works in an attempt to restore Yaśodharapura to its former glory.

Side C

LI. This order of Glorious Jayavarman which follows the Buddha's Dharma is to be followed by the Buddhists in order to attain the happiness of liberation.⁴⁸

LII. The stars of *nakṣatras*,⁴⁹ foremost of which is *Pūrvaphalguṇī*,⁵⁰ are declared most beautiful; therefore, they are regarded as the lords of the twelve months.⁵¹

LIII. Bringing about both prosperity and destruction in the world, highly efficacious and powerful, they (the Lords of *nakṣatras*) observe all beings, those engaged in righteousness and unrighteousness.

LIV. For that reason, terrible winds and rain assail the wicked, but all these gods and *nāgas* bring about delight in the righteous.

LV. Desiring happiness, the festivals of the twelve (lunar months) are to be performed regularly month after month as prescribed in the teachings (*śāstrāḥ*) for the sake of living beings.

LVI. Honoring those who had been established in the order of the Great Sage, the one who has subdued his senses should sound the gong, which is situated before the fire, three times daily.

LVII. Those who are attentive, even in meditative contemplation, to the sound (of the gong), which is purifying since it teaches the proper time of the religious acts of the community, these are the virtuous ones who have gone to the most sacred heaven.

LVIII. Having constructed a monastery, he who dedicates it (the monastery) to the Three Jewels for the welfare of others obtains great merit.

LVIX. All donations (*saṃbhoga*) prepared for the Three Jewels should be separately kept in three portions, not mixed with one another.⁵²

⁴⁸ The following order by Jayavarman V is described, sometimes vaguely, in the stanzas following stanza LI and these declarations represent the official reason for the commissioning of the inscription.

⁴⁹ The term *nakṣatra* refers to a lunar mansion; in other words, an asterism. There are twenty-seven *nakṣatras* reflecting the cycle of the moon in relation to groupings of fixed stars.

⁵⁰ *Pūrvaphalguṇī* is the eleventh *nakṣatra*, and is associated with the Delta and Theta Leonis stars of the Western constellation known as Leo.

⁵¹ Or : moons.

LX. If the consecration of a monastery has not been properly conducted by the monks, then it is not a monastery, but merely a *koṣṭhāgāra* (store-room or treasury).

LXI. If this (the construction of the monastery) has been performed (merely) for the sake of one's livelihood, not for the sake of others, and not for the sake of mental tranquility; there is no *brahmapuṇya* in this place by which he might attain omniscience.⁵³

⁵² That is, donations to the Buddha, Dharma and Saṅgha were to be kept separate from one another. For all intents and purposes, the Buddha was held to reside within a monastery once the image of the Buddha had been ritually installed within a dedicated chamber located within the monastery. As a resident of the monastery, so to speak, the Buddha was entitled to portions of the donations. Such donations would have ensured the upkeep of the Buddha image, as well as ritual activities involving the Buddha image. The donations would have included things such as libation ingredients, food, candles, incense and so forth (or other forms of wealth to ensure the acquisition of such materials). The portion of donations for the Dharma would have been reserved for those preserving the Dharma, often by means of copying the word of the Buddha (i.e., the copying of Buddhist texts) and the explication of the Dharma to others. Although fragmented, such activities are referenced on side D of this inscription (cf. st. LXXIX–LXXXII). The portion of the donations to the Buddhist community (*saṅgha*) would have likely included provisions such as clothing and food, or some form of wealth to ensure their acquisition. Schopen (1997b: esp. 272 for examples of texts indicating a division of donations) has discussed at length the concept of the Buddha as a resident within a monastery and an owner of property. He has also highlighted several sections of the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* which clearly demonstrate that donations were to be equally divided among the Buddha, Dharma and Saṅgha.

⁵³ The technical concept of *brahmapuṇya* ('Merit of Brahma'), a special and immense form of merit, has not been given any attention in this inscription. This is unfortunate since we may learn more about the forms of Buddhism informing this inscription by examining the few Buddhist sources that discuss the concept of *brahmapuṇya*. According to the *Samghabhedavastu* of the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya*, there are four ways to obtain *brahmapuṇya*:

catvāra ime śāriputramaudgalyāyanau brāhmaṃ puṇyaṃ prasavanti; katame catvāraḥ yaḥ pudgalaḥ apratiṣṭhitapūrve pṛthivīpradeśe tathāgatasya śārīraṃ stūpaṃ pratiṣṭhāpayati; ayaṃ prathamah pudgalaḥ brāhmaṃ puṇyaṃ prasavati; kalpaṃ svargeṣu modate; punar aparaṃ yaḥ pudgalaḥ apratiṣṭhitapūrve pṛthivīpradeśe caturdiśasya bhikṣusamghasya vihāraṃ pratiṣṭhāpayati; ayaṃ dvitīyah pudgalaḥ brāhmaṃ puṇyaṃ prasavati; kalpaṃ svargeṣu modate; punar aparaṃ yaḥ pudgalaḥ tathāgataśrāvakaṃ samghaṃ bhinnam sandhatte; ayaṃ tritīyah pudgalaḥ brāhmaṃ puṇyaṃ prasavati; kalpaṃ svargeṣu modate; punar aparaṃ yaḥ pudgalaḥ maitrīśahagatena cittena avaireṇa asapatnena avyābādhena vipulena mahadgatena apramāṇena subhāvitena ekāṃ diśam adhimucya spharivā upasampadya viharati; [. . .] ayaṃ caturthah pudgalaḥ brāhmaṃ puṇyaṃ prasavati; kalpaṃ svargeṣu modate (Gnoli, 1977–78: 206–07).

Four persons, Śāriputra and Maudgalyāyana, produce *brāhmapuṇya*; what four? The person who establishes a *stūpa* (enshrining) the bodily relics of the Tathāgata in a region of the earth where one was not previously established (*apratīṣṭhitapūrve pṛthivīpradeśe*), this is the first person who produces *brāhmapuṇya*. Additionally, the person who establishes a monastery for the Community of monks of the four quarters in a region of the earth where one was not previously established, this is the second person who produces *brāhmapuṇya*; he will rejoice in heaven for a *kalpa*. Additionally, the person who unites the Community of *śrāvaka*s of the Tathāgata which has been divided, this is the third person who produces *brāhmapuṇya*; he will rejoice in heaven for a *kalpa*. Additionally, having received ordination, having been suffused (with compassion), and having been zealously devoted (to the Dharma) in this one place, the person who leads a life with a mind accompanied with loving-kindness (*maitrīśahagatena*) which is thoroughly infused, infinite, immense, extensive, without malice, without rivalry, and without enmity . . .

LXII. When the consecration of a monastery has been performed according to the proper rule, then imperishable merit spreads everywhere like the open sky.

LXIII. Vile men who violate (the object of this)⁵⁴ merit, for whatever reason, shall experience the endless and terrible pain of hell.

LXIV. Householders must not take the Community's possessions, for this is a poison. Excellent *mantras*, indeed, counteract poison, but not (the poison incurred from taking the possessions of the) Buddhist Community.

LXV. Thus, having completed the command of the Omniscient One with his heart set on devotion, by founding a monastery according to the proper rule, the learned one (Kīrtipaṇḍita) settled (there) from afar.

LXVI. Those endowed with good qualities, good character, and who are learned are superior to the masses; various goods are prepared for their benefit by one desiring merit.⁵⁵

LXVII. At dawn and other times, the rites of those who have subdued their senses and which were prescribed by the Sage must be performed in their entirety by the community (*saṅgha*), especially by the *yājaka*.⁵⁶

this is the fourth person who produces *brāhmapuṇya*; he will rejoice in heaven for a *kalpa*. (translation my own)

This aids immensely in understanding the context of the inscription. One of the four ways to earn *brahmapuṇya*, according to the Saṃghabheda, is to establish a monastery where previously there was none, and this is exactly what is being discussed in stanzas LVIII–LXV. Stanza LXI warns the disingenuous that if founding the monastery was only undertaken for one's own livelihood, and not for the benefit of others, and not for the sake of attaining tranquility, then one will not accumulate *brahmapuṇya*. That is, one would be unable to earn an immense amount of merit that would have ensured a rebirth in heaven (Skt. *svarga*) where one could have expected to live for a *kalpa*. Chapter LI of *Mahāprajñāpāramitāśāstra* (see Lamotte, 1944 and 1949, 5: 2310) also references one of the methods for attaining *brahmapuṇya* when it specifically indicates the building of a *stūpa* where previously there was none will earn the bodhisattva *brahmapuṇya*. See Martini (2011: 157–58) for the six-fold version of the *brahmapuṇya* in the Khotanese *Book of Zambastu*.

⁵⁴ i.e., the monastery and/or donations provided to the monastery

⁵⁵ This stanza indicates the high and esteemed status of a Buddhist monk who is also understood to represent a field of accessible merit to the laity. The donation of various goods such as cloth for robes, food, incense and so forth by the laity would earn them merit for their generosity and support. The accumulation of such merit would help ensure the donor (or the donor's family if the donation was performed on their behalf) a more favorable rebirth and general success in life.

⁵⁶ The *yājaka* is the individual in charge of performing the daily oblations. The *yājaka* is also mentioned in later in stanza XCII. The term is often translated in a more literal sense as 'sacrificer.' We must be careful, however, not to assume that this term is referring to some brahmanical priest in charge of non-Buddhist 'sacrifices' since words derived from the √yaj (e.g., Skt. *yajña*, P. *yañña*) were frequently utilized in Buddhist sources not only to refer to brahmanical sacrifice but also gifts and oblations to Buddhist

LXVIII. Members of the Buddhist community (*saṅgha*) are not invited⁵⁷ to approach any sacrificial rites; those who voluntarily come near that place⁵⁸ (i.e., the site where the sacrifices are performed), even with good intentions, incur guilt.⁵⁹

LXIX. The *purohita* who is learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, *vidyā*, *mantra*, *mudra*, and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṅṭā*), is worthy of donations.⁶⁰

LXX. On the *parva* days, the *purohita* should perform the ritual bathing and so forth of the Sage together with the hymns of the Veda, the *ārṣabha*, the *brahmaghoṣa*, the eye-opening ceremony (*unmīla*), and the ritual sprinkling (*abhiṣecana*).⁶¹

monks. For example, T. W. Rhys Davids has demonstrated that the use of *yañña* in Pali Sutta Piṭaka sources has the prevailing meaning of ‘gift, oblation to the bhikkhu, almsgiving’ (PTS, s.v. *yañña*).

⁵⁷ The Sanskrit word here is *animantrita* (‘not invited,’ ‘not summoned,’ ‘not called,’ etc.), and it is being used as an adjective to modify *saṅgha* (‘community’); therefore, both words are declined in the masculine, instrumental, plural case (*animantritaiḥ*, *saṅghaiḥ*). Rendering this into western languages has possibly resulted in some misleading translations. For example, Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 208–09) translates *animantrita* as ‘a moins d’y avoir été invites,’ a translation that is followed by Snellgrove (2001: 809) when he renders Cœdès’ translation into English as ‘unless specifically assigned’ (i.e., ‘unless they have been invited’). But I feel this is misleading and probably incorrect. Based on the overall context of the inscription, this Sanskrit stanza is not indicating an exception to the ban; in other words, it is not indicating that certain members of the *saṅgha* could have attended if they were only invited. Again, *animantrita* is an adjective modifying *saṅgha*. The Sanskrit is indicating that *animantritaiḥ saṅghaiḥ* is a nominal phrase that means the ‘*saṅgha* (is) uninvited,’ or, taking the instrumental plural case into account, ‘by the *saṅgha* who are not invited’ That is, the word *saṅgha* is adjectivally modified to indicate a group that is specifically not permitted to attend the sacrificial rites. The interpretations, especially by Snellgrove, that have resulted from the misleading translation of this phrase are the topic of chapter seven of this dissertation.

⁵⁸ Skt. *tatra*.

⁵⁹ I have translated *pāpabhāginah* simply as ‘incurs guilt,’ but it could be translated a variety of other ways that all basically mean that the transgressors have committed an offense. Much like *pācittiya* offenses in Pali sources, the incurring of guilt also probably required some form of ritual expiation. This verse is almost certainly referring to Brahmanical sacrifices that were condemned by the Buddha as being both cruel and ineffective with regard to one’s welfare. This verse echoes numerous references in Buddhist sources that remind monks about the inefficacy of such practices. Chapter seven argues that this stanza is not an example of Brahmanical tensions or some kind of disparaging remark against Buddhists. It is simply a Buddhist monastic regulation included in an inscription pertaining to the establishment of the monastery. As such, it reinforces the identity of who the Buddhist monks were and what they were expected to do, and not do. For similar remarks in Buddhist sources, refer to chapter seven of this dissertation.

⁶⁰ Also see the notes for st. LXXII.

⁶¹ The *parva* days refer to ritual days marking the four changes of the moon. During these times, the installed Buddha image is to be ritually bathed (Skt. *snāna*); an important meritorious activity also emphasized in stanzas LXXI and LXXIV. See Lessing (1959) and Boucher (1995) for a translation of primary sources focusing on the bathing of the Buddha. The importance of Vedic hymns in the list of rituals is noteworthy, but should not be construed as strange. Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 209, n. 4) noted that the

LXXI. The worlds are happy and the Dharma is prosperous by undertaking such (activities as) bathing the Buddha; for surely, the entire universe of animate and inanimate beings are contained within the body of the Omniscience One.

LXXII. Dependent Origination,⁶² the *brahmaghoṣa*, the Good Dharma that is most excellent (*āṛṣabha*),⁶³ and the hymn on the practice of tranquility (*śānti-avadhāraḥ*) are known as the Gāthāveda.⁶⁴

LXXIII. “When the unparalleled *brahmaghoṣa* (and other) chants are recited on my head, that head is exceedingly fortunate,” (this is the) teachings of the Omniscient One.⁶⁵

reference is specifically referring to the Gāthāveda recorded and defined in stanza LXII, and as such the term may be simply be referring to ‘hymns of knowledge,’ and not necessarily the Vedas used by Brahmins and other non-Buddhist sects. Even if the stanza does refer to the more traditional Vedas, this would not alter the fact that the role of the *purohita* according to this inscription is (re)defined to mean an individual that is also well-versed and acquainted with Buddhist thought and practice.

The word *āṛṣabha* (an adjective derived from *ṛṣabha*, ‘bull’) is, literally, that which comes from or is produced by a bull (*i.e.*, semen; also see PED, s.v. *āsabha* and *usabha*). It may be used to describe something as virile or manly, as well as something most excellent. Edgerton (BHS, s.v. *āṛṣabha*) documents that *āṛṣabha* denotes something “of the first rank (esp. religiously), prime, worthy of admiration,” and that it has been used to refer to *nirvāṇa*. In his translation of the *Mahāprajñāpāramitāśāstra*, Lamotte (1944 and 1949, 3: 1508, 1592; 5: 2194) provides extensive references in Pali texts and corresponding Sanskrit texts on the use of *āṛṣabha* as the ‘place of the bull’ (*i.e.*, the supreme place) and also its use to describe the Buddha’s noble speech as a ‘bull’s speech.’ Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 209, n. 3) states that it is probably a synonym for the Dharma by noting that it appears again in stanza LXXII as *saddharma āṛṣabhaḥ*, which he translated as ‘the Good Law of the Bull.’ Cœdès was probably right, and here I currently understand the term to represent an additional corpus of hymns relating to the Dharma, or the recitation of the Dharma itself.

The term *brahmaghoṣa* (‘voice of Brahma’) may refer to recitation or chanting in general, but in the context of the inscription it appears to represent a specific hymn, or perhaps a specific collection of hymns. The term appears again in stanzas LXXII and LXXIII.

The word *unmīla* (also *unmīlana*) refers to the ritual eye-opening ceremony of a monastery’s installed image, and the *abhiṣecana* refers to the ritual sprinkling or consecration of that image. These are important ritual acts, and to use Richard Gombrich’s words (1966: 24), “The very act of consecration indicates that the statue is being brought to life . . .” See Swearer (2004 and 1995) for more on the consecration of Buddha images.

⁶² Dependent Origination (Skt. *pratītyasamutpāda*) is a foundational Buddhist doctrine of casual theory. See Boisvert (2004) for a concise overview of *pratītyasamutpāda*.

⁶³ Or: Bull-like. See the above notes on *āṛṣabha* in stanza LXX.

⁶⁴ To understand Gāthāveda (‘Songs of the Sacred Knowledge’) we must rely on the inscription’s own definition since I am unable to discover another reference to such a collection.

⁶⁵ In other words, reciting the *brahmaghoṣa* and other chants/incantations (Skt. *vidyāḥ*) in the presence of the Buddha image is an advantageous activity.

LXXIV. When an inauspicious eclipse, a bad omen, the movement of the heavens (*saṃkrāntī*), the rising of a calamity (occurs), such things as the bath of Śāstu should be performed for the peace of all beings.⁶⁶

LXXV. In order for the faith of men and the prosperity of the teachings to grow, instruction in the Dharma must be performed by the wise on the *pratiparva* days.⁶⁷

Side D

LXXVI–LXXVII. STANZA(S) RUINED

LXXVIII. Even though these wise persons . . . *pūjā* should be offered . . . bowed in *añjali* . . . by those with a mind set on devotion.

LXXIX. . . . the most important part of carrying out the Dharma . . . the Dharma prospers always and everywhere.

LXXX. . . . one-pointed attention, moving slightly, . . . also, may he obtain infinite merit speaking . . .

LXXXI. “Indeed, if uncultivated beings have merit, then one who maintains the Good Dharma cultivates abundant merit,” said the Sage.

LXXXII. Therefore, one who is sagacious, having abandoned other tasks, resides in a monastery and embraces the Good Dharma at all times through such activities as transcribing (sacred manuscripts).

LXXXIII. The head of the monastery adorned with all the rules of proper conduct (*ācāra*) must properly approach all exalted *gurus* who are to be honored.⁶⁸

LXXXIV. A voice accompanied by proper conduct, always and everywhere grass, water, and land are for the sages who desire the essence of the body.⁶⁹

⁶⁶ Śāstu is an epithet of the Buddha meaning ‘teacher.’ The word is related to the epithet Śāsta (BHS, s.v. *śāstar*). During inauspicious times and during calamities the stanza is recommending that monks perform the ritual bathing of the installed Buddha image for the welfare and protection of the people. The benefits of bathing the Buddha image are emphasized earlier in stanzas LXX and LXXI.

⁶⁷ The *pratiparva* days are the days of the new moon and full moon. The ceremony being refer to is probably the *poṣadha* (P. *uposatha*), during which the recitation of *prātimokṣa* (P. *pāṭimokkha*; monastic codes of the Vinaya) takes place. During this time monks are required to assemble and publically confess any monastic transgressions. See Harvey (1990: 224–29) and Tsomo (2004) for short overviews on the *prātimokṣa*.

⁶⁸ The imperative verb, *avalam*, (‘must go to, approach, meet, etc.’) can also mean ‘must cherish,’ and this alternative meaning is, in fact, imbedded in the meaning of the stanza. That is, the head of the monastery is expected to properly (*yathā*) approach and honor/cherish all exalted (*abhyudgatāḥ*) *gurus*.

LXXXV. Although the body, like a latrine, is always the receptacle of all impurities; nevertheless, its essence is the Dharma which is regarded as a wish-fulfilling tree.

LXXXVI. The treasure of the Dharma must be seized by the wise because the body quickly perishes just as if it were boat sunk in the ocean or a house consumed in a fire.

LXXXVII. The wise man sees life as the flickering light of a small lamp agitated by violent winds; (and so) he does nothing which should not be done.

LXXXVIII. Even a stupid woman who would ascend the funeral pyre to die understands that acting improperly is pointless. What about those capable of understanding?⁷⁰

LXXXIX. The one who does not strive for the sake of heavenly liberation, does not even work in this world for the welfare of his mother, he is truly like (a person) using a hatchet for cutting a sapling.⁷¹

XC. The wicked man, although he may live as long as a *kalpa*, is born to suffer intensely; indeed, the long life of brutes accumulate much evil.

XCI. Veneration service (*pūjā*) of the Blessed One arranged by the *yajvan*, *ācārya*, and so forth should, in whatever way, be protected like one's own mother with pious zeal.⁷²

XCII. Every year donations/fees (*dakṣiṇa*) are to be given to the *yājaka* and other (monastery officials); every day food is to be given to the Buddhist monks, along with clothing for those teaching the Dharma.⁷³

XCIII. When the property of the *saṅgha* becomes diminished, one who sells even the ornament adorning the head of the Protector for the sake of venerating the *saṅgha* will obtain a share of the merit.⁷⁴

⁶⁹ Unsure of translation. Probably continuing preceding stanza.

⁷⁰ Unsure of translation. cf. Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 210): "Même une femme stupide sur le point d'entrer dans le feu pour y mourir se dit que tous ces tourments ne lui serviront à rien ; que penseront alors ceux qui sont doués de discernement ?"

⁷¹ cf. the story of Sāḷha in the Aṅguttara Nikāya 4.196, see Bodhi (2012: 575) for a recent English translation.

⁷² The title *yajvan* refers to individuals performing oblations or other forms of sacrifice, and *ācārya* is a common title used for teachers or masters. The term *ācārya* can also refer specifically to certain monks with special duties. Also see the note on the *yājaka* in stanza LXVII.

⁷³ The *yājaka* is also mentioned earlier in stanza LXVII.

XCIV. Those placed in charge of the monastery should ensure its prosperity in this place, (and those in charge) should especially not violate (the monastery) by indulging in wickedness.

XCV. After reaching the abode of merit, the wicked will be purified through repentance; but he who resides in that place, having caused destruction, where will he go in order to become purified?

XCVI. Property of the Three Jewels---including among other things, slaves, property, and gardens---should not be bestowed upon relatives by *viṣayādyakṣa*, *dhānyeśa*, and other (officials).⁷⁵

XCVII. From outside the gate to as far as even inside (the gate), men guilty of an offence should not be struck with a whip, or even ill words.

XCVIII. This highly esteemed order is the path leading to Smṛti, wisdom, and so forth, just as the taste of the medicine leads to destruction of all diseases.

XCIX. Indeed, it has been spoken by some that this order of the king is merely another speech⁷⁶ to be grasped by the learned for the attainment of wealth in this world; but instead, it is the doctrine of omniscient to be grasped by the learned, the path of liberation and heaven.

C. Indeed, he who is wicked, even though he has understood this order (of the king), shall produce vile poison instead of nectar; but he who acts piously, even though he may transgress⁷⁷ this (order), shall produce the nectar of merit instead of poison.

⁷⁴ As noted by Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 210, n. 3), this stanza allows us to infer that the Buddha image installed inside the monastery would have been adorned with (a) precious stone(s)/gem(s).

⁷⁵ The title *viṣayādhakṣa* refers to the head of a district, land, or region, and *dhānyeśa* refers to a master of rice (*i.e.*, one responsible for rice yields, distribution, etc.). Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 211, n. 1) notes that the two titles are equivalent to *khloñ viṣaya* and *khloñ srū* in the Old Khmer inscriptions. These terms appear to correspond closely to similar titles in Indian epigraphy. For example, compare titles beginning with *viṣaya*^o, as well as titles using *dhānya*, in Sircar (1966: e.g., 467, 552).

⁷⁶ I choose to translate *aparavaktramātram* as 'merely another speech.' Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 211) translated the first verse as, "D'aucuns prétendent sans doute que cette parole n'est qu'un langage tardif en vue de la réalisation du bonheur terrestre," which I find a bit over literal (especially 'langage tardif' for *aparavaktra*) and awkward with regard to the overall meaning of the stanza. While *apara* can certainly mean 'late,' 'posterior,' 'later,' and so forth, it can also mean 'other,' or 'another,' and this makes more sense with *mātra* ('merely' or 'simply') to mean 'merely another *vaktra*.' Here *vaktra* (lit. 'organ of speech,' *i.e.* 'mouth') refers to the words/speech/order of the king, the subject noted in the second half of the stanza (*nṛpavākyam*) which is completely omitted in Cœdès' translation. The intended meaning of the stanza is to proclaim that merely following the order of the king (following the "letter of the law," so to speak) in order to acquire worldly success completely overlooks the fact that the instructions contained within the inscription, when grasped (*grāhyam*) properly, are of a greater soteriological benefit.

⁷⁷ Skt. *atītaḥ*, lit. 'he who has gone beyond, or neglected.'

CHAPTER 3 BUDDHIST THOUGHT IN THE VAT SITHOR INVOCATION

Triadic configurations are prominent in both the epigraphical and art historical record throughout the Angkorian period. The tenth-century sources document several new triadic configurations never before seen in early Cambodia. There is, for example, the arrival of Vajrapāṇi who appears for the first time during this period alongside figures like Prajñāpāramitā, the Buddha, and Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara). In epigraphy these triads are often the object of veneration in the opening panegyric (Skt. *maṅgala*) of an inscription, and sometimes images of these figures were ritually installed in sanctuaries in order to protect the surrounding land and people. Triads in the epigraphy, however, are not limited to configurations of powerful beings. In some cases, these triadic configurations glorify higher ontological realities such as the embodiments of the Buddha, or vocational pursuits such as the path of the bodhisattva.

This chapter demonstrates that a close examination of the triadic configurations present in the opening invocation of the Vat Sithor inscription sheds additional light on Buddhist traditions in tenth-century Cambodia. This section of Sanskrit inscriptions is known as the *maṅgala*, a prayer-like invocation at the beginning of an inscription whose presence is often considered aesthetically mandatory according to the rules of proper Sanskrit poetic composition.¹ Since the study of Cambodian epigraphy has primarily been focused on the extraction of pertinent historical information, *maṅgalas* often

¹ A *maṅgala* is quite simply anything auspicious and is expressed in a variety of ways in epigraphy. The term *maṅgala* can refer specifically to the auspicious word (or phrase) at the beginning, in the middle, and at the end of an inscription. The term may also refer to the invocatory verses at the beginning of an inscription. For more on the *maṅgala*, see Sircar (1966: 92, 95) and Salomon (1998: 67, 112). Throughout this chapter I will often use the following terms and phrases synonymously when referring to a *maṅgala*: invocation, opening invocation and opening panegyric.

receive minimal attention since they are perceived to be of little historical significance.² In other words, these sections do not provide useful dates, genealogies, information on the ascension of rulers, battles, constructions, and so forth. While it does, indeed, remain exceedingly difficult to ascertain historical details concerning the Buddhist traditions of the time based solely on the presentation of these triads found in opening invocations, a closer examination of these sections can reveal other kinds of information. The poets composing these *maṅgalas* were drawing upon a pool of sources in order to make their similes, metaphors, and doctrinal allusions. While the scant amount of information in an inscription often makes it impossible to pinpoint one specific source, it is certainly possible to locate, examine, and compare multiple sources that share similar concepts, narratives, and literary devices all in an attempt to better understand the full range of meanings being conveyed in these Sanskrit verses. Such an approach, in turn, provides additional insight into how various aspects of Buddhist traditions were being portrayed in tenth-century Cambodia.³ A hermeneutical approach, however, to what are often nothing more than short panegyrics preceding details on land grants, foundations, and so forth warrants caution. Due to the nature of the inscriptions one should not expect to uncover a fully articulated Buddhist phenomenology or a detailed breakdown of ritual procedures; nevertheless, the religious references found in the opening sections do tell us something, however sparse and vague, and thus they deserve serious attention.

² There are exceptions, such as Hendrik Kern's (1899) detailed examination of the *maṅgala* that references the concept of ultimate and conventional truth according to Buddhists in the inscription from Phnom Banteay Neang (K. 214).

³ See Sircar (1966), Salomon (1998), and Pollock (1998) for more on the strengths and weaknesses of epigraphy as a source of data.

What's in a Panegyric? The *Trikāya* and the Path of the Bodhisattva in the Vat Sithor Inscription

The Vat Sithor inscription is one of most important sources for understanding Buddhist traditions in tenth-century Cambodia, and having provided an entirely new English translation in the previous chapter it makes sense to begin by taking a closer look at the opening section of the inscription. The beginning section of the inscription consists of nine stanzas comprising eighteen lines of Sanskrit. Although this is just eighteen short lines of text, the opening invocation in the Vat Sithor inscription is one of the longest Buddhist invocations in the entire Cambodian epigraphical corpus.⁴ Additionally, no other inscription from this era, as a whole, contains more information pertaining to Buddhist traditions, per line, than the Vat Sithor inscription. Only the tenth-century Bat Cum inscriptions (K. 266–268) and the eleventh-century Sab Bāk inscription (K. 1158) come close.⁵ In short, it is the most extensive Buddhist document from early Cambodia currently known.

Despite devoting a large of amount of space to praising the Buddhist *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita, the official purpose of the Vat Sithor inscription is to record an order of Jayavarman V concerning the establishment of a Buddhist monastery, along with rules and regulations associated with the monastery and Buddhist community.⁶ The inscription opens with an invocation to what is known as the *trikāya*, or ‘three

⁴ Only the eleventh-century Sab Bāk inscription (K. 1158) has a longer opening Buddhist invocation. The Vat Sithor inscription, however, is a much larger composition with a large amount of Buddhist-related information contained outside of the invocatory verses. For the Sab Bāk inscription, see Prapandvidya (1990) and Estève (2009: 442–49).

⁵ The Bat Cum inscriptions will be discussed throughout this dissertation. The opening stanzas of the Bat Cum inscriptions are discussed at length in Appendix B. Although important, I will not be discussing the Sab Bāk inscription in any detail since I have limited my analysis to the tenth century.

⁶ Refer to the introduction of this dissertation for a detailed summary of the inscription and chapter two for a complete English translation. Appendix A contains a complete transliteration of the Sanskrit.

embodiments' of the Buddha, followed by praise for bodhisattvas on the path to awakening for the benefit of others. A detailed examination of the nine opening stanzas now follows.

Stanza I

1. *vande pi vyāpinaṃ vyaktaṃ svacchāśayajalāśaye /*
2. *bhrājiṣṇu[m] dharmakāyenduṃ vimuktaṃ skandharāhuṇā //*

I honor the Embodiment of Dharma (*dharmakāya*) which is like the moon, shining in the reservoir of the pure mind, (and) even though pervading all that is perceptible to the senses it is freed from the (five) aggregates just as (the moon is freed) from Rāhu.

Stanza I analysis and commentary. This opening stanza provides a nice analogy between the *dharmakāya* ('embodiment of Dharma') and the moon. In this context the Sanskrit word *jalāśaya* (lit. a container/receptacle for water) refers to a body of water such as a pond, lake, or reservoir. The stanza, therefore, is invoking a nighttime image of the moon being reflected in a body of water. This imagery, in turn, is likened to the moon-like *dharmakāya* which is similarly reflected in the pure receptacle or reservoir that is the mind (*svacchāśaya*, lit. a pure container/receptacle = mind). The choice of 'mind' instead of 'heart' for *āśaya* is based on the overall context of the inscription which is grounded in Yogācāra doctrines that have, like other Buddhist doctrines, a strong emphasis on the mind and its role for understanding, or seeing, reality as it really is (Skt. *yathābhūtarśana*). In the inscription, the *dharmakāya* should also be understood as synonymous with the pure mind (i.e., the awakened mind); which, in turn, is synonymous with enlightenment.

The second part of the stanza provides another analogy to describe the *dharmakāya*. This analogy is a bit more technical and assumes a deeper

understanding of the *dharmakāya*. In short, the verse is illustrating that just as the moon is (eventually) freed from Rāhu—a being held to be the cause of eclipses because he swallowed the sun and moon⁷—so too the *dharmakāya* is freed from conditioned world of beings which is characterized by the five *skandhas* or ‘aggregates,’ the psychophysical components that make up a sentient being according to Buddhists. Both the moon and *dharmakāya*, quite literally, are liberated (Skt. *vimukta*) from these sources. Although the *dharmakāya* pervades the conditioned realm perceptible to our senses (i.e., “even though pervading all that is perceptible to the senses”), it is simultaneously free from this conditioned realm (i.e., “it is freed from the (five) aggregates”); in other words, it is not bound to this conditioned realm since the cognitive basis for the conditioned realm are the five aggregates.⁸ So too, while the moon is reflected in the water it is not actually in, or part of, the water. To better understand and appreciate the stanza, however, a more thorough discussion of *dharmakāya* is now needed. A detailed discussion of the *dharmakāya* will also demonstrate just how important concepts stemming from Yogācāra forms of Buddhism were for the doctrinal and practical foundations of tenth-century forms of Buddhism in Cambodia.

Dharmakāya

The Buddhist orientation of the inscription is immediately made clear by this opening stanza which invokes the *dharmakāya*. The *dharmakāya* is one of three embodiments of the Buddha in what is known as the *trikāya* (‘three embodiments’) doctrine. The other two embodiments are the *sambhogakāya* (‘embodiment for

⁷ Refer to my commentary in chapter two for additional remarks on Rāhu.

⁸ A greater discussion and explanation of the cognitive basis (Skt. *āśraya*) and the role of aggregates will follow the discussion on the *dharmakāya*.

enjoyment') and the *nirmāṇakāya/nairmāṇika* ('embodiment in manifestations'), both of which are also invoked in stanzas two and three (discussed later).⁹

The Sanskrit term *kāya* has many connotations and is often translated as 'body' since the term may literally be used to refer to the physical body of a living being. The term *kāya* may also refer to a collection of aggregates, and, in certain Buddhist usages, the term may refer to a base or substratum, and later as the embodiment of ultimate knowledge.¹⁰ Again, of these usages, 'body' is probably the most common translation for *kāya* in secondary English sources; therefore, *dharmakāya* is frequently translated as 'Dharma body' or 'body of the Dharma.' However, following Makransky (1997: 56), I favor using 'embodiment' for *kāya* since the word 'body' or 'bodies' in English implies distinct and separate ontological realities, which is not the case in this context. In other words, the *trikāya* are not three separate things, but rather one ontological reality 'embodied' in three ways.

This connotation and understanding, however, was developed in a long history of formulations and concepts regarding the so-called bodies of a Buddha (Makransky, 1997). In other words, there was never a single doctrine pertaining to the bodies or embodiments of a Buddha, nor was *trikāya* always understood to consist of three such bodies or embodiments. The *trikāya* invoked in this inscription represents a later formulation directly connected with Yogācāra thought which reformulated earlier two-

⁹ For *sāmbhogakāya*, I prefer Makransky's (1997) explanatory translation, 'embodiment for [communal] enjoyment [of the Dharma].' This, however, makes for awkward reading and will be avoided in this chapter. For more comments, see my commentary in chapter two.

¹⁰ For a short, but informative, overview, see Makransky (1997: 76–9), as well as Williams (2010: 172–86).

kāya descriptions found in texts from the Pali canon and other textual sources such as the *Prajñāpāramitā* corpus of literature.¹¹

The earliest text to provide a clear conception and systematic explanation of the three *kāyas* according to Makransky (1997: 42) is found in the ‘Bodhi’ chapter of the *Mahāyānasūtrālaṅkāra* (*MSA*), verses 9.56–66.¹² He furthermore notes that the *MSA* also served as the basis for discussion of the three *kāya* in the *Mahāyānasamgraha* (*Msaṃ*), and these two texts, along with their commentaries, appear to constitute “a core Yogācāra literature that is closely related to the discussions of three *kāyas* that appear in numerous other texts” (*ibid.*). One such Yogācāra text cited by Makransky that was informed by the core material in the *MSA* and *Msaṃ* is the *Madhyāntavibhāga* (*MAV*).¹³ The *MSA* and *MAV* are often cited in connection with one another since they are traditionally recorded as being two of the five books that Maitreya imparted to Aśaṅga, who later wrote them down.¹⁴ The significance of singling out the *MAV* is that the Vat Sithor inscription explicitly refers to this particular core Yogācāra text by name in stanza twenty-eight, thus further supporting the Yogācāra doctrinal foundations of the inscription as well as providing a source for better understanding Buddhist concepts referred to directly and indirectly in this inscription.

¹¹ The topic concerning the development of the *trikāya* doctrine, along with how the term *dharmakāya* was understood in earlier texts, is actually much more complicated, but a detailed overview of its historical development cannot be provided here. See Harrison (1992) for an argument on how the *dharmakāya* was not always understood as a kind of cosmic ultimate.

¹² Also see Makransky (1997: 377, n. 11) for comments concerning parallel verses between the *MSA* and *Buddhabhūmisūtra*.

¹³ Regarding the *MAV* and its respective commentaries, refer to the primary sources listed in the references.

¹⁴ The other three books are the: *Abhisamayālaṅkāra* (‘Ornament to the Realizations’), *Dharmadharmatāvibhāga* (‘Analysis of Phenomena and Their True Nature’), and *Ratnagotravibhāga* (‘Analysis of the Lineage of the [Three] Jewels’).

He rekindled the lamp for the footpath of the Good Dharma— treatises¹⁵ like the *Madhyāntavibhāga* —which had been extinguished by the wind of Time.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXVIII)¹⁶

According to the later formulations in such texts, the *dharmakāya* is equivalent to the realization of thusness (Skt. *tathatā*); that is, the ultimate nature of things which is hidden from the view of unenlightened beings by their own mental obstructions.¹⁷ In short, the ultimate nature of things is the non-duality of all phenomena; in other words, an unenlightened being is unenlightened due to a false subject-object cognition. Buddhahood is the non-dual realization of this thusness, and Yogācāra texts such as the *Msaṃ* support a yogic path that cultivates an awareness that directly and inseparably realizes the non-existence of any subject-object duality by gradually removing mental obstructions hindering such an awareness. Hence, Buddhahood's essence is the realization of the nature of non-duality, the emptiness (Skt. *śūnyatā*) of all phenomena, and this essence is referred to in later Yogācāra sources as the *dharmakāya*, the embodiment of the Dharma (Makransky, 1997: 46–9). The Vat Sithor inscription, therefore, opens by praising the very essence of Buddhahood, and Buddhahood is the ultimate goal of those on the path of bodhisattvas.

The *MAV* referenced in stanza twenty-eight of the inscription offers another piece of information on the *dharmakāya* that may provide additional insight on how the

¹⁵ Or: teachings. I have decided to favor translating *śāstra* as 'treatises' given that the sub-commentator Sthiramati goes into great detail explaining why the text is, indeed, a treatise. cf. *MAV* I, Y. 5.10 and following.

¹⁶ The Sanskrit is as follows: *śāstram madhyavibhāgādyaṃ dīpaṃ saddharmmapaddhateḥ / kāladoṣāniladvastam bhūyo jvālayati sma yaḥ //*

¹⁷ Chapter 10 of the *Msaṃ* describes the *dharmakāya* as *tathatā*. Here I should also briefly note that one of the main concerns of the *MAV* is the problem of various obscurations that hinder awakening.

relationship between the aggregates and the *dharmakāya* highlighted in the inscription would have been understood. Sthiramati's (c. 470–550) sub-commentary in chapter four of the *MAV* (IV.3.2, Y. 191) describes the *dharmakāya* in the context of the highest attainable state along the path of the bodhisattva. He writes:

The attainment state refers to the Dharma Body of the Buddhas. It is the Dharma Body of the Buddhas since it (a) has the nature of the turning about of the basis (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛtti*), (b) has control over all dharmas and (c) is without a foundation – these are due to both the relinquishment of all obscuration and the accumulation of the 'seeds' of all dharmas that are without impurity and which act as counteragent to those [obscurations]. It is described as the attainment state because by means of this [body the bodhisattva] reaches the culminating point in his penetration of the dharmas.¹⁸

While an extensive treatment of these statements would remove us too far from the inscription, Sthiramati's characterization of the *dharmakāya* as 'turning about of the basis' (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛtti*) is relevant to: (1) understanding more fully the connection between the *dharmakāya*, the aggregates, and other such obscurations, (2) understanding an additional reason as to why later emerging tantric forms of Buddhism evident in tenth-century Cambodia could operate primarily within a Yogācāra doctrinal framework, and (3) understanding more concretely what the actual goal is of the Buddhist practitioner on the path of the bodhisattva. The *āśrayaparāvṛtti* is also connected with the statements made earlier concerning how obscurations need to be counteracted. The next section deals with the concept of *āśrayaparāvṛtti* in detail.

The aggregates and *āśraya-parāvṛtti*

With a brief overview of the *dharmakāya* the allusion to the aggregates in the opening stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription will now be addressed. Analyzing this basic

¹⁸ trans. Stanley (1988: 257). The boldface print is in the original and refers to Vasubhandhu's *bhāṣya*.

Buddhist technical term in the context of the stanza will once again demonstrate how certain Yogācāra doctrinal foundations informed the author(s) of the inscription by suggesting that there was a familiarity with systems of transformation (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛtti*), a concept that received extensive and varied development in Yogācāra circles.

As previously noted, the opening stanza praises the very essence of Buddhahood as represented by the *dharmakāya*, and Buddhahood is the ultimate goal of those on the path of bodhisattvas. The stanza also indicates that the *dharmakāya*, while pervading the realm of senses (i.e., the conditioned realm), is also freed or liberated (Skt. *vimukta*) from the aggregates. In other words, while the very essence of Buddhahood is unconditioned it also simultaneously pervades the conditioned realm characterized by the aggregates, a seemingly paradoxical statement that will now be addressed.¹⁹

In Buddhism, ignorance and attachment provide the epistemological conditions for failing to realize that a person, and reality overall, is characterized by: (1) impermanence, (2) no-self, or selflessness, and (3) suffering. For Buddhists then, the psychophysical aggregates that are said to make up a sentient being aid in deconstructing what a person actually is by illustrating the impermanent, selfless, and suffering nature of what is nominally referred to as a ‘person.’ According to dualistic

¹⁹ Also concerning this seemingly paradoxical claim, I direct the reader to the Yogācāra *Msaṃ* cited previously. In describing one of the five characteristics of the *dharmakāya*, the author states that the *dharmakāya* has the characteristic of non-duality being both conditioned and unconditioned (Skt. *saṃkṛtāsaṃskṛtādvayalakṣaṇa*), and, among other things, has the sovereignty (Skt. *vibhūtva*) to manifest in the conditioned realm. Lamotte (1973 : 271) provides a full translation of *Msaṃ* X.3.3.b: “Il a pour caractère la non-dualité de conditionné et d'inconditionné (*saṃkṛtāsaṃskṛtādvayalakṣaṇa*) : [en d'autres termes, il n'est ni conditionné ni inconditionné], car [d'une part] il n'est pas façonné (*abhisamkṛta*) par l'acte (*karma*) ou la passion (*kleśa*), et [d'autre part] il a le pouvoir souverain (*vibhūtva*) de se manifester (*pradarśana*) sous l'aspect (*ābhāsa*) des conditionnés (*saṃskṛta*).

pre-Mahāyāna conceptions of *saṃsāra* ('the cycle of death and rebirth') and *nirvāṇa*, the eventual realization of the impermanent, selfless, and suffering nature of these aggregates results in a cessation of ignorance and attachment, and ultimately the attainment of an unconditioned state of *nirvāṇa* that stands apart from the conditioned realm of living beings (*nirupadhiśeṣanirvāṇa*).²⁰ As the aggregates are conditioned phenomena (*saṃskāra*), the unconditioned state of *nirvāṇa*, according to Theravāda traditions, is one totally devoid of the aggregates.

When, however, the concept of *śūnyatā* ('emptiness') was taken to its logical extreme in sources like the *Prajñāpāramitā* body of literature, absolutely everything, even the fundamental constituents of reality (*dharmas*) enumerated at length in Abhidharma texts, are taken to be empty of any intrinsic nature.²¹ As famously outlined by Nāgārjuna in the *Madhyamakakārikā*, if all things are without their own intrinsic nature, or own-existence (*svabhāva*), then there is no ontological difference between *saṃsāra* and *nirvāṇa*. In other words, the supposed duality of *saṃsāra* and *nirvāṇa* could not be maintained since they were both, like all things, empty of an intrinsic nature and do not exist autonomously.²²

²⁰ Makransky (1997: 323), Williams (2000: 47–9), Gethin (1998: 74–6).

²¹ As Williams (2000: 134) notes, the terms 'empty' (*śūnya*) and 'emptiness' (*śūnyatā*) had been used in Buddhist traditions from the very beginning; therefore, the terminology was not something invented in later Mahāyāna circles. For example, the terms were used in reference to the five psychophysical aggregates (*skandhas*) empty of Self or anything pertaining to a Self.

²² "There is nothing whatsoever differentiating *saṃsāra* [the round of rebirth] from *nirvāṇa*. There is nothing whatsoever differentiating *nirvāṇa* from *saṃsāra*. The limit of *nirvāṇa* is the limit of *saṃsāra*. Between the two there is not the slightest bit of difference." *Madhyamakakārikā* 25: 19–20. Trans. Williams (2010: 76; refer to pages 65–79 for a more in-depth discussion of emptiness).

Understanding this shift in Buddhist thought aids in deciphering how the aggregates, and their relation to the *dharmakāya*, are to be understood in the opening stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription. In the earlier model mentioned above, the defiled psychophysical structure of the aggregates is ultimately abandoned in that they cease to be in the unconditioned state of *nirvāṇa* that stands apart from the conditioned realm of beings who are immersed in the cyclic state of *samsāra*. Whereas in later non-dualistic models, the bodhisattva rejects the supposed lesser goal (i.e., *nirvāṇa*) of an arhat ('worthy one') by opting instead to remain on the more difficult path leading to the attainment of full Buddhahood, a strenuous practice during which the bodhisattva will continue to compassionately aid the suffering of sentient beings.²³ In this latter model, the aggregates are never abandoned since they are still needed by the bodhisattva operating in the conditioned realm (i.e., 'the realm pervaded by the senses' according to the Vat Sithor inscription).²⁴

Instead, the aggregates are transformed or purified. More literally, they are overturned or turned around. In other words, the aggregates, according to some Yogacāra models of transformation, are the foundational cognitive basis (Skt. *āśraya*) for perpetuating a false subject-object dichotomy that ultimately obstructs

²³ Note here that the bodhisattvas are *not* postponing Buddhahood; rather, the bodhisattvas are rejecting the lesser achievements of the arhat and/or pratyekabuddha. Here I am purposely glossing over the complicated and debated topic concerning whether or not a bodhisattva actually 'opts out' of or 'postpones' *nirvāṇa* out compassion for sentient beings. I do so in order to avoid going on a tangent that would divert too much attention from the inscription itself. See Williams (2010: 58–62) for an updated overview on the issue with reference to important studies and sources. The Vat Sithor inscription is influenced by the position of a non-abiding *nirvāṇa* in which buddhas (as *dharmakāya*) remain active in the world.

²⁴ Also cf. the comments of Davidson (1985: 191). Additionally, Sthiramati explains this same position in his sub-commentary in chapter four of the *MAV* (see *MAV* IV.12; Y. 187; for an English translation, see Stanley (1988: 251–52).

enlightenment; therefore, the aggregates need to be transformed or overturned (Skt. *parāvṛtti*) via yogic practices and discipline in order to fully attain direct knowledge of the non-duality of all phenomena. On this subject, Lusthaus (2003: 537) writes:

Yogācārins describe enlightenment as resulting from Overturning the Cognitive Basis (*āśraya-parāvṛtti*), i.e., overturning the conceptual projections and imaginings which act as the base of our cognitive actions. This overturning transforms the basic mode of cognition from consciousness (*vi-jñāna*, discernment) into *jñāna* (direct knowing). Direct knowing was defined as non-conceptual (*nirvikalpa-jñāna*), i.e., devoid of interpretive overlay.

When the opening stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription claims that the *dharmakāya* is freed or liberated from the aggregates it is alluding to the ontological position that the *dharmakāya* (which is synonymous with the pure mind) is not obstructed by the false subject-object cognitive basis that the aggregates represent when they are understood from a position of ignorance. The *jñāna*, or direct knowledge, of the *dharmakāya* is non-conceptual; or, to use Lusthaus' wording, it is "devoid of interpretive overlay."

As noted by Makransky (1997: 63), in classical Yogācāra texts the concept *āśrayaparāvṛtti* or *āśrayaparivṛtti*—variously translated as 'overturning the basis,' 'overturning the cognitive basis,' 'transforming the basis,' 'fundamental transformation,' 'revolution of the support,' and so on—in classical Yogācāra texts "is a model of full enlightenment in which the basis of ordinary existence is transformed into the enlightenment of a Buddha through a process of yogic realization." It is worth continuing at length with Makransky.

This model puts its focus on enlightenment as the result of a transformative yogic process, the process through which the yogi's total being in its impure state is transformed into the pure state of Buddhahood. The impure state is the "basis," *āśraya*. This is the psychophysical organism, the mental and physical composite that comprises a sentient being prior to enlightenment. Yogācāra literature contains many different models for the basis (*āśraya*), some inherited from early Buddhism (the *skandhas*, *dhātus*, *āyatanas*), and

some that are Mahāyāna or specifically Yogācāra concepts (*samalā-tathatā*, *alaya-vijñāna*, *saṃkleśa-bhāga paratantra-svabhāva*). Through the practice of the Mahāyāna path, the basis is utterly transformed (*parāvṛtti/parivṛtti*) into one of the Mahāyāna models of enlightenment: the purified dharma realm (*dharmadhātu-viśuddha*), the undefiled realm (*anāsrava-dhātu*), purified thusness (*tathatā-viśuddha*), nonconceptual gnosis (*nirvikalpa-jñāna*), embodiment of dharma (*dharmakāya*), the perfect nature (*pariniṣpanna*). At the stage of literature at which the three *kayas* appear, all such models are considered equivalent to each other (*dharmadhātu-viśuddha = anāsrava-dhātu = tathatā-viśuddhi = dharmakāya*).²⁵

As Makransky makes clear, there were (and are) many models of transformation, and the aggregates as a model for the cognitive basis represent only one among many existing models. The Vat Sithor inscription may be alluding to one such model, although this cannot be determined with certainty due to the circumstantial nature of the evidence. Furthermore, such an observation does not rule out the likely possibility that Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia may have been familiar with multiple models of transformation. The work of Ronald Davidson (1985) remains the most extensive examination on the history of these models in English to date. Davidson (1985: 189–90) notes that the *Msaṃ* was the first to apply fundamental transformation (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛtti*) to the aggregates. Again, it is important to recall that the *MAV* which is directly cited in the Vat Sithor inscription was influenced by concepts in the *Msaṃ*. Even more relevant is the fact that with the advent of the aggregates as the basis (Skt. *āśraya*) additional terms were needed to explain the process of this transformation, the primary term being *dharmakāya*.

In the case of *āśrayaparivṛtti*, the six senses was not to be the final psycho-physical model of the fundament. This position of honor was to be held by

²⁵ Here it might also be noteworthy to indicate that one of the five characteristics of the *dharmakāya* according to the *Msaṃ* is that it is characterized by the transformation of the basis (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛttīlakṣaṇa*) and freed (Skt. *vi-√muc*) from all obstacles (*Msaṃ* X.3; Lamotte, 1973: 268).

the five aggregates [*i.e.*, the *skandhas*], certainly one of the most durable and influential of the Buddhist models of reality. It was not, however, until the advent of the *MSam* that fundamental transformation was applied to the five aggregates, and then it required the assistance of multiple other terms, the primary one being the *dharmakāya*, the absolute body of the Buddha (Davidson, 1985: 189–90).

Specifically, the *Msaṃ* is concerned with what sovereignties (Skt. *vibhutva*) are attained by the *dharmakāya* via the transformation (Skt. *parāvṛtti*) of each one of the five aggregates.²⁶ So, for example, with the transformation of the form *skandha* (Skt. *rūpaskandhaparāvṛtti*) the *dharmakāya* attains sovereignty, or mastery, (Skt. *vibhutva*) over manifesting various Buddha fields (Skt. *buddhakṣetrasaṃdarśana*) in order to assist various beings.

As previously noted, the *dharmakāya* is also equated specifically with *āśrayaparāvṛtti* in chapter four of the *MAV*, the very same text mentioned in stanza twenty-eight of the Vat Sithor inscription. The equivalence between these two concepts is asserted because the *dharmakāya* is the pure basis devoid of obscurations. It is not some pre-overtured impure basis, like a person perpetuating a false subject-object view of phenomenon because of an ignorant understanding of the aggregates.²⁷ Thus, *dharmakāya/āśrayaparāvṛtti* is equivalent with enlightenment, the highest attainable

²⁶ cf. *Msaṃ* X.5. Again, Davidson also briefly discusses this section of *Msaṃ* as noted above and in chapter 3 of his work.

²⁷ Sthiramati's commentary in *MAV* IV.3, Y. 167–68 expounds on the uneasiness/disquiet (Skt. *dauṣṭhulya*, a term which Sthiramati also equates with *duḥsthitatā*) brought about via a contemplation of the body, and by obvious extension the aggregates. While a necessary stage in the meditative development of the Buddhist practitioner, the uneasiness is brought about because of how the body is initially perceived by the ignorant, and how one is being taught to understand it as it really is in reality (*i.e.*, a source of suffering and nothing more than impermanent 'heap'). Ultimately, however, the aggregates, when properly understood, act as a counteragent to the erroneous view of a permanent self. This is also detailed in the *MAV*; cf. *MAV* III.10, Y. 142–43. With this in mind, it may be of related interest to draw attention to stanza LXXXV of the Vat Sithor inscription which compares the human body to a latrine full of impurities.

state of a bodhisattva. This last statement is supported by Sthiramati's own sub-commentary in chapter two of the *MAV* (II.3, Y. 21–22). This section of the text is concerned with obscurations (obscurations, however, that are not limited to the aggregates) that affect one on the path of the bodhisattva.

The turning about of the basis is [equivalent to] enlightenment which has thusness, devoid of stain, for its basis.²⁸

Delving even further into the complexities of this subject is unnecessary and risks losing sight of the inscription's opening stanza. Before summarizing the main points learned from this stanza, however, it should be noted that Yogācāra models of transformation continued to be influential in later tantric forms of Buddhism. The importance of this observation will become relevant later when evidence for newly emerging strains of tantric forms of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia is discussed. For now a few brief comments will suffice.

In discussing the importance of the ritualization of the metaphor of the overlord in tantric forms of Buddhism, Davidson (2002: 164) writes:

Thus, for the monks—and I would argue, for all Buddhists—the fundamental reason they could engage the world in this way is that they believed in the transformation of personality. This ideal, called “fundamental transformation” (*āśrayaparivṛtti*) in Yogācāra nomenclature, was expressed philosophically and doctrinally long before the advent of the esoteric system. However, with the accelerated engagement of monks in the ideology of the feudal universe came an equivalent acceleration of the employment of this or similar terminology in meditative ritual. Whereas a total of perhaps two dozen important statements on the idea exist in Yogācāra and related literature, I have not been able to count the number of esoteric scriptures and commentaries that employ the notion—certainly many times the Yogācāra total.

²⁸ trans. Stanley (1988: 109–10). Skt. *sthitikāraṇaṃ bodhau / āśrayaparāvṛttir bodhiḥ / āśrayo nirmalatathatā /*

One could turn to Ratnākaraśānti's (c. late 10th–11th century) commentary on the *Khasama Tantra* in order to support Davidson's observation. In this commentary Ratnākaraśānti devotes an entire discussion to the concept of *āśrayaparāvṛtti*, along with its connection to the embodiments of the Buddha and how these concepts synthesize with tantric thought and practices. He writes:

Now, the Blessed Vajradhara [attains] the enlightenment of all Buddhas. And that (enlightenment) is characterized by the Overturning of the Basis (*āśrayaparāvṛtti*). The body is the Basis. That (body) is threefold.²⁹

The threefold body that Ratnākaraśānti goes on to discuss in the context of *āśrayaparāvṛtti* is of course the *trikāya*: the *dharmakāya*, *sāmbhogakāya*, and the *nirmāṇakāya*. The threefold body is the basis, in the context of the *Khasama Tantra*, only once it is devoid, or purified, of all obscurations. According to the *Khasama Tantra*, such obscurations included the psychophysical afflictions (Skt. *kleśa*) and other latent difficulties (Skt. *dauṣṭhulya*). Likewise, the goal of the practitioner is to attain enlightenment via a practice of purificatory transformation of the body and mind obscured by afflictions. Like many tantric practitioners, Ratnākaraśānti was heavily influenced by Yogācāra systems of thought. Even the passage from Ratnākaraśānti's commentary, as noted by Giuseppe Tucci (1954: 766), can be compared with the same excerpt of Sthiramati's sub-commentary on the *MAV* which was noted previously for claiming that the *dharmakāya* is equivalent to *āśrayaparāvṛtti*.

Before moving on a summary of what has been gleaned from an examination of the first stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription may be worthwhile.

²⁹ The translation is my own. Skt. *iha vajradhara bhagavān sarvabuddhānāṃ bodhiḥ / sā cāśrayaparāvṛttilakṣaṇā āśrayaḥ śarīram sa teṣāṃ trividhaḥ /*. The Sanskrit is taken from Tucci (1954: 766) who edited this commentary of Ratnākaraśānti.

First, the inscription invokes the first embodiment of Buddhist *trikāya*, the *dharmakāya*. According to the inscription, the *dharmakāya* is synonymous with the pure mind of an awakened one, and this pure mind is free of obscurations. A significant point to note is that the first full expression of the *trikāya* is found in Yogācāra texts. Further justification for singling out Yogācāra influence is supported by references in the Vat Sithor inscription to both Yogācāra doctrinal concepts (e.g., *cittamātra* in stanzas VIII and XXVII) and a core Yogācāra text (e.g., the *Madhyāntavibhāga* in stanza XXVIII).

Second, although circumstantial, the inscription appears to assume that the reader is familiar with systems of transformation (Skt. *āśrayaparāvṛtti*). For example, the doctrinal assumption maintains that the pure mind (i.e., enlightenment) is synonymous with the *dharmakāya*. According to commentary on Yogācāra texts like the *MAV* (again, a text directly cited in the inscription), the *dharmakāya* is also equivalent to *āśrayaparāvṛtti*, or ‘over turning the basis’ / ‘fundamental transformation.’ While the *dharmakāya* is luminous and devoid of defilements, the implication assumed by the stanza is that all practitioners on the path of the bodhisattva are hindered in their attainment of enlightenment by an erroneous view of psychophysical aggregates. Specifically, ignorance concerning the nature of the aggregates creates a false view of individuality, or self. The overturning of this false view of the aggregates is, therefore, also synonymous with enlightenment (i.e., “the pure mind”). Such systems of transformation again point to Yogācāra doctrinal foundations that would, in turn, be easily incorporated into later tantric forms of Buddhism.

Stanza II–III

3. *namadhvaṃ dharmmakāyārkkasāmbhogatanumaṇḍalam /*
4. *nānānirmāṇadhāmāḍhyaṃ sādhyam siddhyai maharṣibhiḥ //*

5. *kalpadrumam ivākalpalokābhyarthitadāyinam /*
 6. *dr̥śyaṃ sukṛtinām evadehan nairmmāṇikan name //*

Bow to the *maṇḍala* of the Embodiment for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma),³⁰ the light of the Embodiment of Dharma; (it is) filled with the power³¹ of various manifestations (*nirmāṇa*) to be mastered by great sages for the attainment of perfection (*siddha*).

I bow to the Embodiment of Manifestation of the Virtuous Ones, which is pleasing³² (and) grant the wishes of (those in) the world just like a wish fulfilling tree.

Stanza II–III analysis and commentary. The next two stanzas of the inscription continue the opening invocation by praising the other two embodiments of the *trikāya*: the *sāmbhogakāya* and the *nirmāṇakāya*. Before discussing the details of the stanzas, a few brief remarks about the nature of the *sāmbhogakāya* and the *nirmāṇakāya* are in order.

To better understand the role of the other two embodiments of the *trikāya*, reference may be made to the six Yogācāra categories used to describe Buddhahood: (1) its essence, its own real nature (*svabhāva*), (2) its cause (*hetu*), (3) its result (*phala*),

³⁰ *sāmbhogatanu*—Embodiment(s) for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma)—is equivalent to *sāmbhogakāya*. This term is the same term that is normally just translated as Enjoyment Body, or Embodiment of Enjoyment. I prefer Makransky’s (1997) translation which contains additional implicit meanings that highlight that this embodiment appears for groups of advance bodhisattvas desiring advance instruction in the Dharma.

³¹ Or: abode/domain. In addition to meaning power, glory, strength, splendor, and so forth, the Sanskrit word *dhāman* may refer to a dwelling-place, home, abode, domain, or even members of a family. I think both connotations are implied since they both are describing aspects of a ritual *maṇḍala*. This observation will be returned to later in the chapter.

³² Or: visible. I have opted to translate the Sanskrit word *dr̥śya* as pleasing; that is, something worth looking at, beautiful. However, it may also quite simply mean ‘that which is visible.’ This, too, is perfectly valid and would fit nicely since it would be in line with the nature of the *nirmāṇakāya* described in Yogācāra texts. In other words, as will be noted below, unlike the *dharmakāya* the *nirmāṇakāya* is visible when it manifests in various forms to aid and guide sentient beings. It may be helpful to remember that the *nirmāṇakāya* is a non-abiding aspect of Buddhahood that operates within the conditioned realm of beings; hence, it is visible.

(4) its activity (*karma*), (5) its endowment (*yoga*), and (6) its functional modes (*vr̥tti*).³³

The embodiments of the Buddha are described under the category of functional modes (*vr̥tti*) of Buddhahood. The *MSA bhāṣya* on 21.60–61 states:

Here Buddha's characteristics are explained through six topics: essence, cause, result, activity, endowment, and functional modes. Purified thusness (*viśuddhā tathatā*) is the ultimate that is accomplished (*niṣpannaḥ paramārthaḥ*). And it is the very essence (*svabhāva*) of the Buddhas. Their cause (*hetu*) is their issuance from all the bodhisattva stages. Their result (*phala*) is the attainment of preeminence among all beings. Their activity (*karma*) is the liberating of all beings. Their endowment (*yoga*) is [their] possession of inexhaustible, incomparable qualities. Their mode of function (*vr̥tti*) is threefold: showing [themselves] in various world realms through embodiment in created forms (*nirmāṇakāya*), showing [themselves] among the assemblies through embodiment in communal enjoyment (*sāmbhogikakāya*), and being utterly invisible with respect to their embodiment of dharma (*dharmakāya*).³⁴

Therefore, the *trikāya* is the threefold function of Buddhahood. The *nirmāṇakāya* are the embodiment of created forms manifested in order to teach a limitless amount of beings the Dharma, or the teachings of the Buddha. The *sāmbhogakāya*, embodiment for communal enjoyment of the dharma, proclaim and teach the Dharma to assemblies of advanced bodhisattvas, often via advanced meditational and visualization techniques. The *dharmakāya* is its own realization of thusness and identical to the essence of Buddhahood.³⁵ Regarding the *trikāya* systemization and its relation to the six categories above, it is again worth quoting Makransky (1997: 55) at length:

³³ See Makransky (1997: 50–1). The sixfold analysis occurs in *MSA* and *bhāṣya* 9.56–59. See Makransky (1997: 380, n. 29) for additional comments.

³⁴ Trans. Makransky (1997: 50–1). Refer to the *MSA* beginning with 9.59 for other relevant descriptive passages concerning the *trikāya*. For a full English translation of the *MSA*, along with the *bhāṣya*, see Thurman (2004) and Limaye (1992).

³⁵ Asvabhāva's commentary on *MSA* 21.60–21.61 proclaims that enlightenment as the embodiment of dharma (*dharmakāya*), in its very essence (*svabhāva*), is purified thusness. Also see Makransky (1997: 53).

The fact that the MSA introduces its three-*kāya* model within this final topic of the Yogācāra sixfold analysis has great significance. It reveals the three-*kāya* model's systematic purpose: to relate the nature of Buddhahood (topic 1: essence, *svabhāva*) to its functions (topic 6: functions, *vytti*). The three-*kāya* model delineates how the very essence of Buddhahood (nondual gnosis of thusness) can be understood to function for itself and for others by the ways in which it “embodies” its realization. Buddhahood embodies its realization:

1. In its own knowledge of the thusness of all phenomena, which is its own innermost essence (*svābhāvika*)
2. In the sharing of that knowledge with its closet communities of disciples (great bodhisattvas) in communal enjoyment (*sāmbhogika*)
3. In its communication of that knowledge to limitless beings through diverse manifestations (*nairmāṇika*)

The same functions of the *sāmbhogakāya* and *nirmāṇakāya*, according to the MSA, are also reflected in Vasubandhu's commentary and Sthiramati's sub-commentary on the MAV, the same Yogācāra text cited directly in stanza twenty-eight of the Vat Sithor inscription. Sthiramati (MAV IV.3.2, Y. 191), for example, writes:

(h) The state of benefit refers to the Enjoyment body. The Essential Nature [Body] is the body established in which he becomes perfectly enlightened. The Enjoyment Body is that body on account of which one experiences the Recitation of the Dharma in the circle of assembly together with the bodhisattvas who have reached their final end. **(i) The state of the performance of duty refers to the Transformation Body.** The Transformation Body is that which: (a) has the Essential Nature Body for a basis, (b) takes heed of the aspirations of sentient beings and (c) has infinite divisions in regard to the engagement in undertakings for the sake of those to be trained.³⁶

The third stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription which praises the *nirmāṇakāya* is a direct reflection of the function of the *nirmāṇakāya* described in the above two Yogācāra

³⁶ trans. Stanley (1988: 258). The boldface print is in the original and refers to Vasubandhu's *bhāṣya*. Note, Stanley's translation uses the common English phrase 'Transformation Body' to refer to the *nirmāṇakāya*.

texts. When the inscription states that the *nirmāṇakāya* “are pleasing³⁷ (and) grant the wishes of (those in) the world just like a wish fulfilling tree,” it is describing how these limitless manifestations of a Buddha aid unenlightened sentient beings. Of course the inscription does this by employing the poetic aesthetic of a Sanskrit *maṅḍala*. The second stanza concerning the *sāmbhogakāya*, however, deserves a bit more explanation.

In the second stanza of the inscription the initial image invoked is the *maṅḍala* of the *sāmbhogatanu* (a term synonymous with *sāmbhogakāya*). The term *maṅḍala* may refer to a circle, disk, sun, halo, or some kind of circular object. In the context the inscription the term *maṅḍala* is invoking multiple images and meanings. Symbolically, the word *maṅḍala* is referring to the halo-like rays encircling the sun. A more specific English translation might then be corona, the glowing extended outer atmosphere of the sun. The sun referred to is of course the *dharmakāya*, or embodiment of the Dharma.

There is a reason, however, for leaving *maṅḍala* untranslated. While a term like corona may capture the imagery for the first half of the stanza, it does not adequately capture the meditative ritual aspect being alluded to in the second portion of the stanza. The word *maṅḍala* may also refer to a constructed circular diagram delineating sacred space which may represent the abode of various divinities. A main divinity or Buddha is often depicted at the center of such diagrams encircled by a host of accompanying Buddhas, bodhisattvas, and other kinds of divinities. A *maṅḍala* may also represent a depiction of the universe to be perceived or understood by the religious practitioner through meditative practice—a microcosm of the universe, if you will. These diagrams

³⁷ Again, or ‘visible.’

may also be used in ritual consecration ceremonies (Skt. *abhiṣeka*) for the purpose of various kinds of initiation. Additionally, the *maṇḍala* may be used to physically or mentally evoke a divinity such as a Buddha or a bodhisattva via complex visualization and meditative practices on the part of the practitioner.

These alternative meanings for *maṇḍala* may also be referred to in the second half of the second stanza. In other words, the *maṇḍala* of the *sāmbhogakāya* may also be referring to a circular diagram delineating sacred space which is filled or richly adorned with (Skt. *āḍhya*) the power or abode (Skt. *dhāman*) of various manifestations (Skt. *nānānirmāṇa*; i.e., various manifested beings). This power/abode of beings (Skt. *dhāman*)³⁸ is something to be mastered (Skt. *sādhya*) by sages if they intend to attain perfection (Skt. *siddha*).

The Sanskrit gerundive *sādhya*, here translated as ‘mastered,’ may also be translated as summoned, as in conjured. This alternative and related meaning is also implied in the context of a ritual *maṇḍala*. In other words, the word *sādhya* refers to correctly evoking the divinities of the *maṇḍala*. It is perhaps no accident that the Sanskrit word being used here is also related to the word *sādhana*, a type of text often used to guide a practitioner in the use of *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and various meditative and ritual techniques. Both words derived from the Sanskrit root $\sqrt{sādh}$ which, in general, means to be straight, as in go straight to a goal. In other words, it means to be successful, to accomplish something, to attain a goal, and so on. The root \sqrt{sidh} , from

³⁸ Again, note how in this context one meaning implies the other. For example, the abode (*dhāman*) of manifested beings is, in fact, a source of power (also *dhāman*) to be tapped into by the Buddhist practitioner via meditative visualization practices.

which the word *siddha* ('accomplished,' 'perfected') comes from, is also a weak form of the root $\sqrt{sādh}$, something also used in the same stanza.

The inscription's reference to a *maṇḍala* of the *sāmbhogakāya*, and how it is to be harnessed by sages for the attainment of perfection, may further demonstrate that elements of tantric Buddhism were being incorporated into existing forms of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia. As noted previously, Yogācāra forms of Buddhism with their models of transformation were adopted by later tantric forms of Buddhism that applied ritual significance to the process of transformation. Of course a reference alluding to the ritual use of a *maṇḍala* alone is not enough to justify this claim.

Additional support, however, is found elsewhere in the Vat Sitor inscription's reference to the tantric text (or its commentary) known as the *Sarvatathāgatatattvasaṃgraha* (*STTS*) in stanza twenty-nine of the inscription. The inscription also acknowledges both esoteric and exoteric practices in stanza forty-two, and the employment of heart-syllables, *mantras*, *mudras*, *vidyās*, the *vajra*, and the *ghaṇṭā* ('ritual bell') in stanza sixty-nine. The ritual implements known as the *vajra* and the *ghaṇṭā* are particularly iconic within tantric Buddhist traditions. The reference to Ekādaśamukha—a tantric manifestation of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara—in the tenth-century Prasat Chikreng inscription (K. 168) further supports the claim for a tantric presence in tenth-century Cambodia, although it does not necessarily demonstrate evidence of the same strain of tantric Buddhism being alluded to in the Vat Sitor inscription. While Yogācāra doctrine and phenomenology likely continued to provide the foundation for tenth-century Cambodian forms of Buddhism—an observation based on the frequent allusions to Yogācāra concepts in the epigraphical record—the introduction of tantric practices and

new texts cannot be denied when one notes the tantric references in the Vat Sithor and other inscriptions.

However, gleaned more information on the specific kind of tantric Buddhism, or pinpointing the source of influence for the reference in stanza two, is exceedingly difficult. How developed such tantric traditions introducing these new interpretations and practices were also cannot be determined with absolute certainty, nor can it be determined how comparable these newly arriving tantric practices were with those outside of Cambodia. Simply turning to the *STTS*, the tantric text thought to be referenced in stanza twenty-nine of the inscription, is not so straightforward since many of the concepts emphasized in this text are not expressed, at least directly, in the tenth-century epigraphical record. For example, there appears to be no direct reference to a Five-Buddha family system (a prevalent concept in the *STTS*) until the eleventh century (e.g., the Sab Bāk inscription, K. 1158).

With that said, however, the term *maṇḍala* is also used to simply denote a 'circle' of one or more *sāmbhogakāyas*. In other words, term in the second stanza also simultaneously refers to a gathered *assembly* of the Embodiment(s) for (Communal) Enjoyment.' This interpretation relates directly back to the primary meaning of the *sāmbhogakāya* in both Yogācāra and tantric circles as embodiments manifested in order to relay and teach the Dharma among advanced bodhisattvas who have attained the advanced meditative ability to perceive such enjoyable embodiments. Again, less advanced Buddhist practitioners do not have the ability to perceive the *sāmbhogakāyas*, and must instead rely upon the assistance of the *nirmāṇakāya*. The tantric *STTS* believed to be cited in stanza twenty-nine of the inscription only includes one reference

to the *sāmbhogakāya*. Like the references to the *sāmbhogakāya* in the previous cited Yogācāra texts, the passage in the *STTS* appears in the context of manifesting embodiments of Buddhas (lit. Tathāgatas, ‘Thus Gone Ones’) appearing before an aspiring bodhisattva for the purpose of advance instruction in the Dharma.

At that time All the Tathāgatas filled this Buddha-world just like sesame [seeds packed closely together in a sesame pod]. Then All the Tathāgatas gathered as if in a cloud and betook themselves to where the Bodhisattva and Mahāsattva Sarvārthasiddhi (Accomplishment of All Objectives) was seated at the place of enlightenment (*bodhimaṇḍa*). Manifesting the body of enjoyment (*sāmbhoga-kāya*), they spoke all together as follows: “Good sir, how will you, who endure ascetic practices without knowing the truth of All the Tathāgatas, realize unsurpassed perfect enlightenment?”

Therefore the Bodhisattva and Mahāsattva Sarvārthasiddhi, having been aroused by All the Tathāgatas, arose from the *āsphānaka-samādhi*,³⁹ made obeisance to All the Tathāgatas, and said, “World-honored Tathāgatas, please instruct me! How should I practice? What is the truth?”⁴⁰

Understanding the *sāmbhogakāya* in this manner is reinforced by the Vat Sithor inscription itself later in stanza five.

I bow to the Dharma which is grasped through meditation and proclaimed by the Embodiment for (Communal) Enjoyment (of the Dharma) conforming to the respective insight befitting their attained stage.

³⁹ For more on this particular *samādhi* (a type of meditative technique involving one-pointed concentration of the mind), see Giebel, *Two Esoteric Sutras*, n. 8 pp. 103–04.

⁴⁰ trans. Giebel (2001: 23). Giebel’s translation is of the Chinese translation of the *STTS* made by Amoghavajra (705–774) completed in c. 754 (T. 18.865), which is only a portion of the text.

The corresponding Sanskrit section from the manuscripts edited by Chandra (1981) is as follows:

bhagavān mahābodhicittaḥ samantabhadro mahābodhisattvaḥ sarvatathāgatahṛdayeṣu vijahāra / atha sarvatathāgatairidaṃ buddhakṣetraṃ tadyathā tilabimbamiva paripūrṇama //

atha khalu sarvatathāgatā mahāsamājamāpadya, yena sarvārthasiddhirbodhisattvo mahāsattvaḥ bodhimaṇḍaniṣaṇṇastenopajagmuḥ / upetya bodhisattvasya sāmbhogikairi kāyairdarśanandatvaivamāhuḥ- "kathaṃ kulaputrānuttarāṃ samyaksambodhim abhisambhotsyase, yastvaṃ sarvatathāgatattvānabhijñatayā sarvaduḥkarānyutsahasī-?"ti /

atha sarvārthasiddhirbodhisattvo mahāsatvassarvatathāgatacoditaḥsamānastata āsphānasamādhito vyutthāya, sarvatathāgatān praṇipatyāhū yaivamāha- "bhagavantastathāgatā ājñāpayata kathaṃ pratipadyāmi kīḍṣaṃ tat tattvaṃ" iti /

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. V)

Again, the *sāmbhogakāya* proclaim and teach the Dharma to assemblies of bodhisattvas who have attained a level of meditative mastery which permits them to perceive the manifested Embodiments of Enjoyment, and benefit from their instruction. This verse indicates that the *sāmbhogakāya* skillfully tailor their teaching of the Dharma to the respective level of understanding of the aspiring bodhisattva(s), which can be ascertained by the current stage (Skt. *bhūmi*) that has been attained by these advanced practitioners along the bodhisattva path.

Stanzas IV–VI

7. *śāntam agryaṃ virāgānāṃ yoginām eva gocaram /*

8. *agrāhyānabhilāpyaṅ ca saddharmman namatāṃ muneḥ //*

9. *yathābhūmipraviṣṭānāṃ pṛthakprajñānuvarttinam /*

10. *dharmmaṃ sāmbhoginirddiṣṭaṃ dhyānagrāhyan namāmy aham //*

11. *vuddhājñā devadaityādibhāṣopadhyanurodhinī /*

12. *svavarṇṇāpagatā svacchā sphaṭikābhā punātu vaḥ //*

IV. Bow to the Good Dharma which is tranquil, excellent, inconceivable, inexpressible, and the domain of the passionless ascetics of the Sage.

V. I bow to the Dharma which is grasped through meditation and proclaimed by an Embodiment of Enjoyment conforming to the respective insight befitting their attained stage (*bhūmi*).

VI. The knowledge of the Buddha, like a crystal which is transparent and devoid of its own color, adapts to conditions by utilizing the speech of gods, *daityas*, and so on; may it purify all.

Stanza IV–VI analysis and commentary. The next three stanzas directly parallel the previous three stanzas glorifying the *trikāya*, the three embodiments of the Buddha. That is, stanza four corresponds to stanza one by further describing the non-dual and non-conceptual thusness of the *dharmakāya* by way of listing a number of qualities (Skt.

guṇa) of the *dharmakāya*. As the *dharmakāya* is equivalent with enlightenment, the stanza, therefore, highlights the qualities of enlightenment as well. Stanza five corresponds to stanza two in that it describes explicitly the ability of the *sāṃbhogakāya* to assist advanced bodhisattvas via meditation. This assistance is tailored according to the bodhisattva's level of mastery along the path of bodhisattvas, and this path progresses in stages. Finally, stanza six corresponds to stanza three by describing how the Buddha takes on various physical manifestations (i.e., the *nirmāṇakāya*) and adapts his pedagogical approach in order to cater to the various levels of understanding of less advanced audiences.

In addition to paralleling the first three stanzas in praise of the *trikāya*, stanzas four through six are also collectively praising the Dharma. Both stanzas four and five explicitly praise the Dharma, while stanza seven uses the compound *buddhājñā*, 'knowledge or wisdom of the Buddha,' a compound that is synonymous with the Buddha's Dharma. These three stanzas, therefore, are directed to praising the second jewel of Buddhism, Dharma. The Buddha, Dharma, and *saṅgha* are known as the *triratna*, or 'three jewels of Buddhism.' The first three stanzas correspond to the first of the three jewels—the Buddha—in that the Buddha is embodied in three ways: the *dharmakāya*, the *sāṃbhogakāya*, and the *nirmāṇakāya*. As will be discussed below, the final three stanzas of the opening invocation collectively refer to the third jewel of Buddhism, the *saṅgha* (the Buddhist 'community'). The stanzas accomplish this by praising those who undertake the bodhisattva path in order to attain full Buddhahood. The first nine stanzas comprising the opening invocation, therefore, consist of three triadic sections in which each one of the three jewels is further divided in three parts.

Stanzas VII–IX

13. *vrahmādirūpiṇo nānāvineyāśānurodhataḥ /*
14. *nirābhāsādibhūmiṣṭhā vodhisatvā jayanti te //*
15. *cittamātrañ jagad dr̥ṣṭvā svapnavat taddhitodyatāḥ /*
16. *muditādyāḥ praviṣṭā ye saptabhūmī[ḥ] stavīmi tān //*
17. *māṭṛvad duḥkhitam vīkṣya jagat tadduḥkhapīditāḥ /*
18. *tanmuktyai cittaratnaṃ ye vodhau vaddhnanti tān bhaje //*

VII. Glory to those bodhisattvas who assume the form of Brahmā and other (gods) in order to fulfill the wishes of various devotees, and who are well established in fields⁴¹ (*bhūmi*) such as Nirābhāsa.⁴²

VIII. Having understood that, like a dream, the world is *cittamātra*, I praise those who are intent on its (the world's) welfare, (and who) have entered the seven stages (of the bodhisattva path), of which Muditā is the first (stage).

IX. I honor those who, like a mother, observing the pain of the world and being afflicted by that pain, direct the jeweled-like mind toward awakening (*bodhau*) in order to alleviate it (i.e., *duḥkha*).

Stanzas VII–IX analysis and commentary.

Stanzas seven through nine conclude the opening invocation of the inscription by praising bodhisattvas and the path they undertake in order to attain complete and perfect Buddhahood, a state which, in turn, is praised in the form of the *trikāya* in the previous stanzas. Stanzas seven through nine not only praise the virtues and abilities of more advanced bodhisattvas (e.g., stanza VII), but also praise those just setting out on the path with aspirations to alleviate the suffering of others (e.g., stanza IX). In fact, a closer examination of the

⁴¹ Or: states; stages.

⁴² The term *nirābhāsa* can be variously translated as 'without (false) appearance,' 'formlessness,' 'unmanifested,' and 'imagelessness.' I make extensive comments on this term in my commentary in chapter two.

content of each stanza reveals that there is a structural pattern related directly to the mastery level of the bodhisattva.

For example, stanza seven begins by praising some of the most powerful bodhisattvas, the ones who have attained the ability to change bodily forms. According to the ten-stage advancement schema of bodhisattvas discussed in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*—a schema that was well established by the tenth century—bodhisattvas attain the ability to change forms in order to better assist a variety of beings. This ability is acquired at the eighth stage (Skt. *bhūmi*) of the bodhisattva path; the stage is known as *acala*, ‘immovable’ or ‘steadfast.’⁴³ Thus stanza seven refers to advanced bodhisattvas between the stages of eight and ten. Stanza eight, on the other hand, explicitly refers to bodhisattvas undertaking the first seven stages of the bodhisattva path. The name Muditā (‘Joy’) certainly refers to the first stage known as Pramuditā (also ‘Joy’) elaborated in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, thus further strengthening the possibility that of the various level configurations for the bodhisattva path discussed in various sources it was the configuration found in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*—another Yogācāra text—that likely influenced the author, or authors, of the Vat Sithor inscription. Finally, stanza nine refers to those individuals who first direct their attention to problem

⁴³ See Dayal (1932: 270–91) for various configurations of the bodhisattva stages along with the history and development of those stages. See Kawamura (1981 and 2004) and Buswell and Gimello (1992) for more recent discussions on the bodhisattva path.

It should also be noted that upon attaining level ten, according to the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, the bodhisattva also undergoes a bodily change in which they emerge with a glorious body from a great jeweled lotus.

The *Daśabhūmikasūtra* is also included in the heterogeneous work known as the *Avatamsakasūtra*. It appears as chapter twenty-six. Like the *Gaṇḍavyūhasūtra* which is also included in the *Avatamsakasūtra*, the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* circulated as an independent text, for which there is a surviving Sanskrit version. See Williams (2010: 132–33) for additional details.

See Clearly (1993) for a complete English translation of the *Avatamsakasūtra* based on Śikṣānanda’s translation completed sometime near the end of the seventh century.

of suffering; thereby they set enlightenment as their goal. These individuals are just setting out on the path of the bodhisattva. This sudden arising of compassion for others, paired with the desire to alleviate suffering, is known as *bodhicitta* ('awakening of the mind') in many Buddhist sources. A more detailed analysis of these stanzas now follows.

Stanza seven. Again, stanza seven describes more advanced bodhisattvas with the ability to take on a variety of forms in order to assist in the welfare of sentient beings. The purpose of assuming a variety of forms is that appearing in a particular form may be more conducive to aiding certain beings at various levels of understanding. In other words, the bodhisattva may find it more helpful to appear as a god, as a fisherman, as a woman, or something entirely different depending on the individual or group to which the teaching is directed. According to the schema presented in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, bodhisattvas attain the ability to assume different bodies at the eighth stage of their development. What follows are excerpts from the section describing the eighth stage of the bodhisattva path in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* chapter of the *Avataṃsakasūtra*. The translation is from Cleary (1993: 766–68).

"I will tell you, if the buddhas did not introduce the enlightening beings (i.e., bodhisattvas) this way into ways of effecting omniscient knowledge, the enlightening beings would become completely extinct in parinirvana and would cease all work for sentient beings.⁴⁴ Therefore, the buddhas give the enlightening beings such infinite tasks to develop knowledge, the knowledge-producing deeds effected in a single instant of which are immeasurably, incalculably greater than all former undertakings from the first inspiration up to the attainment of stability in the seventh stage. Why? Because previously it was practice undertaken with one body, whereas having climbed to this stage the power of practice of enlightening beings is relized by infinite different bodies, [. . .]

⁴⁴ i.e., they would no longer be able to assist sentient beings who still operate in the conditioned realm.

“Imbued with such knowledge, well established in this stage, while not moving from one Buddha-land, they appear as reflections in the circle of buddhas in untold Buddha-lands. According to the differences in beings’ physical characteristics, their colors, appearances, statuses, physical sizes, inclinations, and dispositions, in various circles in various forms. In circles of mendicants they appear as mendicants; in circles of priest they appear as priests; in circles of warriors and administrators they appear as warriors and administrators; in circle of peasants they appear as peasants; in circle of servants they appear as servants; in circle of householders they appear as householders; in circle of various classes of celestial beings they appear as those particular types of celestial beings; and in circles of demons they appear as demons. To beings who should be taught by Buddhist followers, they appear as Buddhist followers. To those who should be taught by individual illuminates, they appear as individual illuminates. To those who should be taught by enlightening beings, they appear as enlightening beings. To those who should be taught by buddhas, they appear as buddhas. This, to the extent of the realm of beings’ forms of existence, senses, and inclinations, in the realms of untold Buddha-lands, enlightening beings appear differently in accord with each of them. They are free from all discriminatory conceptions of bodies and have realized the equality of bodies; their manifestation bodies, endless and not in vain, is for the development and education of all.

It is also worth noting that the surviving Sanskrit version of this section of the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*—unlike Śikṣānanda’s Chinese version which is quoted from above—provides a slightly different list of example forms the bodhisattva can appear as. The changes are minor and only have possible significance with regard to the stanza from the Vat Sithor inscription. Stanza seven of the inscription, for example, specifically cites the form (Skt. *rūpa*) of Brahmā, along with other unspecified forms, as being one of the example forms that can be assumed by advanced bodhisattvas. The Sanskrit version of the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* also specifically cites Brahmā as being one the forms that can be taken by a bodhisattva who has attained the eighth stage.⁴⁵ This

⁴⁵ The relevant section is as follows: *yādṛśī sattvānāṃ kāyavibhaktiśca varṇaliṅgasamsthānārohapariṇāhādhimuktyadhyāśayaśca teṣu buddhakṣetreṣu teṣu ca parśanmaṇḍaleṣu tatra tatra tathā tathā svakāyamādarśayati / sa śramaṇaparśanmaṇḍaleṣu śramaṇavarṇarūpamādarśayati / brāhmaṇaparśanmaṇḍaleṣu brāhmaṇavarṇarūpamādarśayati / kṣatriya ... / vaiśya ... / śūdra ... / gr̥hapati ... / cāturmahārājika ... / trāyastriṃśa ... / evaṃ yāma ... / tuṣita ... / nirmāṇarati ... / paranirmitavaśavarti ... / māra ... / brahma ... / yāvadakaniṣṭha ... / śrāvakaṣāyikānāṃ*

observation further supports the claim that stanza seven is specifically glorifying bodhisattvas who have attained the eighth stage or higher.

The second part of stanza seven is a pun that seems to highlight a paradoxical contradiction. Despite that the advanced bodhisattva is one who can assume any form for the benefit of sentient beings, the bodhisattva is also one established in a state or field (Skt. *bhūmi*) ‘free of, or without, (false) appearance’ or ‘without form’ (Skt. *nirābhāsa*). The term *nirābhāsa* can be variously translated as ‘without appearance,’ ‘formlessness,’ ‘unmanifested,’ ‘imagelessness,’ and so on. I think there are two possible ways to understand *nirābhāsa* in the context of this stanza. First, *nirābhāsa* may simply be alluding to the bodhisattva’s ability to assume various forms in order to assist devotees of varying dispositions and levels of knowledge; hence, they are without any *fixed* form, and therefore reside in a field or state of ‘formlessness.’ I think this interpretation is weak, but it may find some support in descriptions about eighth-stage bodhisattvas in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* (refer to the above translated excerpts). In other words, the bodhisattvas at this advanced level are only projecting a great number ‘reflections’ that have no actual form.

One could, however, also consider how the term *nirābhāsa* is used in the context of the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra*. Without delving too deeply into the various nuances of how *citta*, or ‘mind,’ is understood in the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra*, the text does describe *nirābhāsa* as a sphere (Skt. *gocaram*) or “state of mind of the realized person, a condition in which one perceives things directly, without the mediation of conceptual recognition or

sattvānām śrāvākakāyavarṇarūpamādarśayati / pratyekabuddhavaineyikānām sattvānām pratyekabuddhakāyavarṇarūpamādarśayati / bodhisattva ... / tathāgata ... / iti hi bho jinaputra yāvanto 'nabhilāpyeṣu buddhakṣetreṣu sattvānāmupapattyāyatanādhimuktiprasarāsteṣu tathatvāya svakāyavibhaktimādarśayati // (from Vaidya’s edited version of the *Daśabhūmikasūtram*, 45).

interpretation of any kind,” according to Ray (2005: 131). In the context of the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra*, however, *nirābhāsa* is the fruition of the ultimate *citta*; that is, the awakened mind/individual. As such, this state is equated with the *dharmakāya* and *nirvāṇa* in the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra*, which is not the case in the Vat Sithor inscription. Nevertheless, understanding *nirābhāsa* as a state in which conceptual recognition via subject/object duality has collapsed is probably what is being alluded to in the inscription. Unlike the *Laṅkāvatāra Sūtra* in which such a state is part of the final attainment of the awakened being, the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* is clear that advanced bodhisattvas attain perfect insight into the non-duality of all things prior to their final attainment of full Buddhahood. Their reason for continuing along the path after attaining this insight revolves primarily around their desire to assist other beings. According to the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, such insight is attained in the seventh stage, and bodhisattvas are ‘steadfast’ (Skt. *acala*, the name of the eighth stage) in this knowledge by the eighth stage.

They (i.e., bodhisattvas) become detached from everything in the world, yet they produce arrays of adornments for the world. They become ultimately calm and tranquil due to removal from the fires of afflictions, yet they undertake to accomplish the extinction of the flames of afflictions of lust, hatred, and delusion of all beings. They realize the nonduality of essence of being and nonbeing, all things being like illusions, mirages, dreams, reflections, echoes, apparitions, yet they put into effect resolution in innumerable different deeds and works. They have cultivated the perception that all lands and paths are equal to space, yet they undertake the adornment of Buddha-lands.⁴⁶

It seems, therefore, that the second part of stanza seven of the inscription may be glorifying the advanced bodhisattva who is established in state which is free (*nir°*) from

⁴⁶ trans. Cleary (1993: 755).

the appearances of the mind (*°ābhāsa*); in other words, the false subject/object duality conceived by the mind that most beings confuse for reality itself.

Stanza eight. The reference to seven stages (Skt. *saptabhūmīḥ*) of the bodhisattva path may seem a bit perplexing since the ten-stage classificatory system (Skt. *daśabhūmi*) was well-established by the tenth century. Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 203, fn. 1) reconciled the reference to seven stages with the ten-stage schema by simply stating that the first seven stages constitute a distinct group onto themselves, and he references the *MSA* (IV, 2) for support, although he provides no explanation for such a reference. In other words, for Cœdès, the inscription is merely referencing the first seven, of ten, stages of the bodhisattva path. I have come to agree with Cœdès' suggestion. Unlike Cœdès, however, I have further suggested that stanzas seven through nine are praising bodhisattvas at various stages along the bodhisattva path. Despite being in agreement with Cœdès on stanza eight, his reference to *MSA* needs to be examined in order to justify how it supports the claim that stanza eight is praising bodhisattvas between stages one and seven.

The stanza in the *MSA* referenced by Cœdès is discussing how the arising of thought (Skt. *cittotpāda*) consists of four types: *ādhimokṣa*, *śuddhādhyāśayika*, *vaipākya*, and *aṇavarjita*.

*cittotpādo 'dhimokṣo 'sau śuddhādhyāśayiko 'paraḥ / vaipākya bhūmiṣu
matastathāvaraṇavarjitaḥ // (MSA, IV, 2)*

These four types arise, or develop, during the various stages of ten-stage bodhisattva path. For example, as explained in the *bhāṣya* for this stanza, the arising of *ādhimokṣa* ('ferve aspiration') occurs within the first six stages of the bodhisattva path. The arising of *śuddhādhyāśayika* ('superior pure intentions') is a quality of a bodhisattva

in the first seven stages, and it is this grouping Cœdès must have been referring to. His point likely was that there exists textual support for grouping the first seven stages of the bodhisattva path as distinct sub-category.

Additionally, the seventh stage in the ten-stage schema of the bodhisattva path is known as the *dūrāṅgamābhūmi*, what Kawamura (2004) has translated as the ‘proceeding from afar stage [in which a bodhisattva gets beyond one’s self to help others].’ Thus, a seventh-stage bodhisattva is one whose superior pure intentions (*śuddhādhyāśayika*) are being extended beyond one’s self in order to strive for the welfare of other sentient beings. This does, indeed, appear to correspond to the theme being stressed in the inscription since praise is specifically being extended to those individuals engaged in the welfare of others, and who have entered the first seven stages of the bodhisattva path.⁴⁷

The stanza’s direct reference to the name of the first stage, *Mudita*, corresponds directly to the name of the first stage found in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*. This fact, more so than any other, supports the position that the schema for the bodhisattva path, as

⁴⁷ With that said, however, it is important to note that the number of *bhūmis* comprising the bodhisattva path varied among texts and traditions, and perhaps the Buddhists connected with this inscription adhered to a form of Buddhism in which the path only consisted of seven stages. Dayal (1932: 271), for example, has argued that the original number of bodhisattva stages likely consisted of seven. The configuration of the bodhisattva path in *Bd* II.4, III.3 consists of thirteen *vihāras* and seven *bhūmis*. Additionally, *Lañ* II, 54 also mentions seven stages, although it fails to specify those stages. Still, the suggestion that the bodhisattva path mentioned in this inscription may have only consisted of seven stages is weakened by the additional reference to *mudita* (‘joy’) being the name of the first stage of the bodhisattva path in st. VIII. The *muditabhūmi*, or *pramuditabhūmi*, is the name of the first stage according ten-stage classificatory system found in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*. Conversely, the first *bhūmi* of the seven-stage system found in the *Bd* is *gotrabhūmi*. There is a *pramuditavihāra* in the *Bd*, but it is the third of thirteen *vihāras* and is specifically associated with the third *bhūmi* of that system known as *śuddhādhyāśayabhūmi*.

For more on the various configurations of the path of bodhisattva, see the above references and Williams (2010: 200–08, esp. n. 27).

understood by tenth-century Khmers, would have been directly influenced by the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, and this influence is reflected in the Vat Sithor inscription.

Again, the use of the term *cittamātra* in the first part of stanza eight is revealing in that it further supports the conclusion that the epistemological foundations for many (but not necessarily all) Buddhists of the time in Cambodia would have been derived from Yogācāra forms of Buddhism. The term, as noted previously, occurs again in stanza twenty-seven of this inscription.

The *Daśabhūmikasūtra* is pointed to as being the possible source for the earliest reference to the theory of *cittamātra*; although, as Takasaki (1966: 35–6) rightly points out, the early references to *cittamātra* in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* are only speaking of *cittamātra* in the context of the casual arising of consciousness in a series of other causally dependent factors. In other words, the usage of *cittamātra* in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* represents an early expression of the term that does not really reflect the fuller expression found in later texts. Nevertheless, it is interesting to point out that the references to *cittamātra* in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* occur in the context of the first seven stages of the bodhisattva path. For example, the only references to *cittamātra* in the *Daśabhūmikasūtra* —of which there are two—are found in descriptions of bodhisattvas who have attained the sixth stage. This again, fits with the observation that stanza eight of the Vat Sithor inscription is praising bodhisattvas who have undertaken the first seven stages of the path. The *Daśabhūmikasūtra* chapter of the *Avatamsakasūtra* states:

They (i.e., bodhisattvas) also think, ‘All that is in the world is only mind.’⁴⁸
These twelve elements of becoming analyzed and explained by the Buddha

⁴⁸ Skt. *cittamātra* (cf. pp. 31 and 87–8 in Vaidya’s edition of the *Daśabhūmikasūtram*).

are also based on one mind. Why? Whenever the mind is aroused with the desire for a thing, that is consciousness, and the “thing” is conditioning. The delusion of conditioning is ignorance. Name and form are born together with the ignorant mind. The development of name and form is the six sense mediums. Connected with the six mediums is contact. Born together with contact is sensation. Obsession with sensation is craving. The unrelenting seizing of what is picked up by craving is grasping. The conjunction of these elements of existence is becoming. The emergence of becoming is birth. The full development of birth is old age. The end of old age is death.⁴⁹

Here *cittamātra* is connected with the Buddhist concept of interdependent origination (Skt. *pratītyasamutpāda*) in the traditional understanding that consciousness too, like all things, arises in dependence on other causal factors. The above quoted section from the *Avataṃsakasūtra* continues with a detailed account and breakdown of how the concept interdependent origination operates. Interestingly enough the concept of the interdependent origination is also recorded in stanza seventy-two of the Vat Sithor inscription.

The term *vijñaptimātra* (often translated as ‘consciousness only’ or ‘representation only’) is often used synonymously with *cittamātra*. In fact, stanza 275 of the tenth-century Pre Rup inscription references the concept of *vijñapti(mātra)* by way of a pun.

Because of him (i.e., Rājendravarman)—who arose by the elevation of his own Dharma—the righteous entreaty of king Yaśovarman, which was free (*śūnyā*) of motive (*artha*) just as the object (*artha*) of cognition (*vijñapti*) spoken about by the Yogācāra (is also ultimately empty [*śūnyā*]), attained a significance similar to the Triad (i.e, Buddha, Dharma, and Saṅgha).

(K. 806, Pre Rup, st. CCLXXV)⁵⁰

⁴⁹ trans. Cleary (1993: 746).

⁵⁰ Skt. *yācñā yaśovarmmanṛpasya yogācāroktavijñaptir ivārthaśūnyā / dharmmyā svadharmmoddharaṇodhatena yenārthavattāṃ gamitā trayīva //*

Again, the concept of *cittamātra* is referenced a second time in stanza twenty-seven of the Vat Sithor inscription. The stanza is very clear with regard to the importance of *cittamātra* and other Buddhist doctrines in late tenth-century Cambodia.

The sun of doctrines such as *cittamātra* and *nairātmya*, eclipsed by the night of false doctrines, shone greater than the day.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXVII)

In the above stanza *cittamātra* and *nairātmya* ('no-self'/'not-self'/'without self') are essentially presented as the most fundamental doctrines for Buddhists such as Kīrtipaṇḍita in tenth-century Cambodia.

Stanza nine. Stanza nine concludes the opening invocation with general praise to all beings who have directed, or will direct, their attention to the alleviating of suffering in others. In order to accomplish this compassionate goal, such individuals devote themselves to awakening (Skt. *bodhi*); in other words, they have embarked, or will embark, upon the path of the bodhisattva. This path was considered the most advantageous way to compassionately assist other beings.

Unlike the preceding two stanzas that appear to praise particularly high-leveled bodhisattvas, stanza nine praises any and all who have set awakening for the benefit of others as their goal. This stanza is more inclusive in that it does not appear to matter whether the individual was a novice with initial aspirations or a more advanced practitioner already practicing the path. As such, the ninth stanza acts as a nice conclusion to the opening invocation. The Vat Sithor *maṅgala* began by glorifying the highest and most esteemed *dharmakāya*, and then continuing with a descending order of praise it reached one of the fundamental building blocks of the Buddhist community—the individual who strives compassionately for the benefit of others.

The opening nine stanzas of the Vat Sithor inscription should also be understood collectively as an extended paean to the three jewels of Buddhism. Stanzas one through three are directed to the Buddha. Stanzas four through six praise the Dharma. Stanzas seven through nine then conclude with homage to the Buddhist community. The Buddhist community (*saṅgha*)—according to stanzas seven through nine of the inscription—consists of anyone who, out of compassion for the welfare of other sentient beings, undertakes the path of the bodhisattva.

CHAPTER 4
BEFORE KĪRTIPAṄḌITA: THE ACTIVITIES OF KAVĪNDRĀRIMATHANA AND HIS
POSSIBLE IDENTIFICATION WITH KAVĪNDRĀCĀRYA OF INSCRIPTIONS K. 772
AND K. 202

This chapter discusses the activities of the tenth-century Buddhist figure Kavīndrārimathana. The Cambodian epigraphical record reveals that Kavīndrārimathana was one of Rājendravarman's close dignitaries, and he was purportedly responsible for several important building projects in the capital of Yaśodharapura.¹ He is also recorded as having installed several Buddhist images at sites such as Jayantadeśa, Kuṭṭśvara, and Bat Cum. The purpose of this discussion is twofold. First, Kavīndrārimathana's presence and activities demonstrate that advocates of Buddhist traditions had attained a level of royal recognition during the tenth-century that was greater than that of any previous era. This trend would continue during the reign of Rājendravarman's son, Jayavarman, with the activities of Kīrtipaṅḍita, the Buddhist who is praised in the Vat Sithor inscription. Second, I will demonstrate that Kavīndrārimathana's presence in epigraphical records is actually more extensive than previously imagined by arguing that he is also recorded under the name of Kavīndrācārya in two other tenth-century Cambodian inscriptions.² This interpretation, in turn, further bolsters the argument that advocates of Buddhist traditions had become not only increasingly active and established during the mid- to late tenth century, but also more influential.

¹ i.e., the Angkor region.

² The name Kavīndrācārya also appears as Kavindrācārya (cf. K. 772).

An Overview of Kavīndrārimathana

The Bat Cum Inscriptions (K. 267–K. 268)

Kavīndrārimathana—whose name means ‘king of poets, destroyer of enemies’—was a prestigious Buddhist active in the administration of Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 966). Knowledge of Kavīndrārimathana and his activities come almost entirely from the lengthy panegyrics dedicated to this minister in the Bat Cum inscriptions edited by Coédès (1908b).³ These three inscriptions document that he was responsible for the installation of images of the Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, and Prajñāpāramitā at Bat Cum.⁴ The inscriptions also record that he previously established images of the Buddha at Jayantadeśa, and two images of Prajñāpāramita (called Devī) along with an image of Lokanātha at Kuṭṭisvara.⁵

The Bat Cum inscriptions also list a number of buildings that Kavīndrārimathana was responsible for having constructed on behalf of Rājendravarman during a period when this ruler was centralizing himself at the site of Yaśodharapura.⁶ The north shrine

³ Again, for a recent re-translation and examination of the Bat Cum inscriptions in German, see Mertens (2005). Appendix B of this dissertation also provides an overview of the inscription and a discussion on the opening stanzas dedicated to Buddhist divinities.

⁴ K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XIX. Skt. *so sthāpayat sumahatīn jinamūrttim ekāṃ śrīvajrapāṇisahitām api divyadevīm / prāsādaharmmyanivahe svahr̥dīva divye vauddho gradhīś śaranagāṣṭabhir atra bhaktyā //*, Coédès (1908b: 228).

⁵ K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XX. Skt. *jayantadeśe jinarūpam ekaṃ so sthāpayan mūrttirasāṣṭaśāke / kuṭṭisvare so pi ca lokanāthan devīdvayan netranagāṣṭaśāke //*, Coédès (1908b: 228).

K. 267, Bat Cum, st. XXI. Skt. *jayantadeśe vijayī jinam ekaṃ atiṣṭipat / devīdvitayasamyuktaṃ yo vuddhañ ca kuṭṭisvare //*, Coédès (1908b: 232). Note that the word Buddha is used in this stanza instead of Lokanātha. For a few remarks on this change refer to Appendix B of this dissertation.

⁶ I cannot confidently include the actual shrines of Bat Cum as also being architecturally planned by Kavīndrārimathana since the epigraphical record does not provide a clear answer, and scholars are of different opinions. For example, Claude Jacques (1997: 96) has said: “The Buddhist architect was to build on his own account (or rather for the well-being of his *karma*) the small temple of Bat Cum.” Conversely, Jacques Dumarçay and Pascal Royère (2001: 66) believe that Bat Cum was originally a so-called Hindu temple that had simply been transformed into Buddhist temple during the reign of Rājendravarman, a period when the inscriptions would have been added and the Buddhist images

inscription, for example, compares Kavīndrārimathana to the supreme architect of the universe, Viśvakarma, and indicates that Rājendravarman instructed him to construct a palace (Skt. *mandira*).⁷ The inscription continues by indicating that Kavīndrārimathana was also charged by Rājendravarman to construct the East Mebon monument on an island in the middle of the eastern *baray*, originally known as the Yaśodharataṭāka ('reservoir of Yaśodhara').

When urged by all of the world, he who was charged by the king (i.e., Kavīndrārimathana) constructed, among other works, a mountain (*śaila*; i.e., East Mebon) in the middle of Yaśodhara reservoir.

(K. 268, Bat Cum, st. XXXV)⁸

Some scholars such as Claude Jacques (1997: 96) believe that Kavīndrārimathana probably died shortly after the dedication of the Buddhist images at Bat Cum in 953 CE, although there is currently no evidence to support such a conclusion. Nevertheless, due to the architectural similarities between the East Mebon and Rājendravarman's main temple complex Pre Rup, which was later dedicated in 961 CE, Jacques (1997: 100) has suggested that Kavīndrārimathana may have provided some of the initial design plans for this important structure as well. Whether or not this

installed. What can be said with confidence is that Kavīndrārimathana was responsible for the installation and dedication of Buddhist images at Bat Cum in 875 Śaka (953 CE); cf. stanza XIX of K. 266 and stanza XXXII of K. 267.

⁷ K. 268, Bat Cum, st. XXXIV. Skt. *yaśodharapure ramyaṃ mandiraṃ vivudhapriyaḥ / śilpavid viśvakarmmeva yo nenendreṇa kāritaḥ //*, Cœdès (1908b: 236).

⁸ Skt. *preraṇe sarvvalokasya yaś śailādikṛtau kṛti / *yaśodharataṭākasya* (corr. Cœdès: *yaśodharatatākasya*) *madhye rājñā niyojitaḥ //*, Cœdès (1908b: 236).

Many such as Cœdès have translated *śaila* as 'rock.' While the term can mean rock, or anything made of stone, it can also refer to a hill or mountain, sometimes mythical (M.W. s.v., *śaila*). I prefer the word *mountain* because it better reflects the mountain-like architectural style of the Mebon, a point I think the inscription is emphasizing.

is true, it's clear that Kavīndrārimathana was a valuable dignitary and architect during Rājendravarman's reign.

The Bat Cum inscriptions also indicate that Kavīndrārimathana was responsible for the construction of two other important structures: a *parikhā* and a *taṭāka*.⁹ The *parikhā* probably refers to ancillary canal funneling water from Mount Kulen, although the term can also refer to a moat or type of ditch. The *taṭāka* refers to a large reservoir of water known as a *baray* in Khmer, although the identity of the specific *taṭāka* mentioned in the inscriptions remains a matter of debate. These two architectural accomplishments deserve a dedicated discussion since some interpretations surrounding them have affected how scholars understand Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia, as well their relationship with co-existing Brahmanical groups. An immediate examination of this subject, however, will take readers too far astray from the general focus of this chapter; therefore, the subject will be explored in chapter seven. For now, it is sufficient to note that these additional large-scale architectural accomplishments further demonstrate that Kavīndrārimathana was an important figure during the reign of Rājendravarman.

The Tep Pranam Stele (K. 290)

Besides the Bat Cum inscriptions, Kavīndrārimathana is also referenced in an tenth-century Old Khmer inscription that was appended to an earlier Sanskrit stele inscription. The stele is now known as the Tep Pranam stele.¹⁰

⁹ For example, see stanzas XXXVIII–XLI in Coédès (1908b: 236–37).

¹⁰ For the Tep Pranam stele inscription, see Coédès (1908c). For a more recent examination of this inscription, see Estève (2009 : 338–59). For recent scholarship on the *āśrama* of Yaśovarman, see Estève and Soutif (2010–2011) and Pottier (2003).

The Tep Pranam stele is an important ninth-century inscription relating the founding of Saugatāśrama by Yaśovarman (r. 889 – c. 910).¹¹ Only the the appended and damaged Old Khmer lines on Side D that record the donative activities of Kavīndrārimathana, however, are of concern here.¹² These appended lines were undoubtedly added sometime during the tenth century. Unfortunately, other than a reference to the location of Kuṭīśvara, no specifics are given regarding the foundation and offerings. Kavīndrārimathana’s Buddhist proclivities, however, are firmly documented in the Bat Cum inscriptions mentioned previously. Again, two of the Bat Cum inscriptions specifically mention Kuṭīśvara, and how in Śaka 872 (950 CE) Kavīndrārimathana installed an image of the Buddha (or a Lokanātha image according to one inscription) and two Devī images at this very same site.

In discussing the appended Khmer lines of Side D, Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 233 fn. 6) also noted that the Khmer word *jvan* was generally used for a donation to a divinity or temple. Based on Kavīndrārimathana’s other well-documented Buddhist activities at Kuṭīśvara, it seems almost certain that his offerings (*jvan*) referenced in the appended lines of K. 290 would have been directed specifically to a site housing Buddhist divinities.

¹¹ In discussing the Bat Cum inscriptions, Cœdès (1968: 117) once wrote that the inscriptions stand chronologically between the stele of Tep Pranam and the stele of Vat Sithor; and thus, “prove the continuity, in certain quarters, of Mahayanist Buddhism, from whose adherents the Sivaite sovereigns did not disdain to recruit their officials.” The appended tenth-century lines to the ninth-century Tep Pranam stele which documented the Buddhist activities of Kavīndrārimathana also appear to show that Khmer Buddhists were also proactive in maintaining a continuity with their own Buddhist history.

¹² It should be noted that there are another two appended Khmer inscriptions on this stele that are also of no interest since these brief entries were added after the tenth-century and are not concerned with Kavīndrārimathana. The first is dated to 927 Śaka (1005 CE), and the second is dated to 937 Śaka (1015 CE).

The Stele of Vat Kdei (K. 157)

The stele of Vat Kdei, edited in Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 123–27), is an inscription with both Sanskrit and Old Khmer sections. The two larger sides of the stele have fifteen lines of Sanskrit on one side, and fourteen lines on the other. The two smaller sides contain twenty lines of Khmer on one side, and twenty-three lines on the other. An additional line of Khmer recording the activity of the donor runs around the sides of the base of the stele. The engraving of the inscription was ultimately motivated by the installation and dedication of two images of Avalokiteśa (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) along with a Devī image by Vīrendravikhyāta, and the donation of property to his niece, Kontī. According to the inscription this event occurred in 875 Śaka (953 CE), thus placing the installation of the images during the reign of Rājendravarman. The inscription is relevant to a discussion on Kavīndrārimathana since it records that he was married to Kontī. A more in-depth discussion of the inscription is of interest since it can tell us more about certain aspects of Buddhist traditions during the tenth-century.

The Sanskrit section of the inscription contains no opening invocation, and begins by documenting the commencement of Harṣavarman's reign in 863 Śaka (941 CE). This inscription then records how Vīrendravikhyāta (with property received from the king) cultivated forest land, demarcated the land, and founded a village. The culmination of Vīrendravikhyāta's activities involving property comes in stanza seven which records the installation of an image of the bodhisattva Lokeśa undertaken for the welfare of the world. Vīrendravikhyāta's actions illustrate the continuing importance of the accumulation and transference of merit among Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia. It also illustrates how Buddhist divinities were localized by connecting them with the Cambodian landscape. Although stanza seven presents the installation of the

Lokeśa image in an altruistic manner, this action was also undertaken in order to ensure the flourishing of Vīrendravikhyāta's new property; which, in turn, also ensured the success of his own family. It is noteworthy that once land has been cleared and demarcated for the establishment of a village, the divinity must then be ritually installed on that land in order to ensure prosperity.

The Sanskrit section then records the ascension of Rājendravarman in 866 Śaka (944 CE). The genealogies that follow are of interest in that Vīrendravikhyāta was the maternal uncle of Kontī, whom he presented to serve the subsequent king, Rājendravarman.¹³ The inscription also indicates that Kontī was married to Kavīndrārimathana, the same Buddhist dignitary discussed in inscriptions such as Bat Cum.¹⁴ The Vat Kdei inscription, therefore, provides additional evidence to support that Kavīndrārimathana was an important figure in royal circles, as were some members of his family.

Because of Vīrendravikhyāta's devotion to the king, stanza eight indicates that Rājendravarman presented him with a bronze image of Lokeśvara and Devī, along with the ornaments that adorned the images. The very next stanza records how these images were then consecrated and installed in a sanctuary (Skt. *prāsāda*) by Vīrendravikhyāta according to prescribed rites.

The Sanskrit section also indicates that Vīrendrakhyāta built a large reservoir (Skt. *taṭāka*) for benefit of living beings. Ritually, the inscription specifically indicates that the

¹³ The inscription specifically indicates that Kontī was presented (*nivedya*) to the king and was established in the *sevivarṇa* (the social order of those who serve) in the *rājñopaskarageha* (dwelling of household commodities of the king). I take this to mean that she was among those responsible for the everyday maintenance of the king's household.

¹⁴ Stanza IX describes Śrī Kavīndrārimathana as *matimān bh[ūr]jibhāgyo 't[i]vallabhaḥ* ('wise, possessing abundant fortune, and exceedingly beloved').

reservoir was expected to be used for performing ablutions three times per day and for the purpose of bathing the three Buddhist images. The Sanskrit portion then concludes with the donation of numerous properties controlled by Vīrendravikhyāta—including the fields of a monastery—to his niece Kontī. The Khmer sections provide a list of servants responsible for the upkeep of enumerated properties and for servicing the three Buddhist divinities presiding over these properties.¹⁵

Confusion over the number of Buddhist images recorded by Vīrendravikhyāta is present in the remarks of some scholars who have analyzed this inscription. Stanza thirteen records how king Rājendravarman presented Vīrendravikhyāta with a bronze Lokeśvara and a bronze Devī; that is, Vīrendravikhyāta received two images from the king. In the following stanza, however, Vīrendravikhyāta is recorded as having installed and consecrated two images of Avalokiteśa and a single Devī image; in other words, three images were installed. After this event, the final reference to the images comes from stanza sixteen which also indicates that there were three images to be cared for in association with Vīrendravikhyāta’s properties.

In editing the inscription, Coedès (*JC*, 6: 127, fn.2) remarked on the reference to the two donated images in stanza thirteen, and stressed that the inscription later referred to three images, not two. Coedès’ remarks imply that he felt there was some incongruity with the information being presented in the inscription. Similarly, Estève (2009: 392, fn. 256) has stated that Coedès’ translation of *avalokiteśaṃ rūpadvayaṃ . . . saha devīrūpaṃ* in stanza fourteen could mean “cette double image d’Avalokiteśa et celle de Devī,” and suggests that there were either three images, or that the reference

¹⁵ Skt. *saṃsthāpitāmarāṇāñ ca trayāṇāṃ snānakarmaṇe* (st. XVI) more literally translates as ‘and performing the bathing of the three established immortals.’

to two images was merely a reference to one Avalokiteśa image plus one Devī image for a total of two images, not two images of Avalokiteśa plus another image of Devī. Like Coedès, Estève's remarks imply that there may be some incongruity concerning the number of Buddhist images recorded in the inscription.

Taking into account the chronological events of the inscription, however, demonstrates that there is no contradicting information concerning the number of Buddhist images. In the beginning of the inscription, after having initially received his properties and having cultivated the land, stanza seven records how Vīrendravikhyāta then installed an image of Lokeśa for the benefit of the world. Later, in stanza thirteen, Vīrendravikhyāta receives another image of Lokeśvara, along with an image of Devī, from Rājendravarman for his loyal devotion. The reference to three images (two Avalokiteśa and one Devī) in the stanza fourteen—the stanza which documents the installation of these images in dedicated sanctuaries—refers to the original Lokeśa image previously mentioned in stanza seven, along with the new image of Avalokiteśvara and the Devī image later received as a gift from the king. Presumably when Vīrendravikhyāta returned to his properties, the original image of Lokeśa was rededicated during the event recorded in stanza fourteen along with the newly acquired images of Avalokiteśvara and Devī. This explains why stanza sixteen specifically indicates that three divinities were to be bathed daily using the water from the reservoir constructed by Vīrendravikhyāta.¹⁶ Because of the gift of the king, Vīrendravikhyāta's family now housed three Buddhist images on their property.

¹⁶ The alliteration involving repetition of final *-am*, and the repetition of components of three in the inscription's description of the reservoir's dimensions (e.g., the three times of the day, the number of daily ablutions, and the number divinities) is particularly nice.

Returning to Kavīndrārimathana, a few observations can be made. First, like Kavīndrārimathana himself, his family worshipped, and was involved in practices pertaining to, Avalokiteśvara and Prajñāpāramitā. Second, the primary role of the Buddhist divinities—according to the epigraphy—were to serve as tutelary deities concerned with the welfare of the land, and those people connected with that land. Third, Avalokiteśvara and Prajñāpāramita have a physical connection to the land in two primary ways: (1) they are physically housed in shrines erected on the land, and (2) they are ritually bathed with the very same reservoir water that nourishes the land. Finally, Kavīndrārimathana’s influence with the king appears to extend beyond mere individual influence in that both his wife and uncle-in-law also had connections with the royal household, and they were apparently looked upon favorably by Rājendravarman himself.

Kavīndrārimathana = Kavīndrācārya?

The Prasat Beng Inscription (K. 772)

The Prasat Beng inscription, edited in Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 104–05) consists of fifteen lines in Old Khmer followed by four lines of Sanskrit.¹⁷ The Khmer section is damaged in a few places. Most notably the first five lines are unreadable, and a small section of line thirteen is damaged. The four lines of Sanskrit are noteworthy for their Buddhist content, but unfortunately these four lines represent merely the beginning of what was originally intended to be a longer inscription. The fourth line of Sanskrit abruptly ends, leaving the inscription unfinished.

ṣadvyāmaśeṣasaṃyuktam triśatāyāmasaṃyuktam / trivṃyāmatrīśatārdhāṅkavistāram yat taṭākakam // triṣkāla bhūtasatvānām hitārthamakarodayam / saṃsthāpitāmarāṅāñ ca trayāṅām snānakarmmaṇe // (st. XV–XVI)

¹⁷ The site of the inscription is also known as Prasat Beng Tbong, a site south of Kampong Kdei.

The readable Khmer section of the inscription (lines 6–15) merely provides a list of the names of servants. The unfinished Sanskrit section records the name of a Buddhist named Kavīndrācārya, and begins by praising, through the use of a pun, his asceticism (Skt. *tapas*). The second *śloka*, which is unfinished, describes how Kavīndrācārya was possessed of, or ‘holding,’ the Perfection of Wisdom (Skt. *prajñāpāramitādhārī*) and the *vajra* (Skt. *vajrapāṇiḥ*), thus purposely drawing attention to his connection with Prajñāpāramitā and Vajrapāṇi. The fourth line begins by alluding to the worlds or universes (Skt. *lokaika*) of buddhas (Skt. *buddhānām*).¹⁸ The translation of the Sanskrit portion is as follows:

Venerated by venerables rich in austerities,¹⁹ Kavīndrācārya, although emaciated by (his own) austerities, was surely not emaciated by praiseworthy qualities. He was one who possessed the Perfection of Wisdom, held the *vajra*, controlled the senses [. . .] possessor of the *vajra*²⁰ [. . .] of buddhas of the universe [. . .]

(K. 772, Prasat Beng, st. I–II, lines 16–19)²¹

The inscription is undated, but Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 104) claimed that it seemed to adhere to characteristics of other tenth-century inscriptions. He noted, for example, the use of the geminate *r*, a characteristic of tenth-century inscriptions. This inscription,

¹⁸ Cœdès does not include the term *lokaikavuddhānām* in his translation. This was likely because the compound was part of the unfinished part of the inscription.

¹⁹ Skt. *tapodhanaiḥ* (masculine, instrumental, plural). This Sanskrit compound refers to practitioners skilled, or ‘rich in’ (*dhana*) religious austerities (*tapas*), and is used to refer to skilled and esteemed ascetics (Buddhist, Brahmanical, or otherwise). Such austere practices sometimes resulted in various kinds of bodily mortification, such as emaciation from fasting. This characteristic emaciation (*krśā*) of asceticism is employed to setup a contrasting pun indicating that Kavīndrācārya’s praiseworthy qualities were in no way lean, meager or ‘emaciated.’

²⁰ As indicated by Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 105, n. 1), the reading °*jīrī* (completing the possible Sanskrit word, *vajrī*) is unsure. An examination of a photographed copy of an EFEO estampage (n. 989) shed no additional light on the matter.

²¹ Skt. *mānyas tapodhanair mmānyaiḥ kavindrācāryya āsa yaḥ krśo pi tapasā ślāghyair guṇair evākrśo ma - // prajñāpāramitādhārī vajrapāṇir mmitendr[ī]ya[h] vajrī lokaikavuddhānām* [. . . unfinished], Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 105).

therefore, could either have come at the end of the reign of Yaśovarman, or early in the reign of Rājendravarman. I believe, however, that the Kavīndrācārya cited in K. 772 is none other than Rājendravarman's Buddhist minister Kavīndrārimathana. If true, this connection—along with Cœdès' paleographic observations—would strengthen the case for placing this inscription during the time of Rājendravarman in the mid- to late tenth century.

While no absolute proof can be provided, the fact that Kavīndrācārya and Kavīndrārimathana (1) chronology overlap, (2) are explicitly connected with Buddhist traditions, and (3) have similar names support my view. Beginning with the latter (and weaker) observation, one may easily notice that both names share the same beginning epithet of Kavīndra° (*kavi^indra*), 'king of poets.' This, in and of itself however, means very little; it is not enough to make a solid connection between the two figures. The epithet *kavīndra* is used for a few other individuals in the Cambodian epigraphical record, all of whom are clearly not the Kavīndrārimathana of the Bat Cum inscriptions, or the Kavīndrācārya of K. 772. Instead, they are simply different individuals who, among other things, were noted for their skill in poetry, grammar, knowledge of the epics, and so forth.²²

²² We know that epithets beginning with *kavīndra*° were sometimes bestowed upon diligent pupils who had mastered certain subjects such as grammar and poetry. For example, K. 661 (see Cœdès, *IC*, 1: 197–219) records how the grammar master Jayendrapaṇḍita (a servant of Sūryavarman I) upon promoting his pupil, Phalapriya, bestowed upon him the honorary name Kavīndrapaṇḍita, the same person responsible for composing the K. 661 inscription (e.g., refer to stanzas CVI–CXIX). Based on this brief biographical information, as well as the late date of Kavīndrapaṇḍita, this figure cannot be confused with the earlier Kavīndrārimathana.

Another example involves an individual named Pañcagavya who was a member of one of the important sacerdotal families of Anintidapura. According to K. 598 (Finot, 1928: 58–80), he was a servant of both Jayavarman V and later Suryavarman I. He was also known as Kavīndrapaṇḍita. As his name suggests, the inscription notes that he was skilled in such things as treatises, grammar, politics and religious matters, as well as being especially knowledgeable of the *Rāmāyaṇa* and *Mahābhārata*. He was followed by his son who was named Kavīndravijaya.

The close affinity of the names, therefore, is not enough to link these two figures. The connection to Buddhist traditions, as well as the temporal range of their activities, are much stronger reasons to suggest that these two individuals may be one and the same. Recall that one of the Bat Cum inscriptions specifically records Kavīndrārimathana as having erected an image of Lokanātha and two *devīs* at Kutīśvara; whereas another inscription records him erecting an image of the Buddha along with two *devīs*. Additionally, the Bat Cum inscriptions also emphasize devotion to both Prajñāpāramitā and Vajrapāṇi, in addition to Buddha and Lokeśvara. The emphasis on both Prajñāpāramitā and Vajrapāṇi in the opening sections of the Bat Cum inscriptions is comparatively rare when other tenth-century Cambodian inscriptions praising Buddhist divinities are taken into account. Besides praises to the Buddha, inscriptional homage to Lokeśvara is much more common. This fact makes Kavīndrācārya's recorded association with Prajñāpāramitā and Vajrapāṇi even more striking since it immediately bears some semblance to the emphasis of Prajñāpāramitā and Vajrapāṇi in the contemporary Bat Cum inscriptions that record the activities of Kavīndrārimathana.

It may be worthwhile to note that besides the K. 772 inscription itself, the site of Prasat Beng has produced additional collaborative evidence that indicates a tenth-century Buddhist presence in the area. Among the ruins at the site, one particular carved lintel was discovered that depicts the Buddha seated in meditation amid radiating floral bands. Martin Polkinghorne suggests that the lintel is probably from the mid-tenth century, probably sometime between 950 to 975 CE.²³ This would

²³ I am grateful to Martin Polkinghorne for taking the time to examine this lintel on my behalf, and for the information he provided me in a personal email correspondence on 6/8/2014. Although one must be

correspond to the time of the inscription. Fragmented Buddhist statuary, such as the heads of Buddhist figures like Lokeśvara, have also been discovered at this site; however, the majority of these items date to later centuries.²⁴

Phnom Banan (K. 202)

To my knowledge, this inscription has never been included in any discussions on Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia, but it was edited in Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 40–1).²⁵ This may be because the inscription is severely damaged. Only fragments of this inscription remain. The inscription is engraved in Old Khmer and consists of thirty-five lines on a door jamb of the southern shrine of Prasat Phnom Banan in Battambang. Aymonier (1900, 2: 290) observed that the inscription probably belonged to the ninth or tenth century, and that it represented a fragmented epigraphical record of a standard donation. Cœdès (*IC*, 7: 40 and 8: 109) suggested the tenth century Śaka (978–1077 CE), and believed that it was probably composed during the reign of Rājendravarman.

I believe Cœdès was right and that the inscription belongs to the tenth century, not the ninth. The inscription was probably recorded during the reign of Rājendravarman. Additionally, the inscription contains fragmented hints that the donation may have involved Buddhist images. The argument to support this hypothesis is as follows.

careful in dating due to artistic archaisms, according to Polkinghorne, support for a mid-tenth-century date can be found in the style of central foliage band, the ‘goose tail’ decorative motifs above the foliage, and the ‘vong hien’ shapes below. Other key indicators include the fleuron, ‘romyoul’ frieze, and the ‘chakachan’ flower at the top of the polylobe arch which surrounds the Buddha. For a detailed study on Khmer lintels, see Polkinghorne (2007). For more on terms such as ‘vong hein,’ ‘romyoul,’ and ‘chakachan’ refer specifically Polkinghorne (2007: 57).

For an image of the lintel, refer to EFEO archive photo 10808. I am unaware of this lintel appearing in any publication.

²⁴ For example, cf. EFEO archive photo 16232.

²⁵ The inscription was also discussed by Aymonier (1900, 2: 290). Neither scholar noted a possible Buddhist connection; although, Aymonier did note the possible connection (or at least the similarity) between Kavindrārimatha and Kavindrācārya.

First, one of the names recorded near the end of the inscription is Kavīndrācārya (line 22), the same name recorded in K. 772 discussed above. Aymonier (1900, 2: 290) observed that this name called to mind Rājendravarman's minister, Kāvīndrārimathana. As stated in my above discussion of K. 772, I believe Kavīndrācārya and Kāvīndrārimathana are one and the same. If so, it is likely the images involved in the donation mentioned in K. 202 were Buddhist, and this conclusion is based on Kavīndrārimathana's other documented Buddhist proclivities, as recorded in the Bat Cum inscriptions.

Second, K. 202 also contains a few fragmented words that may suggest the donation was Buddhist related. For example, the fragmented word '-keśvara' on line twenty-six has a strong chance of being a Buddhist-related term.²⁶ I would like to suggest that the fragmented word -keśvara is referring to the popular Buddhist bodhisattva Lokeśvara.²⁷ As will be demonstrated in chapter six, Lokeśvara experienced unprecedented attention in tenth-century Cambodia. References to Lokeśvara increased substantially in the tenth-century epigraphical record, as did images depicting the bodhisattva.

With regard to the possible reference to the bodhisattva in K. 202, the fact that the inscription also mentions Kavīndrācārya (i.e., line 22) strengthens this possibility. As discussed above, if one accepts the likelihood that Kavīndrācārya and Kāvīndrārimathana are merely alternative honorific addresses for the same person, then

²⁶ Although I should be clear in that this is merely speculation based upon indirect and circumstantial evidence. The condition of the inscription is so damaged that we will likely never know for sure.

²⁷ The name Lokeśvara is a compound of two phonetically assimilated Sanskrit words: *loka* ('world' or 'worlds') and *īśvara* ('lord'). Hence the name may be translated into English as 'Lord of the World' or 'Lord of Worlds.'

the suggestion that the fragmented ‘-keśvara’ recorded on line twenty-six refers to Lokeśvara becomes all the more compelling. Recall, for example, that one of the Bat Cum inscriptions record Kavīndrārimathna erecting an image of Lokanātha at Kutīśvara in Śaka 872 (950 CE). Additionally, an opening stanza in one of the Bat Cum inscriptions also praises Lokeśvara (K. 266, st. II). K. 772, while not referencing Lokeśvara, does include Buddhist content in that the same Kavīndrācārya is associated with both the Perfection of Wisdom (Skt. *Prajñāpāramitā*, line 18) and Vajrapāṇi (lines 18–19), thus further establishing his connection with Buddhist traditions. As K. 772 was likely composed during the tenth century, this would also make it contemporary with K. 202.

Another point to consider is other Old Khmer inscriptions in which the name of a deity, or other powerful being such as a bodhisattva, ends with *-keśvara*.²⁸ Again, K. 202 is an Old Khmer inscription, not Sanskrit. While there are certainly a number of examples of non-Buddhist divinities in the Old Khmer inscriptions that have names ending in *-keśvara* (especially relating to Śaivism), the only two Old Khmer inscriptions contemporary with K. 202 that record beings whose name end with *-keśvara* are both Buddhist inscriptions (K. 239 and K. 168). In these two inscriptions the names Jagannāthakeśvara and Lokeśvara are used to refer to Avalokiteśvara (or an indigenous divinity localized/assimilated with Avalokiteśvara). The inscription of Kok Samron (K. 239; Cœdès, *IC*, 3: 79–84) includes the date 888 Śaka (966 CE), while one of the Prasat Cikreng inscriptions (K. 168; Cœdès, *IC*, 2: 48–50) includes the date 894 Śaka (972 CE).

²⁸ Not merely *īśvara*, but (?)*ke* + *īśvara*.

To find an inscription composed in Old Khmer in which *-keśvara* was part of the name of a being not connected with localized Buddhist traditions, specifically localized forms of Avalokiteśvara, one would have to go back to at least 744 CE (over 200 years prior) in which Tilakeśvara is recorded in K. 1029. Or else one would have to go forward in the epigraphical record to the reign of Suryavarman I in the eleventh century where Nartakeśvara is recorded in K. 1198 (1009 CE, just over forty years from the end of Rājendravarman's reign). Granted, during the eighth century the references to names with *-keśvara* in the Old Khmer inscriptions were Śaivite related, but beginning around the mid-tenth century, and peaking during the twelfth and early thirteenth centuries during the reign of Jayavarman VII in which ancestor names were posthumously assimilated with Lokeśvara, more names ending with *-keśvara* were Buddhist related, and more often than not referred to Lokeśvara. Table 4-1 indicates all the names containing *-keśvara* from the Old Khmer epigraphical corpus that I found during my research.

Another fragmented word in K. 202 that may support the view that the inscription originally recorded Buddhist-related activities is the occurrence of '*-rmmāśrama*' on line four. According to Coedès (*IC*, 7: 40) line four begins with "[. . .]*rmmāśrama pi jvan vraḥ* [. . .]" Unfortunately, much of the preceding third line is ruined, as is the rest of line four following the word *vraḥ* ('divine/royal being or object'); therefore, the beginning part of the name for the *āśrama* ('hermitage') is unknown, and a meaningful translation of these lines cannot be provided.²⁹ All we know for sure is that something was 'offered

²⁹ The term *vraḥ* often acts as a headword preceding a noun phrase. For more on the term, consult DOK, *s.v.* *vraḥ*.

up' (OK. *jvan*) in connection with the hermitage know as '*-rmmāśrama*.' More than likely the line was recording a donation of some sort to the hermitage.

The fragmented word *-rmmāśrama* may be referring to a location called *dharmmāśrama* ('hermitage of Dharma'). The use of a geminate *m* in the Sanskrit word *dharma* is ubiquitous in Cambodian inscriptions, and it is difficult to propose a more satisfactory possibility for the preceding portion of *-rmma* other than the word [*dha*]*rmma*. In fact, an analysis of the Old Khmer epigraphical record indicates that '*-rmma/ā*' can only be one of four possible words, assuming that the unknown word in question is one that has occurred at least one time in the known Old Khmer epigraphical corpus. The four words are: 1) *dharmma*, 2) *karmma*, 3) °*varmma*, and 4) °*śarmma*.³⁰

The last two terms, °*varmma* and °*śarmma*, can be immediately discounted as possibilities. Both °*varmma* and °*śarmma* are primarily used in the Cambodian epigraphical record as the final constituent of names. The difference between the two being that °*varmma* was, ideally, reserved for the names of rulers and other *kṣatriya* (e.g., *rājendravarmma*, *indravarmma*, etc.), while *śarmma*, again ideally, was reserved for *brahmaṇa*. Of course Cambodian social hierarchy and ranking does not conform neatly to an Indic model of *kṣatriyas* and *brahmaṇas*; nevertheless, both °*varmma* and °*śarmma* are almost always used in the Cambodian epigraphical record as final constituent of personal names.³¹

³⁰ Of course, due to the condition of the inscription, it is impossible to determine if the word *āśrama* was only compounded with one word (e.g., just *-rmma*°) or more than one preceding word (say, *vidyādharmmāśrama*, for example). Regardless, the word immediately preceding *āśrama* can only be one of the four possibilities mentioned since the combination of the characters '*rmma*' only occur in the Old Khmer epigraphical record in those four words.

³¹ Occasionally °*śarmma* was used as the final constituent of a toponym (DOK, s.v. °*śarmma*).

Of the remaining two terms, *dharmmāśrama* appears to be the better possibility since *karmāśrama* ('action hermitage' or 'hermitage of action') sounds more unlikely given the alternative possibility of *dharmmāśrama*. Of course either term would further support the position that K. 202 originally recorded Buddhist-related activities (in this case, a donation to a Buddhist *āśrama*). Although this speculation is weakened by the fact that there is no known occurrence of the term *dharmmāśrama* in the Cambodian epigraphical record (nor, of course, is the term *dharma* exclusively used within Buddhist traditions); nevertheless, the possibility remains intriguing, and not completely beyond the realm of possibility when one considers the other observations concerning this inscription made previously. Those observations are: (1) the recorded reference to Kavīndrācārya, (2) the likely tenth-century date of the inscription, (3) the strong possibility that *-keśvara* may refer to Lokeśvara, and (4) the limited possibilities for *-rma*^o on line four of the inscription.

A fifth factor to consider pertains to archaeological material discovered at the site of Phnom Banan. Archaeological evidence demonstrates that practicing Buddhist communities have operated in the area of Phnom Banan for many centuries. The earliest Buddhist images coming from this area are of bronzes dating between seventh to eighth centuries. For example, a late seventh to early eighth century black bronze of the Buddha (unfortunately now headless) was discovered at Phnom Banan.³² Another

³² Many of the most important Buddhist bronzes come from the region of Battambang, a likely testament to the flourishing of Buddhist traditions in this region. The bronze Buddha at Banan noted above is now located in the Phnom Penh National Museum and has appeared in a number of publications. For example, see Groslier (1925: 308 and pl. 30-B); Giteau (1965: 124, 127 pl. XII); Rawson *et al.* (1995: 498 fig. 436); Dalsheimer (2001: 231); and more recently Bunker and Latchford (2011: 53 fig. 4.4 and 64).

There are many additional Buddhist pre-Angkorian Buddhist bronzes coming from the regions of Battambang and Siem Reap, especially of Lokeśvara. For example, there are several Lokeśvara bronzes

pre-Angkorian image of a standing Buddha was also discovered at the site, although this figure has not received the same attention as the previously mentioned bronze Buddha.³³ There are also later Buddhist images from the site of Phnom Banan, such as the fragmented remains of a twelfth-century stone image of the Buddha seated on a *nāga*, as well as another well-preserved image of a seated Buddha.³⁴ While I am unaware of any tenth-century Buddhist images being discovered at Phnom Banan, the various Buddhist images discovered in the area from both before and after this period—as well as K. 202 itself—suggests that Buddhist communities operated successfully in the region since at least the late seventh century. The claim, therefore, that the K. 202 inscription may record the donative activities of a Buddhist *ācārya* in this region does not seem out of place or unlikely; instead, it represents yet another piece of data attesting to prevalence of Buddhist traditions during this time.

Based on all of the above observations, I tentatively conclude that K. 202 should be included in any discussion concerning Buddhist traditions in Cambodia during the tenth century. Taken as a whole, the data suggests that the inscription records the activities of a Buddhist dignitary, Kavīndrācārya, which quite likely was another name for Kāvīndrārimathana. Furthermore, closer examination of the inscription along with

coming from the site of Ak Yom; see Giteau (1965: 129, 133 pl. XIV) and Dalsheimer (2001: 234–35) for a few examples.

³³ See EFEO archive photo 02894. I have been unable to locate any publications that provide details on this particular image. Based on the photograph, this piece probably dates between the seventh and eighth centuries. Unlike the previously mentioned black bronze from Phnom Banan which depicts the Buddha with the robe worn in the open mode (i.e., the robe only covers one shoulder), this particular piece has the robe covering both shoulders. The left hand is making the *kaṭakahasta mudrā* and the right hand is making the *vitarka mudrā*. The piece shares strong similarities with other pre-Angkorian standing Buddha images; for example, cf. Bunker and Latchford (2011: 68–70 figs. 4.14a/b, 4.15 and 4.16).

³⁴ For an image of the fragmented Bayon-style Buddha seated on a *nāga*, see Giteau (1965: 84 pl. 43). For the other seated Buddha, which looks to be an earlier Angkorian style, consult the EFEO archive photo 02898. I have found no publications discussing this latter piece.

contextual comparisons to other contemporary Old Khmer inscriptions suggests that the –keśvara recorded in the inscription is a reference to an image of Lokeśvara, thus providing additional information on the activities of Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia.

Table 4-1. Old Khmer Inscriptions Containing -keśvara

Inscription	Name Ending in <i>-keśvara</i>	Common Era Date(s)
K. 648 (I.3)	‘amvimuktakeśvara	578–677
K. 664 (I.1-2)	Tilakeśvara	578–677
K. 8 (I.1)	‘āmṛātakeśvara	578–677
K. 1028B (1.5)	‘aṃmrātakeśvara	614
K. 1004 (I.3)	‘amrātakeśvara	691
K. 904 (A.18, A.28, B.13, B.26)	Tripurāntakeśvara	713
K. 668 (I.3)	Kadamvakeśvara	719
K. 1029 (I.1)	Tilakeśvara	744
K. 239 (S.22)	Jagannāthakeśvara	966
K. 168 (I.3, 10, 13)	Lokeśvara	972
K. 202 (I.26)	-keśvara	978–1077 (10th c. Śaka)
K. 240S-2 (I.7)	Lokeśvara	979
K. 158 (C2)	Lokeśvara	1003
K. 1198 AC (A2, A36, CC141)	Nartakeśvara	1009
K. 230 (C15)	Lokeśvara	1026
K. 276 (I.7)	Nātakeśvara	978–1077; likely post 1037* (10th c. Śaka)
K. 274 (C1)	hṛṣīkeśvara	1178–1277
K. 462 (L3)	Samaradivyalokeśvara	1178–1277
K. 461 (I.1)	Raṇadivyalokeśvara	1178–1277
K. 907 (N1)	Paranadivyalokeśvara	1178–1277
K. 907 (Q2)	Ratnalokeśvara	1178–1277
K. 914 (B1)	Sarvalokeśvara	1178–1277
K. 920 (A1)	Mahādivyalokeśvara	1178–1277

Table 1.1 Note.— Information pertaining to the Old Khmer inscriptions was acquired from Cœdès (IC, 1–8) and Jenner, *Manual of pre-Angkorian Khmer with Grammatical Notes*. Philip Jenner’s *Manual of pre-Angkorian Khmer with Grammatical Notes* is maintained online through SEAClassics (a subdivision of SEALang) at <http://sealang.net/classic/khmer/manual/>.

* The date range for K. 276 is a general tenth-century Śaka range provided by Jenner (i.e., 978–1077); however, Cœdès (IC, 4: 153) stated that this inscription must be dated after 959 Śaka (1037 CE), thereby placing the inscription in the reign of Sūryavarman. The inclusion of Sūryavarman’s guru, Yogīśvarapaṇḍita, in the inscription appears to support this claim.

CHAPTER 5

KĪRTIPAṄḌITA: WHO WAS HE, WHERE WAS HE FROM, AND WHERE DID HE GO?

Writing with regard to the reign of Jayavarman V (c. 968–1000/01), L. P. Briggs (1951: 135) once noted that, “There is probably no reign in the history of the ancient Khmers in which more distinguished ministers, scholars, and dignitaries are mentioned in the inscriptions.” One such dignitary was the *ācārya* Kīrtipaṅḍita eulogized in the tenth-century Vat Sithor inscription. This section explores the question of who Kīrtipaṅḍita was according to this tenth-century inscription. In the course of this exploration, I will also make some tentative claims regarding the possible whereabouts of Kīrtipaṅḍita’s travels which are alluded to in the Vat Sithor inscription, as well as some observations concerning his homeland.

All of the information regarding Kīrtipaṅḍita comes from the tenth-century Vat Sithor inscription. No other sources have yet been discovered that would yield additional information on this important figure. As outlined in the introduction, the discovery site of the inscription is in the vicinity of the modern Buddhist Wat of Sithor, which is located in present-day Kandal province. Situated about two kilometers (just over one mile) west of the Tonle Toch River, this site is located in the heart of a riverine network which likely facilitated communications and trade during the tenth-century, as well as earlier and later periods.

Like the Buddhist Kavindrārimathana before him who was active during much of Rājendravarman’s reign, Kīrtipaṅḍita was responsible for part of the building regime during the reign of both Rājendravarman and especially his son Jayavarman V.¹ Whether Kīrtipaṅḍita held a specific titled position with official privileges and

¹ Stanza XLIX clearly establishes that Kīrtipaṅḍita was also active during Rājendravarman’s reign.

responsibilities associated with his constructions and undertakings is unknown; however, the conclusion that he played an important role during these administrations is supported by the evidence. According to the Vat Sithor inscription he erected and consecrated new images of the Buddha and bodhisattvas, and repaired Buddhist images that had been damaged or neglected. The founding and repair of these images often coincided with the construction of temples (*prāsāda*), gates (*dvāra*), hermitages (*āśrama*), and ponds or reservoirs (*jalāsaya*). Furthermore, Kīrtipaṇḍita was also responsible for performing special rites within the palace that were believed to ensure the pacification and prosperity of the kingdom.² The inscription, however, does employ a number of descriptive titles for Kīrtipaṇḍita, both honorific as well as functional. In addition to being described as an *upāntacara* ('close agent' or 'close emissary') and *vidvān* ('learned'), Kīrtipaṇḍita is also called an *ācārya*.³ Stanza XIX, for example, states:

His (Jayavarman V's) trusted emissary was the *ācārya* Kīrtipaṇḍita, a learned man who had crossed over the ocean of knowledge, and whose fame spread like the light of the full moon.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor Inscription, st. XIX)⁴

² Refer to stanzas XXXVI–XLIX of the Vat Sithor inscription in chapter two for all these activities.

³ With regard to the term *upāntacara*, Kīrtipaṇḍita was, in other words, a trusted emissary first in the service of the ruler Rājendravarman, and later his son Jayavarman V.

⁴ Skt. *tasyopāntacaro vidvān vidyāmbhonidhipāragah / ākīrṇakīrttipūrṇendur ācāryah kīrtipaṇḍitah* // Coedès (*IC*, 6: 198). My translation of *ākīrṇakīrttipūrṇenduḥ* is, like Coedès' own French translation, a bit loose in order to convey what I feel is the intended meaning of the compound in the English language. More literally (and blandly) the qualifying compound could be translated as 'a full moon of overspreading fame.' However, it seems clear that what is being conveyed is that Kīrtipaṇḍita's fame was full like the moon when it is full; in other words, his fame covered, or spread throughout, the land like the light of the full moon. Lastly, it should be noted that the verse evokes the literal meaning of Kīrtipaṇḍita's name, which may be literally translated as the 'renowned (*kīrti*) learned man (*paṇḍita*).'

The Sanskrit title *ācārya* affixed to the names of learned men is often translated into English simply as ‘teacher’ or ‘master.’ More literally, it may be translated as one who ‘proceeds toward proper conduct and/or practice.’ The title sometimes refers to individuals who know and teach the *ācāra*; that is, a body of regulatory knowledge concerning proper conduct and behavior, practices, and other established precepts. As such, in many cases the term simply refers to a learned individual who provides instruction to others in, or with, proper conduct; the definition of such conduct varies depending on the particular tradition.

Giving that the term *ācārya* is (1) often used merely as a prestigious honorific for an esteemed instructor and (2) has multiple meanings across various Buddhist traditions even when the term does denote something more than a mere honorific title, it remains exceedingly difficult to ascertain any kind of specific information pertaining this particular title for Kīrtipaṇḍita that would not be entirely speculative. The Vat Sithor inscription, however, is concerned foremost with the establishment of a Buddhist monastery and select regulations pertaining to that monastery. Furthermore, the inscription indicates that after traveling abroad for various Buddhist texts and establishing the monastery Kīrtipaṇḍita settled down at the monastery to live; he was obviously a very important individual at the monastery. Scholars should not gloss over the stanza in the Vat Sithor inscription that states:

Thus, having completed the command of the Omniscient One with his heart set on devotion, by founding a monastery according to the proper rule, the learned one (Kīrtipaṇḍita) settled (there) from afar.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor Inscription, st. LXV)⁵

⁵ Skt. *sarvvajñavākyam evan tat kṛtvā manasi bhaktitaḥ / vidvān utpādyā vidhivad vihāraṃ dūratas sthitaḥ* //, Cœdès (IC, 6: 200).

Although not explicit, establishing himself permanently at the newly constructed monastery suggests that Kīrtipaṇḍita was an actual Buddhist monk, and not just merely an important individual who promoted the teachings of the Buddha during the reign of Jayavarman V. In other words, it is typically a monk who establishes or settles himself (Skt. *sthitaḥ*) at a monastery (Skt. *vihāram*). Other stanzas that indicate Kīrtipaṇḍita had a number of disciples further support this observation, as does the title of *ācārya* since this title can specifically refer to a teacher of Buddhist novices in Buddhist monastic textual sources.⁶ Furthermore, the inscription describes Kīrtipaṇḍita as giving lectures on the Dharma to kings seated in a position of respect and honor atop a Dharma pedestal or throne.

He was appointed *guru* by delighted kings and their ladies of the inner chambers, and he constantly taught the Buddha Dharma seated upon the Dharma-pedestal.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXXII)⁷

Giving these facts, it is not unreasonable to suggest that the title *ācārya*, in this particular context, would have been understood and employed according to guidelines and regulations pertaining to Buddhist monastic life; in other words, in this particular context the term may have been understood from the perspective of the Buddhist *vinaya*, the collection of texts pertaining to monastic regulations, codes of behavior and discipline.

⁶ For explicit references to Kīrtipaṇḍita having disciples, see stanzas XXXI and XVII of the Vat Sithor inscription in chapter two of this dissertation.

⁷ Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 285) takes the word *rājabiḥ* (masculine instrumental plural) in the stanza to be the plural of respect (*ādare bahuvacanam*). He may very well be right; however, I would like to note that the verse appears in a section outlining Kīrtipaṇḍita's numerous activities, some of which involved traveling. Therefore, it is not improbable to interpret the verse in a manner suggesting that Kīrtipaṇḍita provided instruction for the rulers of several regions of early Cambodia. Skt. *sāntaḥpuraiḥ pramuditai rājabhir yyo gurūkr̥taḥ / dideśa vahuśo dharmam vauddam dharmmāsane sthitaḥ II*, Cœdès (IC, 6: 198).

If the theory that the many of the Buddhists in Cambodia of this period probably followed the the Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya is correct, then it may be useful to note how Mūlasarvāstivādin monks would have understood and employed the term *ācārya*.⁸ The *Pravrajyāvastu* of the Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya devotes a fair amount of space defining a Buddhist *ācārya*, primarily in terms of an *ācārya*'s role in monastic ordination and training. The *Pravrajyāvastu* contains a narrative on how the Buddhist monastic community was being ridiculed and disparaged by various competing non-Buddhist groups (Skt. *tīrthika*) because they did not have either *upādhyāyas* or *ācāryas*.⁹

Because of this, the monks did not know how to properly conduct themselves in the

⁸ Snellgrove (2001: 819). While I do not agree with all of Snellgrove's conclusions pertaining to Buddhist traditions in Cambodia during the tenth century, in this matter I agree that the *vinaya* of the Mūlasarvāstivādin tradition is the most likely candidate (although Snellgrove provides no explicit support for his position).

I, however, have found some possible support for adherence to the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* in my own research. For example, the technical term *brahmapuṇya* and its contextual usage in stanza LXI of the Vat Sithor inscription conforms exactly to its usage in the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya*. See my own notes on stanza LXI in chapter two of this dissertation. Unfortunately there exists no complete English translation of the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* from the complete Tibetan sources or the surviving Sanskrit sources. For an overview of the structure of the *Mūlasarvastivādin-vinaya*, see Prebish (1994). Prebish (1975) contains an English translation of the Mūlasarvāstivādin *Prātimokṣa sūtra*. Banerjee (1957) provides a suitable English summary of the contents of the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* based on Tibetan sources, but readers are cautioned because Banerjee's interpretations and translations of certain terms and concepts are sometimes misleading, and at times simply wrong. For extensive discussions on Buddhist monasticism and the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* readers should refer to Schopen (1997, 2004 and 2005) for important work in this field, as well as more comprehensive bibliographies.

⁹ For an English summary and reference to primary source material, see Banerjee (1957: 105–06). Here the Sanskrit title *upādhyāya* refers to a kind of authoritative and learned preceptor who provides novice monks instruction and guidance in monastic life. Both the *upādhyāya* and the *ācārya* are essentially 'teachers' or 'preceptors.' Usually, the relationship with the *upādhyāya* is a close one-on-one relationship. The distinction between the *upādhyāya* and *ācārya* and their relationship with a pupil is often blurred in sources since many of their instructional duties toward the novice are exactly the same. Sometimes the *upādhyāya* is distinguished from the *ācārya* in that the *upādhyāya* is a preceptor that shares the same monastic cell as the novice; furthermore, the *upādhyāya* is often given more prominent status in *vinaya* sources. For more on the distinction between the *upādhyāya* and *ācārya*, see Davids and Oldenberg (1881–85, 1: 178 n. 2). The narrative pertaining to the lack of *upādhyāyas* and *ācāryas* is not confined to the *vinaya* tradition of the Mūlasarvāstivādins. Similar narratives that discuss the communities lack of proper *upādhyāyas* (P. *upajjāya*) and *ācāryas* (P. *ācariya*), as well as their respective duties, occur in the in the *Mahāvagga* (I.25; I.32) of the Therāvādins. See Oldenberg (1879–83, 1: 44–50, 60–61). For an English translation, see Horner (1939–66, 4: 58–67, 78–79).

presence of other groups in society, especially when out collecting alms. Without proper instruction and guidance from *upādhyāyas* and *ācāryas*, the monks were often rude, noisy, and guilty of many transgressions. The Buddha, therefore, is said to have trained the monks on the proper roles of *upādhyāyas* and *ācāryas* within the Buddhist community. In the most basic sense then, the *upādhyāyas* and *ācāryas* were established to be the teachers for novices (Skt. *śrāmaṇera*).

In what follows the narrative, the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya* explains that there are five kinds of *ācārya* operating within the Buddhist monastic community. First, there is the *ācārya* of the *śrāmaṇera* ('novice').¹⁰ Second, there is the *ācārya* who interrogates the prospective novice in private during the ordination ceremony.¹¹ Third, there is the *ācārya* who is in charge of guiding community work, formal events, and actions; the individual who is usually entrusted with making formal public announcements and guiding the community through formal public proceedings. Fourth, there is the *ācārya* responsible for providing *nissaya* to his pupils.¹² Finally, there is the *ācārya* who

¹⁰ In this context *śrāmaṇera* are essentially novices who have only undertaken the Pravrajyā ordination; hence, the *ācārya* of this type (as the *Mūlasarvāstivādin Pravrajāvastu* indicates) are ones responsible for giving the *trīśaraṇa* (triple refuge formula) and ten precepts to novices wishing to join the Buddhist community. For additional comments and summaries, see Banerjee (1957: 107).

¹¹ Here is a perfect example as to why one should exercise caution in using Banerjee (1957) for a summary of the *Mūlasarvāstivāda-vinaya*. His translation of *rahoṇuśāsaka bhikṣu* as the monk who 'trains in the esoteric doctrine' is completely misleading and inaccurate with regard to the actual function of this particular *ācārya bhikṣu*. At one part in the ordination, this *ācārya* is responsible for taking the prospective novice aside in private (i.e., in 'secret') in order to ask a series of questions that determine if the individual is qualified to join the monastic community. Example questions include, "Are you a man?", "Are you at least 20 years of age?", and so forth. A better English translation is 'one who instructs in private;' in other words, a monk who instructs a prospective novice in private on the qualifications for joining the monastic community. For clarification of this term, as well as a good summary of the ordination process, see Sangharakshita (1998: 184–85).

¹² Basically this means entering into a relationship that places the pupil's livelihood, instruction and guidance in the hands of the *ācārya*. In other words, *nissaya* is the formal act of becoming dependent on the *ācārya*.

provides instruction in recitation and reading.¹³ What we essentially have with these respective types of *ācārya* are specialized monks each with particular roles designed to properly intergrate an individual into the monastic community with proper forms of instruction and rites.¹⁴

Given Kīrtipaṇḍita's emphasis on expanding the Buddhist dharma and his explicit connection with the monastery at Vat Sithor, he was almost certainly an *ācārya* renowned for instructing and training both monks and potential monks (i.e., active in proselytizing). Although based on passages from the Vat Sithor inscription it would seem that Kīrtipaṇḍita would have been an *ācārya* monk of the fourth or fifth type, this observation is really nothing more than an educated hunch. The important point to take away is that Buddhist monastic traditions understand an *ācārya* (again, a 'teacher') in a manner that pertains to monastic instruction and training, not merely a teacher of the laity or one who is particularly learned.¹⁵ While Kīrtipaṇḍita is certainly extolled in the inscription for teaching kings and other lay persons, it has been overlooked that the title of *ācārya* in this particular context likely means he played a very important role as a

¹³ For a summary and general description of these types, see Banerjee (1957: 106–7).

¹⁴ One should also note that five is also the minimum number of monks needed to ordain new individuals into the Buddhist monastic community (although there are exceptions).

¹⁵ Although I will stress again that the term *ācārya*, even within Buddhist traditions, has been used and understood in various ways. For example, chapter eighteen of the *Samvarodaya Tantra* defines *ācārya* as: "now, I will explain (the characteristics of the *ācārya* and other things). (A man described as follows) is considered to be a *vajrācārya*: a man who has subdued (his passions), whose appearance is tranquil, who gives safety to all living beings (1), who knows the practice of *mantras* and *tantras*, who is compassionate and who is learned in treatises, who talks sweetly to everybody, who treats all living beings as his own son (2), who always takes pleasure in almsgiving and is engaged in *yoga* and *dhyāna*-meditation, who speaks the truth, who does not injure living beings, and whose mind is compassionate and intent upon benefiting others (3). Sameness (*samatā*) is the emblem (*mudrā*) of his mind; he is the protector of living beings; he knows the various intentions of living beings and is (regarded as) the kinsman by those who have no protector (4). His body is complete as to the sense-organs; he is beautiful and is agreeable to see. He knows the true meaning of consecration (*abhiṣeka*). His speech is clear; he is an ocean of merits (5); (and) he always and continuously resorts to *pīṭha*: he is called an *ācārya* (teacher); The *Samvarodaya Tantra*, XVIII.1–12; trans. Tsuda (1974: 294).

monk within the Buddhist monastic community; a particularly successful and learned monk with authority not only to provide guidance and instruction, but also as a monk whose status would have allowed him to serve as one of the required number of official monks for ordination ceremonies.

As for other descriptive titles, the Vat Sithor inscription also indicates that Kīrtipaṇḍita was appointed as a *guru* (again, ‘teacher;’ literally one who is ‘heavy’ with knowledge) by a number of unnamed kings (or *the* king) and was responsible for propagating the Buddha’s dharma (st. XXXII).

Once again the inscription demonstrates that Kīrtipaṇḍita was an active teacher and proselytizer. Furthermore, his esteem was great enough to warrant regular invitations to teach the Buddha’s dharma to society’s elite. This verse is also interesting in that it suggests that Kīrtipaṇḍita’s teaching activities included not only male members of the ruling administration, but females as well.¹⁶ Besides the title of *ācārya*,

¹⁶ Briggs (1951: 135) has highlighted the relatively high social and political position held by women during the reign of Jayavarman V, and this verse perhaps indicates one more example of women—or more accurately women of note and privilege—having had access to some of the societal privileges of ranking men (e.g., receiving teachings and instructions from a learned man).

Brigg’s observations concerning women during this period, however, must be kept in context. His observations should not be over generalized by including all women of the time as if there existed some sort of widespread gender equality. His examples all include women coming from positions of privilege and power (as is, of course, to be expected since epigraphical records in Cambodia were typically composed by, and for, the elite social stratum). A woman named Prāṇā, for example, was appointed in charge of Jayavarman V’s confidential scribes; but it should be noted that she came from the powerful, sacerdotal family of Saptadevakula, being the niece of Manaśśiva. Manaśśiva bestowed her as queen to king Rājendravarman, Jayavarman V’s father. Thus, Prāṇā’s privileged position during Jayavarman V’s reign had as much to do with her praiseworthy conduct and skill as much as it had to do with her esteemed lineage and the fact that she was one of his father’s queens.

K. 136, A. st. 24 (Barth, 1885: 129), indicates Prāṇā’s important position during the reign of Jayavarman V. Skt. *śiṣṭānvayācāraguṇā mṛte rājendrammaṇi / sāpy abhyantaralekhinām* (read as °*lekhinām*) *adhipā jayavarmmaṇaḥ* // . “Virtuous, (versed in) proper conduct and coming from a learned family, when Rājendravarman had died, she was head of Jayavarman’s confidential scribes.” For more on *abhyantaralekhī* (?) and the emended reading due to metrical reasons, see Barth (1885: 135–36, n. 7).

K. 136, A. v.22, records how Manaśśiva granted (*vyadhāt*) Prāṇā to Rājendravarman. Skt. *yo vallabho bhāgineyīm rājño rājendravarmanṇaḥ / rūpācārābhīrāmāṅgīm* (read as *rūpācārābhīr°*) *prāṇākhayām*

upāntacara, *guru*, and other general epithets highlighting his learned qualities

Kīrtipaṇḍita is not documented in the inscription as having any other official title or position.¹⁷

Kīrtipaṇḍita's Homeland

Stanza forty-six of the Vat Sithor inscription describes how Kīrtipaṇḍita, along with his disciples, traveled about the land erecting images of Lokeśa and other unnamed Buddhist figures. Two of the towns (Skt. *pura*) mentioned specifically are Kumārambha and Amarendra. The stanza referencing these towns, however, contains an additional important piece of historical information in that the town of Kumārambha is specified as Kīrtipaṇḍita's homeland (*svapura*, lit. his 'own town').¹⁸

svāminīm vyadhāt // . "He (Manaśśiva), beloved above all by King Rājendravarman, granted as queen (*svāminī*) his sister's daughter known as Prāṇā, who was beautiful, virtuous, pleasing, and delicate." Note that I am using the word 'queen' very loosely as it is unclear the exact relationship being expressed by the Sanskrit term *svāminī* in this societal context. In Sanskrit, *svāminī* can refer to a mistress or an important lady, as well as a queen. The term does, however, denote a sense of favoritism. As Barth (1885: 135, n. 4) noted, the verse is clear that Prāṇā was donated or granted (*vyadhāt*), but the verse does not indicate that she was 'married' to the king. She may, therefore, have been one among several important and esteemed ladies in Rājendravarman's household.

¹⁷ In his dissertation Peter Sharrock (2006: 12) referred to Kīrtipaṇḍita as a "Buddhist purohita," but this title is never explicitly applied to Kīrtipaṇḍita in the inscription. Although Sharrock does not provide a citation for his claim, it seems his reason for indicating that Kīrtipaṇḍita was a *purohita* ('sacerdotal minister') derive from his conclusions concerning stanza sixty-nine of the Vat Sithor inscription. The Sanskrit reads: *hṛmmudrāmantravidyāsu homakarmaṇi kovidaḥ / bajraghaṇṭārahasyajño dakṣiṇīyaḥ purohitaḥ* //, Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 200). This transliteration incorporates Cœdès' correction of °*mūdra*° to °*mudrā*°. I translate the verse as follows: "The purohita who is learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, vidyā, mantra, mudrā and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the vajra and the bell (ghaṇṭā), is worthy of donations." My translation follows the interpretation in Sanderson (2004: 427) which understands 'hṛd' as an abbreviated reference to the use of heart syllables. For an in-depth examination of the technical terms in this stanza, see my remarks on the translation in chapter two. Sharrock (2006: 27) cites this stanza to support his claim that Kīrtipaṇḍita was an expert in the employment of *mantra*, *mudrā*, and—by related extension—*maṇḍala*. Sharrock, therefore, appears to connect Kīrtipaṇḍita with being one of several such *purohita* worthy of donations described in the above stanza since he is assumed to be learned in the same set of skills. Although concluding that Kīrtipaṇḍita did possess such skills based on the inscription as a whole is very reasonable (in fact, probable) this particular verse never mentions Kīrtipaṇḍita, and it is not so concerned with him specifically as it is with redefining the role of a true *purohita* in the context of Buddhism. See chapter seven for remarks on the use of this term in this inscription.

¹⁸ Like Kumārambha and mountain/hill top (*tuṅgādri*), *svapura* is cited in the locative singular case (*svapure*).

On a mountain top in his own town (svapura) called Kumārambha, as well as in towns such as Amarendra, he erected (images of) Lokeśa and others.

(The Vat Sithor Inscription, st. XLVI)¹⁹

Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 207) translated the verse as follows:

Sur une colline élevée, dans sa ville nommée Kumārambha, à Amarendrapura et autres lieux, il érigea des images de Lokeça, etc.²⁰

Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 207, n. 2) accounts for *svapura* in his translation ('sa ville'), and provides a footnote citing other occurrences of Kumārambha in the epigraphical record (a point which will be returned to below).²¹

Scholarship written in English has either ignored or overlooked this detail, perhaps because when relaying primarily on the French translation 'sa ville' can be translated as 'his town' or 'the town.' For example, Snellgrove (2001: 808), who provided English translations for a few sections of the inscription in an article on the relationship between Buddhism and Brahmanism in early Cambodia, completely overlooked *svapura* and translated the verse as:

On a high summit in the town of Kurārambha [*sic.*], also at Amarendrapura and other places, he set up images of Avalokiteśvara and so on.²²

¹⁹ Skt. *tuṅgādrau svapure khyāte kumārambhapure pi yaḥ / amarendrapurādyeṣu lokeśādīn atīṣṭhipat //* Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 199).

²⁰ "On a high hill, in his town called Kumārambha, at Amarendrapura and other places, he erected some images of Lokeśa, etc."

²¹ I am assuming that by 'sa ville' Cœdès meant 'his town,' and not simply 'the town.' To interpret the French otherwise means that Cœdès completely ignored *svapura*.

²² Snellgrove's oversight may be the result of overly relying on Cœdès' French translation in order to render the inscription into English instead undertaking the time-consuming task of consulting the Sanskrit directly for every verse he wished to discuss. This observations comes about because other than being in English, Snellgrove's select translations of the inscription are virtually identical to Cœdès' French translation. This is not be taken as an attack on Snellgrove's work since it is understandable to refer to existing translations of epigraphical material. However, the over-reliance on Cœdès' French translation also leads to more problematic interpretations concerning purported tensions between Brahmanical groups and Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia, an issue that will be explored in chapter seven.

Where is Kumārambha? As mentioned above, Coédès cited other occurrences of Kumārambha in a brief footnote. He noted that the term appears in the epigraphical record as both a personal appellation and as a physical location. The use of Kumārambha as a personal appellation is not of concern since what is at issue is a location. Additionally, the use of Kumārambha as a personal appellation dates from the eighth century, and thus is situated in a context two centuries earlier.²³ The other two inscriptions are Prasat Krâchap (K. 183) and Prasat Svay Prahm (K. 848), both tenth-century inscriptions.²⁴ Both make brief reference to a region or country (OK. *sruk*) called Kumārambha. Unfortunately, neither inscription is very helpful in determining the exact location of Kumārambha.

K. 183 is a badly damaged Old Khmer inscription which contains the lists of names of servants grouped by country. The inscription is dedicated to Tribhuvanadeva, and the pillar was erected by Jayavarman IV (c.928 –c.941). Kumārambha is one of many countries listed in the inscription. No other details regarding Kumārambha are provided by the inscription.

K. 848 provides a little more information. This inscription is also in Old Khmer, and partly ruined. The inscription opens with a royal order issued by the king. The inscription is damaged where the king's name is engraved, but the opening date of 969 CE corresponds the date of Jayavarman V according to Coédès (*IC* 1: 187, fn. 3). The content of the royal order is also damaged, but enough is legible to ascertain that the order involved how much husked rice was to be collected from the locality of

²³ The inscription is K. 3. See Coédès (1936: 7–9).

²⁴ K. 183, also known as Prasat Rahal, opens with the date 850 Śaka (928 CE). K. 848, also known as Kôk Svay Pream, opens with the date 891 Śaka (969 CE). For both inscriptions, see Coédès (*IC* 1: 52–54 and 187–188, respectively).

Kumārambha as income of the land. The king's trusted servant, Vāp Brahma, was to ensure that the royal order was known to elders and other notable persons in Hariharālaya, an area about eighteen kilometers southeast from the present-day city of Siem Reap.²⁵ Unfortunately, sections of the inscription which may have provided additional details are damaged before and after the mention of Kumārambha; nevertheless, a few conclusions may be drawn concerning the location of Kumārambha that have not been previously made.

As the rice offerings were mentioned in conjunction with the land income (Skt. *bhūmyākara*) of the locality of Kumārambha, which, in turn, were directly connected with notable persons (Skt. *puruṣapradhāna*) in Hariharālaya, and Hariharālaya was the site where the pillar announcing this order was erected, it seems probable to conclude that Kumārambha was within a reasonable distance of the former capital in order to deliver the required rice in a timely manner.²⁶ The order would have also been erected at a location where it would have been accessible to those individuals subject to its mandate. In other words, an order likely would not have been established an extreme distance from those to whom it would have concerned. Another reason to believe the location of Kumārambha was in the close vicinity of Hariharālaya is because the inscription explicitly indicates that a *liḥ* of husked rice was to be offered daily (Skt.

²⁵ Hariharālaya is associated with the so-called Rolous group which includes temples like Preah Ko, Bakong and Lolei. It represents an area located eighteen kilometers (eleven miles) southeast of the city of Siem Reap.

²⁶ This is assuming that the husked rice was to be delivered to the former capital of Hariharālaya. It should be noted that this is not explicit in the inscription.

pratidina).²⁷ If this land revenue was to be offered daily, then Kumārambha could not have been far from Hariharālaya. A more precise location, however, will have to await the discovery of new evidence.

Where Did Kīrtipaṇḍita Go?

One of the mysteries surrounding Kīrtipaṇḍita is where he traveled in order to acquire certain Buddhist texts, which he is said to have brought back to Kambujadeśa and propagated. The verse in question is as follows:

Having obtained the *Lakṣaḡrantham Abhiprajñam*²⁸ from another kingdom, he—subdued in his senses—taught *tantra* including the commentary on the *Tattvasaṅgraha*.²⁹

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXIX)³⁰

As the above translation indicates, ‘another kingdom’ fails to identify a specific destination, thereby making it impossible for scholars to identify with any real certainty the region where Kīrtipaṇḍita acquired such texts. Trying to solve this historical puzzle is important because pinpointing where Kīrtipaṇḍita acquired Buddhist texts would identify regions that played a role in influencing the forms of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia.

In her article, “Le Bouddhisme du Champa,” Nandana Chutiwongs (2005: 81) mentions the travels of Kīrtipaṇḍita in order to highlight that tantric trends were taking

²⁷ OK: *kalpanā raṅko liḡ pratidina*. The exact measurement of a *liḡ* is unknown, but Pou (1992, s.v. *liḡ*) indicates that it was probably a small measurement of husked rice, Pou *Dictionnaire*. *kalpanā* also has a ritual connotation, (*Ibid.*, s.v. *kalpanā*).

²⁸ Sanderson (2004: 427) has suggested that this text refers to the *Lakṣaḡrantham Prajñāpāramitāsūtra* (‘Perfection of Wisdom Sūtra in One-Hundred Thousand Verses’); for additional comments, see the notes to this stanza in chapter two’s translation.

²⁹ i.e., *Sarvatathāgatattattvasaṅgraha* (‘Compendium of Truth of All Tathāgatas’).

³⁰ Skt. *lakṣaḡrantham abhiprajñam yo nveṣya pararāṣṡrataḡ / tattvasaṅgrahaṡikāditantrañ cādhyāpayad yamī //*, Coedès (IC 6: 198, 205 n. 3). Following Sanderson (2004: 427), *lakṣaḡraṅṡham* has been emended to *lakṣaḡrantham*.

place in both Cambodia and Campā during the tenth century. Regarding Kīrtipaṇḍita's destination, Chutiwongs states that he probably traveled to Java. Her tentative conclusion arises from her position that such tantric trends taking place during the tenth century are connected with Java; for example, she suggests (2005: 80–81) that tantric concepts found near the end of the An-Thái inscription of 902 CE (C. 138) may be related to similar—but not identical—concepts found in the tenth-century treatise on tantric Buddhism from Java known as the *Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānikan (SHK)*.³¹

Sharrock (2006: 22) notes Chutiwong's position and adds that Kīrtipaṇḍita could have instead traveled to India or the Isan region of northeastern Thailand. Sharrock offers no support for India, but he suggests the latter region because it may have been an influential Buddhist center based on so-called Prakhon Chai bronzes dating from the eighth century and discovered in the region in 1964.³²

Michael Vickery (2006: 144–45)—in reviewing another article of Sharrock's—asserts that instead of Java, Kīrtipaṇḍita was more likely to have traveled to Campā. In his words, Campā was “long an intermediary between Cambodia and other countries, where the Mahāyānist Indrapura dynasty was then enjoying its greatest development .”

Already, by referencing just three scholars who have commented on the topic, one is supplied with four possible destinations. Each of these scholars has suggested destinations based solely on forms of Buddhism in tenth-century Cambodia sharing similarities with forms of Buddhism established in other regions during the same time period. While this is both an important and necessary approach in narrowing down the

³¹ For an English translation of the An-Thái inscription, see Golzio (2000: 91–2). The An-Thái inscription is one of several tenth-century Buddhist inscriptions associated with northern polity (or polities) of Campā.

³² For a short overview of Prakhon Chai, with reference to additional sources, see Woodward (2005: 105–08).

possibilities, there is yet another approach that may compliment this method. Instead of narrowing down the possible destinations based only on similarities between forms of Buddhism in two different regions, one can also examine how the Sanskrit term denoting ‘another kingdom’ is used contextually in other contemporary tenth-century inscriptions in order to determine if its contextual usage makes certain destinations improbable—and thus further narrowing the possibilities. Since the Sanskrit term is not referring to a specific location this method will not yield a specific destination for Kīrtipaṇḍita’s travels, but it will demonstrate that this seemingly vague term has only been used in tenth-century inscriptions to refer to a specific *type* of location or region.

The Meaning of *pararāṣṭra*

‘Another kingdom’ is just one of several possible English translations for the Sanskrit compound, *pararāṣṭra*. In general, the first member of the compound, *para*^o, denotes a sense of distance or separation between one thing and another. Hence, possible translations for *para* include: ‘far,’ ‘distant,’ ‘remote (in space),’ ‘opposite,’ ‘farther than,’ ‘beyond,’ and so forth.³³ This meaning also has the broader, yet connected, sense of ‘other,’ ‘strange’ and ‘foreign;’ in other words, that which is separated is different. This broader sense, in turn, allows additional possible meanings of ‘enemy,’ ‘foreigner’ and ‘another’ in certain contexts.

The Sanskrit noun *rāṣṭra* is derived from the root $\sqrt{rāj}$, which means to ‘to rule or reign,’ ‘to be king or chief,’ ‘govern,’ and so forth.³⁴ Possible translations for *rāṣṭra*,

³³ s.v. *para*, M-W.

³⁴ s.v. *rāj*, M-W.

therefore, include: 'kingdom,' 'realm,' 'country,' 'district' and 'land.' Other possibilities include: 'people,' 'subjects,' and 'nation.'³⁵

Taking into account the above meanings, as well as the context of verse, a few of the possible English translations for *pararāṣṭra* include the following combinations: 'foreign country/kingdom/realm/land etc.,' 'other/another country/kingdom/realm/land etc.,' 'enemy country/kingdom/realm/land etc.,' and so forth. In the context of the verse from the Vat Sithor inscription, *pararāṣṭra* is specifically referring to a region, or possibly regions, not under the control of the ruler Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 968), during whose reign Kīrtipaṇḍita is likely to have undertaken his journey. Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 205) translated the compound as 'pays étranger.' Sanderson (2004: 427) translated it as 'abroad,' and Tadeusz Skorupski (in Sharrock, 2006: 300) translated it as 'foreign kingdom.'

Contextualizing a Generic Sanskrit Term

The Sanskrit compound *pararāṣṭra* is used only on one other occasion in the epigraphy of the tenth century. The inscription comes from the reign of Rājendravarman. The term occurs in one of the Bat Cum inscriptions, specifically the inscription located on the door jambs of the central tower (K. 267, st. XXI).³⁶ The stanza that follows describes how Rājendravarman's *tejas* ('radiance,' 'radiant power,' 'energy,' etc.) blazed throughout the realm while simultaneously incinerating his enemies:

³⁵ s.v. *rāṣṭra*, M-W.

³⁶ The latest date of 875 Śaka (953 CE) is mentioned in K. 266 (Southern Shrine), st. IXX. The date records the installment of an image of the Jina (i.e., the Buddha) and Vajrapāṇi by Kavindrāmathana. This appears to be the same event described in K. 267 (Central Shrine), st. XXXII; although, in addition to the Buddha and Vajrapāṇi an image of Devī (Prajñāpāramitā) is erected as well.

His radiant power—which was an element of the fire that consumes the world at the end of time—blazed forth throughout the four cardinal directions while enemy kingdoms beginning with Campā were incinerated.

(K. 267, Bat Cum, st. XXI)³⁷

In the above verse, the compound for ‘enemy kingdoms beginning with Campā’ is *campādipararāṣṭra*. Three observations can be made concerning *pararāṣṭra* in this context. First, the context of this inscription calls for translating *pararāṣṭra* more specifically as *enemy* kingdoms/lands/regions, not merely foreign or other kingdoms.³⁸ That is, these kingdoms or polities are ones which were in direct martial conflict with Rājendravarman. Second, referring to *pararāṣṭra* in conflict with Rājendravarman implies a sense of regional nearness; that is, these were very likely polities on the mainland ruled by competing, small-scale, regional rulers that Rājendravarman wished to subdue and incorporate into his own expanding domain. Finally, the verse cites a specific example of one such *pararāṣṭra*: Campā.³⁹ Based on this inscription and others, Campā indeed represented a collection of regional polities on the mainland in frequent conflict with Khmer rulers.

The inscriptions of Rājendravarman are replete with verses extolling his martial prowess.⁴⁰ These inscriptions—like the ones before and after Rājendravarman—have a

³⁷ Skt. *campādipararāṣṭrāṇān dagdhā kālānalākṛtiḥ / tejasām visaro yasya jājvalīti kakummukhe //*, Cœdès (1908b: 231).

³⁸ For attested usage, Monier-Williams (M.W., s.v. *pararāṣṭra*) noted that Kullūkabhaṭṭa in his commentary on *Manusmṛti* used *pararāṣṭra* in the sense of the ‘country of an enemy’ when commenting on the duties of an envoy (*dūta*). The commentary on VII.153, for example, states: *dūtānām saṃguptārthalekhahāritvādinā pararāṣṭraprasthāpanam cintayet*, Shastri (1983: 260).

³⁹ Although Campā is often spoken of in primary and secondary sources as single unified polity; in fact, it is merely a collective term that in actuality represented several independent polities. For detailed arguments, see Taylor (1999), Southworth (2000 and 2001) and Vickery (2005).

⁴⁰ For example, see stanzas CXVI–CXLVII of the Mebon inscription of 952 CE (K. 528) in Finot (1925b: 309–52). See Sharan (1981) for an English translation of the Mebon inscription.

fair amount bombastic praise and description. Unlike some rulers, however, there is probably a bit of truth to the inscriptions since it seems clear that his reign was secured through warfare. As previously noted by scholars such as Briggs (1951: 126), one of the primary enemy kingdoms cited in Rājendravarman's inscriptions is Campā.

The city of the king of Campā, having for its deep moat the sea, was reduced to ashes by the warriors obeying his (i.e., Rājendravarman's) orders.

(K. 528, The Mebon Inscription, st. CXLVI)⁴¹

To summarize, there are two known occurrences of the term *pararāṣṭra* in the epigraphical record from early Cambodia. Both occurrences are from the tenth century. The example occurring in the Bat Cum inscription specifically cites the (or a) polity of Campā as being one such *pararāṣṭra*, and it occurs in the context of being one, among several, enemy kingdoms warring against Rājendravarman. Additionally, in all the inscriptions which make reference to the battles of Rājendravarman Campā is given frequent emphasis. If—and there can be no definitive claims in this regard—*pararāṣṭra* is being used in the same manner in the Vat Sithor inscription, then it must refer to a mainland region in direct contact with Rājendravarman's domain. Again, the argument that the contextual usage would be the same is that *pararāṣṭra* is known to be used twice in contemporary tenth-century inscriptions, and it occurs nowhere else in the entire epigraphical corpus of the region.

In chapter six I also demonstrate that there is a roughly contemporaneous spike in the epigraphy from both Cambodia and Campā that likely indicated increased worship

⁴¹ trans. Sharan (1981: 87). Skt. *yasya sāgaragambhīraparikhā bhasmasātkṛtā / campādhirājanagarī vīrairājñānukāribhiḥ* // . Another example of Campā's defeat at the hand of Rājendravarman can be found in the Pre Rup inscription, stanza CCLXXII (Sharan, 1981: 186).

of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara and overall royal support of forms of Mahāyāna Buddhism previously unknown for both regions. This fact coupled with the above observations appears to support Vickery's opinion that Kīrtipaṇḍita likely traveled to Campā.

The Activities and Buddhism of Kīrtipaṇḍita

Kīrtipaṇḍita's activities bear strong similarities with typical Buddhist activities in the many other regions of the world where forms of Buddhism had been established. Merit accumulation, for oneself and that of others, is by far the most notable underlying motivation for many of the listed activities such as the (re)erecting of many images of the Buddha and bodhisattvas. This motivation is made explicit in stanza forty-one:

Having striven to obtain for the sake of others the fruit in the field (of merit) of the most eminent Muni, he dedicated 4000 *khārī* of rice to the Muni.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XLI)

The accumulation of merit not only was thought to ensure a favorable rebirth, but in the case of Kīrtipaṇḍita it would have been necessary in order to progress along the Mahāyāna path of the bodhisattva. This soteriological path is emphasized in the beginning of the inscription, and it involves mastering a series of perfections (*pāramitā*) as part of the attainment of complete and perfect enlightenment (i.e., Buddhahood). One such perfection is generosity (*dāna*), and Kīrtipaṇḍita's actions illustrate efforts to assist others. All forms of Buddhism emphasize generosity and the compassionate concern of others. Such altruism is not the sole province of Mahāyāna forms of Buddhism. Nevertheless, following the path of the bodhisattva in order to attain Buddhahood was to be viewed as the ultimate act of compassion since such a path was described as being undertaken for the benefit of aiding all other beings. The

Aṣṭasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitā ('The Perfection of Wisdom in Eight Thousand Lines')

states:

he (a Bodhisattva) should train himself thus: "My own self I will place in Suchness, and, so that all the world might be helped, I will place all beings into Suchness, and I will lead to Nirvana the whole immeasurable world of beings." With that intention should a Bodhisattva undertake all the exercises which bring about the wholesome roots.⁴²

Kīrtipaṇḍita was familiar with the corpus of Perfection of Wisdom literature since he is described in the inscription as acquiring the *Lakṣaḡrantham Abhiprajñam* ('Higher Wisdom in One-Hundred Thousand Lines'), another title for the *Lakṣaḡrantha Prajñāpāramitāsūtra* ('The Discourse on the Perfection of Wisdom in One-Hundred Thousand Lines') according to Sanderson (2004: 427, fn. 284). Prajñāpāramitā is also explicitly praised in stanza forty-four of the Vat Sithor inscription, and she frequently is recorded in other tenth-century inscriptions such as those at Bat Cum.

According to the Vat Sithor inscription, the activities of Buddhist practitioners in regions of tenth-century Cambodia had become corrupt and misguided around the period when Kīrtipaṇḍita undertook a series of activities to revitalize the community.

When the monsoon of worldliness came, darkness enveloped the world;
then the moon of the Buddha's Dharma shone with the coming of autumn's
bright fortnight.

The sun of doctrines such as *cittamātra* and *nairātmya*, which had been
eclipsed by the night of false doctrines, once again shone in the day.

He rekindled the lamp for the footpath of the Good Dharma—teachings
(*śāstra*) like the *Madhyāntavibhāga*—which had been extinguished by the
wind of Time.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXVI–XXVIII)⁴³

⁴² trans. Conze (1973: 163).

⁴³ For additional references supporting Kīrtipaṇḍita's revitalization of Buddhist traditions, cf. stanza XXXV and XLII.

Although we should hesitate to take everything the inscription documents as historical fact—primarily since the author(s) of the inscription may have exaggerated conditions in order to elevate the status of this well-respected *ācārya*—the inscription’s claims do make sense in light of the low number of inscriptions dedicated to forms of Buddhism prior to the mid-tenth century. The activities mentioned earlier all indicate that Kīrtipaṇḍita was an active proponent of Buddhist traditions during this period, so what does this actually reveal about the kind of Buddhism being promoted?

For one, the epigraphical record tells us what Buddhists like Kīrtipaṇḍita, in part, actually did, and what Buddhists like himself (or the author of the actual inscription) considered important enough to be recorded in stone. In some ways, it is advantageous that there are no surviving Buddhist manuscripts from early Cambodia that may have distracted scholars from focusing on actual Buddhist practices, as was the case in the early study of Buddhism. Gregory Schopen has written much on this topic and has stated (1997c: 1):

When Europeans first began to study Indian Buddhism systematically there were already two bodies of data available to them, and the same is true today. There was, and is, a large body of archaeological and epigraphical material, material that can be reasonably well located in time and space, and material that is largely unedited and much of which was never intended to “read.” This material records or reflects at least a part of what Buddhists—both lay people and monks—actually practiced and believed. There was, and is, an equally large body of literary material that in most cases cannot actually be dated and that survives only in very recent manuscript traditions. It has been heavily edited, it is considered canonical or sacred, and it was intended—at the very least—to inculcate an ideal. This material records what a small, atypical part of the Buddhist community wanted that community to believe or practice.

Of course surviving manuscripts would be helpful in contributing a more well-rounded image of Buddhist traditions in early Cambodia, but the point is that the epigraphical sources themselves reveal much more about actual Buddhist practices and

beliefs than many texts ever could. What the tenth-century epigraphical record from Cambodia reveals is that Buddhist practices focused on the following: (1) they revolved primarily around the activity of merit making and merit transference, (2) they involved ritual practices surrounding Buddhist images, as well as the donation and construction of other structures, and (3) they included engagement in apotropaic tantric ritual activities, and these activities allowed Buddhists to compete within the socio-political realm alongside other sectarian rivals who offered aesthetically and functionally similar rites.

With regard to the latter point, recall that the Vat Sithor inscription indicates that Kīrtipaṇḍita's revitalization efforts were specifically connected with (re)institutionalizing foundational doctrinal principles found in Perfection of Wisdom literature and Yogācāra sources like the *Madhyāntavibhāga*, and these foundations were accompanied with a concomitant acquisition and introduction of tantric texts that were said to be actively disseminated by the eminent *ācārya*. This observation is further supported by the following stanza from the Vat Sithor:

Having established the Good Dharma in both its exoteric and esoteric forms, he built for the purpose of worship separate hermitages (*āśrama*) for the Buddhist community and their guests.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XLII)

Some of the practices relating to these esoteric forms are recorded in the inscription. Stanza sixty-nine, for example, documents the use of *vidyā* ('incantations'), *mantra* ('chants of sacred syllables and phrases'), *mudra* ('sacred hand gestures'), and heart[-syllables], as well as the specialized employment of tantric ritual tools known as the thunderbolt scepter (Skt. *vajra*) and the bell (Skt. *ghaṇṭā*). Additionally, stanza twenty-six demonstrates that Kīrtipaṇḍita's ritual repertoire included apotropaic rites

adopted from earlier Vedic and Brahmanical sources that had become commonplace in tantric circles.

Having been treated with hospitality, the king charged him with (performing) rites such as *puṣṭi* (i.e., a rite for prosperity) and *śānti* (i.e., a rite for pacification) inside the palace for the sake of protecting the kingdom's territory (*maṇḍala*).

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXVI)⁴⁴

The inscription also suggests that Kīrtipaṇḍita's ritual repertoire (and, by extension, the repertoire of one of his disciples) was powerful enough to instill fear and respect in his opponents. Stanza thirty-one claims, "even the name of his disciple, whispered into the ears of disputants, caused panic (in them) like a *mantra* in a circle of snakes." Kīrtipaṇḍita's entry into royal circles was likely met with some resentment from other officials and ministers serving the king since he was essentially appropriating some of the ritual prerogatives that normally resided with these individuals. Additionally, all of these competitors likely belonged to other rival sectarian groups; nevertheless, the inscription boasts that he was able to subdue such opponents by virtue of his vast knowledge.

After meeting with the son of the lion of the Śākyas (i.e., Kīrtipaṇḍita), those elephant-like logicians (*tārkika*) who were stationed at the side of kings were humbled and overshadowed.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXX)

Regarding the similarity of rites employed by Buddhists in competition with their rivals, Sanderson (2004: 424–25) writes, "The Mahāyāna was already well placed to do this [i.e., empower and protect the state], especially since it had provided itself through the Way of Mantras (*mantranayaḥ*, *mantrayānam*) with an elaborate and impressive

⁴⁴ For detailed comments on the rites of *puṣṭi* and *śānti*, see my translation comments in chapter two.

system of rituals designed along Śaiva lines to offer its royal patrons exactly the protective and apotropaic benefits promised by their rivals.”

Much of what has been observed thus far about the Buddhism of Kīrtipaṇḍita can be described dualistically in terms of two complementary paths: (1) the Pāramitānaya (‘way of *perfections*,’ what the inscription refers to as the exoteric way), and (2) the Mantranaya (‘way of *mantras*,’ what the inscription refers to as the esoteric way), an early tantric division of Buddhism. This division conforms neatly to the categorical system of the eleventh-century tantric practitioner, Advayavajra. In the *Tattvaratnāvalī*, Advayavajra divides Buddhism into three vehicles (Skt. *yāna*): Śrāvakayāna, Pratyekayāna, and Mahāyāna. This is further subdivided into four foundational doctrinal positions (Skt. *sthiti*): Vaibhāṣika, Sautrāntika, Yogācāra, and Madhyamaka. Lastly, Mahāyāna is of two kinds: Pāramitānaya and Mantranaya.⁴⁵ Clearly tenth-century Buddhism in Cambodia would be categorized as belonging to the third vehicle, the Mahāyāna, because of its emphasis on the path of the bodhisattva. Additionally, the foundational position, as discussed at length in chapter three, would be Yogācāra. The Vat Sithor inscription also specifically divides this vehicle of Buddhism into two separate spheres along the lines of Advayavajra’s categorical system. The first time occurs in stanza twenty-nine when the foundational textual sources of both branches are recorded: *Lakṣaḡrantham Abhiprajānam* representing the Pāramitānaya, and the tantras representing the Mantranaya.⁴⁶ The second time, as mentioned above, comes in

⁴⁵ Chandra (1995: 295).

⁴⁶ Although (Sanderson 2004: 427, n. 284) does not mention the term Pāramitānaya, he does indicate that this verse is alluding to two complementary branches of Buddhism, the second being the Mantranaya.

stanza forty-two when Kīrtipaṇḍita is recorded as “having established the Good Dharma in both its exoteric and esoteric forms.”

Therefore, we may conclude that Kīrtipaṇḍita adhered to the so-called ‘great vehicle’, Mahāyāna. As discussed in the introduction, this term is not to be understood as some distinct school or sect. Instead, Mahāyāna is another way of describing those Buddhist practitioners who have opted to follow the demanding path of the bodhisattva as their vocation. For Kīrtipaṇḍita and his contemporaries in tenth-century Cambodia, this path—or vehicle—was grounded in Yogācāra doctrinal foundations. Lastly, this vehicle that was grounded in these Yogācāra foundations consisted of two distinct, yet complementary, paths: (1) the Pāramitānaya stressing the outer aspects of practice that involved the strenuous development of a number of perfections, and (2) the Mantranaya, the inner or secret practices consisting of expedient forms of powerful ritual knowledge usually acquired through initiation and master-pupil relationships.

CHAPTER 6 THE MANY FACES OF LOKEŚVARA: TANTRIC CONNECTIONS IN CAMBODIA AND CAMPĀ BETWEEN THE TENTH AND THIRTEENTH CENTURIES¹

A Khmer tenth-century bronze of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara currently held at the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York provides considerable reason to pause and reflect upon the current academic understandings of Buddhist traditions in early Cambodia (fig. 6-1).² Another Khmer depiction of Avalokiteśvara in and of itself is not unusual. The bodhisattva is well-attested in art historical and epigraphical sources coming from Cambodia. What is intriguing is that this particular bronze depicts an early tantric manifestation of the bodhisattva known as Ekādaśamukha, or the ‘Eleven-faced’ manifestation of Avalokiteśvara. The bronze has a cone-like configuration of eleven heads and eleven pairs of arms; and the bodhisattva is seated in the *vajrāsana*. Scholars studying Avalokiteśvara in regions such as Nepal, China and Japan have long noted the bodhisattva’s tantric associations and so-called esoteric forms. In Cambodia, however, Avalokiteśvara is rarely discussed or examined within a tantric context.³

¹ Earlier versions of this chapter were presented for the 2011 Association for Asian Studies conference in Honolulu and the 2011 “Angkor and its Global Connections” conference in Siem Reap, Cambodia. I thank Vasudha Narayanan, Hiram Woodward, Arlo Griffiths and Rob Linrothe for taking the time to provide extensive suggestions and critiques, all with the aim of improving the essay. I thank the Center for Khmer Studies for its support in 2010.

² This bronze sculpture was acquired in 1987, and is listed in the Metropolitan Museum of Art’s online database. The piece is listed as being acquired from the Margery and Harry Kahn Philanthropic Fund Gift in 1987 (Accession number: 1987.146). The height of the piece is 18.7 cm. (7 ¾ in.) high. Throughout this paper I use the term *Avalokiteśvara* as a mere scholarly convention. The actual word *Avalokiteśvara* is only used once in Cambodian epigraphy (K. 163), although abbreviated forms of this name are also known. By far, the most commonly used denominations for Avalokiteśvara in the Khmer epigraphical record are Lokeśa and Lokeśvara.

³ Bunker and Latchford (2004) devotes space to discussing tantric Buddhist art from Cambodia, but the piece from the Metropolitan Museum of Art is not mentioned, nor are there any connections made in the book between the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara and tantric forms of Buddhism. The later Bunker and Latchford (2011: cf. 176, 384) incorporates new research and devotes more attention to tantric Buddhist influences, but only a few scant remarks connect Avalokiteśvara with these traditions. Chutiwongs (1984) is indispensable and remains the primary work on the art and iconography of Avalokiteśvara in Southeast Asia. Unfortunately, Chutiwongs could not discuss the piece from the Metropolitan her since her book

Instead, Avalokiteśvara is often described in academic works that mention the Buddhist traditions of the famous Angkorian period (from around the late eighth to the fifteenth centuries) in a generalized manner that tends to confine the bodhisattva to some kind of generic and universal Mahāyāna Buddhism. Perhaps one of the primary reasons for this generalization is the lack of surviving manuscripts that would aid in understanding how the bodhisattva was viewed and worshipped at different times in Cambodia's past. Unlike, say, Nepal, Tibet, China and Japan, where there are large bodies of surviving textual materials, there are no surviving Buddhist texts—or any other type of manuscript—from Cambodia's pre-Angkorian or Angkorian periods.⁴ This disparity means that the methodologies employed to uncover clues about Cambodia's early Buddhist traditions must differ from the methodologies used by scholars studying early forms of Buddhism in regions where there are surviving Buddhist texts.

To note that there are no surviving Buddhist texts from early Cambodia does not mean, however, that there are no surviving written records. While there are no surviving manuscripts (palm leaf, etc.), Cambodia does have a vast corpus of surviving epigraphical records composed primarily in Sanskrit and Old Khmer. Nevertheless, although the inscriptions written in Sanskrit often contain traditional opening panegyrics to gods and other powerful and efficacious beings (all of which provide important

was published before the museum acquired the bronze. Chutiwongs does discuss the sixteen-armed Avalokiteśvara bas-relief from Banteay Chhmar (c. late twelfth to early thirteenth century); she does not associate this later depiction with any possible tantric connections, despite following Jean Boisselier's observations that some of the Banteay Chhmar bas-reliefs of Avalokiteśvara are likely connected with the *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra*, a text now known to contain tantric characteristics. Chutiwongs does, however, identify the presence of tantric Buddhism in Cambodia during the tenth century and the early thirteenth century, and notes its possible influence on other images of Avalokiteśvara (214–215, 246).

⁴ By using the term *pre-Angkorian* I am broadly referencing the period prior to the time of Jayavarman II (r. 790–c. 835), whose reign is commonly regarded as marking the transition between the pre-Angkorian period and the Angkorian period.

information on the religious traditions of the time), many of these epigraphical records are more concerned with praising the qualities and exploits of particular rulers and their favored ministers. In the case of the inscriptions in Old Khmer, the majority are concerned with recording property transactions, along with enumerating the donations connected with such property. Since the interested scholar is often provided only glimpses of religious thought and practice in the inscriptions, the epigraphical records must be examined in conjunction with Cambodia's impressive art historical record. By examining both sources, recognizing that these sources studied with respect to one another can provide more historical information than either source alone, the scholar can move beyond merely highlighting such things as royal genealogies and land transactions present in the epigraphy or simply identifying the iconography of a particular art historical piece.

By examining the epigraphical and art historical records of early Cambodia, as well as some of the epigraphical records from Campā, I argue that the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara goes from a relatively minor figure in Cambodia during the pre-Angkorian period to an increasingly important figure within an emerging tantric context beginning around the tenth century. Since it will be shown that Avalokiteśvara's increased importance in tenth-century Cambodia arose amid newly emerging strains of tantric Buddhism in the region, it is within this tantric context that we must begin to reassess the various ways in which this bodhisattva was understood.

Avalokiteśvara before the Tenth Century

Although Mahāyāna Buddhism was well established in Cambodia during the sixth through eighth centuries, in terms of extensive royal patronage it occupied a relatively minor position in the region when compared with forms of Śaivism and, to a lesser

extent, Vaiṣṇavism.⁵ With specific regard to Avalokiteśvara, the surviving epigraphical record from Cambodia documents only two references to the bodhisattva prior to the mid-tenth century. The inscription of Ampil Rolum (K. 163)—dated on paleographic grounds by Aymonier (1900, 1: 442) to the sixth or seventh century—cites donations to a Buddhist triad: Buddha, Maitreya and Avalokiteśvara.⁶ The second reference occurs in the inscription of Kdei Ta Kom (K. 244), dated to Śaka 713 (791/792 CE).⁷ This latter inscription represents the first attested use of the epithet Lokeśvara ('lord of the world') and records the installation of an image named Jagadīśvara (which also means 'lord of the world') in the likeness of Lokeśvara. The epithets of this inscription clearly invoke parallels with Śaivism, and such parallels only increase over time as the competition for royal patronage becomes more pronounced.

According to Chutiwongs (1984: 232), the earliest images of Avalokiteśvara in Cambodia are two-armed representations, although various configurations of two-armed and four-armed images are common throughout the pre-Angkorian period. Like the

⁵ Ascertaining specifics regarding the forms of Buddhism (sects, texts used, rituals, persons involved, etc.) during the early periods in Cambodia is exceedingly difficult due to the limited nature of the evidence. Only a small amount of information can be gleaned from rare references to Buddhism in the epigraphy. Surviving images are much more abundant, but this type of evidence has limitations. For a general overview of Buddhist traditions during the pre-Angkorian and other periods in Cambodia's history, see Harris (2005).

⁶ For K. 163, see Cœdès (IC, 6: 100–01). The actual terminology used is '*vrah kaṃmrātāñ 'añ śāstā vrah kaṃmrātāñ 'añ maitreya vrah kaṃmrātāñ 'añ śrī avalokiteśvara.*' All three names are prefixed with the Old Khmer *vrah kaṃraten 'añ*, a title used for divine beings and sometimes for pre-Angkorian kings. For more on this title, see Vickery (1998: 143–49). Two points of interests should also be noted: (1) this inscription represents the only epigraphical use of this particular triad in Cambodia, and (2) the nomenclature *Avalokiteśvara* is never used again, although abbreviated forms of this name are used.

⁷ For K. 244, see Cœdès (IC, 3: 89). The entire inscription is as follows: *samaguṇaśaśinagaśāke prathito yas supratīṣṭhito bhagavān / jagadīśvara iti nāmnā sa jayati lokeśvarapratimaḥ //*. Sanderson (2004: 424 n. 277) provides the translation "Victorious is the renowned Lord well installed in Śāka 713 under the name Jagadīśvara in the likeness of Lokeśvara."

Kdei Ta Kom inscription above, many of these images display similarities with Śiva.⁸ Of special note are figures that have strong ascetic features such as wearing simple garments, wearing an antelope-skin draped over the left shoulder, and holding a ritual water pot (*kamaṇḍalu*), an item sometimes used to perform ablutions.⁹

Avalokiteśvara in Tenth-Century Cambodia

Although there are indications in the art historical record that by the eighth century Avalokiteśvara had become a somewhat independent figure deserving of special worship (Chutiwongs, 1984: 219), it was not until the tenth century that Avalokiteśvara truly garnered more widespread attention.¹⁰ Perhaps one of the most important indications of this increased significance is a spike in the number of epigraphical references to Avalokiteśvara. As mentioned above, Avalokiteśvara is cited in only two inscriptions prior to the mid-tenth century. In the tenth century, however, this number jumps to at least thirteen, or 62 percent of all the inscriptions that include some reference to Avalokiteśvara in early Cambodia (table 6.1).¹¹

⁸ This observation has also been noted by Chutiwongs (1984: 231). She also notes resemblances to Maitreya in the pre-Angkorian images of Avalokiteśvara.

⁹ The seventh-century bronze now in the National Museum of Cambodia in Phnom Penh is an excellent example of Lokeśvara displaying all these iconographic characteristics (inv. no. ga5332 [E 607, E/I 11,10]); see Chutiwongs (1984: pl. 106). Also of note is that strong similarities and connections between Śiva and Avalokiteśvara would in later periods allow for easy manipulation of Avalokiteśvara images in order to somewhat crudely convert them to Śiva images. This was often accomplished by simply defacing the Amitābha image seated in the *jaṭāmukūṭa* ('crowned locks of hair'). Two examples from the mid-eleventh century can be found in Bunker and Latchford (2004: 213–17, pl. 70a, b, c, and 71).

¹⁰ I should be clear, however, by stating that Buddhist traditions continued to occupy a clearly subordinate position during this period and would continue to do so until the reign of Jayavarman VII (r. 1182–c. 1218).

¹¹ The collective number of inscriptions in Cambodia referencing Lokeśvara from other centuries pales in comparison. Epigraphy is not the sole indicator of popularity or importance, especially due to the incomplete and sometimes fragmentary nature of the evidence. For example, while there are only four inscriptions making reference to Lokeśvara during the reign of Jayavarman VII (K. 485, K. 273, K. 908, and K. 1251), the sheer number of artistic representations of this figure during this period clearly attests to the importance placed on the role of Lokeśvara in spite of a relatively limited amount of epigraphical evidence. I am purposefully setting aside the numerous epigraphical references of *kamrateñ jagats* from

Three broad factors seem to be responsible for the increased interest in Avalokiteśvara during the tenth century. First, forms of Buddhism gained increasing recognition and support during the reigns of Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 966) and Jayavarman V (r. c. 968–1000/1001). Second, new forms of Buddhism emerged and gained prominence in Campā during the late ninth and tenth century in which Avalokiteśvara played an important role, and interregional exchanges between the Khmers and Cams likely played a role in stimulating new forms of Buddhism in Cambodia. Third, Buddhist texts such as the *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra* (KVS) and the *Ekādaśamukhadhāraṇī* (EDMD), which focus on the virtues of Avalokiteśvara, may have increased the appeal of the bodhisattva in this region during the tenth century. Although both these texts predate the tenth century by many years, it is not until then that concepts and figures present in these texts are attested in Cambodia.¹²

The first factor regarding increased support during the reigns of Rājendravarman and Jayavarman V need not be elaborated here since arguments for increased recognition of Buddhism can be easily supported by reference to increased evidence in the epigraphical records of these respective rulers, and the third factor regarding the

the twelfth century that variously incorporate the name Lokeśvara in mini-inscriptions found in locations such as the temple complex of Preah Khan. For example, these lists include such names as *kamrateñ jagat ratnalokeśvara* (S1. K. 907), *kamrateñ jagat śrīraṇḍiyalokeśvara* (C20. K. 621), and *kamrateñ jagat śrīparamadiyalokeśvara* (C30. K. 907). For additional details concerning these later inscriptions, see Cœdès (1951: 107–116). Additionally, I indicate that there are “at least thirteen” inscriptions from the tenth century referencing Avalokiteśvara because my preliminary research suggests that there may be more. For example, I believe the very fragmentary Phnom Banan inscription (K. 202) is probably from the tenth century and that the fragmented word *-keśvara* found in the inscription was probably a reference to Lokeśvara. The details supporting my argument are provided in chapter four. Besides the possible reference to Lokeśvara the fragmentary content of the inscription contributes nothing further to this chapter.

¹² As there are no surviving manuscripts from Cambodia, we cannot determine how closely related such texts would have been to the surviving manuscripts known today. Additionally, it must be admitted that the clues that lead us to determine that the Khmers likely had knowledge of the *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra*, and perhaps the *Ekādaśamukhadhāraṇī* as well, could be alluding to different texts with similar content that were circulating within the region.

KVS and *EDMD* will be highlighted later in the chapter. With regard to Campā, however, a few points should be highlighted now before focusing on Cambodia, since this factor specifically pertains to Avalokiteśvara and newly arising forms of tantric Buddhism in the region.

The Campā Stimulus

Buddhism had gained a prominent role among the ruling class during the late ninth and tenth centuries in Campā, and it is hard to imagine this popularity not spilling over into Cambodia beginning around the mid-tenth century with Rājendravarman.¹³ Around the mid- to late ninth century, the northern Campā polity (or polities) situated in and around the Thu Bồn river system, which is located in present-day Quảng Nam province in Vietnam, (re)gained political and economic significance with regard to maritime trade on the route between India and China. The dynasty associated with this region is frequently referred to as the Indrapura dynasty, after the Sanskrit name for an urban center associated with present-day Đông Dương.¹⁴ The extent of this dynasty's influence should not be limited to Quảng Nam province, since the epigraphical record indicates a zone of influence and control as far north as Quảng Bình.¹⁵

William Southworth (2004: 321–22) has written that “with the return of trade to Guangzhou (Canton) in the late ninth century, the Thu Bon Valley again became economically dominant.” Surely disruptions and changes at China's end of the maritime

¹³ For an additional argument suggesting Khmer forms of Buddhism may have been influenced by Campā, see Mabbett (1986).

¹⁴ For problems in using the term *Indrapura* to denote the entire northern territory of Campā, see Southworth (2000).

¹⁵ Quảng Bình represents the northern-most region in which polities of Campā were located. Since I am focusing on the northern region in this chapter, it should be noted that I am broadly referring to an area ranging roughly from Quảng Nam to Quảng Bình.

routes would have directly affected this northern polity, but whatever the exact reason, based on the increased number of inscriptions in the region it seems clear that the area had achieved a certain level of political success and stability.

What is most interesting about the inscriptions emerging during this period from the area ranging roughly from Quảng Nam to Quảng Bình is that they indicate that a form of Mahāyāna Buddhism was patronized and privileged among the rulers. Prior to these inscriptions, the Cam epigraphical record from this northern region contains no references to Buddhism, although there are a few Buddhist-related Cam inscriptions that have come from the south.¹⁶ In short, the Cam epigraphical corpus from this area jumps from containing no Buddhist content to having at least six inscriptions containing overt Buddhist elements. These six inscriptions are listed in table 6.2.

¹⁶ It was established in 1969 by Jean Filliozat (1969) that the Vỡ Cảnh inscription (dated to the late third to fourth centuries CE) contains nothing explicitly Buddhist based on a reinterpretation of the name Śrī Māra contained in the inscription. For a more recent discussion of the inscription, see Southworth (2001: 198–205). I would like to stress, however, that there are other Cam inscriptions with undeniable Buddhist content south of Quảng Nam province. While I am not denying transregional connections and exchange between the northern polities of Campā and the southern ones, I am limiting my discussion to what the Cam inscriptions from the northern regions tell us. Nevertheless, for the sake of completeness, I include here a list of Cam inscriptions from the south that either predate, or are contemporary with, the northern inscriptions under discussion. A brief overview should make it clear that based on the epigraphy during this period Avalokiteśvara was not very influential in the south. Inscription C. 44 discovered in Phú Yên province is written on the back of a terracotta plaque bearing an image of the Buddha seated in meditation. The inscription contains a version of the *ye dharmā* verse inscribed in four lines. Henri Parmentier (1902: 280–82) suggests the sixth century Śaka as a possible date. For C. 44, also see Parmentier (1909: 134, 137) and Cœdès and Henri Parmentier (1923 : 12–13) A sandstone stele containing a Buddhist inscription was discovered in Phú Yên province at a site about one kilometer from where C. 44 was discovered. The stele probably dates to sometime in the seventh to ninth centuries. The stele bears an image of the Buddha on a lotus flower seated between two *stūpas*. The *ye dharmā* verse is inscribed on the stele twice. On the stele, see Skilling, Southworth and Phương (2010). C. 23 from Ninh Thuận province, which is dated to 829/830 CE, records the donation of two temples, two monasteries, and land to both the Jina and Śaṅkara (i.e., the Buddha and Śiva) by a person named Samanta. The inscription was composed by his son, who was obviously Buddhist based on his name—Buddhanirvāṇa. The Sanskrit section was edited in Bergaigne and Barth (1893: 237–41). For the Cam portion, see Aymonier (1891: 25–27). The inscription C. 38 coming from the southern site of Pô Nagar in Khánh Hòa province can be mentioned insofar as it mentions that Bhadravarman's son, Indravarman, was familiar with the teachings of Jinendra (i.e., the Buddha). For C. 38, see Bergaigne and Barth (1893: 258–60). Also see Huber (1911: 268–69).

I wish to highlight two facts concerning the Buddhist content of these inscriptions. First, Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) is by far the most popular Buddhist figure among these six inscriptions. Lokeśvara—whether being praised, being erected in the form of an image, or simply nominally connected to the establishment of monasteries—is present in five out six inscriptions. Clearly the bodhisattva had become extremely popular during this period, whether worshiped alone or as part of the triad.¹⁷ Only in the very short and fragmentary C. 172 is Lokeśvara absent. In addition to noting this inscription’s fragmentary condition, it should also be noted that C. 172 was discovered in an enclosure near the temple of Mý Đưc, and a stone image of Lokeśvara dating to the ninth or tenth century was discovered at this very temple in 1918; therefore, while Lokeśvara cannot be connected directly to this particular inscription, the bodhisattva can be connected to the temple where the inscription was discovered.¹⁸

The second fact is the occurrence of some tantric elements in a couple of the inscriptions. By far the most significant is the An Thái inscription of 902 CE (C. 138). As has been noted by scholars such as Woodward (2004: 345), the end of this inscription contains an unfamiliar tantric tripartite configuration that bears some similarities to the concept of three Buddha families (*trikula*) elaborated in the early tantric text, *Mahāvairocanābhisaṃbodhi Sūtra* (better known simply as the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra*).¹⁹ The inscription reads:

¹⁷ For additional remarks on the Avalokiteśvara in Campā during this period, see Schweyer (2009). For similar practices in Cambodia, note the donation of an *āśrama* in Lokeśvara’s name mentioned in the Khmer inscription of Ta An (K. 240), which is dated to Śaka 901 (979 CE). See Cœdès (*IC*, 3: 76–78).

¹⁸ This piece is now located in the Musée Guimet (MG 18899). For an image, Baptiste and Zéphir (2005 : 232, pl. 30).

¹⁹ For the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra*, see Giebel (2005) and Hodge (2003).

This Vajradhātu which, although non-existent, is the cause of the Vajrawielder (ie, Vajrapāṇi), became by the command of Śrī Śākyamuni, the abode of the Buddhas.

The Padmadhātu, the great non-existent, (but) the cause of Lokeśvara, became, by the logic of Amitābha's words, the abode of the Jinas.

This Cakradhātu, which, although beyond the state of non-existence, would be the cause of Vajrasattva, became, by the command of Vairocana, the third abode of the Jinas.

(C. 138, An Thái, st. VIII–X)²⁰

Scholars such as Chutiwongs (2005: 80–81) and Schweyer (2009: 315–16) have also argued for a connection between the tripartite configuration in the An Thái inscription and the tenth-century treatise on tantric Buddhism from Java known as the *Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānikan* (*SHK*).²¹ According to Kazuko Ishii (1991: 158–59), the *SHK* pantheon likely bears a close relation to the *Tattvasaṃgraha*—an important text of the Yogatantras—and the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* in that the Buddhist pantheon detailed in the *SHK* is composed of two groups that may have been associated with two *maṇḍalas*: the Garbhamaṇḍala of the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* and the Vajradhātumaṇḍala of the *Tattvasaṃgraha*. The first group in the *SHK* comprises of Śākyamuni, Vajrapāṇi and Lokeśvara; while Vairocana, Akṣobhya, Ratnasambhava, Amitābha, and Amoghasiddhi (i.e., the Five Buddhas) make up the second group.

Another contemporary treatise on tantric Buddhism from Java is the *Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānan Mantranaya* (*SHKM*). Unlike the *SHK*, in which connections with the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* and the *Tattvasaṃgraha* can only be presumed based on certain corresponding similarities between the two, the connections between the *SHKM* and

²⁰ trans. Golzio (2004: 91–92).

²¹ Regarding the *SHK* and *SHKM*, see Chandra (1995): 295–434. Chandra also provides a list of the previous scholarship pertaining to these two texts.

these two early tantric texts is beyond doubt, since the *SHKM* shares textual correspondences with both the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* and the *Tattvasaṃgraha*.²² Whether the tantric concepts in the An Thái inscription from Campā were directly influenced by the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* and the *Tattvasaṃgraha*, or whether they were indirectly influenced by these early tantric texts by way of contemporary tantric treatises like the *SHK* and *SHKM* coming from Java, cannot currently be determined with any real certainty. When we additionally consider, however, that the *Tattvasaṃgraha* is specifically cited in the later tenth-century Vat Sithor inscription (K. 111) from Cambodia, it appears certain that some of the tantric concepts found in the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra* and the *Tattvasaṃgraha* were influential in not only Java but in Campā and Cambodia as well.

Brief mention should also be made of the Nham Biền stele inscription of 911/912 CE (C. 149) from the above list of six inscriptions, although there are difficulties to attributing any tantric Buddhist connection to this particular record.²³ In this inscription an individual named Rājadvāra undertook (twice) some kind of diplomatic mission (*dūtakarman*) to Yavadvīpapura (Java) as a result of which he obtains *siddhayātrā*.²⁴

²² For example, see J. de Jong (1974); Ishii (1991 and 1992). Ishii notes that verses 12 and 13 of the *SHKM* correspond to the *Tattvasaṃgraha* (i.e., the *Sarvatathāgatattvasaṃgraha*).

²³ Griffiths, et al. (2012b : 447) note that the correct spelling of the place of origin for C. 149 is unknown; this has resulted in institutions and scholars employing various spellings.

²⁴ The correct Sanskrit for stanza VIII is: *yavadvīpapuraṃ bhūpānujñāto dūtakarmanī gatvā yaḥ pratipattisthaḥ siddhayātrām samāgamat*. The term *dūtakarman* (specifically, *dūtakarmanī* in the inscription) deserves a few remarks since the term *nūtakarmanī* from Edouard Huber's reading continues to be cited in sources. In 1911 Huber (299–311) published a transcription and French translation of this inscription. He also included plates of the estampages he utilized. Stanza VIII occurs on lines eleven and twelve on side A of the stele. Huber provided the following transliteration: *Yavadvīpapuraṃ bhūpānujñāto nūtakarmanī gatvā yaḥ pratipattisthaḥ siddhayātrām* [read as *siddhayātrām*] *samā(12)gamat*, which he translated as, "Pour un but louable [i.e., *nūtakarman*], lui qui est ferme de propos, il se rendit, avec l'autorisation du roi, dans la capitale de Java où il acquit la science magique" (309). In 1927, R. C. Majumdar (134, n. 3) objected to Huber's reading of *nūta-*, writing that "Huber translates 'Siddhayātrām Samāgamat' as 'acquired the science of magic.' This seems to be

Later in his career, Rājadvāra—who had become very successful and wealthy in his duty to the king—installed and consecrated Devaliṅgeśvara (i.e., Śiva) in a temple, and later still he established a monastery dedicated to Avalokiteśvara. Much has been written on the term *siddhayātrā*—which occurs in several inscriptions from Southeast Asia—and this has led to various interpretations over the years.²⁵

In short, the interpretations can be divided into three camps: (1) those that interpret *siddha* in the context of the inscriptions as pertaining to the acquisition of some kind of magical powers; (2) those that understand *siddha* in a much more secular sense pertaining simply to success or victory in some kind of undertaking; and (3) those that attempt to reconcile these two positions by indicating that *siddha* in the context of the inscriptions pertains to the acquisition of magical power necessary to ensure success or victory. All three interpretations maintain that such magical powers or success were acquired by means of a pilgrimage or journey (*yātrā*).

So, for example, adopting Edouard Huber’s (1911: 309) interpretation of the expressions *siddhayātrām samāgamat* and *siddhayātrām upāgamat* from the Nham

farfetched. Huber reads ‘nūta’ in the first line of the verse which seems to be a mistake for ‘dūta’. ‘Nūta’ means ‘praiseworthy’—so it also leads nearly to the same conclusion;” Majumdar translated the Sanskrit as “At the command of the king he went to the capital of Yavadvīpa on a diplomatic mission [i.e., *dūtakarman*], and obtained credit by the success of his undertaking.” Majumdar’s transcription and interpretation was followed by Golzio (2004: 112) in his more recent English synthesis of the work done on the inscriptions of Campā with a note referencing Huber’s alternate translation of *siddhayātrā*. Majumdar’s initial suspicion is correct; according to Mabbett (1986: 302), Majumdar’s reading was confirmed in a personal communication with Claude Jacques, who had access to the estampage in Paris. After I examined a decent quality image of the estampage provided by Arlo Griffiths on May 27, 2011, it became clear that there is no difference between the *d* in *tadā* in line 10 and the *d* in *dūta* in line 11. In an e-mail communication on June 2, 2011, this reading of *dūta*- was confirmed by Amandine Lepoutre, who was able to provide high-quality photographs of the stone in Hanoi. Arlo Griffiths has also brought to my attention the use of *dūta* in the stele of Bàng An (C. 141, line 14) that is contemporary with C. 149. I sincerely thank both Arlo Griffiths and Amandine Lepoutre for their assistance in (re)confirming what R. C. Majumdar suspected over eighty years ago.

²⁵ For an in-depth overview and a survey of the various interpretations on *siddhayātrā* in Southeast Asian inscriptions, see Sastri (1937).

Biền inscription as “acquired the science of magic,” George Coedès concluded in 1930 (62) that *siddhayātrā* “designates a journey or pilgrimage from which the pilgrim returns invested with supernatural powers.” This was also the basic position of N. J. Krom (1931: 121). B. C. Chhabra (1965: 25–26), however, felt such interpretations were doubtful due to an unnecessary conflation between *siddhi* and *siddha* and argued that *siddhayātrā* referred simply to a successful voyage, much like R. C. Majumdar (1927: 134), who translated the Nham Biền inscription’s *siddhayātrām samāgamat* as “obtained credit by the success of his undertaking.” Attempting to reconcile these positions, Willem Stutterheim—and later Boechari, who adopted Stutterheim’s interpretation—concluded that *siddhayātrā* referred to a “pilgrimage of victory,” which he further elaborated as “a pilgrimage on which one sets out to obtain the magic power necessary for a victory.”²⁶

In his examination of the *Pañcatantra* and the *Jātakamālā*—both of which contain expressions using *siddhayātrā*—K. A. Nilakanta Sastri (1937: 135) concluded that the previous interpretations connecting *siddhayātrā* with something mystical or magical were not far-fetched at all (contrary to the views of scholars like Chhabra and

²⁶ The quotes from Willem Stutterheim’s, “Verslag over de gevonden inscripties,” in *Oudheidkundige vondsten in Palembang* (Palembang: K.A. Ebeling, 1935) are quoted from Boechari (2012a: 378). Stutterheim’s thoughts on *siddhayātrā* are also summarized in Sastri (1937: 130–31). See Boechari (2012b: 389–392) for his thoughts on *siddhayātrā* in relation to the Kedukan Bukit inscription from Sumatra. Boechari (2012a: 378) also stressed the implications of the king in the Kedukan Bukit inscription embarking on the eleventh day of the bright part of the month of Waiśākha: “It is well known that the day of pūrṇamā of Waiśākha is a holy day for the Buddhists; it is considered as the day of the birth as well as the enlightenment and nirwāṇa of the Buddha. We are of the opinion that on that day Dapunta Hyiañ went by ship to a Buddhist shrine, perhaps upstream on the Batang Kuantan, to celebrate the Waiśākha festivals, at the same time praying and giving offerings for the success of his coming military expedition.” This led Boechari to conclude that *siddhayātrā* (i.e., the journey to the Waiśākha festival where prayers for success were performed) referred to a Buddhist pilgrimage (378; see also 2012b: 389, 392).

Majumdar).²⁷ In fact, based on the usage of the term in these two earlier texts, he states, “It seems clear therefore that *siddhayātrā* in the Indonesian inscriptions is a technical phrase with unmistakable reference to the acquisition of magic power of some sort or other.” While Cœdès (1930: 62–63), unlike Krom (1931), was not absolutely convinced that there was necessarily a relationship between tantric forms of Buddhism in these regions and the importance of *siddhi* (‘magic’) he did write that “what we can say is that magic, which since prehistoric times must have been very important among the primitive Indonesian populations, was more easily reconciled with Hinduist or Buddhist Tantrism than with any other religion.”

Ignoring the problems and assumptions that could be associated with the word *magic* in the context of Buddhist rituals, Cœdès does have a point that such rituals involving the acquisition of power or magic may have been more easily accommodated by certain tantric rites. With that said, however, it has yet to be proven that the rites associated with performing a *siddhayātrā* were connected with tantric practitioners and texts, although it is certainly possible. Therefore, additional research on the term *siddhayātrā* is still needed.²⁸

The Avalokiteśvara Parallel

While no explicit connection can be made with Cambodia from the above Cam inscriptions, a similar pattern, however, seems to occur in the Cambodian epigraphy from the tenth century—namely, there is a contemporaneous increased presence of

²⁷ Chhabra was the first to analyze *siddhayātrā* in the context of the *Pañcatantra* and *Jātakamālā*, but he obviously arrived at a different conclusion than Sastri (1937).

²⁸ For more on the term *siddhayātrā*, see Casparis (1956). An additional relevant reference (as noted in Woodward (2004: 336, n. 14) is Kulke (1993).

Avalokiteśvara in the Cambodian epigraphy, as well as newly arising tantric elements, that roughly parallel the Cam epigraphical record.

As mentioned previously, Avalokiteśvara is only cited in two Khmer inscriptions prior to the mid-tenth century, but epigraphical references to the bodhisattva jump to at least thirteen, or roughly 62 percent, of all the inscriptions that include some reference to Avalokiteśvara in early Cambodia.

Recall that similarly in the northern regions of Campā there are no inscriptions mentioning Avalokiteśvara prior to 875 CE (C. 66), but then between the late ninth century and the early tenth century (914 CE, C. 167) the number jumps to five inscriptions connected with the bodhisattva. This is not to imply that in either Cambodia or Campā the bodhisattva was unknown before this period (which is clearly not the case in either region, based on the art historical records) but merely to highlight that in both regions there is a roughly contemporaneous spike in the epigraphy likely indicating increased worship of the bodhisattva and overall royal support of forms of Mahāyāna Buddhism previously unknown for both regions.

The Tantric Connection in Tenth-Century Cambodia

Also noteworthy is that the first attested signs of Buddhist tantric elements which constitute an important aspect of the type of Mahāyāna Buddhism during this period arise in Cambodia during the tenth century, again roughly following the first attested presence of Buddhist tantric elements in the northern regions of nearby Campā (e.g., An Thái, C. 138). For example, we should note that triads consisting of the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Vajrapāṇi first appear in Cambodia in the tenth century.²⁹ This is a

²⁹ For example, a triad of the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Vajrapāṇi is specifically invoked in K. 266; see Cœdès (1908b) and Mertens (2005). The earliest epigraphical reference to this triad in Southeast Asia

well-known triad within Mahāyāna Buddhism in many regions outside of Cambodia, and such a triad does not necessarily imply tantric connections or meanings. The timing with which this triad appears in Cambodia, however, suggests that such a configuration was influenced by contemporary tantric ideas and forms of practice in regions such as Campā and Java.³⁰ As such, Avalokiteśvara is understood to belong to the lotus family (*padma-kula*), while Vajrapāṇi belongs to the vajra family (*vajra-kula*). An excellent representation of this triad in Cambodia comes from the tenth-century sculptures discovered in Kampong Cham and now located in the Musée Guimet.³¹ Also note that Vajrapāṇi first appears in the Cam epigraphy in 902 CE (C. 138) couched in a clear tantric tripartite context. With regard to Java, the tenth-century tantric *SHK* may again be of interest in that Śākyamuni, Lokeśvara, and Vajrapāṇi are often configured together in various ways, as when they are equated with the Three Jewels of Buddhism and combined the five Buddhas:

The holy Śākyamuni has, in truth, the holy Buddha as his essence (*tatva*), Śrī Lokeśvara has the holy Dharma as his essence, Bajrapāṇi has the venerable Saṅgha as his essence. They are called *bhaṭāra Ratnatraya*. Vairocana, Amitābha and Akṣobhya are called *Ratnatraya*. Vairocana, Ratnasambhava and Amoghasiddhi are also *Ratnatraya*.³²

that I am aware of comes from the eighth century Nakhon Si Thammarat inscription dated to 775 CE. See Coedès (1918: 23–25 and 1959: 103–11).

³⁰ Here I would like to point readers to Arlo Griffiths, “An Inscribed Bronze Sculpture of a Buddha in *bhadraśana* at Museum Rangawarsita in Semarang (Central Java, Indonesia),” *Arts Asiatiques* (forthcoming). Among of other things, Griffiths has suggested that the iconography of Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Vajrapāṇi images in South and Southeast Asia may be a reflection of the triadic arrangement described in tantric Buddhist texts such as the *Susiddhikarasūtra* and the *Mañjuśrīyamūlakalpa*. I am grateful to Arlo Griffiths for sharing a draft of his paper with me.

³¹ For images, see Baptiste and Zéphir (2008: 166–71).

³² trans., Chandra (1995: 425).

The tenth-century Vat Sithor inscription (K. 111) provides stronger evidence for a tantric presence in tenth-century Cambodia.³³ Among other things, this inscription indicates that the learned Kīrtipaṇḍita traveled abroad for texts like the *Tattvasaṃgraha* (i.e., the *Sarvatathāgatattattvasaṃgraha*), a key text of the Yogatantras.³⁴ The inscription is also clear that both exoteric (*vāhya* = *bāhya*) and esoteric (*guhya*) forms of Buddhism were taught and propagated during this period (st. XLII). Furthermore, sacerdotal ministers worthy of donations had to be “learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, *vidyā*, *mantra*, *mudrā* and heart[-syllables],” and they also had to be “familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṅṭā*)” (st. LXIX).³⁵ Within this tantric context, the inscription also details how Kīrtipaṇḍita re-installed images of Vajrin (i.e., Vajrapāṇi) and Lokeśa (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) on a mountain top (st. XLV).³⁶ This highlights the continuing importance and role of Avalokiteśvara during a time when tantric forms of Buddhism were becoming prevalent in Cambodia. While the actual extent of tantric Buddhism during this time could be a matter of dispute, such overt

³³ Another good example indicating a probable tantric presence in tenth-century Cambodia would be the archaeological discovery of the remains of a *prastāra* (‘letter diagram’) at the three brick shrines of Bat Cum. For instance, see Coëdès (1952). For the most recent examination on this diagram, see Woodward (2009: 30–32).

³⁴ For more on this topic, see Sanderson (2004: 427).

³⁵ The translation excerpts are my own. Stanza LXIX: *hr̥nmudrāmantravidyāsu homakarmmaṇi kovidaḥ / bajraghaṅṭārahasyajñō dakṣiṇyaḥ purohitaḥ*, the emended reading is from Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284). It may also be worthwhile to highlight that stanzas XLIV and XLV claim that in order to continue the lineage of Sarvavid an image of Prajñāpāramita was erected, and ten images of Avalokiteśvara (Lokeśa) and Vajrapāṇi (Vajrin) were repaired. *Sarvavid* is an epithet meaning ‘all-knowing’ and ‘omniscient,’ and is often used to refer to the Buddha, or a buddha. However, *Sarvavid* is also an epithet often specifically used for Vairocana, a possibility that would not be out of context in this inscription. The full Sanskrit of stanzas XLIV–XLV is *tatsthāne sthāpitā sthityai sarvavidvaṅśabhāsvataḥ / prajñāpāramitā tāṛī jananī yena tāyinām // śrīsatyavarmmaṇā bajrilokeśārccā daśādrikāḥ / stāpitāḥ prāg girau bhagnāsanā yo tiṣṭhipat punaḥ* (Coëdès, *IC*, 6: 199).

³⁶ More recently Griffiths (2013: 48, n. 12 and 14) has suggested that the compound *Vajrilokeśa* does not refer to images of Vajrin and Lokeśa, but rather to one kind of image called Vajrilokeśa. He suggests that this name is likely a synonym for Buddhalokeśvara. Griffiths draws upon the Sab Bāk inscription (K. 1158) for support. Although this may be correct, I am not entirely convinced and remain open to both possibilities.

references in the epigraphical record leave little doubt as to its actual presence in the region.

The Eleven-Headed Avalokiteśvara

As mentioned earlier, tenth-century Cambodian conceptions of Avalokiteśvara may have been influenced by concepts found in the *EDMD*, a text connected with the early development of the Mantranaya movement which extols Avalokiteśvara in his eleven-faced or eleven-headed form.³⁷ The strongest evidence for this claim comes from both epigraphical and art historical sources. With regard to the latter, a Khmer bronze figure of Ekādaśamukha was discovered in 1979 in the village of Wat Khanun, Thailand.³⁸ This figure has eleven heads and eleven pairs of hands and stands on the stamen of a lotus. The heads are arranged in three tiers: a main head on lowermost tier, seven heads on the second tier, and three heads on the uppermost tier. The two primary hands are missing, but the other ten pairs display the *abhayamudrā* ('do-not-fear gesture'). Overall, the artistic arrangement of the *sambat* and other Khmer features are related to the Koh Ker style (921–945 CE).³⁹

A higher-quality image of the above mentioned bronze discovered at Wat Khanum was later published in Krairiksh (2012: 292) alongside yet another Khmer bronze

³⁷ For the Gilgit texts (dated to between the fifth and sixth centuries), see Dutt (1984: 59–60) and Vira and Chandra (1974). For an English translation of the Yaśogupta's translation into Chinese, which was completed sometime between 564 and 572 CE, see Wood (1985: 360–73). For an English translation of Amoghavajra's (705–774 CE) expanded and elaborated version of the text (*Shiyi mian Guanzizai pusa xin miyan yigui jing*, 'The Sūtra of the Eleven-headed Avalokiteśvara Bodhisattva Heart Secret Mantra Rituals'), see Grinstead and Sørensen (1994).

³⁸ Krairiksh (1980: 66, 202). I thank Hiram Woodward for bringing this piece to my attention.

³⁹ Krairiksh (1980: 66) notes that the feature that appears to indicate an exception to the Koh Ker style is the loop on the left side, which he claims are remnant of the preceding Bakheng style (893–925 CE).

Ekādaśamukha also dating from the tenth century.⁴⁰ This second piece is currently held in a private collection. In addition to having eleven heads, the bronze is standing, has only four arms, and appears to conform to the early Khleang style of Khmer art that typically dates from the mid-tenth to the early eleventh century. Unfortunately the provenance of this piece is unknown. This variation can also be seen in another four-armed Ekādaśamukha Khmer bronze documented as having sold at a Christie's auction in September 2000.⁴¹ This third bronze is standing and also dates from the tenth century. As with the other four-armed bronze, the provenance of this piece is unknown.

Finally, a fourth bronze image of an eleven-headed Avalokiteśvara dating from around the tenth century was acquired by the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York in 1987 and was mentioned in the opening of this chapter (fig. 6.1). This piece has yet to appear in publication, which highlights the continuing neglect of this early tantric form in studies pertaining to Buddhist traditions in early Cambodia. Like the bronze discovered in Wat Khanun, this piece has a similar conelike configuration of eleven heads and eleven pairs of arms. Unlike the previously mentioned pieces, however, this figure is seated in the *vajrāsana* instead of standing.⁴²

Regarding the epigraphical evidence, the Prasat Chikreng inscription (K. 168) of 972 CE contains an opening invocation to Ekādaśamukha, Lokeśvara, and Bhagavatī

⁴⁰ The caption in the text also postulates that the arrangement of the heads may be influenced by Chinese eleven-headed Avalokiteśvara images. I thank Joseph Bauerschmidt for bringing this bronze, as well as the bronze that sold at Christie's in 2000, to my attention.

⁴¹ Stern (2000). This piece also appeared in Spink and Son (1997: 28–31).

⁴² I currently know of no other eleven-headed sculptures of Avalokiteśvara connected with the Khmers from the tenth century. There are, however, eleven-headed Prajñāpāramitās (?) dated to the eleventh and twelfth centuries. For an example, see Baptiste and Zéphir (2008: 246–48). These figures are in need of more scholarly attention.

(Prajñāpāramitā).⁴³ This inscription has attracted little scholarly attention. Perhaps one of the reasons for this was the initial lack of corroborative art historical evidence that would justify seeing this single reference to Ekādaśamukha as little more than an inconsequential epithet for Avalokiteśvara. The four tenth-century bronzes of Ekādaśamukha mentioned above, however, appear to indicate that worship and practices surrounding Ekādaśamukha represented new and distinct developments in the cult of Avalokiteśvara in early Cambodia. Overall, the inscription—which is written in Old Khmer—is concerned with documenting the donation of such things as livestock on behalf of these three figures. What is most interesting is the actual triad itself. Here Avalokiteśvara is depicted not just as representing compassion but also as a higher, more esoteric form that incorporates him as both compassion and wisdom. Ekādaśamukha’s supreme hierarchical position in the inscription—a position normally occupied by the Buddha in the epigraphy—appears to indicate that in some circles in tenth-century Cambodia there was no functional difference between this higher form of Avalokiteśvara and a buddha.

Huizhao (651–714 CE) produced a commentary in the early eighth century on a translation of the *EDMD*.⁴⁴ Although outside the geographical context of Southeast Asia, Huizhao’s work provides insight into a Buddhist’s interpretation of a figure that was also present in Cambodia a few hundred years later. In the introduction of his commentary, Huizhao writes,

⁴³ Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 168–69). These three names are all prefixed with the Old Khmer titles *vrah kamraten añ*; for.

⁴⁴ Donald Wood (1985: 14) wrote that Huizhao’s commentary (*Shiyi mian shenzhou xin jing yishu*) was based on Xuanzang’s (c. 598–664) translation of the *EDMD* which was completed in 656 CE. Huizhao was Xuanzang’s disciple. Grinstead and Sørensen (1994: 98), however, have written that this commentary attributed to Huizhao was based on an un-specified version of the text.

The eleven faces [possess] the spiritual power that penetrates the three forms of existence and becomes manifest in the six kinds of renunciation, surpassing even the power of the Buddha himself. Thus has it flowed from time immemorial to the present. It embodies both the dharma-nature and the wonderful mercy and wisdom that fills the miracle body and pervades all things.⁴⁵

Based on this short excerpt, it is not surprising that Ekādaśamukha could represent a greater whole, “surpassing even the power of the Buddha himself.” Avalokiteśvara, as Ekādaśamukha, is the embodiment of both compassion and wisdom. In discussing Avalokiteśvara along similar lines, John Holt (1991: 45) has written that, “He (Avalokiteśvara) is the collectively embodied (*sangha* [*sic*]) energy of enlightenment (*prajñā* [*sic*] [wisdom] united with *karuṇā* [compassion]) in their affective states of expression and realization. That is, Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara is Buddha and dharma in a collectively realized, temporal state of action.” This embodied whole and its doctrinal implications are directly represented in the inscription’s hierarchical order: Ekādaśamukha = Lokeśvara (Compassion) + Bhagavatī (Wisdom).

That said, however, it must be admitted that the evidence for the *EDMD*’s influence in early Cambodia is circumstantial, since the argument is based solely on the iconography of the four bronzes cited above and the appearance of the word Ekādaśamukha in the Prasat Chikreng inscription. While one cannot easily dismiss the tantric connections associated with this particular representation of the bodhisattva, on the above evidence alone it is certainly possible that knowledge of the eleven-faced (or eleven-headed) Avalokiteśvara came from another source, or other sources, in which this particular manifestation of the bodhisattva was also present.

⁴⁵ trans. Wood (1985: 374–75).

The Eleven-Headed Avalokiteśvara and the *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra*

The eleven-headed form of Avalokiteśvara is also cited in the *KVS*—a Sanskrit text of complex origins which extols the virtues of Avalokiteśvara and that likely took the form familiar to us between the late fourth and earlier fifth centuries CE in the region of Kashmir.⁴⁶ The earliest surviving manuscripts come from Gilgit and date from a period no later than the seventh century CE (Dutt, 1984: 42). There are also a large number of surviving manuscripts written in Nepālī and Nevarī scripts, and according to Adelheid Mette (1991: 512) some of these manuscripts are dated very early. The text traditions received by the manuscripts from the area of Nepal are also the source of both the Tibetan and Chinese translations of the *KVS* (*ibid.* 511). The *KVS* was brought to Tibet during a period of Buddhist transmission taking place in the late eighth century, and current evidence indicates that a Chinese translation of the text did not take place until the end of the tenth century (*ibid.*; Studholme, 2002: 15).

The *KVS* has been described as a hybrid text in that it represents a body of work in which the categories of sūtra and tantra have blurred and overlapped.⁴⁷ Some of the overlapping tantric elements present in the *KVS* are: the initiation into the use of a *mantra* (the famous *Oṃ Maṇipadme Hūṃ mantra*), instruction in the creation of a *maṇḍala*, partaking of a consecration ritual (*abhiṣeka*), and the role of a *vidyādhara*

⁴⁶ For a short overview regarding the dating of the *KVS*, see Studholme (2002: 9–17). Also see Mette (1991 and 1997); and Schopen (2005b: nn. 12 and 13). It should also be noted that throughout this dissertation I am discussing the earlier prose version of the *KVS*, not the much later verse version, which probably wasn't written until the fifteenth or sixteenth century (see Studholme 2002: 11, 15).

⁴⁷ Studholme (2002: 13). This observation concerning the overlapping between sūtra and tantra, however, was made much earlier by Ruegg (1964: 84), who also claimed the *KVS* displayed similarities with another Buddhist tantric text of the *kriyātantra* class, the *Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa*. Max Nihom (1994: 139) picks up on Ruegg's observations and slightly expands them.

(‘bearer of *mantras*’), all of which also highlight the emphasis on a controlled transfer of special gnosis to a worthy recipient.

Additionally, the text contains unmistakable Śaivite, as well as Vaiṣṇava and purāṇic influences. Examples include, but are not limited to, the appropriation and alteration of purāṇic narratives involving both Śiva and Viṣṇu, the modeling of Avalokiteśvara’s *mantra* on that of Śiva’s own *Namaḥ Śivāya*, and the transformation of Avalokiteśvara into a Buddhist *īśvara* (‘lord’) in the same vein as Śiva and Viṣṇu. In this sense, Avalokiteśvara is no longer a generic *lokeśvara* (‘lord of the world,’ of which there were many), but the one Lokeśvara.

Alexander Studholme (2002: 85) has suggested that the *KVS* was written from the point of view of a Mahāyāna monastic establishment essentially coming to grips with the ever-increasing popularity of charismatic tantric practitioners and their powerful methods and rituals. It is interesting to note that a very similar context may have made the *KVS* attractive to Mahāyāna-oriented monks in Cambodia.

Returning to the eleven-headed form of Avalokiteśvara, we may note that the *KVS* contains two references to this aspect of Avalokiteśvara, although the text specifically uses the Sanskrit compound *ekādaśaśīrṣa* (‘eleven-headed’) instead of *ekādaśamukha* (‘eleven-faced’). The first occurrence is found in part 1, chapter 2, during a narrative scene in which Avalokiteśvara visits the Avīci hell in order to alleviate the suffering of the beings reborn there (a scene alluded to several times in the epigraphical and art historical record). Toward the end of the narrative, Yama, who is in awe of

Avalokiteśvara’s abilities, prostrates himself before the bodhisattva and recites fifty-nine different titles of Avalokiteśvara, one of which is *Ekādaśaśīrṣa*.⁴⁸

The second reference occurs in the *KVS*, part 2, chapter 2. This section deals with the famous episode detailing the description of Avalokiteśvara’s hair pores. The scene describes Avalokiteśvara’s omnipresent body as having eleven heads and a hundred thousand arms and eyes.⁴⁹

This eleven-headed form of Avalokiteśvara appears to be one among seven other unique relief carvings depicting scenes from the *KVS* on the western side of the second enclosure of Banteay Chhmar—a temple complex located in northwestern Cambodia dating from the reign of Jayavarman VII (r. 1182– c. 1218).⁵⁰ Other scenes from the *KVS* depicted on the wall of this temple—such as the subjugation and conversion of Śiva and Umā and the birth of Hindu deities from the body of Avalokiteśvara—appear to indicate that the *KVS* had become an ideal tool to aid in contesting the supremacy of

⁴⁸ *KVS*, in *Mahāyāna-Sūtra-Saṃgraha*, ed. P.L. Vaidya (1961: 262, line 31). I am fully aware of the problems of Vaidya’s edition of the *KVS*, which is based on a late twelfth-century Nepalese manuscript. Unfortunately, however, no critical edition yet exists for the *KVS*, nor is there any published translation of the text in any modern European language, or even another printed text of the *KVS* (besides the Gilgit fragments). While Mette (1991: 514) notes that Vaidya differs from the so-called Nepalese version, she also adds that the “contents and length [i.e., of Vaidya’s version] correspond on the whole.”

⁴⁹ *KVS* 290, line 15. A fair amount of additional detail is devoted to the description of this manifestation, which highlights its importance. An English summary of this scene is found in Studholme (2002: 138). Also note that this description of the eleven-headed Avalokiteśvara is partially preserved in the Gilgit fragments; although only the *e* character from the word *ekādaśaśīrṣa* remains. See Mette (1997: 74–5).

⁵⁰ These scenes were examined in Finot (1925a). Finot’s work was later elaborated on by Jean Boisselier (1965). For images of the reliefs, see plate 141 in Chutiwongs (1984). Also note that only two panels are still standing in situ, while two more panels are on site collapsed amid the rubble. In 1998 a large section of wall, consisting of four panels, was stolen. Two of the panels have since been recovered and are now located at the Phnom Penh National Museum. The other two panels remain unaccounted for. I owe special thanks to Joyce Clark for funding and making possible my first trip to Banteay Chhmar. Additional support for follow-up trips came from a fellowship granted through the Center for Khmer Studies.

Śaivism when Jayavarman began to reign in the late twelfth century.⁵¹ The *KVS*, however, did not obtain this position of privilege overnight. In Cambodia, the roots for dissemination of the text lie in the tenth century.

The *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra* in Tenth-Century Cambodia and Campā

Although the *KVS* is never mentioned by name in Cambodian sources, there is epigraphical evidence that supports the argument that the text—or one closely related to the *KVS* as we know it today—was well known in Cambodia no later than the mid- to late tenth century. The fact that we do not find evidence for the *KVS* in Cambodia until then corresponds to what is known about the wider transmission of this text into areas such as China. Again, while the text was brought to Tibet during the transmission of Buddhism occurring in the late eighth century, it was not brought to China until the late tenth century. Specifically, the Kashmiri Tian Si Tsai (Devaśānti ?) departed for China from the famous Buddhist site of Nālandā in 980 CE; he would later translate the sūtra into Chinese around 983 CE⁵² Therefore, the fact that the text may not have come to Cambodia until later in the tenth century actually corresponds to a period of more widespread transmission of the *KVS* occurring between the late eighth and the late tenth centuries. When we recall that around the mid- to late ninth century the northern polity (or polities) of Campā situated around Thu Bồn valley had regained economic and political power with regard to maritime trade on the route between India and China, it is not implausible to suggest that during this period of widespread transmission the *KVS*

⁵¹ For a summary description of the all eight bas-relief panels, see Chutiwongs (1984: 222–25).

⁵² The Chinese translation of the text I am discussing in the chapter is collected in the *Taisho* version of the Chinese Buddhist *Tripitaka* as volume number 1050 and number 782 in the Nanjio, a collection of Chinese translations of Buddhist texts. Imaeda (1979: 71). Also see Studholme (2002: 15).

may have been brought to the mainland via trading outposts in Campā before eventually being transmitted to Cambodia.

The strongest epigraphical support suggesting influence from the *KVS* is found in two inscriptions from Cambodia (K. 417 and K. 1154) and one from Campā (C. 66).⁵³ Both Cambodian inscriptions are from the tenth century, while the Campā inscription is dated to the late ninth century.

In a paper presented in 1962, and later published in 1965, Jean Boisselier (81) observed that the opening stanza from K. 417 appeared to be a direct reference to the scene in the *KVS* in which Avalokiteśvara transforms the stove used for tormenting the poor souls of Avīci hell into a lotus pool.⁵⁴ The Sanskrit lines can be translated as:

Glory to Lokeśvara, the dust of whose excellent feet thoroughly transformed the vast crackling fires of *avīci* hell into water! Let my obeisance to Him who takes away the torments of hell be a thousandfold!

(K. 417, Prasat Chikreng, st. I)⁵⁵

This observation was later supported by scholars such as Max Nihom (1994: 119–41), who also made connections with the *KVS* in Java.⁵⁶ More recently, Hiram Woodward (forthcoming) has argued that a stanza in inscription C. 66—which is connected with the construction of the temple of Đông Dương in Campā—is likely

⁵³ Regarding these inscriptions, see tables 6.1 and 6.2.

⁵⁴ *KVS* 262, line 9. For a summary of this episode in English, see Studholme (2002: 122).

⁵⁵ My translation. The Sanskrit reads, *lokeśvaro jayati yasya varāṅghridhūlir āvīcikan dhagadhag ity ativṛddhavadhahnim / nīricakāra narakavyasanāpahāre tasmin madīyanatir astu sahasravāram //*.

⁵⁶ Yet again we should note the likely regional connections with Java. We should also note that Nihom argues that the *KVS* influenced part of the *Kuñjarakarnadharmakathana*, a fourteenth- or fifteenth-century Old Javanese didactic poem, which highlights the extent of Buddhist tantric influence in classical Indonesia.

evoking the third chapter of the *KVS* in which Avalokiteśvara liberates the ghost (*preta*) realm:

By day and in the night men afflicted with suffering—and those men condemned to hell—constantly long for your *darśana*; just as thirsty men tormented by the heat of the sun long for cool water in summer, so too they, tormented by the many sufferings in this land, long to see you.

(C. 66, Đông Dương Stele Inscription of Indravarman II, B st. VIII)⁵⁷

Finally, perhaps most important is the only epigraphical citation of the *Oṃ Maṇipadme Hūṃ mantra* in inscription K. 1154, which dates to the tenth century.⁵⁸ The *mantra* appears for the first time in the *KVS*, and this inscription is the only surviving example of its use in early Cambodia.⁵⁹ The inscription appears on one side of a stele on which an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara is depicted on the other side. The two main hands of the bodhisattva are lowered in *pretasantarpitamudrā*, or the gesture of ‘satiated hungry ghosts,’ which invokes the narrative of Avalokiteśvara entering the city of hungry ghosts (*preta*), whereupon ten rivers flow from his fingers (as well as his toes and pores) in order to restore the deformed creatures’ bodies and satiate their thirst and hunger.⁶⁰ This very same iconographic form of Avalokiteśvara can also be seen on a tenth-century stele now kept in the Bangkok National Museum.⁶¹

⁵⁷ My translation. The Sanskrit reads: *duḥkhenābhīhatā narāś ca narake kecit tathā nārakā rātrau vā ca divā tadā ca satataṃ kāṅkṣanti te darśanam / tarṣābhīś ca narā divākarahatā grīṣme jalaṃ śītaṃ ye te draṣṭum anekaduḥkhavihata vecchanti bhūmau yathā //*. For more of Woodward’s work on the *KVS* in Cambodia, see Woodward (2004) and (2007: 70–83).

⁵⁸ For more on this inscription see Pou (2002: 129); Woodward (2007: 72–73); and Skilling (2003).

⁵⁹ Although the *mantra* is referred to throughout the *KVS*, the actual six syllable *mantra* occurs only twice. See *KVS* 297, line 3, and 300, line 23. Although the context differs, the textual counterpart for the six syllable *mantra* in the Gilgit fragments can be found in the National Archives of India (New Delhi), G1 fol. 46a1; facsimiles are collected in Vira and Chandra (1974). Also see Mette (1997: 87).

⁶⁰ Regarding the identification of the *pretasantarpita* gesture, Woodward (2011). The narrative of Avalokiteśvara visiting the *preta* city is found in *KVS* part 1, chapter 3, 263–64. *Pretasantarpita* Lokeśvara is also one of the forms of Avalokiteśvara described in the *Sādhanamālā*, but the iconography described in the *Sādhanamālā* is significantly different from the bodhisattva depicted on the stele.

Taken together, these inscriptions (K. 417, C. 66 and K. 1154) offer enough evidence to suggest that the *KVS* was, in one form or another, circulating in the region during the tenth century and had attained a level of popularity with Buddhists and ruling elites. When considering the tantric characteristics of the *KVS*, the attested presence of Ekādaśamukha in both epigraphical and art historical sources, and the overt references to tantric texts and practices in inscriptions like that of Vat Sithor and An Thái (both of which reference the bodhisattva), we may conclude that the role of Avalokiteśvara was adapted and reconceptualized around the tenth century to conform to new practices and thoughts espoused in tantric Buddhist circles emerging in tenth-century Cambodia.

Final Thoughts

The evidence discussed is enough to indicate that there was an emerging and developing tantric presence in tenth-century Cambodia, connected in some ways with Avalokiteśvara, that should be explored in more depth. In the case of early Cambodia and Campā, I have demonstrated that there are contemporaneous spikes in the epigraphical records of both regions related to the patronage of forms of Mahāyāna Buddhism, and more specifically to the inclusion of Avalokiteśvara in the inscriptions. In other words, Avalokiteśvara becomes a popular figure of royal devotion and patronage at roughly contemporary times in both Cambodia and Campā. Also at this time, both regions for the first time contain Buddhist tantric elements in the inscriptions indicating that existing forms of Mahāyāna Buddhism in the region were being influenced by and adapted to emerging strains of tantric thought and practice.

Bhattacharyya (1924: 141–42); and Sakuma (2002: 154). Also see Bhattacharya (2001) for more on Pretasantarpita Lokeśvara.

⁶¹ For more on this stele, including plates, see Woodward (2007: 74–78).

Due to the nature of the evidence, which is incomplete and fragmentary, the details of these newly emerging forms of tantric Buddhism are still vague and in need of additional examination. Nevertheless, the common tendency to confine Avalokiteśvara to the overgeneralized category of Mahāyāna Buddhism overlooks the complex and multifaceted role of the bodhisattva. Finally, Mahāyāna Buddhism as a catch-all and static category describing roughly seven centuries of Buddhism in Cambodia oversimplifies a history that was likely characterized by frequent change, development, and innovation by Buddhist practitioners and communities. The evidence presented above from the epigraphical and art historical record highlights just a few examples of such change and development.

Figure 6-1. Tenth-century Khmer Bronze of Ekādaśamukha. Source: Green (2014).

Table 6-1. Tenth-Century Cambodia Inscriptions Connected with Avalokiteśvara

Inscription	Provenance	Date	Reference
K. 872	Prasat Beng Vien	944 CE	<i>IC</i> 5: 97–104
K. 238	Toek Chum	949 CE	<i>IC</i> 6: 119–22
K. 157	Vat Kdei Char	953 CE	<i>IC</i> 6: 123–27
K. 266	Bat Chum	953 CE	<i>JA</i> 1908 (2) 213–52
K. 239	Prasat Kôk Samrong	966 CE	<i>IC</i> 3: 79–84
K. 111	Vat Sithor	968 CE	<i>IC</i> 6: 195–211
K. 417	Prasat Chikreng	970 CE	<i>IC</i> 2: 48–50
K. 168	Prasat Chikreng	972 CE	<i>IC</i> 6: 168–69
K. 240	Prasat Ta An	Tenth Century	<i>IC</i> 3: 76–77
K. 214	Phnom Banteay Neang	982 CE	<i>IC</i> 2: 202–06
K. 452	Prasat Plang	988 CE	<i>IC</i> 5: 156–57
K. 225	Thmâ Puok	989 CE	<i>IC</i> 3: 66–69
K. 1154	Unknown	Tenth Century	<i>NIC</i> II & III: 129

Table 6-2. Ninth-Century Northern Cam Inscriptions with Buddhist-Related Content

Inscription	Date	Province	Buddhist Content
C. 66	875 CE	Quảng Nam	Praises to Lokeśvara; founding of monastery
C. 171	Ninth century	Quảng Bình	Silver image of Ratnalokeśvara
C. 172	Ninth century	Quảng Bình	Mentions Jagadguru (epithet Buddha) Praises Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Vajrapāṇi;
C. 138	902 CE	Quảng Nam	installation of a Lokanātha image; mentions Pramuditalokeśvara monastery and unfamiliar tantric three-body doctrine
C. 149	911/912 CE	Quảng Trị	Founding of an Avalokiteśvara monastery
C. 167	914 CE	Kon Tum*	Installation of Mahīndralokeśvara

Table 6.2 Note.—For C. 66, C. 138 and C. 149, see Jacques (1995: 41–57, 252–56, 273–85). For C. 171 and C. 172, see Finot and Goloubew (1925: 472–75). For C. 167, see Finot (1925: 234). The stone beam inscription of Rồn in Quảng Bình (C. 150), possibly from the early ninth century, is often cited as additional evidence from this period for the presence of Avalokiteśvara worship, and Buddhism in general (e.g., Mabbett (1986: 300). The inscription records the donation of land on behalf of a figure called Ḍamareśvara ('lord of riots'). Huber (1911: 267) claimed that Ḍamareśvara was another name for Avalokiteśvara inherited from Śiva. Ever since that time many scholars, myself included, have uncritically accepted Huber's observation, although Huber failed to support his claim with any evidence. Nandana Chutiwongs (1984: 295), and later Arlo Griffiths (in Griffiths et al., 2012: 235–36) who supports Chutiwongs' position, have noted that the primary reason to associate the inscription with Buddhism is the inclusion of the word *vihāra* ('monastery'), and the fact that many of the northernmost Cam inscriptions are Buddhists; however, they both note that such reasons are not conclusive and the word *vihāra* may also refer to a Śaiva monastery. Therefore, until additional evidence is put forth conclusively demonstrating that Ḍamareśvara refers to Avalokiteśvara I cannot include C. 150 with the other Buddhist inscriptions from the northernmost regions of Campā.

* The Kon Klor inscription (C. 167) remains unpublished; however, according to Finot (1925a: 234) the inscription was found on one of two ablution receptacles (*yoni*) found in the village of Kon Klor located in Kon Tum province. This province neighbors Quảng Nam province to the south(west). Based on its location, date and Buddhist content which record the installation of Mahīndralokeśvara by one Mahīndrādhipati, I think it should be grouped with the other inscriptions mentioned in the table.

CHAPTER 7

THE RHETORIC OF IDENTITY: A CRITIQUE OF BUDDHIST AND BRAHMANICAL CONFLICT ARGUMENTS IN TENTH-CENTURY CAMBODIA

Certain stanzas in the Vat Sithor inscription—as well as a few stanzas from other tenth-century inscriptions such the Bat Cum inscriptions—are sometimes interpreted in a manner that suggests some kind of unique ongoing tension and conflict between Brahmanical and Buddhist groups in tenth-century Cambodia.¹ The small amount of examples cited in support of this view are purportedly representative of the disparaging attitude directed toward Buddhist groups by their Brahmanical rivals, and this hostility and tension arose from a certain amount of resentment brought about when Buddhists began to intrude upon the domain the more dominant Brahmins. In short, the current paradigm maintains that the emerging Buddhist presence in tenth-century Cambodia was unwelcomed by Brahmanical groups, and this position is supported by the epigraphical record. To be sure, Buddhism and Brahmanism share a long history of polemical debate and competition for patronage that sometimes created tensions and hostilities between the two groups.² This fact would seem to support the view that there was a strain between the two groups in early Cambodia that was in line with similar interactions that continued to take place in other regions such as India. I will argue,

¹ Snellgrove (2001) is the best example of a work stressing this Brahmanical/Buddhist tension purportedly present in tenth-century Cambodia epigraphical sources such as the Vat Sithor and Bat Cum inscriptions. The underlying assumption of tension and conflict between these two groups, however, permeates other works, even when subtle or not being emphasized. Sharrock (2012), for example, assumes such a stance when he observes that Buddhists must have been met with resentment and that the friction between the two groups is apparent in examples such as stanza LXVIII of the Vat Sithor inscription, which he sees as an admonition of the Buddhist community. Mertens (2000: 400) remarks that this and other stanzas in the Vat Sithor inscription are disparaging against Buddhists. Even early on when he examined the Vat Sithor inscription Senart (1883: 190) spoke of the two groups as opposing cults because of how he interpreted the inscription.

² For a recent historical examination with new insights on the evolving relationship between Buddhism and Brahmanism, see Bronkhorst (2011).

however, that whether or not there was any real tension or hostility between Buddhists and Brahmans in tenth-century Cambodia misses the point. The primary purpose of the oft cited stanzas was to not to disparage or subordinate the Buddhist community; rather the purpose of their inclusion in the epigraphy was to provide didactic reminders to the Buddhist monastic community concerning what practices were held to have no efficacious effect according to the teachings of the Buddha. Because such practices were not efficacious, there was an expectation that such activities would be abstained from for soteriological reasons. While such a strategy helped establish and maintain a distinction between these two groups, the purpose of stressing this distinction was not undertaken to foster discontent and tension (although it may have to some extent); instead, by emphasizing certain distinctions a clear Buddhist identity was promoted and maintained. I call this process of identity distinction and creation in the epigraphy the rhetoric of identity.

The Ban on Sacrifice in the Vat Sithor Inscription

Section VI of the Vat Sithor inscription describes certain behaviors, practices, and rites that were expected to be followed at the Buddhist monastery, primarily for the purpose of obtaining religious merit (Skt. *punya*). Stanza LXVI, for example, indicates how one should be respectful toward particularly learned individuals and prepare donations for them if one desires merit. Stanza LXVII states how at dawn and other times the monastic community is expected to perform the rites that have been explained by the Buddha. Stanza LXXI claims that the Dharma is prosperous when one performs the rite of bathing the Buddha's image, and stanzas LXXII and LXIII stress the importance of ritual recitation (especially in the presence of the Buddha's image). Again, all such activities were held to have soteriological benefit in that the religious

merit accrued from these practices could, for example, affect one's rebirth. This section is a natural follow-up to the section V, a section which explains what is necessary for the proper establishment of a Buddhist monastery and the merit one can expect to attain if such guidelines are followed. For instance, stanza LVIII indicates that dedicating a monastery to the Three Jewels of Buddhism results in great merit. Both stanzas LXI and LXII also stress the role of merit in the proper establishment of a monastery. Of course the emphasis on merit acquisition in both sections was also of social and economic importance. A Buddhist economy of merit represents "a symbiotic structural exchange of material donations for religious merit [that] directly connects the establishment, maintenance, and growth of Buddhist monastic institutions to networks of social and economic support" (Neelis, 2011: 17). This observation appears just as true in early Cambodia as it was in other parts of the world where Buddhist monastic centers were established.

Despite this rather overt concern with the proper establishment of the monastery, the proper practices to be observed at the monastery, and the acquisition of religious merit in this section of the inscription, one particular stanza stands out from the rest as representative of some kind of Brahmanical oppression and tension. Stanza LXVIII states:

Members of the Buddhist community (*saṅgha*) are not invited to approach any sacrificial rites; those who voluntarily come near that place (i.e., the site where the sacrifices are performed), even with good intentions, incur guilt.

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. LXVIII)³

³ Skt. *na saṃghais sarvvayajñeṣu gantavyam animantritaiḥ / svayaṃ prāptā hitenāpi tattraite pāpabhāgiṇaḥ //*, Coedès (*IC*, 6: 200). For comments regarding my choice of translation for this stanza along with a few critiques on previous translations, refer to chapter two of this dissertation.

In this context the sacrificial rites (Skt. *yajña*) being referred to were almost certainly the Brahmanical sacrificial practices that were grounded in Vedic and later Brahmanical sources. Snellgrove (2001: 809–10) has interpreted this stanza, along with other stanzas in the Vat Sithor and Bat Cum inscriptions, as proof that Buddhist traditions were “clearly at a disadvantage” compared to their Brahmanical rivals. Snellgrove is right to observe that Brahmanical traditions and Buddhist traditions were clearly separate and (in many cases) doctrinally hostile to one another, but he is reading this and other stanzas as the hostile interjections of Brahmanical rivals looking to suppress and restrict the activities of encroaching Buddhists. This is not the case. The stanza is not proof of a restrictive regulation stemming from hostile Brahmanical opponents; rather, it is a restrictive regulation directed to the Buddhist community by Buddhists themselves who were critiquing the purported efficacy of certain Brahmanical practices such as sacrifices that involved the killing of the animals.

The Buddhist critique of Brahmanical practices of sacrifice is well attested in textual sources. What is often specifically repudiated in Buddhist sources is the practice of animal sacrifice. This practice is depicted not only as cruel, but also as ineffective with respect to one’s well-being and salvation. The *Kosalasaṃyutta* of the *Saṃyutta Nikāya* (I.3.9), for example, not only condemns Brahmanical sacrifice of animals, but also claims that such a practice fails to produce ‘fruit’ and that the ‘great seers of right conduct’ (i.e., monks) are not to attend such practices (much like monks in the Vat Sithor inscription being told that they are not to attend Brahmanical sacrifices).

The horse sacrifice, human sacrifice, these great sacrifices, fraught with violence, do not bring great fruit. The great seers of right conduct do not

attend that sacrifice where goats, sheep, and cattle of various kinds are slain.⁴

This is not an isolated example. The *Kūṭadanta Sutta* of the *Dīgha Nikāya* (1.5), for instance, contains a lengthy narrative that focuses on what constitutes, from a Buddhist perspective, proper and beneficial sacrifices. The narrative reveals how in a former life as a sacerdotal minister, the Buddha performed a great many beneficial sacrifices on behalf of the king, and none of these sacrifices involved the killing of animals. When the Buddha is explaining this story of the past to an interested Brahmin in the present, he outlines various examples of what a proper (Buddhist) sacrifice would entail. He indicates, for example, that continually donating gifts to virtuous monks is both less difficult than violent forms of sacrifice and more advantageous to one's spiritual welfare. Other examples of proper sacrifices listed include: constructing a monastery for the benefit of the Buddhist community (a meritorious act that is also exemplified in the Vat Sithor inscription), taking refuge in the Three Jewels (the Buddha, Dharma, and Saṅgha), adopting the Buddhist precepts (a moral set of practices that involve abstaining from violence and the taking of life), and so forth.⁵

In some sources even Brahmanical fire sacrifice is depicted as ineffective, as is the case in a narrative found in the *Mahāvagga* of the Vinaya piṭaka that depicts the Buddha as claiming that once he discovered the Dharma he no longer employed fire

⁴ trans. Bodhi (2000: 171–72). It should be noted, however, that this section does not condemn all forms of sacrifice, only those sacrifices involving animals. For example, traditional family offerings that do not involve violence are not condemned. Pali canon sources vacillate between condemning and accepting other forms of sacrifice (e.g., the acceptance of fire sacrifice). Often an acceptable sacrifice (Skt. *yajña*, P. *yañña*) is viewed in Pali sources as the donation of gifts and other offerings to monastic community (for numerous examples, see PTS s.v., *yañña*). Krishan (1993) argues that only Buddhist monks were banned from more traditional forms of sacrifice and that the laity was free to continue many of these practices, with the exception of the widespread condemnation of animal sacrifice.

⁵ For more on this particular discourse, see Davids (1899: 160–85).

implements or delighted in the fire sacrifice.⁶ A much more scathing attack against Brahmanical fire sacrifice is found in the *Bhūridatta jātaka*.⁷ Part of what is really under attack in this particular *jātaka* is the Brahmanical position that maintains an individual's transgressions and other vices can be absolved by means of performing a sacrifice. The Buddhists repudiated the belief that Brahmanical sacrifices could purify the performer of the sacrifice and that such practices could result in a heavenly rebirth or liberation. Buddhist sources, however, are not consistent in their position on this non-violent form of sacrifice since some sources do not depict this practice in a negative light.⁸ Additionally, fire sacrifice was clearly not condemned according to the Vat Sithor inscription since sacerdotal ministers skilled in this practice were considered worthy of donations.⁹ The real issue, therefore, is the ban on sacrifices involving the killing of animals, a practice that would have been regularly performed by Brahmins existing and operating in the same vicinity.

The condemnation of animal sacrifice is strongly related to one of the foundational Buddhist precepts that insist on practitioners abstaining from taking any life. One of the initial oaths taken by a novice entering the *saṅgha* involves reaffirming these foundational precepts. In the *Pravrajyāvastu* of the Sanskrit Mūlasarvāstivādin Vinaya, for example, the prospective novice recites, “Let the ācārya hear me. Henceforth for life, I, such and such a one, abandon the killing of living beings and desist from it, as

⁶ See Horner (4: 46–48) for a translation of this narrative.

⁷ See *jātaka* number 543 in Cowell (1907).

⁸ Again, see Krishan (1993).

⁹ cf. stanza LXIX.

was done by the venerable arhats during their life time.”¹⁰ Furthermore, taking an animal’s life is considered a *pāyantika* offense and requires expiation on the part of the transgressing monk. In the *Prātimokṣa Sūtra* of both the Mahāsāṃghika and Mūlasarvāstivādin Vinayas *pāyantika* offense number 61 of 90 states, “Whatever monk should intentionally deprive an animal of life, that is a offense requiring expiation” (i.e., a *pāyantika* or *pācattika* offense).¹¹ The taking of a human life is a much more severe transgression, and is one the four *pārājika* offenses; that is, a serious offense resulting in permanent expulsion from the saṅgha.¹²

These are just a few examples, but they are enough to illustrate that there is nothing particular odd about stanza LXVIII of the Vat Sithor inscription. The stanza is simply reiterating a position found in many Buddhist textual sources concerning the ban on Brahmanical sacrifice (involving animals), and there is certainly no justification in seeing this stanza as evidence of Brahmins attempting to undermine Buddhists or somehow subordinate or disparage them. In the context of other Buddhist sources, the stanza becomes an articulation of a Buddhist monastic position critiquing Brahmanical practices. If any group is disparaging the other, it is the Buddhists who are disparaging the Brahmins. The monastic importance of the stanza is evident in the fact that attending such sacrificial rites resulted in an offense for the transgressing monk. I would argue that voluntarily attending these sacrifices was considered equivalent to

¹⁰ For a synopsis, see Banerjee (1957: 108).

¹¹ The Mūlasarvāstivādin Vinaya uses the term *pāyantika*, while the Mahāsāṃghika Vinaya uses the term *pācattika*. For a complete translation of the *Prātimokṣa Sūtra* from both these Vinaya traditions, see Prebish (1975).

¹² The other three *pārājika* offenses are: (1) sexual intercourse, (2) theft, and (3) false proclamation of superhuman abilities.

actual participation, and thus resulted in an offense requiring expiation. This punishment is in line with Buddhist Vinaya sources that also require expiation for taking the life of an animal.

Before turning to a similar misunderstanding in the Bat Cum inscriptions, the use of one particular term used in this same section of the Vat Sithor inscription also needs to be discussed since its presence appears to bolster the argument that Buddhists were somehow being disparaged and overshadowed by more dominant Brahmins. The term is *purohita*, a Sanskrit word variously translated as ‘sacerdotal minister,’ ‘royal chaplain,’ ‘head priest,’ etc. In general, the word is used either for the head priest of a family or for a high-ranking socioreligious advisor responsible for conducting the ceremonial rites of a ruler. In early Cambodia, the king’s *purohita* often came from one of several powerful sacerdotal families of Brahmins which had been granted hereditary rights to provide official ceremonial functions.¹³ The word is used twice in the Vat Sithor inscription. Both occurrences appear in section VI of the inscription immediately following the stanza recording the restriction on attending Brahmanical sacrifice.

The *purohita* who is learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, *vidyā*, *mantra*, *mudrā* and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṇṭā*), is worthy of donations.

On the *parva* days, the *purohita* should perform the ritual bathing and so forth of the Sage (i.e., the Buddha) together with the hymns of the Veda, the *ārṣabha*, the *brahmaghoṣa*, the eye-opening ceremony (*unmīla*), and the ritual sprinkling (*abhiṣecana*).

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. LXIX–LXX)¹⁴

¹³ Briggs (1952) still remains one of the best works devoted to the sacerdotal families of early Cambodia.

¹⁴ For extensive comments on these stanzas, especially the technical terms, refer to the translation in chapter two. I will reiterate one point with regard to the mentioning of the Veda. The importance of Vedic hymns in the list of rituals is noteworthy, but should not be construed as strange. Cœdès (*JC*, 6: 209, n. 4) noted that the reference is specifically referring to the Gāthāveda recorded and defined in stanza LXII,

These stanzas reconfirm that the *purohita* was a high-ranking officiant responsible for presiding over and performing some of the most important ceremonies conducted at the monastery during the *parva* days (i.e., special ritual days marking the four changes of the moon). Based on these passages it would seem that the authority and influence of Brahmins in early Cambodia was powerful enough for them to have a *purohita* conduct important ceremonies even at a Buddhist monastery. Furthermore, arguments for tensions, hostilities, disparaging attitudes, and so forth appear quite justifiable if this is an example of a high-ranking Brahmin operating within a Buddhist monastery and conducting important ritual practices that involve, among other things, the image of the Buddha installed at the monastery.

The first of the two stanzas (st. LXIX), however, reveals a subtle but important clue concerning how a *purohita* was understood according to the Vat Sithor inscription. In fact, stanza LXIX actually redefines what kind of person was to be considered a true and authoritative *purohita*, and this redefinition makes clear that the individual had to be a person well-versed in Buddhist doctrine and practice. Again, the stanza indicates that not only is the worthy (i.e., acceptable) *purohita* a person that has knowledge of traditional fire sacrifice, but the worthy *purohita* is also a person that has knowledge of *vidyā* ('incantations'), *mantra* ('sacred formulas'), *mudrā* ('sacred gestures') and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṇṭā*). The reference to the *vajra* and the bell, two iconic ritual instruments utilized in tantric forms

and as such the term may be simply be referring to 'hymns of knowledge,' and not necessarily the Vedas used by Brahmins and other non-Buddhist sects. Even if the stanza does refer to the more traditional Vedas, this would not alter the fact that the role of the *purohita* according to this inscription is (re)defined to mean an individual that is also well-versed and acquainted with Buddhist thought and practice.

of Buddhism, demonstrates that the monastery engaged the services of an officiant grounded in Buddhist thought and practice (some of which would have required years of study and training), not some traditional sectarian Brahmin hostile to Buddhism. This stanza, therefore, is not an example of Brahmanical infringement of the Buddhists' domain but, rather, quite the opposite. The stanza demonstrates that it was the Buddhists who were infringing upon the traditional domain of Brahmins by appropriating and redefining some of their sacerdotal roles. This is also evident in an earlier section of the Vat Sithor inscription (st. XXXVI) that records how Kīrtipaṇḍita was employed by the king to perform at the palace the official rites of pacification (*śānti*) and prosperity (*puṣṭi*) for the kingdom, official ceremonial rites typically performed by the king's head officiant, the *purohita*.

This appropriation and redefinition of what a so-called true *purohita* is according to Buddhists has some precedent in textual sources. As noted by Bronkhorst (2011: 37), the word *purohita* is known in Buddhist canonical sources, but it does not appear frequently. The term appears, for example, in the *Kūṭadanta Sutta* that was mentioned previously. Again, in that narrative the Buddha is the *purohita* of a king in a past life. As the king's *purohita*, all of the sacrificial rites the Buddha conducts, however, are quite different from those performed by the typical *purohita*. His sacrificial rites, for example, involved no killing of animals; yet they ushered in peace and prosperity for the realm. The author(s) of the narrative was essentially redefining how a so-called true and effective *purohita* should be understood (according to Buddhists). In short, the Sutta is a perfect example of Buddhist polemical writing. Remarking on the use of the word *purohita* in this and other Pāli Suttas, Bronkhorst (2011: 38) writes, "all of them, with the

exception of the *Mahāpadāna Sutta*, which is totally uninformative on this matter, criticize the way of life the Purohita stands for, either by involving him directly in activities that are to be rejected, or more subtly by suggesting that the only good Purohita is a buddhist Purohita (to adapt a well-known expression).”

Rules and Pools

Two architectural accomplishments recorded in the Bat Cum inscriptions deserve special attention since similar anti-Buddhist interpretations surround the use of these structures that have affected how scholars understand Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia and their relationship with Brahmanical groups. The structures in question are the *parikhā* and the *taṭāka* constructed by Kavīndrārimathana. The *parikhā* probably refers to an ancillary canal, although the term can also refer to a moat or ditch of some sort. The *taṭāka* refers to a large reservoir of water known as a *baray* in Khmer. Due to a rather loose reading of the inscriptions Snellgrove (2001) erroneously conflated these two structures. This conflation of the *parikhā* and *taṭāka*, as well as the resulting scholarly interpretation regarding the rites and regulations pertaining to these two structures, has adversely affected our understanding of Buddhist traditions in tenth-century Cambodia. Furthermore, as in the case of the Vat Sithor inscription, lines of interpretation that insist Buddhists residing in the vicinity of Bat Cum were somehow subordinated to local Brahmins and their ritual interests is both mistaken and a misunderstanding of the inscription’s content.

The Conflation of Kavīndrārimathana’s *parikhā* and *taṭāka*

Snellgrove (2001: 809–11) examined the contents of the Bat Cum inscriptions and the Vat Sithor inscription and argued that that Buddhist traditions between the tenth to eleventh centuries were severely disadvantaged, especially in the vicinity of Angkor.

Furthermore, he believed that the pool (singular) constructed by Kavīndrarāmathana was primarily reserved for the use of Brahmanical prelates whom he viewed as somewhat antagonistic, or unwelcoming, toward Buddhists who operated in the same vicinity. Snellgrove's interpretations, however, are based on a rather loose, and sometimes faulty, reading of the Bat Cum inscriptions. His conclusions appear to be primarily based on Cœdès' own reading and translation of the inscriptions, and this explains part of the problem.¹⁵ Although Cœdès' enormous corpus of scholarly contributions, particularly in the field of epigraphy, continue to be influential, informative and often invaluable, his interpretations of the inscriptions were not always correct (Vickery, 2000). But the problematic issues cannot be attributed solely to Cœdès since on more than one occasion Snellgrove fails to appreciate certain lexical distinctions in French made by Cœdès, especially with regard to the distinction between the *parikhā* and *taṭāka*.¹⁶

A comparison of select stanzas rendered into English by Snellgrove, and my own English translations from the original Sanskrit illustrate this point. I have purposely left several Sanskrit terms untranslated in my version in order to highlight them for later discussion. Cœdès' original French translation, as well as the Sanskrit, is included in the footnotes for additional reference.

¹⁵ Although Snellgrove does cite Cœdès' work on Bat Cum, he does not explicitly indicate if the English translations he includes are secondary translations from the French. In comparing the two translations, however, it appears that Snellgrove rendered most of the English translations included in the article directly from Cœdès' French translations of the original Sanskrit. Snellgrove does, however, occasionally depart from the French in order to make certain clarifying remarks in his article. Whether or not Snellgrove examined the actual Sanskrit I cannot say.

¹⁶ For example, Snellgrove sometimes uses the English word 'pool' for both structures in his article and this was a disservice to Cœdès who was a bit more consistent in distinguishing the two structures. He used different French words for the structures *parikhā* (fossé or mare = moat, ditch, pond, etc) and *taṭāka* (étang = pond, lake, etc.). Snellgrove, therefore, was not only loose with the Sanskrit, but with Cœdès' French translation as well.

(Kavīndrārimathana) has constructed a pool, which purifies with its pure water just as knowledge leads to nirvāṇa. In accordance with Buddhist ritual he has created this pool,¹⁷ honored by the great and intended to bring joy to living beings, while contributing to the prosperity of the Dharma. In the sacred water of this lake,¹⁸ worthy of the frolics of flamingos, only the King's chief prelate (purohita) and Brahmans have the right to bathe. Elephants which destroy the banks of this pool must be kept away by the lion-like sadhus (holy men) with the hair-style of the Dharma.

(K. 268, Bat Cum, st. XXXVIII–XLI, Snellgrove, 2001: 805–06)¹⁹

He has constructed this *parikhā* which is filled with pure clear water, just as he (has constructed) *nirvaṇa* (which is filled) with knowledge.²⁰ For the delight of all beings he has built a *taṭāka* according to the Buddhist way, which is respected by the great (and) increases the prosperity of the Dharma.²¹ “Only the king's *purohita* (and) *vipra*²² may perform ablutions²³

¹⁷ Note here that according to the Sanskrit this ‘pool’ is not the same structure as the ‘pool’ referred to in the first sentence.

¹⁸ Now he is using the term ‘lake’ for what he previously called a ‘pool.’ It is not at all clear what structures are being referred to and how.

¹⁹ Cœdès' French translation is as follows: XXXVIII. Il a construit ce fossé qui donne la purification par son eau pure, comme la science donne le Nirvāṇa. XXXIX. Il a fait selon les rites buddhiques, cet étang destiné à faire la joie de tous les êtres, honoré des grands, et contribuant à faire prospérer le Dharma. XL. « Dans l'eau sacrée de cette mare digne des ébats des flamants, le Purohita du roi et les Brahmanes seuls auront le droit de se baigner. » Tel est son désir. XLI. Les gens de bien, pareils à des lions, portant la splendide crinière du Dharma, devront écarter de l'eau de cet étang les éléphants qui détruisent les rives.

²⁰ My translation of this stanza is influenced by the interpretation in Mertens (2005: 109–10), which I think rightly identifies the underlying pun, and therefore, better captures the intended meaning. In short, Mertens suggested that the stanza is alluding to Kavīndrarīmathana's earlier act of installing (i.e., ‘constructing’ or ‘establishing’) a Prañjāpāramitā image, and Prañjāpāramitā (as the very personification of the Perfection of Wisdom and synonymous with *nirvāṇa*) is ‘filled’ with knowledge.

²¹ Note here that unlike Cœdès' translation, it is the Buddhist way (Skt. *-caritaṃ buddhaṃ . . .*) that is respected by the great (i.e., individuals of high social standing) not the *taṭāka* itself. Mertens (2005 : 110) also shares this interpretation.

²² The word *vipra* refers to a learned or wise individual. The word is also sometimes synonymous with Brahmans, or particularly learned Brahmans.

²³ The use of *snāyaka* deserves some special remarks. More literally, the Sanskrit *rājahaṅśāvagāhārhe puṇye rājapurohitaḥ / snāyakāḥ parikhānīre *viprā* (corr: *vīprā*) *eveṭi tanmatih* // could be translated as “In the water of the *parikhā*, which is meritorious and worthy of bathing royal swans, only the king's *purohita* (and) *vipra* (are) *snāyakas*,” this (is his) decision. Mertens (2005: 111) suggested that the word was probably related to *snāyin* (‘bathing,’ or ‘performing an ablution’), but was not lexicographically known. I understand *snāyaka* to be a reference to a some kind of Brahmanical purifying water ritual. In the context of the inscription, it probably refers to the either the Brahmanical ablution rite that is believed to purify the individual of any transgressions (Skt. *pāpa*) or devotional offerings of water performed in order to satiate gods, seers, and ancestors (i.e., *tarpaṇa* rites), an observation strongly supported by the Bat Cum

in the water of the *parikhā*, which is meritorious and worthy of bathing royal swans,” this (is his) decision.²⁴ From the grove of the *taṭāka*, elephants must be kept from destroying its banks by the lion-like *sādhus* with shining Dharma-manes.

(K. 268, Bat Cum, st. XXXVIII–XLI, Green)²⁵

The first and most obvious point that needs to be stressed is that two different water-related structures were constructed by Kavīndrārimathana: a *parikhā* (a type of canal) and a *taṭāka* (a reservoir). The inscription is not discussing a single pool of water. Additionally, according to the Bat Cum inscriptions all Brahmanical rites pertaining to ablutions (‘bathing’) are limited to the *parikhā* and do not extend to the *taṭāka*. The inscriptions do not record any other special prerogatives that Brahmins may have enjoyed at the site of Bat Cum. There is no indication that any Brahmanical influence or control confined Buddhists to a small amount of space at Bat Cum. The inscription merely indicates that Kavīndrārimathana, on behalf the king, had two water-related structures built. The first, the smaller *parikhā*, was imposed with a restriction by the king that limited who could perform ritual ablutions in its waters. According to the

inscription located at the south sanctuary which indicates that the pure waters of *parikhā* provide abundant fruit for those who bathe in its waters (K. 266, st. XXI). Also cf. M.W. s.v., *snāṭaka*. The word has appeared in at least one other source. Edgerton (BHS s.v., *snāyaka*) glossed the word as ‘in order to bathe’ and noted that it was a form of Buddhist-Hybrid Sanskrit that was used in the *Mahāvastu* (iii.313.7). But we should note that even in the narrative found in the *Mahāvastu*, the term is referring to no ordinary bath. According the account in the *Mahāvastu*, after six years of austerities, the Bodhisattva (i.e., the Buddha just prior to his enlightenment) realized that such practices were not conducive to his goal, so he decided to approach the problem of suffering differently. In leaving behind a life of austere asceticism, he decided to enter a sacred river and ‘bathe,’ an event that marks his transition from practicing extreme asceticism to practicing the middle way. This bath in the river was a purifying event in anticipation of his upcoming enlightenment. I should note that the *Mahāvastu* includes another event involving the washing of a dusty hemp robe given to him by a poor washerwoman just prior to his bath, but a discussion of the significance of his actions with the robe would take us too far astray.

²⁴ i.e., the decision of Rājendravarman.

²⁵ The Sanskrit for stanzas XXXVIII–XLI is as follows: *svacchena pāvanenāptāṃ payasā parikhāṃ imam / yathā nirvaṇasaṃprāptiṃ jñānena sa vinirmame // sarvasattvābhinandārthaṃ taṭākaṃ mahatāṃ matam / sa yathācaritaṃ baudhaṃ vidadhau dharmavardhanam // rājahaṅsāvagāhārhe puṇye rājapurohitaḥ / snāyakaḥ parikhānīre *viprā (corr: vīprā) eveti tanmatih // taṭākavanatas tasya mātaṅgās taṭabhaṅginaḥ / sādhusinḥair nirudhyantāṃ dharmakesarabhāsurañ //*, Coedès, (1908b: 236–37).

inscription, only the *purohita* and *vipra* (probably other learned Brahmins) were allowed to perform such ablutions, and only in the special waters of the *parikhā* at the site Bat Cum. The *purohita* and *vipra* are described as *snāyakas*, a word that probably means something along the line of ‘those who perform the bath’ or ‘those who perform ablutions.’ This part of the inscription has often been translated to mean that only the *purohita* and Brahmins had a right to ‘bathe’ in the *parikhā*. The term, however, is not referring to mere hygienic bathing; instead, it is probably a reference to either traditional Brahmanical ablution rites in which a Brahmin purifies oneself of transgressions (Skt. *pāpa*) by means of a ritual bath or devotional offerings of water performed in order to satiate gods, seers, and ancestors (i.e., *tarpaṇa* rites).²⁶ These rites were not only considered efficacious and purifying by Brahmins, but also meritorious. This observation is supported by another Bat Cum inscription located at the south sanctuary which indicates that the pure waters of *parikhā* provide abundant fruit for those who bathe in its waters (K. 266, st. XXI), an important stanza that will be returned later in the chapter. The second larger structure, the *taṭāka*, was built for the enjoyment and use of all beings with no apparent restrictions. The king assigns the upkeep and protection of the banks or dikes of the *taṭāka* to the local Buddhist monks (the ‘lion-like *sādhus* with shining Dharma-manes,’ i.e., the ones with shining shaven pates).

Based on this information, there seems to be a fair demarcation of property between two sectarian groups (Buddhist and Brahmins) operating and coexisting in the vicinity of Bat Cum. The intent of the regulations in the Bat Cum inscriptions does not seem to be a negative one that seeks to exclude Buddhists from participating in special

²⁶ cf. *R̥g Veda* 10.9 for a textual source extolling the benefits of water purification.

ritual privileges granted to select learned Brahmin, as if to deprive them of honor and subordinate them to the latter. Two additional observations support this conclusion: (1) the Buddhists, according to other textual sources, had no desire to perform Brahmanical ablutions since, like animal sacrifices, viewed such rituals as being ineffective; therefore, they were not being deprived of any special privilege, and (2) the king's regulation also coincides with some outside Brahmanical sources that insist such sacred cleansing spots are not to belong to other men and that the source of water should be natural (a point discussed later in the chapter); therefore, the imposed regulation is not highlighting divisions and hostilities between Brahmins and Buddhists unique to an early Cambodia setting. With this slight shift in perspective, the king's regulation can be understood as an order that was merely reinforcing already established Buddhist and Brahmanical positions on certain activities, rather than an order to be seen as subordinating Buddhists to Brahmins by granting the latter special privileges supposedly desired by both groups.

Buddhists and Water Purification

According to many textual sources, the Buddha is frequently described as deriding the efficacy of Brahmanical ritual bathing. The Saṃyutta Nikāya of the Pāli Tipiṭaka, for example, goes as far as to claim that the celibate, or holy, life of a monk is a higher path that does not require ritual bathing, and that this celibate path is the bath without water.²⁷ Elsewhere in the *Brāhmaṇasaṃyutta* of the Saṃyutta Nikāya (I.7.21), the

²⁷ SN I.1.58. The quotation occurs in the *Uppatha Sutta* ('The Discourse Concerning the Wrong Path') as part of a series of questions posed by a *devatā* to the Buddha. The full quotation from the Myanmar Tipiṭaka is as follows:

(Devatā:) kiṃsu uppatho akkhāto kiṃsu rattindivakkhayo / kiṃ malaṃ brahmacariyassa kiṃ sinānamanodakan'ti //

Buddha explains to a Brahmin named Saṅgārava who is performing purification by water that the Dharma is the true source of purification and its 'lake' does not become muddy when people enter its water for purification.²⁸

The *Vatthūpama Sutta* of the Majjhima Nikāya (M.I.7) contains a similar argument. When asked by the Brahmin Sundarika Bhāradvāja (who believes the Bāhukā river was a source of liberation, merit, and purification) why he does not go to the river to bathe, the Buddha replies that a fool may bathe in a river forever and still not be purified. He then tells him that if he seeks purification he should bathe in the Dharma by not injuring anyone, being honest, not stealing, and so forth. Perhaps one of the most witty and disparaging retort to the supposed efficacy of Brahmanical ablution is attributed to a Buddhist nun named Puṇṇa who asks rhetorically that if cleansing in water can purify and liberate then why have not the fishes, turtles, frogs, snakes and all of creatures that inhabit the water gone straight to heaven?²⁹

(Bhagavā:) rāgo uppatho akkhāto vayo rattindivakkhayo / itthī malaṃ brahmacariyassa etthāyaṃ sajjate pajā / tapo ca brahmacariyañca taṃ sinānamanodakan'ti //

(Devatā:) "What is proclaimed the wrong path? What is decayed day and night? What is the stain of a celibate life? What is the bath without water?"

(Bhagavā:) "Passion is the wrong path. Youth is decayed day and night. A woman is the stain of a celibate life. In these matters men* are attached. Austerities and the celibate life, that is the bath without water."

*As women are singled out as an obstruction to leading a celibate/holy life, I selected 'men' for the term *pajā* as opposed to some gender-neutral term like 'humanity' or 'living beings.' The passage is clearly elevating the life of those celibate Buddhist male monks who diligently practice the Buddhist Dharma, as opposed to those Brahmins who rely on bathing rituals to purify their sins and make them better.

²⁸ The Brahmin tells the Buddha that he performs this water purification because whatever evil deed he commits during the day he is able to wash away at night with his ritual bath. For an English translation with notes, see Bodhi (2000: 278–79).

²⁹ This account is found in the *Puṇṇātherīgāthā*, a section of the Therīgāthā ('Songs of the Female Elders') in the Khuddaka Nikāya (IX.65). Specifically, see stanzas 238–241. Interestingly enough, Brahmanical sources have actually addressed this specific critique. Nārāyaṇa Bhaṭṭa's *Tristhalīsetu* quotes the *Kāśīkhaṇḍa* that states: "A man does not become pure by getting rid of bodily impurities; but when metal impurities are abandoned, then he becomes immaculate within. Fish are born and die in the

A Brahmanical Justification for the *parikhā*

The act of ablutions or religious bathing (Skt. *snāna*) is considered in later law books such as the *Parāśarasmṛti* to be one of the six daily duties for traditional Brahmins (Skt. *ṣaṭkarman*), thus highlighting the importance of the practice.³⁰ Performing this important traditional rite specifically at the *parikhā* may also have an explanation grounded in traditional sources. According to one of the other Bat Cum inscriptions, the *parikhā* had one more significant characteristic that the *taṭāka* lacked; it was fed by the pure and natural waters streaming down from the Mount Mahendra (i.e., Phnom Kulen). This location atop Mount Mahendra was considered a sacred and auspicious *tīrtha*.³¹ The south sanctuary inscription states,

With the exception of the *hotar*,³² most eminent among the twice-born, all those at this place must not perform ablutions in the clear water of the *parikhā*, which is pure, worthy of the highest blessings, (and) brought about by the *tīrtha* whose (water) originates atop glorious Mount Mahendra (i.e., Phnom Kulen); even a small amount (of this water) provides abundant fruit.

waters (of *tīrthas*); but they do not go to heaven, for the impurities of their minds are not removed" (see Salomon (1985: 207).

³⁰ According to the *Parāśarasmṛti*, the other five duties are *saṃdhyājāpa* ('repetition of prayers at the three'), *brahmayajña* ('worship of the Supreme Being by repeating the first words of sacred books'), *tarpaṇa* ('daily oblations of water to the gods, sages, and ancestors'), *homa* ('oblations of fuel, rice and so forth to fire'), and *devapūjā* ('worship of the secondary gods either in the domestic sanctuary or in temples'), M.W., s.v. *ṣaṭkarman*.

³¹ There are various ways to understand the word *tīrtha*. Most commonly, however, it refers to an auspicious location connected with a river crossing or some body of water (although some *tīrtha* sources have mentioned forest and mountain *tīrthas*, as well as other non-water sources). Such locations are often pilgrimage destinations where one can perform, for example, rites in order to purify ones faults (Skt. *pāpa*), perform devotional rites to one's ancestors (i.e., *śraddha* rites), and perform daily water offerings (i.e., *tarpaṇa* rites). In the context of the Bat Cum inscriptions, the *tīrtha* atop Mount Kulen is the source of the sacred waters feeding the *parikhā*. For an excellent source on *tīrthas* in the context of India, see Salomon (1985) which contains a translation of Nārāyaṇa Baṭṭa's *Tristhalīsetu*, a sixteenth-century text often considered the standard and most authoritative text of *tīrtha* literature.

³² Here we have a small discrepancy between the three Bat Cum inscriptions. According to K. 266 only the *hotar* (a type of officiants responsible for oblations and sacrifices) is allowed to use the *parikhā* for ablutions; however, in the K. 267 and K. 268 other learned Brahmins can also perform ablutions in its waters.

(K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XXI)

The corresponding stanza from the central sanctuary at Bat Cum adds only that the *parikhā* was constructed according to prescribed rites found in the Vedas.

After (this) great *parikhā* has been dug according to the prescribed rites, no one may perform ablutions here in its sacred waters other than a *vipra* knowledgeable in the Vedas.

(K. 267, Bat Cum, st. XXXVIII)

That the waters of the *parikhā* were part of the sacred *tīrtha* waters originating from Mount Mahendra is likely significant. The fact that the water was channeled from the water flowing down from Mount Mahendra also explains the use of the term *parikhā* ('canal'). The water source would have been considered a natural and sacred source of water for the performance of mandatory Brahmanical ritual practices such as religious bathing, unlike the *taṭāka* since the latter was strictly a man-made reservoir. The waters of the *parikhā*, therefore, would have been considered especially efficacious and meritorious. Not only does the *Mānava Dharmaśāstra* (IV.201–203), for example, state that one should not bathe in a reservoir belonging to other men because of the possible taint brought about by the latter, but it also states that one should always bathe in rivers, natural ponds (lit. 'dug by the gods'), lakes, pools, and springs.³³ Although there are certainly noted exceptions in other texts, the emphasis on the naturalness of sacred *tīrtha* waters is found in other sources. Nārāyaṇa Baṭṭa, for instance, in discussing the nature of *tīrthas* notes that the epic *Mahābhāratha* describes two kinds of *tīrthas*: natural and created by the gods.³⁴ The separation between the *parikhā* and *taṭāka*, therefore, appears to be based primarily on the former's connection with the sacred waters said to

³³ Olivelle (2004: 79–80).

³⁴ Salomon (1985: 202).

originate atop Mount Mahendra. This would have made the *parikhā* an ideal location for the performance of traditional Brahmanical rituals such as religious bathing. The allocation of this particular site to learned Brahmins probably had nothing to do with disparaging Buddhists or placing them at a disadvantage by imposing a restriction. Again, the Buddhists frequently derided the supposed effectiveness of Brahmanical religious bathing and were instructed by the Buddha (according to textual sources) to abstain from such practices; thus, the supposed restriction concerning the *parikhā* only reinforced a normative Buddhist position concerning certain ritual practices. The restriction seems to have taken into account the traditional positions of both Brahmins and Buddhists coexisting in the area and proffered a solution suitable to both parties. Again it should be noted that there is no restriction placed on the use of the *taṭāka*. Finally, the restriction was also part of a process of identity formulation (whether purposeful or inadvertent) in that the restriction highlighted the distinct roles and positions of these two groups. The Brahmins performed ablutions in sacred waters for the purpose of purification, while the Buddhists restricted themselves from this practice because they believed it to be ineffective. This is simply another way to understand what makes a Brahmin a Brahmin, and what makes a Buddhist a Buddhist.

Final Thoughts

In this chapter I have demonstrated that there are alternative ways to understand stanzas found in both the Vat Sithor inscription and the Bat Cum inscriptions that have sometimes been seen as examples of Brahmanical and Buddhist tensions and hostilities in tenth-century Cambodia. Instead, I have shown that the restrictions can be understood as short articulations of two distinct sectarian positions that highlight who Brahmins and Buddhists were, what they thought, and what they did. In that way, the

stanzas represent a kind of rhetoric of identity. Looking at the stanzas from a more logical position and with the support of other outside textual sources, one should realize that there can be no real restriction and disadvantage placed on Buddhists if the supposed restrictions involve matters that were ridiculed and already abstained from by Buddhist themselves. The ban on sacrifice in the Vat Sithor inscription, for example, is an articulation of a Buddhist position, not a Brahmanical one, that demonstrates active disengagement from a frowned upon practice, not the marginalization of a disadvantaged group. The restriction not to perform ablutions found in the Bat Cum inscriptions did not actually hinder the local Buddhists since they already abstained from such practices and viewed their supported efficacy in a negative light. Reading between the lines, so to speak, it appears if any group was being disparaged it was the Brahmins whose practices were either being ridiculed or being actively appropriated by Buddhists who were becoming more prevalent during this period.

CHAPTER 8
A CENTURY OF CONFUSION: THE BRICK RELIEFS OF PHNOM TRAP

I have continued to demonstrate the importance of Buddhist figures like Lokeśvara, Vajrapāṇi, and Prajñāpāramitā for tenth-century Buddhists in Cambodia. Influential Buddhists such as Kīrtipaṇḍita and Kāvīndrārimathana are recorded as having erected images of these figures in epigraphical sources such as the inscription from Vat Sithor and the Bat Cum inscriptions. This chapter again highlights the importance of these Buddhist figures in the tenth-century Cambodia. Rather than examining another decontextualized epigraphical reference or image, however, I will focus on the in-situ brick reliefs of a tenth-century sanctuary complex. Specifically, this chapter reexamines the iconography of three tenth-century sanctuaries located at Phnom Trap and argues that the figures depicted on the inner brick reliefs of the three structures are Buddhist, not Vaiṣṇava or Śaiva as glossed by previous scholarship.¹ I will demonstrate conclusively that the brick reliefs thought to be depicting Viṣṇu are instead reliefs of the bodhisattva Lokeśvara, and the one relief believed to be Śiva or some kind of wrathful ogre is a depiction of the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi. The identification for the female figures in the reliefs present more difficulties, but I argue that the figures were either understood simply as accompanying *devīs* ('goddesses') or dual aspects of Prajñāpāramitā. By establishing the Buddhist orientation of this site, I once again demonstrate that tenth-century forms of Buddhism in Cambodia involving worship to

¹ As there is still no standard romanization of Khmer, Phnom Trap has been variously rendered as Trop, Trâp, Trab, Trâb, and Tráb. The site is also known as Vat Praeus Meas. Additionally, in order to distinguish this particular site from other nearby areas, the specific location on the hill with the three brick sanctuaries is sometimes labeled Phnom Trap D. I will refer to the site as 'Phnom Trap.' I am grateful to Martin Polkinghorne for providing logistical advice on Phnom Trap. I also thank Friends of Khmer Culture, Inc. for providing field research support.

figures such as Lokeśvara and Vajrapāṇi were much more widespread and influential than previously acknowledged in various historical reconstructions of the region.²

Location of Phnom Trap

The shrines of Phnom Trap were erected atop a steep hill (*phnom*) which is located in present day Kampong Cham province, Banteay district. The site is about sixty-three kilometers (about forty miles) northeast of the capital Phnom Penh. To this day the site remains somewhat difficult to access because of its remote and undeveloped location. Visitors must leave National Highway 7 at the market town of Paav and travel along a network of unpaved back roads before arriving at the village community of Trap.

The Shrines of Phnom Trap

Remaining atop the hill from a bygone era are three brick sanctuaries (K. *prasat*, Skt. *prāsāda*) dating to the tenth century CE.³ The three structures run parallel along a north-south axis with the entryways opening to the east (fig. 8-1). A much later open-air Buddhist structure with wall paintings and housing a few Buddha images is now situated at the southern end of these three sanctuaries, and within the last couple of years an

² A few words of acknowledgment must be made before continuing. The possibility that the brick reliefs at Phnom Trap may be Buddhist is an idea that has been circulating among a few scholars in personal correspondences. The first person I know to have posited this idea is Martin Polkinghorne in his email correspondences with Hiram Woodward in early 2011. Hiram Woodward (2011) had been pondering the possibility of the area's connection with Buddhism, as indicated in a paper on tenth-century forms of Buddhism in Cambodia. At a conference in Siem Reap in 2011, I also met Eric Bourdonneau who informed me of an upcoming article in which he briefly notes the possibility of the brick reliefs being Buddhist (2011: 135, n. 87). Bourdonneau's paper was later published after conducting my research, and just prior to the presentation of my conclusions in Siem Reap during the summer of 2012 at the conference on "Religious Studies in Cambodia: Understanding the Old and Tracing the New," Siem Reap, Cambodia, June 9–11, 2012. He was kind enough to forward me a copy on 4/6/2012. The contribution of this chapter is that it puts forth, for the first time, a detailed argument to support such a Buddhist identification which has previously only been speculated by interested scholars.

³ Jean Boisselier (1966: 179) devoted only a single line to Phnom Trap, but in that line he noted the site was closely dated to the same time as Prasat Kravan; in other words, the tenth century.

enormous standing Buddha image, far exceeding the height of the sanctuaries, was erected by individuals from the local community.⁴

The three brick sanctuaries are all roughly square, and are all erected atop a laterite foundation. The center sanctuary is larger than the north and south shrine, being roughly 4 meters at the base, while the other two sanctuaries are roughly 2.8 meters. Each of the three sanctuaries are separated by a distance of 2.2 meters. As previously mentioned, the sanctuaries are made of brick, while the doorjambs, entryway steps, decorative frame colonnettes, and lintels at the entry points are all made of grey sandstone. The outer sides of the three sanctuaries are embossed with false doors and doorframes.

While the three sanctuaries are still standing, the structures are in a severe state of decline due to centuries of exposure and neglected maintenance. Sections of all three structures, especially the top of the center sanctuary, have collapsed. The decorative lintel of the central sanctuary has also toppled; it now rests on the ground in front of the shrine. Additionally, this particular lintel has also been the source of repeated acts of vandalism since it is now easy to chip off sections of the lintel scene for either souvenirs or use in a home shrine.⁵

⁴ The modern Buddhist structure at the southern end of the three sanctuaries was built sometime after first decade of the twentieth century since Lunet de Lajonquière (1: 122) noted in 1902 that only the doorframe of a ruined structure was standing at this location during his time. Aymonier (1900, 1: 322) also noted that the fourth structure at the southern end of the three brick sanctuaries was completely ruined. It should also be noted that the previous ruined structure which today's modern structure sits atop was still posterior to the three tenth-century sanctuaries. This conclusion is based on a comparison of the lintel work of that one remaining doorframe with the lintels of three sanctuaries (Lunet de Lajonquière, 1: 122).

⁵ While the damage to the lintel is obvious, reasons explaining some of vandalism came from conversations with local villagers during a field research trip in 2011. In earlier twentieth century examinations of this site this lintel was still in place atop the doorway. For example, note the photo plate in Lunet de Lajonquière (I: xxiv). It has only collapsed relatively recently which highlights the continuing decline and neglect of this site. This neglect continues despite the fact that the sanctuaries, especially

The entryways are also in a state of decline due to the elements, with some lower sections worn smooth by rainwater. Portions of the sandstone colonnettes and lintels have also broken off, but are still largely intact. The colonnettes are polygonal and banded, which is what one would expect from this period.⁶

Two of the three lintel scenes are still discernable and stylistically date the sanctuaries to around the middle of the tenth century.⁷ The lintel above the southern sanctuary depicts the goddess Lakṣmī seated atop a lotus flanked by two elephants with raised trunks coming together to form an arch above the goddess.⁸ Sharp carved ornamental foliage decorates the rest of the lintel, including the uppermost frieze. In the center a large garland scrolls outward terminating in curls of foliage (fig. 8-2).

The lintel of the central sanctuary, now toppled and severely damaged, is topped with a frieze depicting a row of worshippers (fig. 8-3). The center of the lintel shows Indra standing atop his elephant, Airāvata. The upperpart of horses emerge from the central garland radiating out from Indra, and atop this horse-garland are riders galloping along its length. The riders are probably those said to protect the legs of Airāvata when the mighty elephant is in battle. Before being damaged the garland would have terminated in curls of foliage.

the southern structure which has a modern Buddhist image installed, continue to play a role in the worship and practice of today's Cambodians.

⁶ Additionally, for a few remarks comparing the colonnettes from Phnom Trap with stylistically similar colonnettes at other sites such as Vat Tomnop, see Dalet (1936: 49, n. 1).

⁷ The lintels would be classified as conforming to so-called Pre Rup style of the mid-tenth century; or, in the language of Coral-Rémusat (1940: 47, 121), Transition C. In other words, stylistic conventions developing/transitioning into the so-called Banteay Srei style of the second half of the tenth century. See Polkinghorne (2007: esp. chapters 5 and 6) for a recent work on Khmer lintels which provides an overview of the strengths and weaknesses of previous temporal and stylistic categorizations of Khmer lintels found in the works of scholars like Lunet de Lajonquière, Philippe Stern, and others.

⁸ See Ghosh (1979: 75–87) for more on Lakṣmī's iconography and her connection with elephants.

The third lintel of the northern sanctuary (fig. 8-4), while still in place above the doorway, is now severely damaged making identification impossible. Some of the damage must be relatively recent because Lunet de Lajonquière (1: 122) noted that the lintel once depicted a male figure (which he did not name) holding the ends of a central garland which radiated outward. He also noted the presence of riders overlapping the foliage at the end of the garland.

The Brick Reliefs of Phnom Trap

The back inner walls of each shrine have figures carved in relief. Like the rest of the site, the reliefs are in extremely poor condition. Large chunks of the figures have long since crumbled away making identification difficult. Despite such difficulties, however, an identification of the figures was made just over a hundred years ago and has remained unchallenged. In volume one of his three volume work entitled, *Le Cambodge*, Étienne Aymonier (1900, 1: 321–22) wrote that the figures in the central and south sanctuaries were depictions of the god Viṣṇu, a conclusion he felt was supported by the lintel scenes of these two shrines. Additionally, he wrote that the northern sanctuary was “sans doute” reserved for the god Śiva (*ibid.*). Since that time no in-depth analysis of the brick reliefs and their iconography has been conducted. To my knowledge only Eric Bourdonneau (2011: 135, n. 87) has mentioned the Buddhist orientation of the site in a publication, and this only recently. Because of the scarcity of surviving brick reliefs in the Khmer art historical record references have occasionally

been made to the site, especially in connection with the Vaiṣṇava brick reliefs of Prasat Kravan, a tenth-century site located near Angkor just outside of Siem Reap.⁹

Description of the north sanctuary relief

Unlike the other two shrines, the inner-back wall of the northern sanctuary depicts only one figure (fig. 8-5). The male figure is depicted dancing and has four arms. The *sampot* (a traditional long cloth worn around the lower body) conforms to the Pre Rup style of the tenth century, and the folded over cloth in the front is depicted swaying in order to emphasize the figure's dancing motion. The facial features are fierce and wrathful (Skt. *krodha*), and the figure is also clearly depicted with protruding fangs. The figure is wearing ornate earrings and what remains of the lower left leg reveals that the figure is wearing an anklet, or possibly bell anklets which are commonly worn when dancing. The chignon is heavily eroded, but what remains places it stylistically in the tenth century. Only one of the four attributes being held can be firmly identified, but enough of the relief is preserved to make tentative identifications for the other attributes as well. The attributes are as follows:

Lower Right: *vajra* (thunderbolt, a handheld ritual object)

Upper Right: sword or other type of elongated weapon such as a club (?)

Lower Left: probably a *ghanṭā* (ritual bell) (?), or perhaps another *vajra* (?)

Upper Left: heavily damaged, unknown

The lower right hand clearly holds a *vajra*, a short (often metal) ritual object particularly common in tantric forms of Buddhism. Although damaged, the upper right hand appears to be holding a bladed weapon such as a sword atop his head. This attribute may be mirrored in the upper left hand, but the attribute in the upper left hand

⁹ For example, in discussing Prasat Kravan, Claude Jacques (1997: 87) has noted on several occasions that the only other low reliefs in brick come from the contemporary sanctuaries of Phnom Trap. He also notes that the brick reliefs at Phnom Trap are cruder.

is even more damaged making absolute identification impossible. The fact that the figure has fierce and wrathful facial features supports the suggestion that the figure is wielding weapons.

The lower left hand is also badly damaged; therefore, I can only speculate on the identification of the attribute. There is a strong possibility that the attribute is a *ghaṇṭā* (bell), another ritual implement often used in conjunction with the *vajra*. I base this identification on the following observations: (1) the figure is wielding a *vajra* in his lower right hand, and therefore, the *ghaṇṭā* would naturally complement the presence of this *vajra*; (2) the *ghaṇṭā* would be held in one of the figure's left hands, which is the appropriate side for this ritual object; (3) the figure is dancing, and this may reflect that the *ghaṇṭā* is also in motion; thus, the relief could be indicating that the *ghaṇṭā* is reverberating with efficacious sound during an ecstatic dance; (4) the attribute is lowered near the figure's hip, and while this is not a required or universal position it is consistent with the manner in which the *ghaṇṭā* is typically held; (5) the surviving structural outline on the relief of the damaged attribute does not exclude the possibility of this attribute being a *ghaṇṭā*.

Nevertheless, it is certainly possible the attribute in the lower left hand is something else. Other possibilities include a second *vajra*, or maybe even a ritual water pot (*kamaṇḍalu*). A vessel full of water, however, or some kind of special elixir, seems unlikely since the figure is depicted in motion.

A case for Vajrapāṇi. The above description of the figure depicted in the northern sanctuary makes Śiva an unlikely candidate. The fact that the figure in this relief is holding a *vajra* is significant because this is not an attribute normally associated

with Śiva. In fact, I know of no Khmer depictions of Śiva that are holding a *vajra*, making it highly unlikely that the figure depicted in the northern sanctuary is Śiva. Nor would the sanctuary, at least originally, have been reserved for Śiva as Aymonier would lead us to believe. This is not to imply, however, that the *vajra* was unknown, or not used, in other sectarian traditions such as Śaivism; rather, I am simply highlighting the point that in Khmer iconography Śiva is not depicted holding this ritual implement, or even typically associated with it. On the other hand, the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi is, indeed, frequently depicted holding the *vajra*, as his name indicates. Vajrapāṇi translates as ‘*vajra* in the hand;’ in other words, he is the one who holds/wields the *vajra*.

Additionally, the figure in the relief is also wielding a weapon, probably a sword, and representations of Vajrapāṇi wielding a sword or club-like weapon are known, especially in conjunction with the *vajra*, *pāśa* (‘noose’), and *ghaṇṭā*.¹⁰ These attributes could very likely be the same ones depicted on the wall inside the northern sanctuary at Phnom Trap. Although the upper left attribute of the figure in the northern sanctuary is too heavily damaged to make an absolute identification, it seems reasonable to suggest that this item could have been a noose based on the other attributes being held by the figure. Furthermore, contemporary Khmer art historical sources depicting Vajrapāṇi with a sword/club and a noose lend support to this claim.

Artistic depictions of Vajrapāṇi in early Cambodia are relatively rare in comparison with the ubiquitous depictions of Avalokiteśvara. A tenth-century Khmer monument now

¹⁰ See Mallmann (1986). Although her work is dated, Getty (1914: 52–53) also noted several images from the tantric Buddhist traditions of Tibet that depict Vajrapāṇi with four arms wielding the *vajra*, sword (*khadga*), noose (*pāśa*), and *ghaṇṭā*. She also noted that the so-called “Acala-Vajrapāṇi” is depicted with arms wielding a *vajra*, sword, noose and skull-cap (*kapāla*).

in the Bangkok National Museum, however, depicts Vajrapāṇi, as well as other Buddhist figures such as the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā.¹¹ As at Phnom Trap, Vajrapāṇi is depicted with four arms on this important monument. According to Woodward (2011: 18), the attributes of Vajrapāṇi on the Bangkok monument are the *vajra* (lower right), sword/club (upper right), *ghaṇṭā* (lower left), and noose (upper left). This monument, therefore, represents a contemporary depiction of Vajrapāṇi very similar to the figure at Phnom Trap; in fact, if we accept the possibility that the unknown item being held in the upper left hand of the Phnom Trap figure could be a noose, then the attributes being held in these two examples are identical.

Another four-sided Buddhist monument from tenth-century Cambodia depicts the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, Prajñāpāramitā, and Vajrapāṇi. The monument, or so-called *caitya*, is now located in the Angkor National Museum of Siem Reap (fig. 8-6).¹² Like the Bangkok monument, Vajrapāṇi is also depicted with four arms. Unfortunately, the Vajrapāṇi side of this stele is more eroded from the elements than the other sides; thereby, identification of the small attributes are difficult to determine with certainty. After examining the piece, however, it became clear that the lower right attribute is definitely a *vajra*, and the upper right attribute is an elongated weapon, either a sword or club. The other two attributes are much more difficult to ascertain due to their size and centuries of erosion. The upper left attribute, however, appears to be a noose. A faint circular impression at the end of the stick or staff (or possibly a straightened section of rope) is visible on the monument. The lower left attribute appears to be a *ghaṇṭā*, but

¹¹ Bangkok National Museum, Inventory number 12.2475. See Woodward (2007).

¹² Inventory number N.127; 5690. On the term *caitya* and its usage in this art historical context, see Boisselier (1966: 98–99).

like the attribute in the lower left hand of the figure at Phnom Trap it could also be a water pot, or even another *vajra* (none of which would discount the possibility of these depicted figures being Vajrapāṇi).¹³ In any case, the similarities between the Vajrapāṇi figures on the Bangkok monument, on the walls of the Phnom Trap sanctuaries, and on this stele located in Siem Reap are striking.

Even stronger evidence for a Vajrapāṇi identification comes from three tenth-century Buddhist images discovered only a few hundred meters south from the three brick sanctuaries at Phnom Trap. The images are of the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Vajrapāṇi; the images are now kept at the Musée Guimet in Paris (fig. 8-7).¹⁴ This contemporary image of Vajrapāṇi also has four arms. Unfortunately the arms are broken at the elbow; therefore, the attributes held, if any, remain unknown. The facial features of the Guimet Vajrapāṇi, however, are nearly identical with the facial features of the relief figure in the northern sanctuary at Phnom Trap. Both are fierce/angry/wrathful and have protruding fangs (*daṃṣṭra*); thus, these depictions represent the *krodha* or *caṇḍa* manifestation of Vajrapāṇi. So prominent are these facial characters that Aymonier (1900: 322) identified (incorrectly) the Guimet Vajrapāṇi as an ogre.

A wrathful manifestation of Vajrapāṇi in a triad with the Buddha and Avalokiteśvara (specifically Lokeśvara) is also attested in a contemporary tenth-century inscription from Cambodia. The tenth-century Bat Cum inscription from the reign of Rājendravarman

¹³ There are known depictions of Vajrapāṇi holding a water pot (*kamaṇḍalu*). For example, Gouriswar Bhattacharya (1995/96: 335) cites a ninth-century four-armed Vajrapāṇi holding a water pot from Ratnagiri. For other images of Vajrapāṇi from this region, see Donaldson (2001, 1: 214–18).

¹⁴ The inventory numbers are as follows: MG 14880, 14912, and 14892. For pictures, see Baptiste and Zéphir (2008: 166–71).

opens with praise to the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and the wrathful Vajrapāṇi who is praised for conquering his enemies. Vajrapāṇi is described as follows in the opening of the south sanctuary inscription at Bat Cum:

Glorious Vajrapāṇi, the invincible, conqueror of the enemy Jambha, he, who is skilled at removing obstacles churned about by the torrent of a multitude of transgressions of the unrestrained and presumptuous *dānavas* in the Kali (*yuga*), bears of the *vajra* that resembles a blazing flame of fire.

(K. 266, Bat Cum, st. III)¹⁵

Taking all of the above presented information together it becomes quite clear that the figure depicted inside the northern sanctuary at Phnom Trap is the bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi, not the god Śiva as Aymonier believed. The iconography, the facial features, and the nearby discovery of a large Vajrapāṇi image all support this conclusion. A Vajrapāṇi identification is further strengthened when the relief figures depicted in the southern and central sanctuaries at Phnom Trap are also taken into account, a point which will now be addressed.

Description of the central sanctuary reliefs

The brick reliefs in the central sanctuary depict three figures: two smaller female figures flanking a larger male figure. All three figures have four arms and are standing (fig. 8-8). Again, Aymonier claimed the main figure was Viṣṇu. While he does not specifically identify the female figures, his identification of the central figure as Viṣṇu would suggest that the females were manifestations of Devī, perhaps specifically Lakṣmī and Bhūdevī. There is, however, support in both the Cambodian art historical and epigraphical record for an alternative Buddhist identification. In describing the

¹⁵ Skt. *śrīvajrapāṇir ajito jītajambhavairī / vajrañ jvalajjvalanadīptinibbhaṃ bibharti // uddāmadṛptakalidānavadoṣaṣaṇḍa- / niṣyaṇḍasaṃkṣubhitavighnavighāṭadakṣaḥ //*, Cœdès (1908b: 226). For commentary on this particular stanza refer to Appendix B.

iconography I will argue that the central figure is a depiction of a four-armed Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) flanked by two *devīs*. The *devīs* are either basic representations of goddesses or possibly Prajñāpāramitā metaphorically understood in a dichotomous manner as both the sun and moon. This dual aspect of the Prajñāpāramitā (discussed previously in chapter three in the context of the Bat Cum inscriptions) highlights her importance as the actual source of wisdom (the full moon) and the illuminating path that leads the practitioner to attain that very same wisdom (the sun).

Female figures. The four-armed female figures are identical. They are clothed in a long *sampot* with a prominent overlap at the waist, echoing an archaistic Koh Ker style. The heads and faces are badly damaged, but the figures clearly wore ornate earrings. Their attributes are as follows:

Upper Right: holding a stem of what was probably a flower/lotus (?)

Upper Left: heavily damaged, unknown

Lower Right and Left (lowered at sides): lotus bud

Based on this sparse information alone it proves difficult to identify these two female figures as anything other than two *devīs*, or ‘goddesses.’ These *devīs* display no special iconographic features that would set them apart from other female goddesses since the lotus is an attribute shared by many goddesses across several sectarian traditions. Any attempt to go beyond such an inclusive and basic *devī* identification would be dependent on the identification of the central male figure and other surrounding contextual evidence. Even then, however, the simplicity of the two female figures, and the fact that they are both identical, appears to suggest that they are merely basic representations of goddesses accompanying a more prominent male figure. Unlike the Lakṣmī brick reliefs at Prasat Kravan, for example, there are no dedicated brick reliefs of female goddesses at Phnom Trap. I will return to these female figures

later in the chapter in order to discuss alternative identifications that rely on outside epigraphical sources for support.

Male figure. The central male figure is much larger than the two flanking *devīs* and has four arms. The figure is clothed in a *sampot* with an overlap and scarf shaped like a fishtail. Originally, there were probably double fishtail panels. The face and head are in very bad condition and all that may be said about this area is that the figure wears a diadem with a protruding chignon. The attributes and gestures are as follows:

Upper Right: heavily damaged, unknown

Upper Left: heavily damaged, unknown

Lower Right and Left: arms lowered in the *varada mudrā* ('boon granting gesture')

A case for Avalokiteśvara. Due to the extreme state of decline of this relief figure, and the central sanctuary in general, it would seem that not much could be said with regard to identification. The two upper hands are far too damaged to tell us anything about what attributes might have been held, even though it seems clear that both upper hands held something. There is, however, one very important and revealing iconographic clue that has been overlooked: the *mūdra*, or gesture, of the lower two hands (fig. 8-9).

Both lower arms and hands are well preserved and the gesture being displayed is clearly the *varada mudrā*. This iconographic detail seriously undermines Aymonier's claim that this figure, as well as the eight-armed figure in the southern sanctuary, is Viṣṇu. In the art historical record of early Cambodia there is not a single depiction of Viṣṇu—that I am aware of—where both hands are lowered in the *varada mudrā*.¹⁶ This

¹⁶ This is also one of the primary reasons why piece N.135 in the Angkor National Museum of Siem Reap labeled "Brahmanism Boundary Stone" is not, as the museum would have visitors believe, depicting Śiva (two-armed), Viṣṇu (eight-armed), and two Lakṣmī (four-armed). All these figures have their lowermost

is not to claim that the *varada mudrā*, or other *mudrā*, were the sole province of Buddhist traditions; they were not. This particular *mudrā*, however, is not iconographically associated with Viṣṇu. On the other hand, the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara is often depicted in Khmer art, especially on stele and so-called *caityas*, with the two lowermost hands making the *varada mudrā*.¹⁷

Chutiwongs (1984: 283), for example, notes that in the Angkorian period, the broad period to which Phnom Trap belongs, the *varada mudrā* is often shown with both hands and notes several examples of the bodhisattva to support her observation. This boon-granting *mudrā* is especially connected with the bodhisattva's role as a supremely compassionate being ever concerned with helping those afflicted with pain and suffering. In this role, the bodhisattva is often referred to as Mahākāruṇika, or the 'great compassionate one'.¹⁸ Another tenth-century depiction of an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara from Cambodia with pendant arms making the *varada mudrā* is found on

arms making the *varada mudrā*. In all likelihood, this is a misidentified work that is not brahmanical, but Buddhist.

¹⁷ cf. Chutiwongs (1984: plates 117, 118A, 118B, 121A, and 122).

¹⁸ In fact, the *varada mudra* is not merely common, but an essential expression of Avalokiteśvara's compassion. In iconography outside Cambodia, for instance, the suffering hungry ghost (Skt. *preta*) Sūcīmukha is sometimes depicted below Avalokiteśvara's outstretched palm gathering the assuaging *amṛta* (ambrosial-like nectar) that drips from the Bodhisattva's fingers. The *Sādhanaṃālā* describes Sūcīmukha as follows: [Avalokiteśvara] is an expert in distributing the stream of nectar that flows from his hand, and Sūcīmukha who stands below with an uplifted face, a protruding belly and very pale appearance receives the same" (Linrothe, 1999: 97 and figs. 79, 109, and 110). I thank Rob Linrothe for discussing this topic with me in personal e-mail correspondences. Finally, the *KVS* is one of the pivotal texts that extol Avalokiteśvara as the 'great compassionate one' (e.g., the text opens by referring to Avalokiteśvara with this very epithet) by presenting the bodhisattva as the primordial source of compassion and ultimate refuge. Kapstein (1992: 85, 88) has noted that Atīśa (982–1054 CE) drew upon concepts in the *KVS* and was one of the first Buddhist to actively promote practices focusing on Avalokiteśvara, and Tibetans would continue to draw upon the works of this master in later compilations such as *Mañi bka'-bum*, a heterogeneous collection of works concerned with the cult of Mahākāruṇika Avalokiteśvara. There are of course other early texts that view Avalokiteśvara as Mahākāruṇika; the *EDMD* discussed in chapter six is another example.

the back of a stele now located in the Walters Art Museum.¹⁹ This stele also contains an inscription (K. 1154) that records the only attested use of Avalokiteśvara's *Oṃ Maṇipadme Hūṃ mantra*, a mantra first used in the *KVS*. Woodward (2007) has demonstrated that the *varada mudrā* of this eight-armed depiction of the bodhisattva, along with the bodhisattva's *mantra*, point directly to the influence of the *KVS* in tenth-century Cambodia by highlighting that this depiction of Avalokiteśvara is likely alluding to a narrative in the text that details the bodhisattva alleviating the suffering of hungry ghosts (Skt. *preta*) tormented in Avīci hell, a narrative that also highlights the bodhisattva's supreme compassion.

If this figure is, as I am claiming, the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara/Lokeśvara, then what about the two flanking female figures? Besides the uncritical comparison with the Vaiṣṇava brick reliefs of Prasat Kravan, these flanking females are perhaps one of the reasons why the Viṣṇu identification has remained unchallenged for so long. Examples of a four-armed Viṣṇu flanked by Lakṣmī and Bhūdevī/Bhūmidevī are well attested.²⁰ Although it should be noted that in such examples Viṣṇu is *not* making the *varada mudrā*. There is also perhaps a tendency to initially turn to Vaiṣṇava or Śaiva traditions when confronted with depictions of a male divinity flanked by two females/goddesses/consorts. Additionally, while Avalokiteśvara is frequently depicted alongside Prajñāpāramitā in Cambodian sources where she is sometimes simply called Devī or Mother of Jinas in epigraphical sources, one is more hard-pressed to link the bodhisattva to two flanking females, especially in an early Cambodian context. Of

¹⁹ For more detailed information on this stele and the inscription engraved on one side, see Pou (2002: 129); Woodward (2007: 72–73); and Skilling (2003).

²⁰ For example, cf. N.26 of the Angkor National Museum in Siem Reap.

course examples do come to mind, especially from sources outside of Cambodia. For instance, Avalokiteśvara (especially in his Amoghapāśa manifestation) is sometimes depicted with Tārā and Bhṛkuṭī.²¹ A possible explanation, however, may lie in the Cambodian epigraphical record.

During the reign of Rājendravarman (r. 944–c. 966) one of his Buddhist *ācārya* named Kavīndrārimathana was responsible for many Buddhist activities and is recorded as having erected many shrines and images. In the tenth-century Bat Cum inscriptions he is recorded performing the following activities:

In Śaka 868 (946 CE) he (i.e., Kavīndrārimathana) established an image of the Jina at Jayantadeśa, and in 872 Śaka (950 CE) he also established Lokanātha and two *devīs* at Kuṭīśvara.

(K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XX)²²

This contemporary inscription quite explicitly records that an image of Lokanātha (in this context a reference to either Avalokiteśvara or the Buddha) was installed along with two accompanying female divinities, or goddesses, referred to as *devīs*. My initial impressions were that any attempts to delve deeper for more specific identifications of these female beings was probably unnecessary since it appeared that these female divinities were simply understood as basic representations of accompanying *devīs*. However, the overall context of the Bat Cum inscriptions, which also include several explicit references to Prajñāpāramitā, seem to suggest that the *devīs* being referred to may, indeed, be referring to Prajñāpāramitā. In chapter three I briefly discussed how

²¹ For example, see Huntington and Bangdel (2003: 186–89, numbers 47 and 48). For other contemporary Pāla period images of Amoghapāśa Avalokiteśvara, see Huntington (1984: figs. 112 and 115).

²² Skt. *jayantadeśe jinarūpam ekaṃ so sthāpayan mūrttirasāṣṭaśāke / kuṭīśvare so pi ca lokanāthan devīdvayan netranagāṣṭaśāke //*, Coedès (1908b: 228). It should be noted that the Bat Cum inscription on the central shrine indicates that image of a Buddha along with two *devīs* was installed at Kuṭīśvara.

Prajñāpāramitā may have been understood in a dichotomous manner in which she, as the mother of Buddhas, simultaneously represents both the illuminating path to awakening itself and the omniscience of all Buddhas. Thus the Bat Cum inscriptions describe her in terms of both a sun illuminating the path and as a full moon encapsulating all the knowledge attained from such a path. This observation, if correct, may explain why two images of Prajñāpāramitā were installed at some locations, and perhaps why she would be depicted twice in both the central and south sanctuaries at Phnom Trap; although, this is difficult to prove with any certainty. Furthermore, whether the two female figures are simply *devīs*, Tārā and Bhṛkuṭī, dual aspects of Prajñāpāramitā, or some other divinities yet to be considered, it remains highly likely that the image of the central figure depicts a manifestation of Avalokiteśvara.

Description of the south sanctuary reliefs

Similar to the brick reliefs in the central sanctuary, the reliefs in the southern sanctuary depict a central male figure flanked by two female figures. The female figures are identical with the female figures in the central sanctuary; however, the male figure in south sanctuary has eight arms (although several have long since crumbled away), not four as in the central sanctuary. All three figures are decorated and clothed in the same manner and style as the figures in the central sanctuary described above (figs. 8-10 and 8-11).

Female figures. Although smaller than the two female figures in the central sanctuary, they are otherwise identical to them. The only additional noteworthy observation is that the female figure on the central figure's left side in this sanctuary has a preserved upper left hand and attribute. The attribute is a lotus; therefore, the other three female figures almost certainly held a lotus as well (that is, the two female figures

from the central sanctuary as well as the second female in the south sanctuary).

Following the same argumentation given above for the female figures in the central sanctuary, these figures may have been understood as simply being two accompanying *devīs* or dual-aspects of Prajñāpāramitā.

Male figure. The male figure in this relief is decorated and clothed in the same fashion as the male figure in the central sanctuary; however, this figure has eight arms, not four. Unfortunately, the two uppermost right arms have disappeared leaving only a faint outline attesting to their former presence. The next lower right arm is almost completely gone as well, but a section of it remains, as does a fragment of the held attribute. The other arms are all intact, but heavily eroded. Many of the attributes are badly damaged. Like the male figure in the central sanctuary, the left and right lowermost arms are lowered and are making the *varada mudrā*. A breakdown of the attributes and gestures are as follows:

Uppermost Right: heavily damaged, unknown, may have been symmetrical with uppermost left

Second Uppermost Right: heavily damaged, unknown

Third Uppermost Right: heavily damaged, unknown

Uppermost Left: miniature shrine sitting atop lotus flower

Second Uppermost Left: heavily damaged, unknown, but looks to have been an elongated attribute

Third Uppermost Left: *kamaṇḍalu* (water pot)

Lower Right and Left: arms lowered in the *varada mudrā* ('boon granting gesture').

The left hand is missing, but it is obvious that it is symmetrical with the right hand

A case for an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara and two *devī*. I suggest that this eight-armed figure is also a representation of Avalokiteśvara flanked by two *devīs*. Like the four-armed Avalokiteśvara in the central shrine, the figure in this relief has both lower hands making the *varada mudrā*. As discussed above, this is not an iconographic characteristic attested in depictions of Viṣṇu in Cambodia, but rather it is a common

iconographic feature of depictions of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara. This relief figure, however, has yet another iconographic feature that makes a Viṣṇu identification unlikely.

The uppermost left hand holds a lotus with a miniature shrine situated on top (fig. 8-12). While damaged, there is no doubt that the item is a small shrine with a triangular roof and floral-decorated base. Unfortunately, what would have been situated inside this shrine is now obscured due to the damage the relief has sustained. This miniature shrine may have enshrined a small effigy of some sort. One possibility is that the shrine perhaps held a small depiction of Prajñāpāramitā, either as a small book (i.e. as a representation of the Perfection of Wisdom corpus of literature) or as a personified deity.²³ If so, this representation could be similar to later reliefs on the walls of Banteay Chhmar in northwestern Cambodia depicting Avalokiteśvara holding a small multi-armed image in his lower right hand, something Boisselier has identified as *prajñā*.²⁴

My opinion is that the shrine did not house Prajñāpāramitā. Rather, I believe the shrine may have held a seated Buddha image. This Buddha image could have represented Amitābha, although it just as likely may have been a representation of Śākyamuni or some other Buddha image. Another art historical example to consider in

²³ Citing Philippe Stern's *Les Monuments Khmers du Style du Bàyon et Jayavarman VII*, Nandana Chutiwongs (1984: 248–49, n. 486) writes that there were other examples of Buddhist deities holding figurines in their hands in Cambodia. The example she draws from Stern is of a Hevajra bronze that probably dates to around the mid- eleventh century. Chutiwongs also cites examples coming from outside of Cambodia. Also see Stern (1965: fig. 202).

²⁴ cf. Boisselier (1965 : 77). For example, the relief scene at Banteay Chhmar representing the birth of various gods such as Viṣṇu and Śiva from the body of Avalokiteśvara—as related in the *Kāraṇḍavyūha Sūtra*—shows a small four-armed figure seated in the palm of the lowermost right hand of the sixteen-armed Avalokiteśvara. Note, however, that this small figure is not enshrined in a miniature structure. Although only marginally related, Getty (1914: 65 and plates XXII a and d) describes two depictions of Avalokiteśvara as Amoghapāśa from Tibet in which the bodhisattva is holding a small seated image above its head with the uppermost arms.

which Avalokiteśvara is holding a small Buddha image comes from the caves at Aurangabad in India. Brancaccio (2011: 125, figs. 24 and 25) notes that just outside of the shrine of Cave 2—which was probably excavated around the sixth century CE—are two sculpted bodhisattvas, one Avalokiteśvara and the other, perhaps, Maitreya.²⁵ Each of these bodhisattvas holds an elongated lotus flower on top of which sits a small Buddha image seated in the *dhyānāsana* ('meditation pose').

Unlike Aurangabad, however, where Avalokiteśvara both holds a Buddha image seated atop a lotus *and* has a clearly depicted Amitābha figure seated in the bodhisattva's hair, the head of the relief at Phnom Trap is too badly damaged to discern if an Amitābha figure was originally present. While a depiction of Amitābha atop Avalokiteśvara's head is a very common iconographic feature in Cambodia and abroad, it is not mandatory. According to Chutiwongs (1984: 257), in such cases where Amitābha is absent the *varada mūdra* often becomes the primary identifying characteristic. If the Phnom Trap relief did not have an Amitābhā image seated on Avalokiteśvara's head, then perhaps an image of Amitābha was included in the shrine being held aloft by Avalokiteśvara.

This miniature shrine is, however, only one of two that were most likely originally depicted with the eight-armed figure. There were likely two shrines: one on the left and one on the right. Both would have been sitting atop lotus flowers held in the upper-most arms of an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara. This second shrine would have been completely symmetrical to the left shrine. Although the entire upper right side of the relief is almost completely deteriorated, I have detected a partial structural outline that

²⁵ For a discussion on the identification of the two bodhisattvas, see Brancaccio (2011: 139–45).

appears to conform to the shape and symmetrical position of a shrine similar to the one on the left side (fig. 8-13). Of course, this structural outline could merely be a coincidence created as the relief deteriorated, but I do not think so since evidence of two flanking shrines held aloft by lotuses in the uppermost hands of an eight-armed depiction of the Avalokiteśvara is attested to in the Cambodian art historical record.

The tenth-century monument now located in the Bangkok National Museum (briefly mentioned above in arguing for a Vajrapāṇi identification of the figure in the north sanctuary) depicts an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara flanked by two small Buddhas seated atop lotuses held by the bodhisattva.²⁶ This eight-armed Avalokiteśvara is standing above a slightly smaller ten-armed female figure with five heads, probably Prajñāpāramitā/Devī. In fact, it is interesting to note that each of the male figures on this monument is paired with a female figure. I believe these female figures were probably understood as various manifestations of Devī/Prajñāpāramitā. Each of the female figures are smaller and situated below the male figures. Besides the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara mentioned above, the other sides of this monument depict the following figures: a standing four-armed Avalokiteśvara and a two-armed female figure,²⁷ a four-armed Vajrapāṇi and a four-armed female figure, and a Buddha seated atop a coiled *nāga* with a very small female figure positioned below him, probably Pṛthivī ('Earth').

Chutiwongs (1984: 238) was almost certainly right when she observed that eight-armed depictions of Avalokiteśvara began to appear around the early part of the tenth

²⁶ For images, see Chutiwongs (1984: plates 118A, 118B, and 118C. Also see Woodward (2007: 76–77; 2011: 4–6).

²⁷ Woodward (2011: 5) identifies this female figure as the Buddhist divinity Tārā.

century, and that such depictions were connected with “new religious ideas from abroad [which] entered the country.” As discussed in chapter six, frequent interaction with the polities of Campā represented one important source of influence and active appropriation, especially with regard to the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara. The increasing number of depictions of Buddhist male figures with female figures represents another new development taking place in the tenth century, a development being represented prominently in the reliefs at Phnom Trap which depict Avalokiteśvara paired with two *devīs*. Of course such developing religious currents were probably not entirely new in terms of independently developed Buddhist thought and practice since they were likely connected to frequent interactions with, and responses to, other competing sectarian traditions such as Vaiṣṇavism and Śaivism in which the pairing of a male deity with a female counterpart was much more prominent.

Returning to the Bangkok monument, the seated Buddhas flanking the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara are seated atop lotuses. At Phnom Trap, the miniature shrine is clearly positioned atop a floral base that was probably a representation of a lotus flower. Additionally, the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara on the Bangkok monument is making the *varada mudrā* with both the left and right lower arms, the exact same gesture as the eight-armed figure in the south sanctuary at Phnom Trap.

The only other held attribute of the eight-armed figure at Phnom Trap that is clearly identifiable is the *kamaṇḍalu* (water pot), which is held in the second left hand from the bottom (also seen in fig. 8-12). The *kamaṇḍalu* is usually depicted in the left hand of Avalokiteśvara, and according to Chutiwongs (1984: 244) when it is present in eight-armed representations of Avalokiteśvara from Cambodia it is always in the left

hand counterbalancing the *pustaka* (manuscript or 'book'). This is the exact configuration of the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara on the Bangkok monument. I conclude, therefore, that the second from the bottom right hand of the eight-armed figure at Phnom Trap probably originally depicted a manuscript for the attribute. The entire attribute configuration for the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara on the Bangkok monument is as follows:

Uppermost Right and Left: *padma*, or lotuses upon which sit two enshrined Buddha images

Second Upper Right: *akṣamālā* (rosary)

Third Upper Right: *pustaka* (manuscript/book)

Lowermost Right and Left: *varada mudrā*

Second Upper Left: *aṅkuśa* (hook/goad)

Third Upper Left: *kamaṇḍalu* (water pot)

Because of heavy damage I cannot definitively say that all the attributes held by the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara on the Bangkok monument correspond to the ones held by the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara depicted at Phnom Trap; however, I can state that the surviving attributes at Phnom Trap correspond exactly to the Bangkok Avalokiteśvara.²⁸ Furthermore, the configuration of identifiable attributes of the eight-armed figure at Phnom Trap do not correspond to any known depiction of Viṣṇu in Cambodia, or elsewhere. Based on this information, as well as the collaborating evidence and arguments made earlier in regard to the central and north sanctuary, I

²⁸ Mention should again be made of the tenth-century stele now located in the Walters Art Museum that depicts an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara with pendant arms displaying the *varada mudrā*. As mentioned previously, this stele also has an inscription (K. 1154) that contains the only attested use in early Cambodia of Avalokiteśvara's *Oṃ Maṇipadme Hūṃ mantra*. Woodward (2007) has argued that this depiction of the bodhisattva provides the basis of understanding for the eight-armed Avalokiteśvara in a tenth-century Cambodian setting by noting the figure's connection with the *KVS*, specifically the *KVS* narrative in which the bodhisattva satiates thirsty and suffering *pretas* ('hungry ghosts'). In other words, the Walters Art Museum stele provides a connective link of iconographic understanding with the eight-armed depiction of Avalokiteśvara on the Bangkok monument.

maintain that the eight-armed figure depicted in the central sanctuary at Phnom Trap is an eight-armed representation of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara.

Two Depictions of Avalokiteśvara?

One question that may arise from my proposed identifications for the brick reliefs at Phnom Trap concerns the nature of the tripartite configuration as some kind of artistic redundancy. In other words, some may question why two of the sanctuaries—the central and south sanctuaries—are each dedicated to depicting a manifestation of Avalokiteśvara instead of one of the sanctuaries depicting a third and different bodhisattva, or some other Buddhist figure, that would coincide with other attested Buddhist triads. For example, Buddhist triads consisting of the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Vajrapāṇi, or the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā, or some other Buddhist triad would, for some, appear to make more sense because each sanctuary would then be devoted to a separate Buddhist being. This kind of questioning may arise because of underlying assumptions that believe art historical representations of a religious tradition in a particular culture can be identified with, or traced back to, descriptions and configurations detailed in that tradition's textual sources.

First, art historians have critiqued the general position that sculptures, reliefs, architecture, and other forms of visual art must correspond to some kind of foundational text, or texts. Second, the above point, in turn, relates to a similar position that assumes local artisans must have relied upon a model or copy in order to produce their visual art, whether in the form of imported textual models or in imported foreign images, paintings, and other forms of visual art circulating in the region.

Citing Philip Rawson, A. H. Christie, and Robert Brown for support, Emma Bunker and Douglas Latchford (2004: 9) write the following in their essay on the Khmer aesthetic:

Although the early Khmer images depict primarily Hindu deities, “they were far from being mere copies or even transcriptions” of Indian prototypes, but exhibit elements that “were never created by sculptors in India,” and must instead reflect local Khmer predilections. Early Khmer artisans had no models to copy and may have relied on descriptions learned from imported religious texts and oral recitations that they ingeniously translated into visual sculptural forms.

Of course this is not to say that local Khmer artisans and their patrons were never inspired or influenced by non-local sources; rather, the point is that such external stimuli are neither mandatory nor immune to altering processes of localization. Seeking, therefore, a one-to-one key from outside Buddhist sources for the tripartite configuration of the Phnom Trap bas-reliefs may be misguided. There are, nevertheless, massive amounts of unedited and untranslated Buddhist Sanskrit texts, and future research may reveal that the Phnom Trap configuration has Buddhist textual antecedents; however, such a possible external textual antecedent is not required, nor can the current lack of such an external textual antecedent alone discredit the above posited identifications.

While external Buddhist textual sources have so far failed to provide supporting evidence for the triad depicted in the Phnom Trap bas-reliefs, the Cambodian epigraphical record may provide additional support for the proposed Buddhist identifications. The Cambodian epigraphical record was already referenced earlier in order to provide contemporary support indicating that Buddhist images of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara and/or the Buddha were sometimes established in conjunction with two accompanying *devī* images. Again, the tenth-century Bat Cum inscription on the south sanctuary records that in 950 CE an image of Lokanātha was

established along with two *devīs* at Kuṭṭīśvara. The Bat Cum inscription from the central sanctuary also records that an image of the Buddha and two *devīs* was installed at the same site of Kuṭṭīśvara.

Another contemporary Cambodian inscription indicates that Buddhist triadic configurations consisting of two manifestations of Avalokiteśvara were also known and worshipped. As discussed in chapter six, the Prasat Chikreng inscription (K. 168) of 972 CE contains an opening invocation to Ekādaśamukha, Lokeśvara, and Bhagavatī (Prajñāpāramitā).²⁹ In this inscription Ekādaśamukha—the eleven-faced manifestation of Avalokiteśvara—is recorded at the apex of a triad with Lokeśvara, another manifestation of Avalokiteśvara, and Bhagavatī. In this context, Ekādaśamukha is clearly to be understood as a higher embodiment of both compassion (Lokeśvara) and wisdom (Bhagavatī).³⁰ Granted, this particular contemporary triad does not include Vajrapāṇi, but rather Bhagavatī. The point in referencing this inscription, however, is to illustrate that Buddhist triads consisting of two manifestations or forms of Avalokiteśvara are attested in tenth-century Cambodia; therefore, such a triad should not be considered odd or deviant.

Significance and Concluding Remarks

Phnom Trap was, and remains so today, a Buddhist site.³¹ It was erected with reverence to powerful Buddhist beings, and was located in an area of Cambodia where

²⁹ For the inscription, see Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 168–69). Again, these three names are all prefixed with the Old Khmer indigenous titles of *vrah kamrateñ añ*.

³⁰ See chapter six of this dissertation for a more in-depth discussion concerning this inscription and Ekādaśamukha.

³¹ Granted, the form of Buddhism at Phnom Trap today is very different than the form of Buddhism that was practiced in the tenth century.

Buddhism was thriving in the tenth century. One of the most important inscriptions documenting the revitalization and flourishing of Buddhism in the tenth century, the Vat Sithor inscription (K. 111), comes from Sithor which is located not that far southeast of Phnom Trap.³² Recognizing the original Buddhist orientation of the sanctuaries of Phnom Trap after more than a 100 years of misidentification is a significant contribution to Khmer and Buddhist studies in and of itself. This new identification, however, is also significant with regard to one of this dissertation's running arguments: tenth-century Cambodia was a time in which Buddhist traditions were receiving a high level of support and recognition that was previously unheard of in the region. Statuaries and inscriptions dating to the tenth century in the region of present-day Kampong Cham province demonstrate that forms of Buddhism were flourishing in the region, and the Buddhist identification of these sanctuaries further strengthens this observation.

³² I hesitate to provide an exact distance since I am unsure as to the exact river and/or land route that would have been used in the tenth century between these locations. Drawing a straight line between the two locations on a map one arrives at a figure of roughly twenty-six miles, or forty-two kilometers.

Figure 8-1. The Three Sanctuaries of Phnom Trap. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-2. South Sanctuary Lintel at Phnom Trap. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-3. Central Sanctuary Lintel at Phnom Trap. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-4. North Sanctuary Lintel at Phnom Trap. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-5. North Nantuary Relief of Four-Armed Vajrapāṇi. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-6. N. 127: Four-Armed Vajrapāṇi Located in the Angkor National Museum in Siem Reap. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-7. Tenth-Century Buddhist Triad: Avalokiteśvara, Buddha, and Vajrapāṇi (MG 14880, 14912, and 14892. Source: Baptiste and Zéphir (2008: 166–71)

Figure 8-8. Central Sanctuary Relief of Four-Armed Avalokiteśvara Flanked by Two *devīs*. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-9. Central Sanctuary: Double *varada mudrā* of Four-Armed Avalokiteśvara.
Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-10. South Sanctuary Relief of Eight-Armed Avalokiteśvara Flanked by Two *devīs* (modern Buddha image in foreground). Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-11. South Sanctuary Relief of Eight-Armed Avalokiteśvara Flanked by Two *devīs*. Photo courtesy of author.

A

B

Figure 8-12. Avalokiteśvara Holding Shrine. A) miniature shrine atop a lotus, B) close-up of shrine. Photo courtesy of author.

Figure 8-13. Surviving partial outline of second shrine. Photo courtesy of author.

CHAPTER 9 CONCLUSION

In 1875 when the German Max Planck was deciding whether or not to pursue studies in the field of physics, he was advised against doing so by one professor in Munich who informed him that there was really nothing left to do because almost all the fundamental laws in the field had already been discovered.¹ With the benefit of hindsight and history, we now know that this advice was amusingly premature. Albert Einstein's 1905 papers on the special theory of relativity would eventually revolutionize the field of physics, and Planck himself would go on to originate quantum theory, for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1918. Now, the modest contributions in this dissertation in no way compare to the groundbreaking and world changing discoveries of eminent scientists like Planck and Einstein. The point of the anecdote is to stress that there is always more to study and learn in any field. While initially George Cœdès' monumental work in the field of Cambodian epigraphy would seem to make another translation of the Vat Sithor inscription unnecessary, I hope to have shown that additional examination of this inscription, along with other tenth-century inscriptions, can still teach us new things.

In the mid- to late tenth century when the Angkorian administrative infrastructure was beginning to expand and become more complex, the presence of Buddhist traditions had become more prevalent in the epigraphical record. For the first time, inscriptions from this period record the actual names of influential Buddhists like Kavīndrārimathana and Kīrtipaṇḍita, as well as other less influential donors. The works and activities of these Buddhists are recorded in the inscriptions, thus providing insight

¹ Lightman (2005: 8).

into which aspects of the traditions were being emphasized in day to day practice. Inscriptions like the one from Vat Sithor indicate that the path of the bodhisattva, Buddhist monasticism, the economy of merit, and rituals surrounding Buddhist images constituted some of the core practices for Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia. All of this practice seems to have been grounded in Yogācāra epistemological foundations that ultimately supported the path of the bodhisattva as the highest vocation for any individual. Furthermore, a newly arriving, yet conspicuous, tantric presence in the epigraphy records activities closely mirroring the practices of non-Buddhist groups. These newly arriving tantric practices likely allowed Buddhists to be more successful in their competition for support and patronage. Although still dominant, Śaivite priests would no longer have a monopoly on performing special rituals for a ruler. The Vat Sithor inscription makes clear that Buddhists, too, could perform apotropaic rites on behalf of the ruler in order to protect the land and its people. Having royal privilege extended to Buddhists occur at the same time as the first attested presence of tantric Buddhism in Cambodia is surely not a coincidence.

Nevertheless, this influx of tantric ideas and practices only represented the beginnings of a foundation that had just taken root. Despite the tenth-century epigraphical reference to the *STTS*, a full and mature form of Vajrayāna Buddhism is not really evident until the eleventh century where we finally find for the first time explicit reference to a five-Buddha family system so characteristic of later and more developed forms of tantric Buddhism (Prapandvidya 1990). What began in the tenth century eventually finds its fullest expression in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries with Jayavarman VII (r.1182 –c. 1218), an era during which Buddhist traditions had reached

their apex. Under Jayavarman VII, evidence of Vajrayāna traditions is evident mainly in the numerous remaining stone and bronze images of the tantric deity known as Hevajra.²

Even some of the influences responsible for the increasing importance and ubiquitousness of Avalokiteśvara during the reign of Jayavarman VII have their origins in the tenth century. The walls of Jayavarman VII's Banteay Chhmar temple complex depict scenes from the *KVS*. Similarly, the numerous so-called radiating Lokeśvara images from this later time are also inspired by the cosmic character of Avalokiteśvara depicted in the *KVS*.³ The influence of this hybrid tantric text, or a text closely similar, was first attested to during the tenth century, a time when popularity in the worship of Avalokiteśvara as a supreme lord, rivaling the Buddha himself, had firmly established itself in Cambodia. Containing narratives that included the subordination of gods such as Śiva, the polemical character of the *KVS* would have likely carried the same appeal for twelfth-century Buddhists as it did for the tenth-century Buddhists competing in a socio-religious environment dominated by rival sectarian groups.

That there was some level of competition between Buddhists and rival sectarian groups during the tenth century is firmly attested in the epigraphical record. This competition has been interpreted, however, in a way that has tended to characterize Buddhists as passive objects subordinated and marginalized by powerful Brahmins whose ritual prerogatives took precedence over the interests and practices of Buddhists. But this kind of interpretation fails to appreciate that the epigraphical

² For more on Hevajra in Cambodia, see Boeles (1966) and Lobo (1994). For a study on Vajrayāna Buddhism during the reign of Jayavarman VII, see Sharrock (2006).

³ See Chutiwongs (1984) for more on these images.

evidence relating to this rivalry and competition was couched in a context primarily concerned with Buddhist monastic regulations. As such, the rivalry was expressed from a Buddhist point of view, not a Brahmanical one. Buddhist themselves disparaged certain Brahmanical practices that were deemed not only soteriologically ineffective, but also were a violation of monastic regulations—regulations quite likely grounded in the tradition of the Mūlasarvāstivādins.

All of this points to a Buddhist community (consisting of monks and a laity of influential officiants) actively carving out opportunistic niches in an expanding administrative infrastructure revolving around land, material goods, constructions, and religious endowments. Buddhist traditions during this period may have been less dominant, but no less active in their quest for support and relevance. Studies focusing on Buddhist traditions in early Cambodia are predominantly concerned with the era of Jayavarman VII, a time when the success of Buddhism is most evident. I hope this dissertation has demonstrated that an examination of Buddhist traditions during the tenth century is no less important, especially since many of the foundations for much of the Buddhist thought and practices in the later twelfth and thirteenth centuries have their beginnings in the changes and events that occurred in the tenth century.

APPENDIX A
TRANSLITERATION OF VAT SITHOR INSCRIPTION (K.111)

Side A

- I. 1. Il vande pi vyāpinaṃ vyaktaṃ
svacchāśayajalāśaye
2. bhrājīṣṇu[ṃ] dharmmakāyenduṃ
vimuktaṃ skandharāhuṇā ||
- II. 3. namadhvaṃ dharmmakāyārka-
sāmbhogatanumaṇḍalam
4. nānānirmmāṇadhāmāḍhyaṃ
sādhyaṃ siddhyai maharṣibhiḥ ||
- III. 5. kalpadrumam ivākalpa-
lokābhyarthitadāyinaṃ
6. dr̥śyaṃ sukṛtinām eva
dehan nairmmāṇikan name ||
- IV. 7. śāntam agryaṃ virāgānāṃ
yoginām eva gocaram
8. agrāhyānabhilāpyaṅ ca
saddharman namatāṃ muneḥ ||
- V. 9. yathābhūmipraviṣṭānāṃ
pṛthakprajñānuvarttinam
10. dharmmaṃ sāmbhoginirddiṣṭaṃ
dhyānagrāhyan namāmy aham ||
- VI. 11. vuddhājñā devadaityādi-
bhāṣopadhyanurodhinī
12. svavarṇṇāpagatā svacchā
sphaṭikābhā punātu vaḥ ||
- VII. 13. vrahmādirūpiṇo nānā-
vineyāśānurodhataḥ
14. nirābhāsādibhūmiṣṭhā
vodhisatvā jayanti te ||
- VIII. 15. cittamātraṅ jagad dr̥ṣṭvā
svapnavat taddhitodyatāḥ
16. muditādyāḥ praviṣṭā ye
saptabhūmī[h] stavīmi tān ||
- IX. 17. mātṛvad duḥkhitam vīkṣya
jagat tadduḥkhapīditāḥ

18. tanmuktyai cittaratnaṃ ye
vodhau vaddhnanti tān bhaje || (Circle Marker, End of Section I)
- X. 19. ānamrāvanibhṛṇmauli-
bhṛṅgalīḍhāṅghripañkajaḥ
20. rājā śrījayavarmmasīd
vyomadvārāṅgarājyabhāk ||
- XI. 21. bhāsvaty apakṣapāte pi
yatrodyaty upakāriṇi
22. sādhipadmonnatis sadyaḥ
pāpidhvāntakṣayas svayam ||
- XII. 23. svarggāpavarggamārggeṇa
yaḥ piteva vahan prajāḥ
24. smṛtiraśmir vvimārggebhyaḥ
svendriyāśvān nyavārayat ||
- XIII. 25. vyavahāre satāṃ mārgge
manvādīnāṃ mate same
26. kāladhvāntaniruddhe yo
madhyāhnārka¹ ivābhavat ||
- XIV. 27. śauryyādayo guṇā yatra
tādātmyena vyavasthitāḥ
28. tattejasā parasmin nu
vahnau loha ivoṣṇatā ||
- XV. 29. vārayitrāpi yatnena
parastrīharaṇāt parān
30. śrutyaiva yena kenāpi
paravidyā svayaṃ hṛtā ||
- XVI. 31. tyaktāṃ dharmmasutenāpi
kalidoṣamahodadhau
32. yaś śrutismṛtihastābhyām
uddharet satyatāṅganām ||
- XVII. 33. sādihāraṇāpi rājanye
rājanītir yyam āśritā
34. pāvanī bhavinām ambho-
dhārā tirthālayaṃ² yathā ||

¹ Cœdès transcribed *madhyāhnārka* as *madyāhnārka* ('d' instead of aspirated 'dh'), but the rubbing reads correctly as *madhyāhnārka*.

² Corr.: *tīthālayaṃ*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 198).

- XVIII. 35. prajānāṃ dayitaś cakre
pīditānāṃ³ piteva yaḥ
36. prasāritakarākāraiś
cārair aśrupramārjjanam || (Circle Marker, End of Section II)
- XIX. 37. tasyopāntacaro vidvān
vidyāmbhonidhipāragaḥ
38. ākīrṇṇakīrttipūrṇṇendur
ācāryaḥ kīrttipaṇḍitaḥ ||
- XX. 39. niśśeṣaśāstrajaladhīn⁴
tīrtvā⁵ vīryoduvena⁶ yaḥ
40. labdhvārthatattvaratnāni
vibheje dhīdhanārthinām ||
- XXI. 41. saujanyādiguṇāḥ khyātāḥ
prakṛtyāgner ivoṣṇatā
42. doṣās tv āgantukā⁷ yasya
lohasya dravatā yathā ||
- XXII. 43. hṛdi roṣādayo yasya
kathañ cid yadi jīmbhitāḥ
44. krīdoragā⁸ iva kṣipraṃ
yayur vvidyāvidheyatā[t ||]
- XXIII. 45. catussandhyāsu yogātmā
caturddānānvito nva[ham]
46. caturmmūdrātmako⁹ dharmmanñ
catuṣparṣatsu¹⁰ yo [diśat ||]¹¹

³ Use of 'd' for 'ḍ.' Read as *pīditānaṃ*.

⁴ Cœdès transcribed *niśśeṣa* as *niśśesa*, but the rubbing clearly reads *niśśeṣa*.

⁵ Corr.: *tīrtvā*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 198).

⁶ Corr.: *vīryoḍupena*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 198).

⁷ Cœdès transcribed *āgantukā* as *agantukā*, but the rubbing clearly reads *āgantukā*.

⁸ Read as *krīḍoragā*.

⁹ Corr.: °*mudrā*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 198).

¹⁰ Read as °*paraṣatsu*.

¹¹ Although not checking the rubbing or stone, Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284) provided the conjectural emendation *diśat* based on Cœdès' reading of *yo ~-*. Sanderson is probably correct since after referring to the rubbing the top of the dependent vowel marker for 'i' is still visible in this damaged section of the inscription.

- XXIV. 47. tyāgāyopārjītāsa[m]khyā-
svāpateyo pi dhī[dānaḥ ||]¹²
48. kvāpi ṣaṭpiṭakārthāḍhyo
yas sūribhir udīrita[h ||]
- XXV. 49. yaḥ parasmaipadañ karttā
sarvvabhāveṣu ka[r]mma[su]
50. na tv ātmanepadañ jātu
kenāpy uktaḥ prayo[jayan ||]

Side B

- XXVI. 1. tamaḥ pravṛttau jagatām
prāvṛṣavati rohitaḥ
2. yatpravṛtte śaratśuddhe¹³
vuddhadharmmendur āvabhau ||
- XXVII. 3. nairātmyacittamātrādi-¹⁴
darśanārkkas tiraskṛtaḥ
4. mithyādrṣṭiniśā yasmin
bhūyo dina ivāvabhau ||
- XXVIII. 5. śāstraṃ madhyavibhāgādyaṃ
dīpaṃ saddharmmapaddhateḥ
6. kāladoṣāniladhvastaṃ
bhūyo jvālayati sma yaḥ ||
- XXIX. 7. lakṣagraṅtham¹⁵ abhiprajñam
yo nveṣya pararāṣṭrataḥ
8. tattvasaṅgrahaṭkādi-
tantrañ cādhyāpayad yamī ||
- XXX. 9. āśritā bhūbhṛtām pārśve
dṛptās tārkkikakuñjaraḥ
10. śākyasiṃhātmajaṃ prāpya
nirmmadās te yam aprabhāḥ ||
- XXXI. 11. yadīyaśiṣyanāmāpi

¹² For support in restoring *dhīdānaḥ*, cf. *dhīdhanārthinām* in st. XX, ln. 40. Coedès (*IC*, 6: 198) reads as *dhī ~-*.

¹³ *Sic*, sandhi incorrect. Read as *śaracchuddhe*, per Coedès (*IC*, 6: 198).

¹⁴ Coedès (*IC*, 6: 198) contains a transliteration typo in this verse. °*cittmātrādi* should read °*cittamātrādi*.

¹⁵ Sanderson (2004: 427, n. 284) provides the following emendation, *lakṣagraṅtham**.

vādikarṇṇapuṭe patat

12. santrāsañ janayām āsa
mantravat sarppamaṇḍale ||
- XXXII. 13. sāntaḥpuraiḥ pramuditai
rājabhir yyo gurūkṛtaḥ
14. dideśa vahuśo dharmmaṃ
vauddhaṃ dharmmāsane sthitaḥ ||
- XXXIII. 15. deśakālātmasaṃvittvaṃ
pare ṅkitaparīkṣaṇam
16. ≡≡ tvaṃ yadgiraṃ nityaṃ
ninye śrīkamvuhūbhṛtām ||
- XXXIV. 17. ≡≡ ā sāntvagarbheṇa
yatnenārādhyā bhūpatim
18. nānārājabhayād yena
vadhārḥā apī mocitāḥ ||
- XXXV. 19. rājakāryyakṛtau drṣṭvā
yatayo vipadañ gatāḥ
20. rājñe niveditā yena
mocitās sthāpitā naye ||
- XXXVI. 21. rāṣṭramaṇḍalarakṣārthaṃ
satkṛtyāyuñkta yan nṛpaḥ
22. maṇḍirābhyantare¹⁶ bhīkṣṇaṃ
śāntipuṣṭyādikarmmasu ||
- XXXVII. 23. ghṛṇanirmmitamūrttiṃ yo
vauddhatrāṇārthaṃ āpadaḥ
24. sthāpitaṃ sthāpayām āsa
bhūyo bhagnāsaṇaṃ munim ||
- XXXVIII. 25. mokṣadvāre khilāl lokān
praveśayitum arthayan
26. rairūpyarañjitan¹⁷ dvāraṃ
vyatarad yo mudā munau ||
- XXXIX. 27. advayānuttaraṃ yānam
anyeṣām svam ivārjjayan

¹⁶ Read as *mandira*°.

¹⁷ Coedès transcribes *rairrupya*° instead of *rairūpya*°, but the rubbing indicates ‘ū’ not ‘u.’

28. yo diśan munaye haimaṃ
rājataṃ śivikādvayam ||
- XL. 29. mahat tāmramayan yaś ca
bhavanācchādanāṃ muneḥ
30. prāsādaṃ maṇihemāḍhyaṃ
tārasimhāsanaṃ vyadhāt ||
- XLI. 31. yaḥ prakṛṣṭe munau kṣetre
pārārthyaphalam arthayan
32. khārīcatussahasrāṇi
dhānyānām adīśan munau ||
- XLII. 33. vāhyaṃ guhyañ ca saddharmmaṃ
sthāpayitvā cakāra yaḥ
34. pūjārthan tasya saṃghasyā-
tithes ca pṛthagāśramān ||
- XLIII. 35. karīndrān kariṇīr aśvān
mahiśān vṛṣabhān vahūn
36. dhenūr yya āśramān bhogān
dāsīdāsam adān munau ||
- XLIV. 37. tatsthāne sthāpitā sthityai
sarvavidvañśabhāsvataḥ
38. prajñāpāramitātārī¹⁸
jananī yena tāyinām ||
- XLV. 39. śrīsatyavarmmaṇā bajri-
lokeśārccā daśādhikāḥ
40. sthāpitāḥ prāg girau bhagnā-
sanā yo tiṣṭhipat¹⁹ punaḥ ||
- XLVI. 41. tuṅgādrau svapure khyāte
kumārambhapure pi yaḥ
42. amarendrapurādyeṣu
lokeśādīn atiṣṭhipat ||
- XLVII. 43. yo nekā dikṣu bhuddhārccās
siddhā bhagnāḥ purātanāḥ

¹⁸ The word *tārī* is unattested and the rubbing does, indeed, read *tārī*. I am reading it as some adjectival form derived from \sqrt{tr} (e.g., *tāra*, *tārin*, etc.) modifying *prajñāpāramitā*. Also cf. Coedes' (IC, 6: 207, n. 1).

¹⁹ Coedès' transliteration reads *tiṣṭhipat*. Corr. : *tiṣṭhipat*.

44. saṃskṛtyātiṣṭhipad bhūyas
sāśramāś ca jalāśayān ||
- XLVIII. 45. [ya]dīyaśīṣyavarggo pi
śāstānugrāhako nṛṇāṃ
46. [sa]prāsādās savibhavāś
cakre nekā nimā muneḥ ||
- XLIX. 47. ≍ – rmmapaṭṭane grāme
svaparāṛthaprasiddhaye
48. ≍ ≍ dīn sthāpayām āsa
navaṣaṇmaṅgale śake ||
- L. 49. ≍ ≍ tuma ~ – sarvvam
etad rājājñayaiva saḥ
50. ≍ h śa ≍ y -- ≍
piṇḍasyāgneḥ²⁰ prabhāvataḥ || (Circle Marker, End of Section III)

Side C

- LI. 1. eṣā śrījayavarmmājñā
buddhadharmmānucār[iṇī]
2. vauddhānām anukarttavyā
mokṣābhyudayasiddhaye ||
- LII. 3. ye nakṣatragaṇāḥ pūrvva-
phalguṇīpramukhāḥ smṛtāḥ
4. śreṣṭhā dvādaśamāseṣu
te māsapatayo matāḥ ||
- LIII. 5. kṣayavṛddhikarā loke
mahāvīryyā maharddhikāḥ
6. te prekṣante prajās sarvvā
dharmmādharmmaparāyanāḥ²¹ ||
- LIV. 7. tato nighnanti pāpiṣṭhān
viṣamā vṛṣṭivāyavaḥ
8. devā nāgās samās tv ete
dharmmiṣṭhān ramayanti ca ||
- LV. 9. satvārthāya²² tataś śāstrā

²⁰ Read as *piṇḍasyāgneḥ*.

²¹ Read as *parāyanāḥ*.

10. yathoktā dvādaśotsavāḥ
māse māse tathā kāryyāḥ
krameṇa sukham icchatā || (Circle Marker, End of Section IV)
- LVI. 11. sthāpitān diśi vahneḥ prāk-
sthāpanāyā mahāmuneḥ
12. triṣkālaṃ pratyahaṃ gāndi[ṃ]²³
saṃpūjyākoṭayed yamī ||
- LVII. 13. taddhvaniṃ pāvanaṃ saṃgha-
kāryyakālāvavodhanāt
14. ke cittenāpi śṛṇvanti
dhanyās te tridivaṅ gatāḥ ||
- LVIII. 15. vihāraṃ kārayitvā yas
triṣu ratneṣu kalpayan
16. pareṣāṃ hitasiddhyartham
sa mahāpuṇyam āpnuyāt ||
- LIX. 17. tribhāgas sarvvasaṃbhogo
ratnatritayakalpitaḥ
18. sthāpanīyaḥ pṛthaktvena
mā miśras syāt parasparam ||
- LX. 19. na jñaptiś ced vihārasya
bhikṣubhir vvidhivat kṛta
20. avihāra iti jñeyaḥ
koṣṭhāgāras sa eva tu ||
- LXI. 21. jīvikārthe kṛtas so ya[ṃ]
na parārthe na śāntaye
22. vrahmapuṇyan na tatrāsti
yena sarvvajñatā[ṃ] vrajet ||
- LXII. 23. vihārasya yadā jñaptis
sādhunā vidhinā kṛtā
24. tataḥ puṇyam ivākāśam
sarvvatra gatam akṣayam ||
- LXIII. 25. ata evavidhaṃ puṇyam
ye lumpanti narādhamāḥ
26. tair ghoran nārakaṃ duḥkham

²² Corr. : *sattvā*°, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 200).

²³ Read as *gaṇḍīm*, per Cœdès, (*IC*, 6: 208, n. 1).

- anantam anubhūyate ||
- LXIV. 27. gṛhibhiḥ nnopabhoktavyaṃ
saṃghadravyaviṣādhikam
28. viṣaṃ hi pratikurvanti
mantrādyāḥ na tu sāmghikam ||
- LXV. 29. sarvvajñavākyam evaṃ tat
kṛtvā manasi bhaktitaḥ
30. vidvān utpādyā vidhivad
vihāraṃ dūratas sthitaḥ || (Circle Marker, End of Section V)
- LXVI. 31. guṇinaś śīlavantaś ca
dhīmantaś te gaṇādhikāḥ
32. nānābhogas tadarthāya
kalpitaḥ puṇyam icchatā ||
- LXVII. 33. pratyūśādiṣu yat karma
yamināṃ muninoditam
34. kāryaṃ saṃghena tat sarvvaṃ
yājakena viśeṣataḥ ||
- LXVIII. 35. na saṃghais sarvvayajñeṣu
gantavyam animantritaḥ
36. svayaṃ prāptā hitenāpi
tatraite pāpabhāgiṇaḥ ||
- LXIX. 37. hṛnmūdramantravidyāsu²⁴
homakarmaṇi kovidaḥ
38. bajraghaṇṭārahasyajño
dakṣiṇīyaḥ purohitaḥ ||
- LXX. 39. vedasūktarṣabhavrahma-
ghoṣonmīlābhiṣecanaiḥ
40. muneḥ parvādine kuryyāt
snānādīni purohitaḥ ||
- LXXI. 41. buddhasnānādibhir llokāś
sukhitā dharmmavarddhanāḥ
42. antarbhūtā hi sarvvajña-
kāye satvās²⁵ carācarāḥ ||

²⁴ Corr. : °mudrā°, per Cœdès (IC, 6: 200).

²⁵ Corr. : sattvās, per Cœdès (IC, 6: 200).

- LXXII. 43. pratīyotpādanam vrahma-
ghoṣas saddharmma āṛṣabhaḥ
44. sūktaś śāntyavadhāraś ca
gāthāveda iti smṛtaḥ ||
- LXXIII. 45. vrahmaghoṣādayo vidyā
yadokrā mama mastake
46. tan mūrddhātīva maṅgalya
iti sarvvajñasāsanaṃ ||
- LXXIV. 47. grāse vakre tha saṃkrāntau
sarvvotpāte samutthite
48. śāstuḥ snānādi kartavyam
prajāśāntir yyathā bhavet ||
- LXXV. 49. śraddhāyā vṛṇhane nṛṇāṃ
śāsanasya vivṛddhaye
50. pratiparvadinam kāryyā
viduṣa dharmmadeśanā ||

Side D

- LXXVI. 1. ॐॐॐॐॐॐ
ॐॐॐ vā yathāvalam
2. ॐॐॐॐॐॐ
ॐॐॐॐ parāyanaiḥ ||
- LXXVII. 3. ॐॐॐॐॐॐ
ॐॐॐॐ ṇ sīkrta
4. s ॐॐ mān n -- ॐ
ॐॐॐ vi ॐ ātitām ||
- LXXVIII. 5. [bha]ktimā sthāyimanasā
ॐॐॐ ddhvāñjalin nataḥ
6. – r ān nivedayet pūjā
ॐॐ stā. eṣu satsv api ||
- LXXIX. 7. ॐॐॐ ṣana eveṣṭam
pradhāna[m] dharmmasādhane
8. ॐॐॐॐॐ tāṃ dharmmas
sadā sarvvatra varddhate ||
- LXXX. 9. ॐॐॐॐ kam ekāgraś
calayann īṣad āṇanam
10. ॐॐॐ. ām api vadann
anantaṃ puṇyam āpnuyāt ||

- LXXXI. 11. puṇyāny evākhilās satvās²⁶
sa cet kuryyus tato dhikam
12. saddharmmadhāriṇaḥ puṇyam
ekasyety uktavān muniḥ ||
- LXXXII. 13. tasmāt tyaktānyakarttavyo
vihārastho vicakṣaṇaḥ
14. saddharmmaṃ parigrhṇāti²⁷
sarvavadā lekhanādinā || (Circle Marker, End of Section VI)
- LXXXIII. 15. samyagācārabhūṣeṇa
vihārādhikṛtādinā
16. guravo bhyugatās²⁸ sarvve
satkarttavā yathāvalam ||
- LXXXIV. 17. ācārapūrvvikā vānī²⁹
trṇāny ambhāṃsi bhūmayaḥ
18. sarvatra sarvavadā santi
dehasārāthinām satām ||
- LXXXV. 19. deho hy avaskarasamas
sarrvvāsūcyālayas sadā
20. tathāpi tasya sāro sti
dharmaḥ kalpadrumo mataḥ ||
- LXXXVI. 21. dahyamānād yathāgārān
majjatkaulād ivāmvudhau
22. dehād vināśināś śīghraṃ
grāhyo dharmmanidhir vudhaiḥ ||
- LXXXVII. 23. vāyuvegākulasvalpa-
dīpaśobhānavasthitam
24. jīvita[m] vīkṣate vidvān
tasya nākāryyakāritā ||
- LXXXVIII. 25. jadāpi³⁰ strī pravekṣyanti
vahnau mṛtyuṃ samīkṣate

²⁶ Corr. : *sattvās*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 201).

²⁷ Read as *parigrhṇāti*.

²⁸ Corr : *bhyudgatās*, per Cœdès (*IC*, 6: 201).

²⁹ Cœdès transliterated this incorrectly as *vāni* (and read it as *vāni*). The rubbing clearly depicts a long 'ī,' as in *vānī*.

³⁰ Read as *jadāpi*.

26. nārthas sarvvāpakaraṇais
tasyāḥ kim u vivekinām ||
- LXXXIX. 27. na kuryāt svarggamokṣārtham
yatnan nehahite pi yaḥ
28. mātur yyauvanavr̥kṣasya
ṭaṅkaś chedārtham eva saḥ ||
- XC. 29. jāyate gāḍhaduḥkhāya
kalpāyur api durjjanaḥ
30. paśūnām vahvanarthāya
dīrghajīvo hi sañcitaḥ ||
- XCI. 31. kā cid bhagavataḥ pūjā
yajvācāryyādikalpitā
32. poṣaṇīyā svamāteva
yatnaiś śraddhāpurassaraiḥ ||
- XCII. 33. dakṣiṇā yājakādibhyo
dātavya prativatsaram
34. bhikṣubhyo nudinaṃ bhojyaṃ
savastraṃ dharmmavādine ||
- XCIII. 35. saṃghabhoge parikṣiṇe
mūrdhastān api tāyinaḥ
36. yo vikretā maṇīn saṃgha-
pūjanārtham sa puṇyabhāk ||
- XCIV. 37. tad deśam varddhayeyus te
vihārādhikṛtādayaḥ
38. viśeṣān nāśayeyur mmā
mahāpāpaprasaṅgataḥ ||
- XCV. 39. pāpī puṇyālayam prāpya
paścāttāpena śuddhyati
40. tatsthas tu tatṣayaṅ kṛtvā
viśuddhyai kutra yāsyati ||
- XCVI. 41. ārāmakṣetradāsādyā
ratnatritayakalpitāḥ
42. nāyattā viṣayādhyakṣa-
dhānyeśādyena vandhuṣu ||
- XCVII. 43. vāhyadvārāt prabhṛty eva
yāvad abhyantare narāḥ
44. na prahāryyāḥ kaśenāpi

durvvācā vāpi doṣiṇaḥ ॥

- XCVIII. 45. eṣājñā dhimato mārggas
smṛtīmedhādisādhane
46. rasāyanasya jihveva
sarvvadoṣanisūdane ॥
- XCVIX. 47. grāhyaṃ vudhenāparavaktramātram
ihārthasiddyai kila kaic śid uktam
48. prāg eva sarvvajñamataṃ vimukteḥ
svarggasya mārggo nṛpavākyam etat ॥
- C. 49. ājñām imāṃ yo nugato pi pāpī
kalpeta tatpāpaviṣaṃ sudhāyai
50. yas tām atītas tv api puṇyakarmmā
jāyeta tatpuṇyasudhāṃ viṣāya ॥ (Circle Marker, End of Section VII)

APPENDIX B
THE TRIKĀYA AND TRIADIC PARALLELS IN OTHER CAMBODIAN INSCRIPTIONS

Phnom Banteay Neang (K. 214)

Like the Vat Sithor inscription, the *trikāya* is also recorded in a tenth-century stele inscription from Phnom Banteay Neang which was documented by Bergaigne in 1882, and later edited by Coédès in *IC II* (2: 202). The invocatory verses to the *trikāya* were also discussed at length by Kern (1899). Located in western Cambodia, Banteay Neang is in Banteay Mean Chey province, about 4 kilometers southeast of the district Mongkol Borei. The inscription records some of the donative activities of the family of Tribhūvanavajra, the *yogī* and *ācārya* who authored the inscription.

The inscription on side A opens with an invocation to the Absolute Truth (Skt. *paramārtha*). This Absolute Truth is described in terms of three embodiments for the purpose of liberating the Three Worlds (Skt. *trailokya*); in other words, the *dharmakāya*, *sāmbhogakāya/sāmbhogikakāya*, and the *nirmāṇakāya/nairmāṇikakāya* are invoked as a collective representation of the Absolute Truth in Buddhism. Since Kern (1899) has already devoted much attention to this stanza, it will suffice to briefly summarize his primary observation and direct the reader to his own work. In short, Kern argued that the inscription's opening stanza reflected the Buddhist concepts of ultimate truth (Skt. *paramārthasatya*) and conventional truth (Skt. *lokasaṃvṛtisatya*, or simply *saṃvṛtisatya*). This means that from an ultimate perspective there is only the Absolute Truth, which is unconditioned, non-dual, empty, and so forth. Furthermore, this absolute level of truth is synonymous with the *dharmakāya*. Whereas the other two embodiments of the Buddha represent a conventional truth from which the truth of the ultimate can be approached and understood. For example, the manifestation of the

sāmbhogakāya is a method in which the Dharma is conveyed to advanced bodhisattvas; whereas the *nirmāṇakāya* are manifestations appearing in the world of form in order to make the Dharma known to less advanced sentient beings. The world of conventional truths is the world of things, the everyday world of religious practice, the world of concepts and ideas, the place we live in, and so on. But this world of conventional truths is ultimately empty and lacks any intrinsic existence; this is the ultimate truth.

The invocation continues in stanzas two and three with praise for Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) and Prajñāpāramitā. Thus, the first three stanzas result in praise to a Buddhist triadic configuration consisting of (1) the Absolute Truth which takes on the embodiments of *dharmakāya*, *sāmbhogakāya*, and *nirmāṇakāya*, (2) Lokeśvara and (3) Prajñāpāramitā. Similar to the Vat Sithor inscription, the inscription of Phnom Banteay Neang has a triadic configuration embedded within another triadic configuration. Again, the first stanza praises the Absolute Truth; which, from the perspective of conventional truth, takes on three embodiments that together represent one ontological reality. The other triadic configuration consists of the Absolute Truth, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā.

The placement of Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā within the triad can be explained in terms of the personal preference and affiliation of the author of the inscription. With regard to the latter, Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā are clearly, according to the inscription, the primary divinities (Skt. *deva*) of Tribhūvanavajra's family. For example, stanza five of the Sanskrit section indicates that Tribhūvanavajra's maternal grandfather

donated a slave to Jagadīśvara¹ (i.e., Lokeśvara). Stanza six records that in 982 CE an individual named Somavajra donated an image of Lokeśvara to his wife, Tribhūvanavajra's sister. Lines fourteen and fifteen of the Khmer section corroborate this event. The inscription also indicates that the image installed in 982 CE restored or reestablished the family Jagadīśvara originally installed by the grandfather. In that same year an image of Prajñāpāramitā was installed, and various gifts were offered to the family's gods (Skt. *devas*). Based on the family's personal affiliation with Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā as divinities worthy of veneration and gifts in return for protection of the family and land, it simply makes sense to include them in the opening invocation of the inscription.

Nancy Dowling (1996) has argued that Prajñāpāramitā is understood in this inscription, as well as other tenth-century Cambodian inscriptions, as representing a personification of the second jewel of Buddhism, the Dharma. She writes:

Though tenth-century Khmer inscriptions often commence with an invocation to the *triratna*, both the Ben Vien and Phnom Banteay Nan inscriptions affirm the personification of the three jewels (1996: 338).

Dowling's argument essentially claims that since there are tenth-century Cambodia inscriptions that explicitly open with an invocation to the Three Jewels (Skt. *triratna*), other inscriptions such as the one from Phnom Banteay Neang that open with a triad consisting of the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā should be understood as personifications of the same *triratna* configuration explicitly invoked in other contemporary inscriptions. She then attempts to support her observation with

¹ cf. the use of Jagadīśvara in K. 244 which is recorded in Cœdès (*IC*, 3: 89). This inscription is discussed in chapter six. Stanza seven of K. 214 also indicates that Tribhūvanavajra and his family restored the Jagadīśvara of the family; that is, the newly donated image of Lokeśvara restored/replaced the original image of Jagadīśvara installed by Tribhūvanavajra's grandfather.

references to a couple of Buddhist texts, which she admittedly could not connect with early Cambodia.

Certainly Prajñāpāramita, the very personification of the Perfection of Wisdom corpus of literature, can be associated with the Dharma (in this case, Mahāyāna texts). Additionally, bodhisattvas (especially Lokeśvara) have been associated with the third jewel of Buddhism in other sources.² While I am not completely adverse to Dowling's observation, there is a puzzling feature of the Phnom Banteay Neang inscription that perhaps weakens the argument for seeing the invocation to the Absolute Truth, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā as equivalent to the three Jewels of Buddhism.

² For example, see Holt (1991: 46–53). Although this does not invalidate his connections between Avalokiteśvara and the *saṅgha*, readers should note that the *Avalokiteśvara-Guṇa-Karaṇḍavyūha Sūtra* cited by Holt is a 15th or 16th century Nepalese text that draws heavily on the earlier text also known as the *Karaṇḍavyūha Sūtra* (which also has the full name of *Avalokiteśvara-Guṇa-Karaṇḍavyūha*). Holt cites a date between 4th to 11th century which indicates that he, like many other scholars, have confused these two texts as being same. They are not. The first chapter from the later Nepalese text that Holt draws upon for support in identifying Avalokiteśvara with the *saṅgha* is entirely new and not found in the earlier *Karaṇḍavyūha Sūtra*, which, according to scholars such as Adelheid Mette (1991 and 1997), dates to the fifth or sixth century. Woodward (2007: 80 and n. 51) also makes a passing reference to this text when discussing the problematic nature of associating the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, Prajñāpāramitā triad with the Three Jewels of Buddhism, but he rightly notes that the text comes after the tenth century. For additional discussion on the confusion between these texts and issues of dating, see Stulldhome (2002) 9–17.

If we set aside doxographical assumptions deriving mainly from Tibetan categorical systems, alternative configurations concerning the *triratna* could be considered. There are, for instance, Southeast Asian Buddhist sources indicating that Lokeśvara is sometimes expressed as representing the Dharma, or the second jewel of Buddhism. In the contemporary tenth-century Cambodian inscription K. 452 (discussed later) an image of Lokeśa (i.e., Lokeśvara) is described as a personification of compassion that embodies the Dharma. Associating Lokeśvara with the Dharma, not Prajñāpāramita, would fit the hierarchical structure of the Phnom Banteay Neang inscription. The tenth-century Javanese tantric Buddhist treatise known as the *Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānikan* also explicitly connects Lokeśvara with the Dharma. The *Saṅ Hyaṅ Kamahāyānikan*, according to Lokesh Chandra (1995), is actually a collective title for an anthology of Mahāyāna texts. The reference concerning the *triratna* is in the *Advaya-Sādhana*. It states: “The holy Śākyamuni has, in truth, the holy Buddha as his essence (tatva), Śrī Lokeśvara has the holy Dharma as his essence, Bajrapāṇi has the venerable Saṅgha as his essence. They are called bhaṭāra Ratnatraya. Vairocana, Amitābha and Akṣobhaya are called Ratnatraya. Vairocana, Ratnasambhava and Amoghasiddhi are also Ratnatraya” (trans. Chandra 1995: 425). Of course the inclusion of Vajrapāṇi as the third jewel does not coincide with the Phnom Banteay Neang inscription; nor is it justifiable to suppose knowledge of a five-family system in the Phnom Banteay Neang inscription. I bring up these examples to highlight the diversity of Buddhist categorical systems relating to the *triratna*, and also to highlight that Southeast Asian sources should not be neglected in our quest for answers.

When reading the inscription, for example, the order (or hierarchy) of Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā are not what one would expect if Prajñāpāramitā was supposed be synonymous with the second jewel of Buddhism. The traditional order for the *triratna* is (1) the Buddha, (2) the Dharma and (3) the Saṅgha. The Vat Sithor inscription and the inscription of Prasat Kôk (K. 164)—both cited by Dowling—maintain this traditional order when explicitly praising the *triratna* in the opening invocation, as do Buddhist texts.³ The only possible exception is the inscription of Kôk Samrong since the first surviving stanza praises the *saṅgha*, and then the following second stanza praises the Buddha and Dharma. It should be noted, however, that the opening two stanzas of this inscription are badly damaged. Because of this damage, it is certainly possible that all three jewels may have originally been mentioned together in stanza two, despite the opening homage to the Buddhist community.⁴ Regardless, however, Dharma still follows directly after the Buddha in the Kôk Samrong inscription.

Jumping ahead to the time of Jayavarman VII during the late- twelfth to early thirteenth centuries, we have explicit epigraphical evidence that Prajñāpāramitā, despite her elevated importance, was not synonymous with the second jewel of Buddhism. The opening invocations of the Preah Khan inscription, for example, clearly separate the *triratna* and both Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā. The order of praise in the Preah Khan inscription is as follows: (1) praise to the *triratna* across three stanzas,⁵ (2) praise to

³ Although I am certainly not familiar with every Buddhist text, I have not yet come across one that lists the three jewels in any order other than Buddha, Dharma, and Saṅgha.

⁴ The fragmented Sanskrit is as follow for the first two stanzas: *namas sa[m]ghāya ān - ॐ ॐ ॐ ॐ ॐ - ॐ - / jalāñjalir api nyasto ॐ ॐ ॐ ॐ ॐ - // saṃvuddharatnaṃ praṇamāmi dharmma - - ॐ - - ॐ - - / nirbhinnatā - ॐ - - striloke / ja - - - ॐ - - - //* (Cœdès, IC, 3: 80).

⁵ (a) praise to the Buddha who takes on three embodiments (i.e., the *trikāya*), (b) praise to the Dharma and (c) praise to the Saṅgha

Lokeśvara in one stanza, and (3) praise to the ‘Mother of Jinas’ (i.e., Prajñāpāramitā) in one stanza. The invocation to Prajñāpāramitā in stanza five further states that she is not synonymous with the Dharma, but one who goes before the Dharma of the Buddha.

Bow your head in devotion to the Mother of the Jinas, she who goes before the Law (i.e., Dharma) of the Lord of Sages (the Buddha), replete with virtues; she who is to be seen by the learned with their own eyes, dispelling the web of all doubt.⁶

T.S. Maxwell (2007: 7) who recently translated this inscription comments that “In the Triratna hierarchy (described in verses 1–3), she is said to arise before the Law, because the Dharma proceeds from insight and wisdom explained in the scripture, which in this sense is its mother.” While the meanings and associations in tenth-century inscriptions are not necessarily the same as those in later eras, it seems safe to conclude that Prajñāpāramitā was not to be understood as personification of the second jewel of Buddhism as Dowling contends.⁷

The Inscription of Prasat Plang (K. 452)

The Prasat Plang inscription, edited by Cœdès (*IC*, 5: 156–57), is a short Sanskrit inscription containing the last six stanzas of what was originally a longer inscription. Located within the Puok district of Siem Reap province, the prasat (Skt. *prāsāda*, ‘sanctuary,’ ‘shrine,’ ‘temple’) is located in the vicinity of the river Plang in Prei Chrouk commune. The inscription records the installation (or re-installation) of an image of Lokeśa (i.e., Lokeśvara / Avalokiteśvara) along with various goods, slaves, cattle, a

⁶ trans. Maxwell (2007: 7).

⁷ On this matter, Woodward (2007: 80) suggests that it was certainly possible that some contemporary Buddhists may have made the connection between the Buddha, Avalokiteśvara, Prajñāpāramitā triad and the Three Jewels of Buddhism, but there is simply no epigraphical evidence to support this connection.

monastery, and so on by a donor whose name is now lost. The installation took place in 910 Śaka (988 CE), firmly placing the event during the reign of Jayavarman V.

The first surviving stanza of the inscription states:

Through the efforts⁸ of the (or: his) Mind, Speech, and Body he guided⁹ the minds of his own family, and others who are wise, in the principles pertaining to the Teachings.¹⁰

The rest of the inscription records the installation of a Lokeśa image in 910 Śaka, along with a list of various donations to the bodhisattva. As a result of these donative acts, Lokeśa was expected to preside over that particular region. The inscription ends with a brief homage to the Buddha, and by expressing how those who refrain from bad deeds in order to instead uphold virtuous deeds will prosper. The inscription is another example testifying to the popularity of Lokeśvara among Buddhists in tenth-century Cambodia. Furthermore, it attests to the importance of tutelary deities presiding over specific regions. The inscription also emphasizes the pan-Buddhist importance of spreading the Dharma for the benefit of others, the practice of giving (Skt. *dāna*), and the concept of karma via a rather formulaic expression of karmic reward and retribution.

The reference to the efforts or activities of the Mind (Skt. *buddhi*), Speech (Skt. *vāk*) and Body (Skt. *kāya*) of the unnamed donor, however, may well have other intended meanings pertaining to Buddhist thought. From a basic Buddhist position one is concerned with the alleviation of suffering (Skt. *duḥkha*) arising from physical and

⁸ Skt. *ceṣṭābhiḥ* (masculine, instrumental, plural) may be translated to denote that the action of guiding (Skt. *vyanayan*) was accomplished via the activities, efforts, or endeavors of the mind, speech, and body.

⁹ Skt. *vyanayan* (imperative, 1st person singular of *vi + √nī*). More literally the root of this word provides the sense of leading someone or something, hence my preference for ‘guiding.’ Therefore, by extension, this basic meaning can also mean to be trained, taught, instructed, educated, etc. in some topic (i.e., being properly led or guided in a subject).

¹⁰ Skt. *kāyavāgbuddhiceṣṭābhir yo manāṃsi manasvinām / svakulānām pareṣāñ ca dharmmeṣu vya[na]yan nayān //*

cognitive activities often expressed in terms of the activities of the body, speech, and mind. In other words, the uncultivated activities of the body, speech, and mind are often spoken of as giving rise to a false view of self and erroneous dualistic conceptions. Conversely, one can cultivate the activities of the body, speech, and mind in order to attain a correct view of reality, and thus ultimately alleviate suffering and attain enlightenment.

But later tantric Buddhist traditions extend this general understanding the mind, speech, and body by employing ideas and vocabulary associated with the *trikāya* doctrine. In some tantric circles, for example, the Mind is associated with the *dharmakāya* (which is equivalent with Buddhahood, Mahāvairocana, etc.), Speech is associated with the *saṃbhogakāyas*, and the Body is associated with the *nirmāṇakāyas*. One good example relating to how the Mind, Speech, and Body are understood in this later context is found in the early tantric text commonly referred to as the *Mahāvairocana Tantra/Sūtra (MVT)*.¹¹ Making use of the earlier Yogācāra position that understands emptiness (Skt. *śūnyatā*) as the absence of a falsely imagined subject-object duality, sources like the *MVT* claim that one's own mind, speech, and body are ultimately inseparable from the 'bodies' of the Buddha. Using practices that employ such things as *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudras* in order to help bridge this gnostic gap, the goal of the practitioner is to make this identification and attain enlightenment. In his introduction to *MVT*, Stephen Hodge (2003) summarizes the connection between the Mind, Speech, and Body and the embodiments of the Buddha. I will quote him (2003: 33) at length.

¹¹ For the *Mahāvairocana Sūtra*, see Giebel (2005) and Hodge (2003).

Finally there is the result of Perfect Enlightenment. This is mentioned several times with specific reference to Mahā-vairocana. Basing himself on the MVT, Buddhaguhya states that ‘*at the moment of his Perfect Enlightenment, [Mahā-vairocana] spontaneously pervaded all of the Three Realms . . . with the Adornments of his Inexhaustible Body [Speech and Mind]*’ (3a) and acted for the benefit of all beings by revealing the Dharma. These adornments are the self-revelation of the qualities or ‘content’ of Perfect Enlightenment on the physical, verbal and mental levels in structured patterns throughout the universe. It is because of their meaningful configuration in this way that these Adornments are also termed ‘*cakras*’ or ‘*maṇḍalas*’. This revelation of the Dharma is said to occur spontaneously at the moment of Vairocana’s Perfect Enlightenment by virtue of his compassion and so the three mandalas described in the MVT are collectively said to be ‘arisen from the matrix of compassion (*karuṇā-garbodaya*)’. However, in keeping with the general Mahāyāna concept of a Buddha’s three modes of being or embodiment (*tri-kāya*), this expression of the ‘content’ of Perfect Enlightenment operates on two levels according to the ability of the beings to be assisted. The first of the three modes of being is the *dharmakāya* which forms the ground for the other two and is equivalent to Perfect Enlightenment itself or Vairocana’s Mind. Not only does it transcend all perceptual forms and so cannot be directly manifested or perceived, it is also said to be primordially existent. From the *dharmakāya*, two other modes of being arise, the *saṃbhoga-kāya* and the *nirmāṇa-kāya* which are equivalent to Vairocana’s Speech and Body respectively. According to the MVT, these two modes of being form the intrinsically existent mandala and as such are the Inexhaustible Adornments of Body, Speech and Body respectively. According to the MVT, these two modes of being form the intrinsically existent mandala and as such are the Inexhaustible Adornments of Body, Speech and Mind mentioned above. The *saṃbhoga-kāya*, as Vairocana’s Speech aspect, is especially concerned with communication of the Dharma and appears in the form of various Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, though these are beyond the perceptual range of ordinary beings. To cater for their needs and abilities, Vairocana further creates various *nirmāṇa-kāyas*, a lower order of manifestation, in the physical form of Śākyamuni and other spiritual teachers. Moreover, those manifestations of the qualities of Perfect Enlightenment, the Inexhaustible Adornments of Vairocana’s Body, Speech and Mind, are transformed by Vairocana into what we normally think of as mandalas, mantras and *mudrās*. These transformations act as a bridge between ourselves and Vairocana by which we may identify ourselves with and indeed actually become Vairocana.

So, according to the MVT, the Inexhaustible Adornments of Vairocana’s Body (which operates via the mode of the *nirmāṇakāyas*), Speech (which operates via the mode of the *saṃbhogakāyas*) and Mind (the *dharmakāya*, or the ultimate mode of being

from which the other two modes manifest) are synonymous with the efficacious rituals involving *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudrās*. These adornments, or rituals, are the vehicles of praxis employed by practitioners in order to assist them on the path to perfect enlightenment.

Based on this information, one could entertain an additional underlying meaning in the activities of the unnamed donor in the Prasat Plang inscription. When the inscription states, “through the efforts of the Mind, Speech, and Body he guided the minds of his own family, and others who are wise, in the principles pertaining to the Teachings,” it could be alluding to the use of *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudras* (i.e., the ‘Adornments of the Body, Speech, and Mind’) that were employed to assist the donor’s family and other individuals who desired to understand the ‘principles pertaining to the Teachings.’ That is, the stanza could be read on another level as “through the use¹² of *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudrās* he guided the minds of his own family, and others who are wise, in the principles pertaining to the Teachings.” If correct, by alluding to some fundamental practices employed in tantric circles, this inscription would represent yet another example that points to the arising of tantric Buddhist traditions in tenth-century Cambodia.

To add further support to this tentative interpretation, the following points should be considered. First, we have epigraphical evidence from tenth-century Cambodia that indicates tantric forms of Buddhism were active, and these traditions employed rites involving *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudras*. I have already discussed how the second stanza of the Vat Sithor inscription likely suggests the use of *maṇḍalas* in order to

¹² Skt. *ceṣṭā*; i.e., the efforts or activities involving . . .

visualize the various embodiments of enjoyment (*saṃbhogakāyas*) that manifest from the *dharmakāya*.¹³ Additionally, stanza twenty-three of the same inscription records that:

He (i.e., the Dharma master Kīrtipaṇḍita) whose mind was fixed on yoga during the four divisions of the day, who endowed with the quality of the Four Donations, who was endowed with the character of the Four Mudrā, [taught] the Dharma to the four assemblies everyday.¹⁴

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XXIII)

Stanza forty-two states:

Having established the Good Dharma in both its exoteric and esoteric forms, he (Kīrtipaṇḍita) built for the purpose of worship separate hermitages (*āśrama*) for the Buddhist community and their guests.¹⁵

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. XLII)

And finally, stanza sixty-nine claims:

The *purohita* who is learned in the rite of the fire sacrifice, *vidyā*, *mantra*, *mudra*, and heart[-syllables], and who is familiar with the secrets of the *vajra* and the bell (*ghaṇṭā*), is worthy of donations.¹⁶

(K. 111, Vat Sithor, st. LXIX)

While such circumstantial evidence does not directly point to the *MVT* and its ideas concerning the Inexhaustible Adornments of Body, Speech, and Mind as being influential in tenth-century Cambodia, it does demonstrate that tantric Buddhist practices and doctrine were employed and known in the region during this era. Furthermore,

¹³ Also refer again to stanza V of the same inscription. The stanza indicates that the *saṃbhogakāya* are grasped through meditative practices.

¹⁴ Skt. *catussandhyāsu yogātmā caturddānānvito nva[ham] / caturmmūdrātmako dharmmanñ catusparṣaṣu yo [diśat] //*

¹⁵ Skt. *vāhyaṃ guhyañ ca saddharmmaṃ sthāpayitvā cakāra yaḥ / pūjārthan tasya saṃghasyātithes ca pṛthagāśramān //*

¹⁶ Skt. *hṛnmūdramantravidyāsu homakarmmaṇi kovidaḥ / bajraghaṇṭārahasyajñō dakṣiṇīyaḥ purohitaḥ //*

while the *MVT* cannot be directly connected with tenth-century Cambodia, the text was certainly influential in other regions of Southeast Asia which were in contact with Cambodia during the tenth century.¹⁷

So while circumstantial (and perhaps a bit of a stretch), it does not seem unreasonable to suggest that the reference to mind, speech, and body in the Prasat Plang inscription is not simply referring to the generic efforts of the unnamed donor. Instead, it could represent yet another example in which a triadic configuration pertaining to Buddhist doctrine and practice alludes to additional layers of meaning (e.g., Mind, Speech, and Body = the *trikāya* = understood via Inexhaustible Adornments = tantric rites such as *maṇḍalas*, *mantras*, and *mudras*). Lastly, it may be interesting to note that if this interpretation proves correct, then the one Sanskrit line pertaining to mind, speech, and body in the Prasat Plang inscription (*kāyavāgbuddhiceṣṭābhiḥ*) actually encapsulates an entire Buddhist epistemology and outline of praxis for the attainment Perfect Enlightenment.¹⁸

The Bat Cum Inscriptions (K. 266–268)

The Bat Cum inscriptions were probably composed by poets without any particular affiliation with the Buddhist traditions of the time, although this did not prevent them from extolling Buddhist divinities over the rival gods of some other traditions. These poets were likely commissioned to compose attractive eulogies to commemorate the consecration of the Buddhist images installed at the site. Like many Sanskrit

¹⁷ Such connections are discussed at length in chapter six, and therefore will be repeated here.

¹⁸ This method of concise doctrinal summary also bears similarity with the *MVT*. As noted by Hodge (2003: 33, also see 44–46 for an actual commentarial explanation on the terms and title), the full title of the *MVT* (*Mahāvairocanābhisambodhivikurvitādhiṣṭhānavaipulyasūtrendrarajānāmadharmaparyāya*) summarizes all three modes of Perfect Enlightenment: *abhisambodhi*, *adhiṣṭhāna* and *vikurvita*.

inscriptions the aesthetic objectives of poetry take precedence in the opening invocations of the Bat Cum inscriptions. Literary devices that highlight the acumen of the poets were employed and coupled with basic religio-cultural knowledge to create the illusion of profundity. One important point that will be highlighted in examining the opening stanzas of the Bat Cum inscriptions is that the poets made allusions to non-Buddhist narratives and beings in order to elevate and praise the Buddhist figures. Recourse to non-Buddhist sources must then be made in order to properly understand the full range of meaning intended by the poets.

A Short Overview of the Bat Cum Inscriptions

The site of Bat Cum consists of three brick sanctuaries aligned along a north-south axis facing east. The site is located in Siem Reap province within Angkor Archaeological Park, just south of Srah Srang and Banteay Kdei. Originally the site would have had a Buddhist monastery and other dwellings located near the sanctuaries, but these have since vanished. Bat Cum is one of the few Buddhist sites currently known to have been built within the confines of Angkor prior to the accession of Jayavarman VII.¹⁹ The site was planned by the Buddhist Kavīndrārimathana, a minister to Rājendravarman who was also responsible for the construction of Yaśodharataṭṭaka (i.e., the Eastern Baray), the East Mebon, and a palace for Rājendravarman; it was almost certainly due to his influence and close relationship with the king that allowed for the construction of Bat Cum. The inscription from the southern sanctuary reveals that Kavīndrārimathana installed images of the Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, and Divyadevī at the

¹⁹ The only others are the Buddhist hermitages (Skt. *āśrama*, e.g., Saugatāśrama) erected by Yaśovarman (r. 889 – c. 910). For the Tep Pranam stele inscription which records information about Saugatāśrama, see Cœdès (1908c). For a more recent examination of this inscription, see Estève (2009 : 338–59). For recent scholarship on the *āśrama* of Yaśovarman, see Estève and Soutif (2010–2011) and Pottier (2003).

sanctuaries of Bat Cum in 875 Śaka, but the context also reveals that the sanctuaries had probably already been established prior to that date.

He installed a single grand image of the Jina, as well as Divyadevī accompanied with Vajrapāṇi, bringing (them) to the altar (i.e., the heart or center) of the shrine just as (he brought them) into his own divine heart; with devotion, that eminent Buddhist (installed them) in this place in 875 (Śaka).

(K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XIX)²⁰

First edited and translated in full by Cœdès (1908b), the inscriptions are located on the right and left door jambs of each of the three small shrines (Skt. *prāsāda*).²¹ There are three Sanskrit inscriptions and one Khmer inscription which, according to Cœdès, is contemporary with the other three Sanskrit inscriptions. The inscription located on the southern sanctuary has a total of forty-eight lines of Sanskrit comprising twenty-four stanzas, with an additional thirteen lines of Khmer appended at the end. The central sanctuary inscription has a total of eighty lines of Sanskrit comprising forty stanzas, with one additional line of Khmer appended at the end. And finally, the inscription of the northern sanctuary consists of eighty-six lines of Sanskrit comprising forty-three stanzas. Despite some variations, all three are concerned with the same information despite being composed by three separate poets. Śrī Indrapaṇḍita composed the inscription of the southern sanctuary (K. 266). Vāp Rāmabhaḡavat composed the inscription of the central sanctuary (K. 267). While Śivāyuta-(?)

²⁰ Skt. *so sthāpayat sumahaṭin jīnamūrtīm ekāṃ śrīvajrapāṇisahitām api divyadevīm / prāsādaharmmyanivahe svahr̥dīva divye vauddho gradhīs śaranagāṣṭabhir atra bhaktyā //*, Cœdès (1908b: 228). This information also conforms with stanza XXXII from the central shrine inscription (K. 267). Again, it should be noted that the actual installed images at Bat Cum, as indicated in this stanza, match the triadic configuration in both opening invocations from the central and northern sanctuaries, but not the southern sanctuary invocation.

²¹ For a recent re-translation and examination of the Bat Cum inscriptions in German, see Mertens (2005).

composed the inscription of the northern sanctuary. Although one cannot be absolutely certain, the names of the poets commissioned to compose the inscriptions appear to indicate that they were not Buddhist themselves.

All three inscriptions follow the same basic pattern. First, all three open with an invocation to Buddhist divinities. The next section for all three inscriptions include a eulogy (Skt. *praśasti*) of Rājendravarman recording the foundations of Yaśodharapura (i.e., the restoration of the city of Angkor) and the large eastern reservoir known as Yaśodharataṭāka. This then is followed by a eulogy for Kavīndrārimathana which includes an account of various foundations established by this esteemed Buddhist minister. Finally, the end of all three inscriptions deal with injunctions and rules surrounding a *parikhā* ('canal') and *taṭāka* ('reservoir'), prohibitions concerning elephants on dikes, and formulaic warnings against those who would rob the site.²²

The Buddhist-related content of the inscriptions is found mainly in the opening invocations to Buddhist divinities, along with the information pertaining to a number of Kavīndrārimathana's foundations. The inscription of the southern sanctuary opens with an invocation to the Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Vajrapāṇi, respectively.²³ As has been noted by previous scholarship, the opening invocations for the inscriptions of the central and northern sanctuaries differ in that they open with an invocation to the Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, and Prajñāpāramitā, respectively. Not only is Lokeśvara absent from the

²² Refer to chapter seven for more on the *parikhā* and *taṭāka*.

²³ st. I – III. It should be noted that stanza I of the southern sanctuary is damaged; therefore, it is not known for sure that the Buddha is the one being praised in the stanza. However, context does suggest that the praise would be directed to the Buddha, as does the fact that both inscriptions of the central and northern sanctuaries open with praise to the Buddha or the Buddha's teachings. Cœdès (1908b) and Mertens (2005) also made this assumption when reading and translating the inscription of the southern sanctuary.

opening invocation of the other two inscriptions, but the hierarchy pertaining to Vajrapāṇi has been changed from third to second. In other words, simply stating that Lokeśvara has been replaced by Prajñāpāramitā is not entirely correct.

The Opening Invocations of the Bat Cum Inscriptions

Stanza I–III: southern sanctuary

1. *jejīyatāṃ vraja* ॐॐॐॐॐॐ
ॐॐॐॐॐॐॐॐ *parārthavṛttiḥ*
2. *ātmapradānakṛtasa[r]vva(jagaddhitārthāṃ)*
*[sa]rvvajñatāṃ svamudam āpa nitāntasāntām*²⁴
3. *lokeśvaro jayati lokahitārtharūḍhas*
sandarśayann iva catuṣṭayam āryyasatyam
4. *dharmmasthitim sthirapadābhyadhikān dadhāno*
dhatte caturbhujavibhāṃ bhuvanarddhaye yaḥ
5. *śrībajrapāṇir ajito jītajambhavairī*
bajrañ jvalajjvalanadīptinibbhaṃ bibhartti
6. *uddāmadṛptakalidānavadoṣaṣaṇḍa-*
niṣyaṇḍasamkṣubhitavighnavighhāṭadakṣaḥ

(The Buddha?) is victorious! . . . the path²⁵ . . . (he) acts for the benefit of others, . . . he attained his own happiness, equanimity, (and) omniscience— (through which) he cultivated his own donation for the salvation of the entire world.

²⁴ Unless noted, the Sanskrit comes from Cœdès (1908b: 226–233). The restoration *jagaddhitārthāṃ* has been suggested by Mertens (2005: 125).

²⁵ Skt. *vraja*. This is likely a reference to the path of the bodhisattva. The third stanza of the inscription on the north shrine at Bat Cum also makes a reference to the path when likening Prajñāpāramitā to a sun that illuminates the path (Skt. *nirvāṇavīthīraveḥ*).

Lokeśvara, arising for the purpose of benefiting the world, is victorious; manifesting like the Fourfold Truth of the Noble One,²⁶ maintaining the steadfastness of the superior and firmly rooted Dharma, he directs the splendor of his four arms²⁷ for the prosperity of the world.

Glorious Vajrapāṇi, the invincible, conqueror of the enemy Jambha,²⁸ he, who is skilled at removing obstacles churned about by the torrent of a multitude of transgressions of the unrestrained and presumptuous *dānavas*²⁹ in the Kali (*yuga*), bears the *vajra* that resembles a blazing flame of fire.

Stanzas I – III: central sanctuary

1. *vuddho vodhiṃ viddaddhyād yena nairātmyadarśanam*
2. *viruddhasyāpi sādhuḥktaṃ sādhanam paramātmanah*
3. *śrībajrapāṇir avyād vaś śrīmadvāhur bbibhartti yaḥ*

²⁶ Skt. *catuṣṭayam āryasatyam*. This phrase is almost universally translated as ‘Four Noble Truths.’ I have long since adopted K. R. Norman’s (1997: 13) interpretation of this famous phrase. In discussing the Pali equivalent he wrote, “Another way in which philology, the study of why words mean what they do, can be helpful is that we sometimes find that those who made the first English translations of Buddhist texts gave a particular meaning to a word which we have for the most part followed without change ever since. When we come to look at the words themselves we find that the meanings which we have accepted for so long are very often not the only possible meanings but in some cases not even the most likely meanings. Take for example, the phrase ‘noble truth’, which I mentioned a few minutes ago. It has become a commonplace to talk about the four noble truths, and this is a perfectly acceptable translation of the compound *ariya-sacca*: *ariya* means noble and *sacca* means truth, so *ariya-sacca* means noble truth. This translation is so common and so fixed in our minds, that it seems almost like blasphemy to have to point out that not only is this not the only possible translation, but it is in fact the least likely of all the possibilities. If we look at the commentators we find that they knew this very well. They point out that the compound can have a number of meanings. It can mean ‘truth of the noble one’, ‘truth of the noble ones’, ‘truth for a noble one’, i.e. truth that will make one noble, as well as the translation ‘noble truth’ so familiar to us. This last possibility, however, they put at the bottom of the list of possibilities, if they mention it at all. My own feeling is that it is very likely that ‘the truth of the noble one (the Buddha)’ is the correct translation, although we must never lose sight of the fact that in Indian literature multiple meanings are very often intended, so that it is not always possible to say that there is a single correct meaning.”

²⁷ Four-armed images of Avalokiteśvara are the most common forms of this bodhisattva in Cambodia. The poet uses the number four here to suggest that each of Lokeśvara’s four arms upholds one of the Four Truths realized by the Buddha out of compassion for the world.

²⁸ This is a common example of the assimilation between Vajrapāṇi and Indra. Indra is said to have slain the leader of the *dānavas* known as Jambha by cutting of his head with his *vajra* (cf. *Bhāgavata Purāṇa* VIII.11.18 and the *Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa* XVIII.16). In this stanza, however, it is Vajrapāṇi who is said to have slain Jambha.

²⁹ The *dānavas* are often loosely described as a class of ‘demons,’ and they are frequently identified with *daityas* and *asuras*. The stanza is referencing one of the battles between the *devas* and *dānavas* headed by Jambha. Jambha is eventually slain by Indra.

4. *śrīpālanan trijagataś śrībajraṃ bajribajravat*
5. *prajñāpāramitā pātu pātakād vo varīyasaḥ*
6. *vuddhasarvajñabhāvendoḥ paurṇnamāsīva pūraṇī*

Although it opposes [the view of] *paramātmāna*,³⁰ the Buddha teaches *bodhi* (i.e., enlightenment) by means of the doctrine of *nairātmya*,³¹ which is well-said (and) leads straight to the goal.

Glorious Vajrapāṇi will protect you all, (he) whose illustrious arm bears the radiant *vajra* which protects Śrī³² of the Three Worlds, just like the *vajra* of Vajrin (i.e., Indra).

Prajñāpāramitā preserves you all, most excellent (people), from waning,³³ like the night of a full moon she is the one who fulfills the moon from which arises the omniscience of the Buddha.

Stanzas I–III: northern sanctuary

1. *vuddho virājati samādhisamitsamṛddha-
vairāgyahetinihatāripamāravīryaḥ*
2. *yo vāpya vodhim avinaśvararājyalakṣmīn
nirvvāṇamaṇḍiravare ramate dhirājāḥ*
3. *śrībajrapāṇir avatāṃ mahatāṃ vibhūtiṃ
yo dviṇmadāpakṛtikalyam akuṇṭhitāgram*

³⁰ Some non-Buddhist doctrines posit the existence of an essential or individual self (*ātman*) that transmigrates from life to life. Although the details vary depending on the tradition, with proper devotion and practice the individual may come to realize that this individual self is actually identical with the Supreme Self, or Absolute (*paramātmāna*); on the other hand, the tradition may maintain that the individual self is eventually expected to merge with the Supreme Self in order to attain liberation from the cycle of rebirth and death.

³¹ The Buddhist doctrine that claims there is no essential or individual self that persists through the cycle of rebirth and death.

³² Here Śrī refers to both the goddess Śrī (i.e., Lakṣmī) as well as the prosperity, fortune, and sovereignty that she personifies (also cf. stanza VI of Bat Cum's south shrine which praises Lakṣmī as *lakṣmīs trilokalalanā*, 'playful woman of the Three Worlds'). I will discuss the references being alluded to in this stanza in more detail below.

³³ Skt. *pātaka*, lit. 'causing to sink or fall' (fr. √pā, 'to fall' or 'sink'). As a noun it refers to that which causes one to fall, sink, or decline (i.e., 'sin,' 'transgression,' 'crime,' etc.). I opted for 'waning' (i.e., when the phases of the moon are in 'decline') to better connect and highlight the simile found in the next verse pertaining to a full moon.

4. *bajraṃ vahan prahasatīva sahasranetraṃ*
saṃgrā mavairimadakuṅṭhitavandhyabajram
5. *prajñāpāramitā vibhāti bhuvanāmbhojodayaśrīkarī*
kalākāramahāndhakāramathanī bhūtārthasaṃvodhini
6. *yā līlām api maṇḍalasya dadhatī nirvāṇavīthīraver*
abhrāntā rucim ātanoty apihitān naktan divaṃ bhāsvatīm

The Buddha, by whom the power of Māra, protector of enemies, was struck down by the flame of worldly detachment which blazed successfully due to the firewood that is *samādhi*,³⁴ shines afar; having obtained *bodhi*, Lakṣmī's imperishable kingdom, that supreme king (*adhirāja*) rejoiced (with Her) in that most excellent abode, *nirvāṇa*.

Glorious Vajrapāṇi defends the sovereignty (*vibhūti*³⁵) of the great. He who bears the *vajra* whose tip is not blunt (and) which drives away the offense of pride (*mada*) in enemies as if mocking the Thousand-Eyed One (i.e., Indra) whose *vajra* was useless and blunted in battle with the enemy Mada.

Prajñāpāramitā shines widely, (She is) the glorious ray of light emitting from the Lotus World, (She is) the destroyer of the darkness brought about by ignorance, (She is) true knowledge of reality as it really is; even though She exhibits (*dadhatī*) the semblance (*līlā*) of a sun (*maṇḍala*)—a sun (*ravi*) for the path to *nirvāṇa*—She is non-bedazzling (*abhrāntā*³⁶), spreading luminous light both night (and) day.

³⁴ The technical term *samādhi* refers to the practice of intense meditative concentration. Just as firewood is the foundation for fueling a fire, so too, the meditative practice of *samādhi* is the foundation for fueling a proper detachment from worldly affairs and developing true insight.

³⁵ Here again is likely another reference to both Lakṣmī along with the fortune, sovereignty, and power that she personifies.

³⁶ The loose translation of 'non-bedazzling' for the Sanskrit word *abhrāntā* was selected because I feel it better conveys one of the more overt meanings of the stanza for non-Sanskritist. The second part of the stanza is likening Prajñāpāramitā to the sun, or the halo around the sun (*maṇḍala*, lit. a 'disk' or 'orb,'). The implication is that a sun's intense light can be blinding (i.e., bedazzling), and thus confuse and cause one to wander aimlessly (Skt. *bhrānta*). Prajñāpāramitā does not cause one to wander, become confused, make errors, become perplex, and so forth; therefore, she is *abhrānta* (without error, unmistaken, does not confuse, clear, etc.). Her light is luminous (*bhāsvat*); that is, easily comprehended, guiding, clear, and so forth. Thus, Prajñāpāramitā both supports and reveals (both meanings captured by the verb *dadhatī*) the path to *nirvāṇa*.

I believe, however, that the above comments only capture some of the more obvious meanings of the stanza. As noted by Mertens (2005: 93, n. 348), the second verse contains examples of *virodhālamkāra*, a literary device which juxtaposes incongruous or contradictory words and/or ideas. For example, *līlā*

The foundational aesthetic pattern of the Bat Cum invocations

Before attempting to ascertain any relevant Buddhist information from these opening panegyrics it must be stressed that the stanzas contain numerous allusions to non-Buddhist narratives and ideas. This is likely because the poets commissioned relied upon a pool of motifs and narratives familiar to them that were not Buddhist. Many of these sources appear to come primarily from the epics and various purāṇic sources. This observation should not be construed as an example of syncretism, but rather something more along the lines of a functional method meant to render foreign or less-popular ideas and figures more understandable and accessible by describing them using ideas and narratives more familiar to both the poets themselves and the intended audience. Alternatively, the allusions to non-Buddhist sources could have been part of a conscious effort to elevate the status and prestige of Buddhist divinities by illustrating their superiority over rival deities known through popular narratives.

Much of the allusions being made by the poets reiterate the sovereignty of a ruler. In the context of the inscription, these literary motifs and devices would have bolstered

(‘appearance,’ ‘semblance,’ ‘pretense,’ ‘disguise,’ etc.) is contrasted with *abhrānta* (‘clear,’ ‘without mistake,’ ‘error’ or ‘deception’), while *naktam* (‘night’) is contrasted with *divam* (‘day’). The concept of *līlā* can also imply some kind of deception, or something illusory (Skt. *māyā*). The word *līlā* is also likely being used in a contrasting manner with other non-Buddhist traditions and their use and understanding of *līlā* as the creative play of a supreme being. That is, all of reality as we know it is merely *līlā*, appearances resulting from the creative play of (depending on the tradition) divinities like Śiva, Kriṣṇa, or the monistic concept of Brahman discussed in the Upaniṣads (for a detailed description of *līlā*, see Śaṅkara’s commentary on *Brahma Sūtra* 2.1.33). A sort of deception or illusion is often caused by *līlā* because while humans see and interact with reality, they fail to understand that it is merely the result of creative play.

The Perfection of Wisdom, however, produces no such deception. Again, according to many Buddhists, as well as this inscription, The Perfection of Wisdom is without error and clear. It is synonymous with the very truth of reality itself, not an intermediary resulting creation or mere appearance. Contrast the inscription with verse fifteen of the *Īśa Upaniṣad* which states, “the face of Truth is covered by a golden plate (i.e., the sun); you, O Pūṣan, should uncover that in order to see the True Dharma” (Skt. *hiraṇmayena pātreṇa satyasyāpihitam mukham / tat tvam pūṣann apāvṛṇu satyadharmāya dr̥ṣṭaye //*). Unlike this verse from the *Īśa Upaniṣad*, the sun likened to Prajñāpāramitā in the Bat Cum inscription does not obstruct or blind one to the Truth; rather, it illuminates it.

the prestige and right of Rājendravarman's own hierarchical position. Thus, while praising the Buddhist divinities whose images were installed at Bat Cum is an important part of the inscription, it may be just as important to remember that much of the praise directed at these figures was presented in an aesthetical manner that also sought to further empower the ruler and prominent individuals within the administrative structure.

Each of the poets appear to emphasize, in general, a specific theme. Although there is some overlap between the different opening invocations (e.g., Vajrapāṇi's role as a powerful protector is stressed by all three poets), it does seem that one particular theme is stressed more than others. The first three stanzas of the south shrine, for instance, highlight the theme of victory and conquering. The Sanskrit words *jeṣṭhātām* ('victorious,' S., I), *jayati* ('victorious,' S., II) and *jita* ('conquered,' S., III) all emphasize this concept of being victorious and (in the context of the inscriptions) having overcome obstacles for the betterment of humanity. While verbal conjugations like *jeṣṭhātām* and *jayati* may be expressed more idiomatically in the inscriptions to mean 'glory to' or 'long live,' this does not change the meaning of the underlying root for all these terms (√ji – 'win,' 'conquer,' 'success'). Furthermore, even when rendering these terms as 'glory to' or 'long live' it is implied that such glory and praise is appropriate due to success and victory (i.e., 'glory to [the one who is victorious, etc.]'). Therefore, the first stanza glorifies the Buddha whose success, or victory, has made possible the path of liberation for all sentient beings. Lokeśvara is glorified for his compassion which is responsible for successfully maintaining the Dharma for all sentient beings. And finally, Vajrapāṇi is glorified for his success in conquering demons like Jambha, and for removing various obstacles that hinder one on the path to liberation.

The north shrine opening invocations all emphasize the manifestation of beneficial power. This theme is usually expressed using light motifs which are to be understood as an illuminating or a guiding light, as well as an intense blazing that wards off the darkness of ignorance. This theme is stressed in the use of words like *virājati* ('shines,' N., I), *samidh* ('blazing,' N., I) *heti* ('flame,' N., I), *vibhūtim* ('glory,' 'manifestion of power,' N., II), *vibhati* ('shines,' N., III), *ravi* ('sun,' N., III) and *bhāsvatīm* ('luminous,' N., III). Thus, the Buddha's intense meditative concentration (*samādhi*) manifests like a great blazing fire that struck down the enemy Mara that shines throughout the world. The verse to Vajrapāṇi on the north shrine lacks the light motifs, but it does emphasize how his thunderbolt (*vajra*) preserves *vibhūtim*, the very manifestation of (sovereign) power and glory. This concept of power is often described in terms of light elsewhere in the inscription when describing the greatness of Rājendravarman's rule. Finally, Prajñāpāramitā, the very manifestation of the Perfection of Wisdom, is described as a luminous light spreading throughout the world and dispelling the darkness of ignorance.

Lastly, the central shrine invocations focus upon the accessibility and preservation of a few select concepts, as well as the protection of those desirous of benefiting from them. This is most notable in the second and third stanza. For example, Vajrapāṇi defends (Skt. *avyāt*) humanity and is described as the protector (Skt. *pālanam*) of Śrī (i.e., Lakṣmī, the goddess of prosperity, sovereignty, etc.). The third stanza extols Prajñāpāramitā for protecting (Skt. *pātu*) the great from falling or 'waning' (Skt. *pātakāt*), and for being the source of a Buddha's omniscience. Although the first verse praising the Buddha does not employ vocabulary that means to protect or defend, it does emphasize that he is responsible for making known the doctrine of *nairātmya* which

leads to the goal of liberation. The verse may imply that by making known this important Buddhist concept in the face of other competing and contracting ideas, the Buddha is, indeed, preserving and defending such knowledge.

Vajrapāṇi, Indra, and the preservation and restoration of power and sovereignty

Besides the Buddha, only Vajrapāṇi is praised by each of the poets. This is a testament to the importance of this bodhisattva. Vajrapāṇi, however, is always understood in connection with Indra. According to the inscriptions, Vajrapāṇi either (1) replaces Indra's role in certain non-Buddhist narratives extolling the achievements of Indra, or (2) is described in juxtaposition with Indra—again, as understood in non-Buddhist textual sources—in order to elevate his status over Indra. The frequent assimilation with (or appropriation of) Indra is well attested outside of Cambodia and not particularly surprising; however, careful attention must be paid to this phenomena in order to understand the full range of meaning of the stanzas.

Take, for instance, the stanza devoted to Vajrapāṇi from the south shrine. This stanza indicates that Vajrapāṇi is the conqueror of the enemy Jambha (Skt. *jītajambhavairī*). Jambha is an enemy of the gods (Skt. *deva*), and he is often described as chief or foremost among the *dānavas* (a class of beings who are also mentioned in the stanza). While Jambha is known to have fought other gods, he is primarily known for being slain by Indra who cut off his head with his thunderbolt.³⁷ At the end of the account of the churning of the ocean of milk in book I, chapter forty-four, of the *Rāmāyaṇa*, Indra is also said to have slain all the sons of Diti.³⁸ The churning account

³⁷ cf. *Bhāgavata Purāṇa* VIII.11.18 and the *Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa* XVIII.16.

³⁸ i.e., the daityas/dānavas. These beings also came to be known as *asuras* for not accepting Sura, daughter of Varuṇa.

in which the *daityas* and *adaityas* desire immortality may be alluded to in the stanza by the inclusion of vocabulary such as *niṣyaṅḍa/nisyanda* (the ‘flowing,’ ‘gushing,’ ‘stream,’ ‘discharge’ of any fluid such as water) and *saṃkṣubhita* (‘agitated,’ ‘violently shaken,’ ‘churned’).³⁹

The opening stanza to Vajrapāṇi from the central shrine may also have been intended to invoke certain parallels with the churning of the ocean of milk narrative. Especially the part that describes Vajrapāṇi as a protector of Śrī (i.e., Lākṣmī). This would have been parallel to sources that describe Indra in this very same role. Specifically, the stanza appears to call to mind aspects of the churning narrative told in the *Viṣṇu Purāṇa*.⁴⁰ This version of the narrative differs significantly from the one found in the *Rāmāyaṇa*, and is more akin to the telling in the *Mahābhārata* in that Viṣṇu is supreme and plays a significant role in the narrative. According to the *Viṣṇu Purāṇa*, Indra is rendered impotent due to the curse of the sage Durvāsa. Out of respect Durvāsa gave Indra a garland which the god haphazardly tossed on the head of his elephant, Airāvata.⁴¹ When the naturally intoxicated Airāvata cast the garland on the ground with his trunk, Durvāsa was infuriated and cursed the disrespectful Indra by promising that the sovereignty of the Three Worlds that he presided over would be subverted. As a result, the Three Worlds went into decline and lost their vigor and prosperity. With the world(s) now devoid of the energy necessary for prosperity

³⁹ It should be noted that the churning of the ocean of milk narrative is explicitly referenced a number of times throughout the Bat Cum inscriptions. cf. stanza A.X, for instance.

⁴⁰ The version of the churning of the ocean of milk told in the *Viṣṇu Purāṇa* is found in chapter IX.

⁴¹ Note, unlike the churning narrative told in the *Mahābhārata*, Airāvata is not one of the things that comes out of the ocean as a result of the churning.

because of Indra's impotence, the *dānavas*⁴² mounted a war against the now helpless gods and Indra.

Indra and the other gods seek the counsel of Brahmā who informs them that they must procure the aid of Viṣṇu if they wish to restore the prosperity of the Three Worlds. After proper supplication to Viṣṇu, the gods are given instructions to churn the ocean of milk to bring about the aid they seek. Like other accounts of the churning, the gods must get the assistance of their enemies, the *dānavas*, to properly churn the ocean. They do this by promising the *dānavas* a share of the nectar of immortality. With the alliance made, the world serpent Vāsuki is used as a rope wrapped around Mount Mandara which acted as a churning post. Viṣṇu assumed several forms during this narrative, one of which was the form of a giant turtle which served as the pivot for Mount Mandara during the churning. The gods pulled Vāsuki from the tail end, while the *dānavas* pulled Vāsuki from the head end.

Many wonderful treasures are tossed up from the ocean due to the churning: the cow Surabhi, the goddess Vārunī, the Wishfulling Tree, *āpsarasas*, etc. As in the Mahābhārata, when the nectar of immortality comes up Viṣṇu deceives the *dānavas* into giving up their share by assuming the shape of beautiful woman. Now in possession of the nectar, Indra and the other gods quaff the elixir and then go on to rout the *dānavas*.

According to the *Viṣṇu Purāṇa*, however, the most precious treasure to come about from the churning is the goddess Śrī (i.e., Lakṣmī) who is responsible for

⁴² From here I will simply use the term '*dānavas*' out of convenience, even though the sources fluctuate back and forth between using the terms *dānavas*, *daityas*, *asuras*, sons of Diti, and so forth. The terms are frequently synonymous, although there are exceptions.

returning prosperity to the Three Worlds. Once the host of usurpers are defeated, Indra supplicates Śrī with a long and graceful eulogy.⁴³ From this exchange two important promises are granted because of the boons requested by Indra. One, Śrī will never again abandon the Three Worlds; two, Śrī will never abandon anyone who praises her with the same prayer uttered by Indra.

A similar narrative describing the battle between the gods and *dānavas* that involves both Śrī and Indra is told in the *Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa*. Chapter eighteen begins with a King desirous of ruling justly and attaining the state of a *yogi*. One of his ministers informs him that he should worship the great sage named Dattātreya (in the context of the text, Dattātreya is a manifestation of Viṣṇu) who is worshipped by the gods and responsible for regaining Indra's sovereignty that was stolen by the wicked *dānavas*. The king asks how Dattātreya assisted Indra in his battle, and this is what the sage tells him.

There was a battle between the gods (headed by Indra) and *dānavas* (headed by Jambha).⁴⁴ The gods are soundly defeated. Dejected, the gods seek advice on how to defeat their enemies. The gods are told by a sage that they should seek out and supplicate a powerful ascetic named Dattātreya since he will be capable of granting a boon that will lead to the downfall of the *dānavas*. The gods follow the sage's advice and seek out Dattātreya. They quickly find him in the company of his beautiful wife, Lakṣmī, while drinking wine and eating meat.⁴⁵ The gods beseech the ascetic for

⁴³ For an English translation of this intriguing exchange, see trans. Wilson (1840: 77–80).

⁴⁴ cf. the explicit reference to Jambha in the third stanza of the south shrine Bat Cum inscription discussed above.

⁴⁵ Typically sages do not indulge in alcohol and meat, and thus, Dattātreya's behavior is rather antinomian and transgressive. Antonio Rigopoulos (1998) has conducted a study of Dattātreya arguing

assistance which, after some hesitation, is granted. Dattātreyā instructs the gods to bring Jambha and the rest of the *dānavas* within sight of him because they will be drained of their power and doomed once viewing the fire of his countenance.

The gods follow Dattātreyā's instructions, and in the next battle the *dānavas* slay more gods before arriving at the hermitage of Dattātreyā where they see him with his wife Lakṣmī. Upon seeing the beautiful Lakṣmī they forget about the gods and are overcome with desire. The *dānavas* then devise a new plan which entails kidnapping Lakṣmī since they maintain that anyone who possesses her possesses the very essence of the Three Worlds. They snatch Lakṣmī and place her on a palanquin atop their heads which they begin to carry away. This is a fatal mistake since, according to Dattātreyā, whenever Lakṣmī is mounted on the head she forsakes the culprit and resorts to another abode. This act of disrespect deprives the *dānavas* of their power; furthermore, their store of merit is exhausted by taking the wife of another man.⁴⁶ Because of these things the gods headed by Indra are now able to finally slay Jambha and the other *dānavas*, thus restoring the sovereignty of Indra.

In both narratives Indra destroys the *dānavas*, albeit with the necessary assistance of Viṣṇu, or a manifestation of Viṣṇu. Furthermore, Lakṣmī is integral to both narratives. In the *Viṣṇu Purāṇa*, Lakṣmī is procured in order to restore the prosperity of the Three Worlds and the sovereignty of the gods in heaven presided over by Indra. Indra recognizes Lakṣmī's importance and power, hence his own supplication to her in which he pleads that she never again abandon the Three Worlds. Indra's humble gesture to

that the more sanitized Vaiṣṇava portrayals of the ascetic are likely posterior to his more basic identity as a heterodox, antinomian figure found in Tantra literature and promoted in various tantric sects.

⁴⁶ An explanation on how exactly this draining of energy works is given in chapter XVI of the text.

Lakṣmī in the form of a long eulogizing prayer also indicates that he will forever serve her, and by extension serve the Three Worlds.⁴⁷ The *Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa* also has Indra and the other gods destroy the *dānavas* (again with assistance) when they tried to kidnap Lakṣmī. Once again prosperity returns to the Three Worlds, and the proper balance of sovereignty is restored once Lakṣmī is rescued.

The themes being stressed in narratives such as these (and likely additional ones not touched upon here) are likely some the sources of influence for the descriptions of Vajrapāṇi in the Bat Cum inscriptions. In other words, it is non-Buddhist Sanskrit sources that help us make sense out the descriptions in the Bat Cum inscriptions that claim Vajrapāṇi is the conqueror of Jambha, the one who overcomes the *dānavas*, and the defender of Śrī who presides over the Three Worlds.

The third stanza eulogizing Vajrapāṇi from the north shrine inscription is no exception. In that stanza, Vajrapāṇi is described in juxtaposition to Indra in order to elevate his status over the latter. The stanza is drawing upon a narrative found in the *Mahābhārata* in which Indra is overmatched against the monstrous demon known as Mada ('pride,' note the stanza's pun).⁴⁸ In short, Indra was incensed that the sage Cyavana was allowing the Aśvin twins a share of sacrificial offerings typically reserved for the other gods. Indra, therefore, attacked Cyavana with his thunderbolt (*vajra*), but due to Cyavana's ascetical energy the creature Mada manifested and warded off Indra's attack. Indra's thunderbolt could not overcome Mada, and so he begged Cyavana to relent and call of the beast. The stanza from Bat Cum contrasts Indra's useless and

⁴⁷ Also note that, according to *Bhāgavata Purāṇa* VIII.8, Indra brings Lakṣmī a seat when she first appears out of the ocean of milk.

⁴⁸ *MBh* III.124.

blunt thunderbolt with that of Vajrapāṇi's which, unlike Indra's, is actually able to destroy pride (i.e., *mada*), thereby allowing an individual to precede along the path of the bodhisattva unhindered.

Additionally, the description of Vajrapāṇi defending the sovereignty/power (Skt. *vibhūti*) of the great echoes the same theme from the other Vajrapāṇi stanzas that stress the importance of the maintenance of prosperity, power, sovereignty, and so forth. In this context the Sanskrit word *vibhūti* means might or power, particularly the sovereign power of a king. By extension, the word carries a variety of implied meanings pertaining to the greatness of a ruler such as splendor, magnificence, and glory, as well as the prosperity and welfare brought about by such great individuals.⁴⁹ All these meanings are sometimes understood as attributes possessed by rulers and other powerful individuals.

Once again note that prosperity, well-being, royal power, illustriousness, and forth are all qualities embodied by Śrī. Based on the her explicit presence elsewhere in the Bat Cum inscriptions, it seems very likely that she is once again being referenced here.⁵⁰ This observation is further strengthened by the fact that the word *vibhūti* has been used in other textual sources as an epithet of Śrī Lakṣmī.⁵¹

The importance of Vajrapāṇi according to the Bat Cum inscriptions is his role as a protector, but not just a mere protector of Buddhism. Rather, his real appeal is his ability to defend and protect the sovereign power of the ruler, and by extension the

⁴⁹ M-W, s.v. *vibhūti*.

⁵⁰ She is also explicitly referenced in the north shrine's invocation to the Buddha where she is likened to *bodhi*, or enlightenment, and described as cohabitating with the Buddha in the realm of *nirvāṇa*.

⁵¹ cf. the use of the compound term *mahāvibhūti* in *Bhāgavata Purāṇa* VI.19.4, VI.19.7, and VI.19.8.

associated wealth, prosperity, and welfare of the realm. According to the Bat Cum inscriptions, Vajrapāṇi quite literally protects Śrī and *vibhūti*. The poets highlight the importance of this role by relying on a pool of literary motifs drawn from the *purāṇas* and epics, the same pool of sources used throughout the remainder of the Bat Cum inscriptions when glorifying Rājendravarman and others.

It may also be worth noting that one of the major themes common to a couple of the narratives outlined above is the re-establishment of Indra's sovereignty and the prosperity of the Three Worlds after their temporary loss due to the battles with the *dānavas/daityas/asuras*. When one recalls that Rājendravarman is depicted in epigraphical sources (including that of the Bat Cum) as being responsible for re-establishing the center of power in the capital of Yaśodharapura (i.e., Angkor) after its temporary relocation at Koh Ker, then it seems entirely plausible that the poets of the Bat Cum inscriptions were attempting emphasize this parallel as they had done elsewhere in the inscription. “Just as Kuśa (i.e., the son of Rāma and Sitā) had done for Ayodhyā, he restored the glorious city of Yaśodhara, which had been abandoned for a long time, and made it superb and charming by constructing a palace with a sanctuary of brilliant gold, like the palace of Mahendra (i.e., Indra) on earth.”⁵²

Some musings on the Bat Cum *maṅgala* configuration

The fact that the configuration of the opening invocation triad differs between the inscriptions has been a source of interest in scholarship. Why are the opening invocations different? Is this an important detail in relation to some systematic configuration with significant meaning, or merely the result of inscriptions written by

⁵² K. 266, Bat Cum, A. XIII. English rendering of translation from Cœdès (1968: 115).

different poets who may have invoked different Buddhist figures based on personal preference?

In his work on Khmer bronzes, Cœdès (1923: 37–38, fn. 3) once wrote in passing that if one were to set aside the presence of Vajrapāṇi (who is invoked in the opening of all three inscriptions) then it would leave the core triad of Buddha, Lokeśvara, and Prajñāpāramitā, a triad that had become popular during this period. Cœdès' observation, however, seems rather arbitrary and does not provide a satisfying explanation as to why Vajrapāṇi would have ever been included in the first place. Nor does removing Vajrapāṇi simply leave Buddha flanked by Lokeśvara (south) and Prajñāpāramitā (north) since Prajñāpāramitā is actually invoked in the central inscription as well. In other words, Prajñāpāramitā is invoked twice and Lokeśvara is only invoked once. Lastly, while Lokeśvara is certainly important during this era, elevating Lokeśvara significance in these particular inscriptions (i.e., as part of some underlying core triad) over Vajrapāṇi does not coincide well with other sections of the Bat Cum inscriptions. According to the inscription, the triad of the Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, and Prajñāpāramitā appear to have been favored at Bat Cum since the inscriptions inform us that images of the Buddha, Vajrapāṇi, and Divyadevī were installed in the shrines at Bat Cum.⁵³ According to the inscription from the south shrine, an image of Lokanātha was also established by Kavīndrārimathana at the site of Kuṭṭīśvara, but no mention is made of such an image being installed at Bat Cum.⁵⁴

⁵³ Again, K. 266 st.XIX and K. 267 st.XXXII record this information.

⁵⁴ It should also be pointed out that the coinciding verse in the inscription from the central tower contains what may be a significant difference. Stanza XX of K.266 records that an images of Lokanātha and two Devīs were installed at Kuṭṭīśvara. Stanza XXXI of K.267 (the central shrine) indicates, however, that images of Buddha and two Devīs were installed at Kuṭṭīśvara. While Lokanātha is often used for Avalokiteśvara, these inscriptions may be using Lokanātha ('Lord of the World') as an epithet for the

Cœdès (1908b: 223–24) is fully aware of this and states in his article on Bat Cum that the substitution of Lokeśvara for Prajñāpāramitā in the south shrine inscription is not accidental. Rather, he argues, it is related to the strong relationship between Lokeśvara (as the supreme agent) and Prajñāpāramitā, a relationship that also supposedly parallels that of Śiva-Devī. Unfortunately, the inscriptions Cœdès references in support of this conclusion, the Vat Sithor and Tep Pranam inscriptions, do not actually support his claims as he insists (although they do not refute them either). The connections between Lokeśvara and Prajñāpāramitā are, indeed, well attested, but this connection alone offers a weak explanation for the substitution of Lokeśvara in the inscription at south shrine.

Mertens (2005: 219), on the other hand, has suggested that the inclusion of Lokeśvara was essentially a mistake by the commissioned poet, Indrapaṇḍita, brought about by the possibility that he did not actually live near (or compose the work near) the site of Bat Cum, and thus the poet had no actual vision of the site and the images to be installed there. This hypothesis, however, is weakened by the high number of structural parallels between the inscriptions which suggest that the poets, and likely Kavīndrārimathana, were in communication with one another. Mertens also suggests

Buddha. On the other hand, things may not be that simple. For example, each of the inscriptions could be simply providing different additional information. That is, perhaps an image a Buddha *and* an image of Lokanātha were installed at Kuṭṭīśvara along with the two Devī images? Or, perhaps, the two poets were simply ‘not on the same page,’ so to speak. In other words, one poet actually meant Lokanatha (i.e., Lokeśvara) while the other meant only the Buddha. The latter suggestion would support Mertens’ (2005: 219) theories that the Bat Cum inscriptions (at least the opening invocations) contain mistakes and possible contradictions due to the inscriptions being composed by different poets.

On other hand, I also tentatively maintain that different manifestations of Lokeśvara (i.e., Avalokiteśvara) were sometimes understood among the Khmers as functionally equivalent with a buddha, and therefore, this may be an example where the term Lokanātha (i.e., a higher (?) manifestation of Lokeśvara/Avalokiteśvara) and buddha were being used synonymously to refer to a specific higher form of Lokeśvara. This, however, is a tentative claim.

that the dedications at the site of Bat Cum could have changed (e.g., from including Lokeśvara at the site to including Prajñāpāramitā) after Indrapaṇḍita had already composed the beginning of his work, and he may have been either unable or unwilling to alter his work once he had begun. This, too, is certainly possible.

Based on the observations of scholars like Cœdès and Mertens, it may be preferable to simply explain the differences between the three opening invocations in terms of different authorial preferences, compositional constraints, or even as errors as a result of different authors. In other words, the three invocations may not have been written with the goal of fitting together as a neat epistemological whole.⁵⁵ Although this may be the case, some alternate possibilities that do not assume information needs to be removed from the inscription for it to make sense (*à la* Cœdès), or that the inscription contains unrectified mistakes (*à la* Mertens), could be suggested. The reader should note, however, that much of what follows cannot be proven; it is ultimately speculation provided merely as an alternative consideration to a currently unsolved problem.

The content of the Bat Cum inscriptions suggests that the selection and number of divinities in all three invocations may have been specifically chosen for specific purposes. Prajñāpāramitā, for example, is repeatedly referenced in a dichotomous manner, and this may indicate that invoking her twice (and only twice) was intended. For instance, both the south shrine inscription (K.266) and the central shrine inscription

⁵⁵ Mertens (2005: 207) goes so far as to suggest that the three separate inscriptions may have been the result of a compositional contest between the poets.

(K.267) record the installation of two Devī images at Kuṭīśvara along with an image of Lokanātha/Buddha.⁵⁶

In Śaka 868 (946 CE) he (i.e., Kavīndrārimathana) established an image of the Jina at Jayantadeśa, and in 872 Śaka (950 CE) he also established Lokanātha and two Devīs at Kuṭīśvara.

(K. 266, Bat Cum, st. XX)⁵⁷

The victorious one (i.e., Kavīndrārimathana) established a single Jina at Jayantadeśa and a Buddha together with⁵⁸ two Devīs at Kuṭīśvara.

(K. 267, Bat Cum, st. XXXI)⁵⁹

Prajñāpāramitā is invoked twice at Bat Cum: once in the opening invocation of the inscription from the central shrine, and once in the opening of the inscription from the northern shrine. One of the explicit differences in these two invocations is that Prajñāpāramitā is likened with the moon in one invocation, and with the sun in the other. The two invocations to Prajñāpāramitā at Bat Cum are not merely redundant praises; rather, these two invocations are careful expressions that praise two different, yet intimately related, aspects of Prajñāpāramitā.⁶⁰ The stanza dedicated to her from the north shrine stresses the foundation that she represents—the path to *nirvāṇa*. In this stanza, her light is likened to a sun illuminating the path on which beings will perfect

⁵⁶ Again, K. 266 indicates that a Lokanātha image was installed, but K. 267 indicates that a Buddha image was installed. See the previous footnote on Lokanātha earlier in the chapter.

⁵⁷ Skt. *jayantadeśe jinarūpam ekam so sthāpayan mūrttirasāṣṭaśāke / kuṭīśvare so pi ca lokanāthan devīdvayan netranagāṣṭaśāke //*, Coedès (1908b: 228).

⁵⁸ The Sanskrit word here is *saṃyukta* which may imply a greater significance other than the two Devī images simply accompanied or were installed together with the Buddha image. The word *saṃyukta* also denotes a sense of being joined or united together in some manner. The stanza may, therefore, be alluding to how the Perfection of Wisdom is united with an enlightened being such as the Buddha.

⁵⁹ Skt. *jayantadeśe vijayī jinam ekam atīṣṭipat / devīdvitayasamṃyuktaṃ yo vuddhañ ca kuṭīśvare //*, Coedès (1908b: 232).

⁶⁰ This observation should not be taken so literally as to imply epistemological dualism. The wisdom of Prajñāpāramitā is still non-dual.

insight into the non-duality of all things. The central tower's invocation describes her as the light of the full moon, and this imagery is equated with the perfect knowledge of the Buddha. The omniscience of the Buddha and the Perfection of Wisdom are one and the same—it is knowledge that all things (*dharmas*) are empty of any intrinsic nature. In Cambodian inscriptions Prajñāpāramitā is described as the 'Mother of Jinas' (i.e., Buddhas) because she is responsible for all individuals becoming Buddhas by means of the knowledge she represents. The *Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra in 8000 Lines* XII.1 translated by Conze (1973: 172) states,

So fond are the Tathagatas of this perfection of wisdom, so much do they cherish and protect it. For she is their mother and begetter, she showed them this all-knowledge, she instructed them in the ways of the world. From her have the Tathagatas come forth. For she has begotten and shown that cognition of the all-knowing, she has shown them the world for what it really is.

Thus, Prajñāpāramitā represents both the path and the destination itself. Not only does she illuminate the path to *nirvāṇa*, but she also encapsulates it via the non-dual teachings that she personifies. This may be why she is praised twice in the Bat Cum inscriptions. The poets may have been trying to convey this point in an aesthetic poetical manner. Emphasizing these two characteristics may also explain why the Khmers installed two images of Prajñāpāramitā at some sites, such as at Kuṭṭīśvara.

Lastly, recall that two of the Bat Cum inscriptions record that an image of Prajñāpāramitā called Divyadevī was installed at Bat Cum. The epithet Divyadevī for Prajñāpāramitā is not common, and to my knowledge this is the only attested use of the epithet in the Cambodian epigraphical record. This may suggest that the term had a specific intended use and meaning in the context of the Bat Cum inscriptions; although, it could just as likely be due to more mundane and practical reasons such as meter.

The Sanskrit word *divya*, however, can refer to celestial regions such as the sky and heavens. It is particularly associated with the light of these regions. The word is commonly used adjectively to describe something divine, heavenly, or celestial.⁶¹ Both *divya* and *devī* come from the Sanskrit root \sqrt{div} , which means ‘shines.’⁶² Hence, both *deva* (often translated as ‘god’) and *devī* (often translated ‘goddess’) may be literally translated as ‘the shining one’ or ‘one who shines.’ *Divyadevī*, then, simply means something along the lines of the ‘heavenly shining one,’ or ‘one whose light shines from the sky/heavens.’ When we recall the two invocations to Prajñāpāramitā in the Bat Cum inscriptions of the central and north shrine and their emphasis on her light—again, likened to both the sun (= path) and the moon (= knowledge)—then it seems possible that the epithet *Divyadevī* was specifically used as a clever pun that alluded back to the light motifs stressed in the opening stanzas. This, in turn, would have emphasized how Prajñāpāramitā is both the light that illuminates the path to *nirvāṇa* and the light that encapsulates the knowledge of all buddhas.⁶³

Admittedly, this is a rather contrived interpretation that fails to account for the presence of *Lokeśvara* in the south shrine inscription. It also does little to discount either Cœdès’ explanation that *Lokeśvara* was popular, or Mertens’ explanation that maintains *Lokeśvara*’s inclusion was essentially a mistake. Again, I merely offer the above observations as additional possibilities that may be equally worth considering.

⁶¹ M-W, s.v., *div*, *divya*, *deva* and *devī*. Also cf. the numerous examples of *divya* used in the *R̥g Veda*.

⁶² Note the etymological connection with the Latin *divus* and *divinus*, as well as English words such as **div**-ine and **div**-inity.

⁶³ Of course this suggestion also assumes that the poets had knowledge of each other’s work.

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